

CHILD
RESCUE

Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue

D1.4 – ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release II

Workpackage: WP1 – ChildRescue Operational Requirements and Methodology
Definition

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ChildRescue Project Profile

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is part of ChildRescue WP1 – ChildRescue Operational Requirements and Methodology Definition and it represents the work conducted for all tasks of the work package. It acts both as the aggregation of the corresponding deliverables from the first stage of their development (“D1.1 – User Requirements”, “D1.2 – Regulatory framework for data protection, privacy, and ethical issues”, and “D1.3 – ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release I”), as well as a comprehensive update of their results, based on the developments of the first iteration of the project.

The aim of this deliverable, according to the DoA is to revise and finalise the ChildRescue integrated missing children investigation cycle methodology, as well as the requirements, taking into account the ChildRescue project advancements. The resulting deliverable will be independently assessed by the Ethics Advisory Board of ChildRescue. The result of this assessment will be appended on the final report of the project.

As such, in Part A, the stakeholders’ and system requirements are included, starting from an explanation of the changes from the first iteration, the approach followed, the AS-IS and TO-BE scenarios and user requirements of both use-cases of ChildRescue, the Missing Children Emergency and the Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors. The update takes into consideration the changes and additions to the features requested by the pilot organisations to the TO-BE scenarios, while the AS-IS scenarios remain virtually the same. These lead to the updated System requirements, including the updated user stories and the integrated use case scenarios.

Following the requirements, Part B of the document deals with the regulatory framework for data protection, privacy, and ethical issues. This part aims to identify restrictions in relation to privacy and data protection as well as to access to personal information. The goal is to ensure that the methods, tools, technologies and processes proposed by ChildRescue partners will be able to be adopted without any legal barrier in the piloting countries. The path followed starts from identifying the main properties of the resulting platform and research, the current national and European legal framework, the identified ethical aspects related to regulations for the platform, the mobile application and the individual functions they provide, as well as the special conditions and consideration concerning unaccompanied minors. The main changes to this part reflect the increased maturity of the GDPR, the feedback by the project's Ethics Advisory Board on deliverables submitted under other work packages and the updates stemming from the design, the implementation, the testing, and the piloting of the methodology, platform and app.

Lastly, Part C presents the second and final version of the integrated methodology of ChildRescue, based on the definition and development of the missing children investigation cycle. This is achieved by initially performing a landscape analysis on the domains of interest for the project, performing mapping of the stakeholders and platform’s actors, and finally producing the resulting workflows and data flows for each step of these processes, as implemented with the use of the software being developed. The main changes to this part consist of the addition of another domain of interest, that of Human Mobility Patterns, and the addition of two new platform actors.

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Abbreviations List

API	Application Programming Interface
Best Interest Assessment	BIA
BIPT	Belgian Institute for Postal Services and Telecommunications
BKA	German federal police
CAPS	Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation
CB Radio	Citizen's Band Radio
CCB	Centre for Cybersecurity Belgium
CCB	Centre for Cybersecurity Belgium
CDRs	Call Detail Records
CIPL	Centre for Information Policy Leadership
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DSI	Digital Social Innovation
Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
EC	European Commission
ECAAS	European Child Alert Automated System
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
ECJ	European Court of Justice
EKEPY	National Centre for Health Operations
EKKA	National Centre for Social Solidarity
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
HDPA	Hellenic Data Protection Authority
ICRC	International Committee of Red Cross
IOCFI	Innovation and Organizational Change management Institute
IOM	International Organisation for Migration
IP	Internet Protocol

IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LBSN	Location-Based Social Network
MCIP	Missing Children Investigation Process
MCOs	Missing Children Organisations
MoMP	Ministry of Migration Policy
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
NSARDA body	National Search and Rescue Dog Association UK
OSN	Online Social Network
PD	Personal Data
PDD	Physical Description Document
PFIF	Person Finder Interchange Format
PP	Public Prosecutor
PPEM	Police, Prosecutor, EKKA, Ministry (of Migration Policy)
RCM	Red Cross Messages
S&R	Search & Rescue
TEU	Treaty on European Union
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
TS	Tracing Service
Tx.x	Task x.x
UDHR	United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights
UMC	Unaccompanied Migrant Children
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

The present deliverable is released under the framework of WP1 "ChildRescue Operational Requirements and Methodology Definition", and contributes the second and final iteration of the work conducted in all three tasks of the Work Package; T1.1 "Identification of Stakeholders' Needs and User Requirements", T1.2 "Regulatory Framework for Data Protection, Privacy and Ethical Issues" and T1.3 "ChildRescue Integrated Methodology for Missing Children Investigation". In that view, the results reported in the deliverables D1.1, D1.2 and D1.3 are aggregated and updated in the context of this deliverable, taking into account the ChildRescue project advancements. The present deliverable is concise and self-standing, in order for the reader to be able to gain a good understanding of the main points and work conducted in WP1, highlighting in each respective section the main changes and updates that had to be made with respect to the work done during the 1st iteration and presented in the first three deliverables.

In that view, the present deliverable D1.4 "ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release II" is structured in three main parts, one for each task, updating respectively the relevant previous deliverable, as follows:

- Part A - ChildRescue Requirements: This deliverable's part is associated with Task 1.1 "Identification of Stakeholders' Needs and User Requirements" and revises and updates the work reported in D1.1 "User Requirements" regarding the ChildRescue user needs, and the collected and analysed user requirements.
- Part B - Regulatory Framework for data protection, privacy and ethical issues: Part B is associated with T1.2 "Regulatory Framework for Data Protection, Privacy and Ethical Issues" and revises and updates the work reported in D1.2 "Regulatory framework for data protection, privacy, and ethical issues" includes the examination of European legislation as well as different national legal frameworks for data protection and privacy, along with an analysis of any ethical issues and provisions related both to technical and non-technical aspects of the ChildRescue development.
- Part C - ChildRescue Integrated Methodology Release II: Part C is associated with T1.3 "ChildRescue Integrated Methodology for Missing Children Investigation" and revises and updates the work reported in D1.3 "ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release I". As it can be seen, Part C of the deliverable uses the same naming with the whole deliverable D1.4, highlighting the fact that this is the main output of the WP1 activities. Part C updates and finalises the integrated, holistic ChildRescue methodology that will transform the way missing children investigations are currently held by re-engineering the existing business processes of the organisations operating in the missing children or unaccompanied migrant minors domains, without disrupting their current processes. This final methodology will then be used as a guide for all the forthcoming development activities of the project.

D1.4 will be publicly available after delivery, through the ChildRescue site and other project communication channels, as determined in the dissemination plan and the data management plan of WP5.

1.2 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

Figure 1-1 Relation of WP1 with other WPs

As depicted in Figure 1-1, WP1 is directly linked with WP2, WP3 and WP4, providing them with input and guidelines and taking feedback from them.

In that view, the user requirements, elicited by Task 1.1 and reported in D1.1 have already provided input for both the ChildRescue platform architecture and specifications in WP3 and T3.1 in specific, as well as for the elaboration of the validation framework in WP4 (T4.1). The update of the user requirements will be a continuous process throughout the project's lifecycle and will be promoted in particular by the results of WP3 and especially "T3.4 - ChildRescue Platform Technical Verification" and WP4 through "T4.3 - ChildRescue Platform Deployment, Operation and Support" and "T4.6 - ChildRescue Pilots Evaluation, Lessons Learnt and Impact Assessment".

D1.3 "ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release I" reports, as already mentioned, the work implemented until M6 of the project duration in Task 1.3 for the elaboration of the integrated methodology. D1.3 takes input from D1.2 "Regulatory Framework for Data Protection, Privacy and Ethical Issues" and most importantly from D1.1 "User Requirements" to understand what is needed, what are the current problems and limitations that impede progress of Missing Children Investigation processes, which are the data protection, privacy and ethical issues that should be respected, and elaborate on the Integrated Missing Children Investigation Cycle Methodology accordingly.

On the other hand, D1.3 played an instrumental role in ChildRescue since it was and is being used as a "guide" for the work to be conducted during the project duration, therefore influencing all other WPs and Tasks. However, the connection is more intense with WP2 "Grassroot Collective Intelligence in the Missing Children Investigation" and WP3 "ChildRescue Platform Architecture Definition and Implementation" that were based on the elaborated methodology to define in deeper analysis the scientific and technical background and develop the ChildRescue solution with respect to the Integrated Methodology reported in this deliverable.

D1.4 takes input from the implementation experience as resulted mainly from T3.1 and T4.1 activities. It revises and finalises the ChildRescue integrated missing children investigation cycle methodology and user requirements based on that feedback and the ChildRescue project advancements. From that point forward and until the end of the project, D1.4 will be the guide for all forthcoming activities, representing in the best possible way the project goals and methodology to achieve them.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

The rest of the document at hand is structured as follows:

➤ **Section 2 - Part A:**

- Section 2.1: reports on the identified stakeholder requirements both for the Missing Children Emergency use case, as well as for Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors use case, after highlighting the main differentiations and updates from the results of the first iteration. For each use case, the document analyses the AS-IS scenario and identified challenges and juxtaposes these to the improved TO-BE scenario, in order to derive the user requirements.
- Section 2.2: transforms the user requirements into system requirements, which are updated compared to the system requirements reported in D1.1. Along with the provision of the generalised system requirements, the final user stories for the ChildRescue solution are also presented. Two use case scenarios are finally shaped to demonstrate in a clearer manner, the roles of the various identified actors and how a concrete scenario for a missing child mission can be formed using ChildRescue.

➤ **Section 3: Part B:**

- Section 3.1: In that section national legal frameworks for ethical, data protection and privacy issues for Greece, Belgium and Germany are studied along with the general European legislation in order to identify restrictions in relation to privacy and data protection as well as to access to personal information.
- Section 3.2: Section 3.2 investigated general ethical aspects related to regulations and technical aspects of the mobile application, to ensure that the methods and technologies proposed for the development and use of the ChildRescue mobile application will be able to be adopted without legal barriers and are compliant with international, European and national legal provisions.
- Section 3.3: Ethical provisions related to non-technical aspects of individual functional components are the subject of this section, such as ensuring a user-friendly interface, specifying the terms of use, providing detailed step-by-step instructions to the end users etc.
- Section 3.4: Ethical issues related to unaccompanied minors are presented in this section to ensure that any ChildRescue developments are not in opposition to ethics related to child protection and privacy.
- Section 3.5: Section 3.5 recommends specific actions, taking into account the previous analysis that has taken place in Section 3, to ensure in advance that ChildRescue R&D activities -including methods, tools, technologies and processes- comply with existing legal framework, ethical and privacy principles concerning access to personal information and data protection.

➤ **Section 4: Part C:**

- Section 4.1: exposes the ChildRescue Landscape Analysis for the identified domains of interest. It starts from a revision of the domains analysed in D1.3, namely Business Process Management, to identify methods and solutions that could change business processing without being intrusive, proceeding with Crowdsourcing and Collective Awareness techniques and Behavioural and Activity Profiling theories, to explore ways to engage people and leverage behavioural and activity information to predict and come up with decisions. Then, a new research area is introduced, that of Human Mobility Patterns, both from the perspective of citizens acting as "social sensors" and the perspective of the missing child, to understand mobility patterns in different situations, understand the factors influencing mobility and examine ways to extract patterns of human mobility, to be used as insights on the ChildRescue "Preparation" phase for the extraction of the possible locations and routes followed by the child and on the "Action" Phase as an evaluation of the coverage of a geographic area by social sensors. Technologies and systems that are currently in use both for missing people identification, as well as for refugee management are also analysed, and reported.
- Section 4.2: implements a stakeholder mapping, visualising relationships among the different stakeholders and also their correspondence to platform's actor roles.
- Section 4.3: describes the ChildRescue Integrated Methodology for the Missing Children Investigation Cycle. The scope, the workflow and the dataflow for each of the 4 stages of a missing child investigation cycle, as firstly identified in the DoA, are updated with respect to the ones reported in D1.3 and are described in a final way, not as part of a sequential process, but in a way that every stage is autonomous and can run in parallel and/or independently with the other processes.

2 Part A: ChildRescue Requirements

2.1 Stakeholders' Requirements

2.1.1 Changes from 1st iteration

In the context of D1.1 – “User Requirements” a first batch of requirements was compiled as identified during the first months of the project. These requirements were derived from the AS-IS and TO-BE scenarios of the two use cases, as defined in the deliverable submitted in [M3]. Until [M21], however, the initial requirements have been modified, enriched and updated to reflect the common understanding that grew among partners, as the project progressed. Additionally, the implementation activities concerning the platform’s development brought to light a number of new requested features, but also a number of constraints, which resulted in the System Requirements and User Stories that are presented in detail in sections 2.2.2 and 2.2.3.

In this context, on [M21] of the project and having progressed with the development of the ChildRescue platform, a number of alterations to the initial requirements, presented in D1.1, took place. For example, new actors were added, new links connecting actors were identified, a subprocess was added and the requirements of the previous version are explained in more detail.

2.1.2 Approach for Requirements Elicitation

Both the waterfall and the agile approaches were used to build the requirements. The requirements were gathered with a multitude of techniques. More specifically, in D1.1 three techniques were used:

- **Interviews** (2 physical and 1 online) with the pilot partners of the consortium (SoC, REDCROSS and Child Focus) that handle missing children cases or/and are engaged in the care of unaccompanied minors. The aim was to understand and document their current applicable processes and the modifications that will result. Technology partners participated in the interviews. Apart from the definition of the user requirements, a formalisation of the processes these organisations apply in their normal operations for the AS-IS scenarios was performed and used as the input for the derived TO-BE scenarios.
- **Questionnaires** were used to gather requirements from the pilot partners and guide the interview discussions.
- Two **Use Cases** (the missing children emergency use case, and the discovery and identification of unaccompanied minors) were thoroughly described after conducting the interviews and analysing the questionnaires. The AS-IS as well as the TO-BE scenarios were used to build the use cases.

Furthermore, throughout the project’s first 21 months, the plenary meetings, the workshops, the physical informal meetings, the regular teleconferences offered the opportunity to the ChildRescue partners to re-examine the requirements and update them.

2.1.3 The Missing Children Emergency Use Case

2.1.3.1 AS-IS scenario & Identified Challenges

The purpose of the techniques mentioned in 2.1.2 was to identify the steps of the investigation process the pilot organisations follow when a child is first reported missing, either to the police or the Missing children organisation. It needs to be noted that this process pertains only to internal organisational

processes, while external organisational processes, such as authorities' support, is outside the scope of this work.

All activities following the process input and preceding the process output define the boundaries of the Missing Children Investigation Process (MCIP). Therefore, the SoC's and Child Focus's MCIP starting boundary is defined by the reception of a call notifying about the disappearance of a child. The process ending boundary is defined by SoC and Child Focus the finding of the missing child. In that sense, identification of the location of a missing child and their return to their legal guardians is the one and only output of the process unless the child requires further protection (e.g. in case of runaway due to child abuse) by decision of the prosecutor. In any other case the process remains active.

The process by which the Missing Children Organisations (MCOs) can be summarised in a generalised form in Figure 2-1 and Figure 2-2. Overall, it consists of four identified steps (Preparation and Profiling, Coordination and Collaboration, Action, and Archiving). These steps are neither time-bound, nor are necessarily sequential, although representing a logical progression. Additional to the process, the MCO constantly provides support to the family of the missing child or the found child, even long after a case is closed. The concept of the entire process can be broken down to the following key states of a case:

1. A child is reported missing to the police and the MCO and information is collected and shared.
2. The authorities in charge of the case instruct the MCO to issue an alert or perform other actions, by disseminating material or requesting cross border collaborations within the MCE network.
3. If Search & Rescue (S&R) teams exist for the MCO and are available, the police might ask them to run an operation on the field.
4. When and if a case is resolved, the dissemination material is retracted, and the case files are updated and archived.

Figure 2-1 MCO Missing Child Process Part 1

Figure 2-2 MCO Missing Child Process Part 2

The two organisations follow similar processes, while there are some differences concerning mainly how active their investigation is and how their volunteers are involved in the investigation process. Their processes and their similarities and differences are described in the following chapters.

Preparation and Profiling

Preparation

Child Focus operates the European Hotline for Missing Children 116000 in Brussels. The people who work at the emergency line are called *call managers* (or operators) and they just take the calls. They ask the main information about the disappearance. They have to be quick and efficient on the calls they respond to, to ensure that the lines remain free for new incoming calls, in case there is a limited number of available call managers. When they have enough information about the case e.g. how old

the child is, which police station works on the file, etc., they transfer this information to the *case managers*, who are in charge of the call managers and mainly have a relevant academic background, e.g. psychologists, social scientists etc. The case managers communicate with the *police*, the appointed *prosecutor*, and the *parents*.

“The Smile of the Child” (SoC) has call centres in six locations in Greece. The centres are staffed with qualified personnel (i.e. social scientists and psychologists) and are equipped with computer hardware and software, including the ECAAS – European Child Alert Automated System.

For the facilitation of the actions of the organisation, the 6 call centres are interconnected. This results in:

- Minimising the call waiting time
- Strengthening the capacity to manage more requests/calls
- Better coordination between the officers of all lines
- Expansion of the human resources of all lines
- Reliability and elimination of technical problems through multiple redundancies.

SoC has a central server, so its employees across Greece have access to the same information concurrently.

Furthermore, since a CRM system is in place, if someone has called SoC in the past using the same phone number, a tab automatically opens and lists the details of the person who called and any information from a previous case. If the person calls from a different number, the operator searches the CRM for the name of the caller and brings up the same information.

Profiling

The Missing Children Investigation Process (MCIP) is activated when a child is reported missing. This applies to both organisations. The MCIP is activated, when:

- parents call directly to SoC or Child Focus
- parents go in person to a mandated police station, report on their child’s disappearance, and the police decides to either call SoC or Child Focus

In the first case, both SoC and Child Focus, call operator/manager asks the parents to report on their child’s disappearance to the police. MCOs are only authorised to perform any action relating to a disappearance by the police. They then contact the police department where the report was or is being made and share all the information they have on the disappearance.

In the second case, if the parents (or the police) call SoC/Child Focus after contacting the police, the organisations verify with the police that a report was made. SoC’s/Child Focus’s call operator/manager records all the information given to them by the police. The police usually call SoC/Child Focus to ask for their contribution to a case.

The call operator/manager requests the caller’s information and contact details. The profiling phase follows, where all information about the missing child is collected. SoC’s/Child Focus’s call operator/manager requests from the caller as much information about the child as possible. Indicative data requested include the name, the date of birth, a physical description, eye colour, hair colour, scent, height, weight, last clothes wearing, the last place they had seen the child, the child’s relationship with the social media, etc. A recent photograph of the child is also requested. The call operator saves this

information in digital format on the CRM system. The questions asked depend on the details the caller/parents provide regarding the child. SoC's experts (Psychologists and Sociologists) work with the family of the missing child for collecting additional data to build an initial psychosocial profile of the missing child. It needs to be noted that there are certain situations/answers that may raise "red flags", based on the experience of the operators and the past cases of missing children. These are evaluated on the fly by the operators and are added to the case file. If needed, SoC/Child Focus experts may also visit the child's relatives even from this early stage to provide counselling and support.

Additionally, case files are a chronologically ordered collection (physical or digital) of the material and the events related to it, including communication logs about the case (phone calls, emails, interviews etc.), documents exchanged with the police, prosecutors, other organisations etc.

Both SoC and Child Focus do not employ any standardised profiling method to pinpoint locations on a map to perform investigations, although they do make predictions based on their expertise and previous experience. In this respect, they provide consultancy services to the police, while their role is to act as a bridge between the parents and the police, the public prosecutors and other involved public authorities.

Coordination and Collaboration

In this step, although both Child Focus and SoC are the only organisations in their countries directly involved in the investigation of missing children cases, greater distinctions among the two organisations were identified.

Based on the decision made by the police and/or the prosecutor in charge of the case, the MCOs crudely classify the cases to three levels, based on the level of publicity the investigation will have: private, public and Amber Alert. The **private** level of investigations has the minimum amount of information distribution, which excludes public broadcast, posters etc. Flyers may be distributed, and verbal information may be given, but only to specified individuals (tellers at supermarkets, garbage truck drivers, security companies' employees etc.). Next, the **public** level of investigations can include broadcasting of information to news outlets, websites, social media, TV and radio stations etc., posters in public places, but excludes mandatory public service announcements channels (highway signs, metro stations, mandatory broadcast by TV stations etc.). When an **Amber Alert** is raised, all available channels can be activated, and usually they all are by default.

Child Focus is in contact with its volunteer network to perform actions like distributing flyers and putting up posters. The network of volunteers is organised by maintaining a list of local coordinators, each able to mobilise their team of volunteers. Child Focus cooperates with a security company (Securitas). The company is contacted to provide services that relate to active cases.

Child Focus also cooperates with other organisations, not NGOs, like the railway company, the subway company in Brussels, supermarkets, etc.

Child Focus is also in regular contact with the police for updates applying a protocol where the police know what information to share and vice versa. Communication between them is mostly done by phone and emails.

SoC, on the other side, cooperates with many organisations, being more involved in the investigation process.

When a child is reported missing, SoC informs the police Immediate Action service and the National Centre for Health Operations (E.K.EP.Y.), looking for missing children in hospitals, while also cooperates with the Electronic Crime Prosecution Division, to find out if the child has a social media account and possibly elicit useful information.

Among others, SoC/Child Focus cooperates with Facebook to further disseminate missing children information in a wider public. SoC also cooperates with the Hellenic Red Cross Samaritans, Hellenic Rescue Team Attica and Hellenic Rescue Team Thessaloniki.

At Marousi, SoC has its centre of operations, where the coordination and contact with volunteer (search and rescue) teams takes place. SoC has been set up the «Thanasis Makris» Search and Rescue Team for missing children. The aim of this volunteer group is the active investigation in urban or non-urban environments to locate children who have gone missing. All Search & Rescue team members are trained regularly. Key members of Missing Children Search and Rescue Team «Thanasis Makris» are the Canine Teams participating. The Canine Teams (handler and dog) are the only ones in Greece certified by the international NSARDA body (National Search and Rescue Dog Association UK) and the only Canine Teams in Greece, seeking a particular person. The Canine Teams look for a person, based on the person's own scent. Their response time is less than 24 hours, after the request for their assistance. To the accomplishment of its project, the Search and Rescue Team for Missing Children «Thanasis Makris» has at its disposal a Mobile Operations Unit and other vehicles (jeeps, ATV, motor vehicle, ambulances). If the child has disappeared near the sea, where the coast guard is responsible, then SoC cooperates with them as with the police. The General Secretariat for Civil Protection under the Ministry of Public Order & Citizen Protection is also able to mobilise local actors in case of a child's disappearance, e.g. inform the local garbage truck drivers to be on alert.

As far as the cross-border cooperation, SoC and Child Focus collaborate also with Missing Children Europe (MCE), as members of it, and all its members in case there are indications that a child that has gone missing may have crossed their countries' borders towards other countries.

Action Stage

As stated above, SoC/Child Focus may be informed about the case by either the police or the parents themselves and the police are responsible for finding the missing child.

In both SoC's and Child Focus's case, call manager/operator speaks with the parents or anyone who provides information about the case, without, however, a fixed questionnaire. Their personnel are trained to handle such cases and ask specific, appropriate questions.

SoC/Child Focus also receive calls from people that claim to have seen the missing child. In SoC's case, after an appropriate set of questions, if the testimony about the missing child is considered reliable, the information is kept, and the police is called to inform them. Then, SoC notifies the police department of missing persons, sending a document with the information it received from the call. The phone calls are not being recorded from SoC, and if someone calls it, they are not obliged to give their personal information and SoC in any case does not save their personal details. This is a distinction from Child Focus, that records the conversations of all the incoming calls, while the callers know that the conversations are recorded.

As far as social media is concerned, if the child has a public Facebook or other social media account, SoC's and Child Focus's employees monitor the activity in these accounts and inform the police, in case

of an event that inspires concern. Both SoC and Child Focus have social media accounts to contribute to their purpose. In particular, SoC has a Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, YouTube and LinkedIn account and Child Focus a Facebook and a Twitter one.

SoC uses two ways to publicise the missing child's disappearance. The first action is "Publicity" and the second action is "Amber Alert Hellas". These two actions are activated with the written consent of the guardian(s) or the legal representative(s). The public prosecutor, however, has the right of Amber Alert activation regardless of the consent of the child's guardians. The prosecutor is the person who is in charge of the case file. If activation of Amber Alert is decided by the prosecutor, the police contact SoC/Child Focus in order to activate an Amber Alert. The police and the public prosecutor decide the activation time of Publicity and Amber Alert Hellas. In addition, SoC distributes also flyers and posters and then removes them.

Child Focus uses both private and public methods to find a missing child. When Child Focus handles children runaways, it uses private actions. For instance, in case of a teenager's runaway, Child Focus, along with the other investigation actions, activates also private broadcast, e.g. flyers. In fact, they leverage their collaboration with supermarkets, asking their employees to hide their flyers of the missing child and inform Child Focus and police, if they see the child. For a private broadcast, Child Focus does not need the request of the prosecutor. It is not a must have, but it is a nice to have. For the public broadcast, Child Focus needs the request of the prosecutor, just like SoC's case. Child Focus keeps track of the locations where posters and flyers were handed out or put up, so that they can be collected after the case is closed for the protection of the children's privacy. Child Focus also maintains a list of local coordinators. If a decision is made to focus the distribution of information to a specific area, the network manager contacts the coordinator of the area who contacts their team of volunteers for the distribution of flyers/posters.

For both SoC and Child Focus, the necessary information for the activation of Amber Alert are shared by the police via email or fax. These organisations do not need formal request from the police. This happens in order to be as efficient as possible. After the Amber Alert or Publicity activation, the rest of the paperwork is filled.

In the Publicity action, a poster is uploaded on SoC's/Child Focus's social media accounts, on SoC's/Child Focus's official website, and on other websites that SoC/Child Focus cooperates with. Moreover, a poster is sent with a press release to various TV stations. In Belgium, TV stations are obliged to present the child's disappearance, whereas in Greece, it is at the TV stations' discretion to present it, e.g. as a subject on the news or a TV show. This is not the case when Amber Alert is activated where they are mandated to broadcast. Child Focus creates posters and Child Focus's volunteers distribute them in order to be seen either locally or nationally. These posters are only removed when the child is found. A case file is maintained to record the places where posters are placed and collect them when the case is closed. This action is less massive than the Amber Alert.

The poster that is used in both "Publicity" and "Amber Alert" actions should have the following information: recent photo of the child, name, age, disappearance date and place, hair and eye colour, height, weight, a brief description of what the child was wearing the day of disappearance, special characteristics, health issues. In the past, in case of parental abduction the poster contained a photo of both the child and their father. In case, there are two siblings or friends that were together and are

missing, the poster may contain two photos and descriptions of them. This is decided case by case. Both Publicity and Amber Alert actions contain the same information.

Amber Alert is a National Coordinating Programme of timely and accurate notification of citizens on cases of missing or abducted minors. The operation of the Amber Alert is based on the provision of quick, accurate and detailed information to citizens on a missing child case few minutes after the reporting of the case to the police or the SoC/Child Focus. To achieve this, a number of actors (public private, voluntary) are involved with the purpose to communicate the details of the missing child and other basic information through the mass media (TV channels and radio spots), social media (Facebook posts), SMS, announcements on airports' monitors, subways etc. In Greece, today, there are 61 partners participating in Amber Alert Hellas, initiated by SoC in 2007.

It needs to be pointed out that special attention is needed when activating Amber Alert, since risks for the child may rise. For example, a child may leave on their own and decide to come back after a few days but be scared of that due to the activation of Amber Alert. Therefore, decision on Amber Alert's activation should be careful and meet some of the following criteria:

- Young age of child / children
- Clear indications that the life or health of the child may be at risk.
- Suspicions that indicate a possible abduction or kidnapping of a child.
- The activation of the system will help to identify the child

The activation process of Amber Alert is the following:

At first, a SoC's expert logs in the European Child Alert Automated System (ECAAS); Child Focus's expert logs in a Belgian platform respectively. They fill in the necessary information of the missing child, e.g. recent photo of the child, name, age, disappearance date and place, hair and eye colour, height, weight, a brief description of what the child was wearing when last seen, special characteristics, health issues. There is an upper limit on the letters that can be used.

After 6-7 minutes, the system develops all the available file formats such as video spot, radio spot, posters, mp4, pdf, jpg, xml, etc. Then the SoC's/Child Focus's operator/manager checks the correctness of the data on the generated files. After they are sure about it, they send the appropriate files to the partners who participate in the Amber Alert action. Each partner doesn't receive all the file formats, but the ones which fit in their system. Additionally, an email is sent to them in order to inform them that information has been sent.

In Belgium, Amber Alert's initial duration is 3 hours, unless police, after the prosecutor's confirmation, tell Child Focus to stop Amber Alert earlier than that. Then, the police, after the prosecutor's request, makes a new debriefing and tells Child Focus, to have Amber Alert activated, e.g. for 3 hours more or until they find the missing child. In any case, the prosecutor has to give confirmation every 3 hours, else Child Focus stops to transmit the Amber Alert in Belgium.

In Greece, Amber Alert's initial duration is 48 hours, unless police tell SoC to stop Amber Alert earlier than that. Then, the police make a new debriefing and tell SoC to have Amber Alert activated, e.g. for 24 hours more or until they find the missing child. The decision about this time extension is made by the prosecutor.

When the police notify SoC/Child Focus to stop Amber Alert, then they send a press release to notify the partners who participate to Amber Alert to stop broadcasting it. In order to be sure, SoC/Child Focus calls the partners to ensure they received the notification to stop broadcasting.

In case of a cross-border collaboration, two types of cooperation can be identified.

The first is when a foreign country asks SoC/Child Focus to broadcast a disappearance. In that case, they don't have to ask the prosecutor to broadcast the disappearance, although they have to be sure that their colleagues from the foreign countries have their prosecutor's permission.

The second kind is when the child disappeared from Belgium/Greece, and they believe that the missing child is in another country. In case there are indications that the child is abroad, SoC/Child Focus informs the police about these indications. If they want to broadcast the disappearance in a foreign country, they have to request the prosecutor's permission. Then, SoC/Child Focus which is a Missing Children Europe (MCE) member, contact MCE, in order to examine if there is the possibility of collaboration with the other country's organisations, filling in a transnational form which is sent to the corresponding organisation(s) - MCE members - of the country(ies) where the child may be.

Finally, as far as active search is concerned, SoC does have active investigation in the field, while Child Focus does not (as also the protocol that Child Focus has with the justice department and the police explicitly indicates).

In particular, Child Focus's volunteer network's actions are restricted to sharing and distributing flyers and putting up posters, while it also calls the security company it collaborates with (i.e. Securitas) when they need them, providing them all necessary information about the missing child and its location when lost. In this sense, in their normal daily operations of patrolling areas, houses and businesses, Securitas also pay attention for the disappeared child.

SoC activates active search upon request by the authorities in charge of the operations to perform an active investigation. Then, the field operations coordinator of the operational centre is mobilised, and sends an SMS from SoC's platform to the volunteers to find out about their availability. Then, all available volunteers are gathered in order to help find the missing child. If there are indications that the child may be in a specific area, SoC prints flyers, which are distributed there. Creation of posters and flyers takes place in order to be distributed in patrol cars throughout the country for the discreet search of the missing child. These flyers contain the same information as Publicity and Amber Alert actions. Moreover, when asked, Missing Children Search and Rescue Team «Thanasis Makris» is also engaged in coordination with the authorities to search for the child in the designated area. The Canine teams of the Search and Rescue team are also activated and wherever they are needed, they go by car and using the mobile operational unit, which is equipped with a geo-tracking system of its team members. Rescue team members communicate with each other via CB Radios or mobile phones. Whatever information they receive, they also inform the police and SoC. The Rescue Team is dismissed only if the child is found or if the police end the operation for any reason. During and at the end of the search, SoC records all the information from the volunteers (what went well, what went wrong) and updates the case file.

Archiving

Concerning SoC/Child Focus, a case is closed only when the child is found. This means that SoC/Child Focus never stops trying to trace a missing child. Child Focus keeps the case files in digital format,

while SoC keeps them in both digital and printed format, due to the fact that part of the communication with the police is done by fax.

The file of the missing child is updated when a case is closed, with all the actions that took place. SoC/Child Focus handle the case's closure in a secure and privacy-respectful manner. When a case is closed, the data are not subject to changes.

SoC/Child Focus stays in touch with the parents in order to provide psychological support, advisory support and sessions with a psychologist, in case they agree with that.

2.1.3.2 TO-BE Scenario

ChildRescue aims to work in parallel with the current process SoC/Child Focus follow, as shown in Figure 2-1 and Figure 2-2. Its ambition is to effectively reduce the time needed for locating a missing child. In fact, the existing missing children investigation process will be enhanced by the ChildRescue platform. It aims to solve challenges already identified in the process, such as the volunteers' coordination, insufficient capture and diffusion of information, etc. It will also optimise the process and improve record keeping and sharing of information.

Preparation and Profiling

The case file will be added to the platform, in order to capture and diffuse the information easier. There will be continuous update of the case profiles using extensive forms. It will include personal and psychosocial information about the child as these will be collected and provided by the operators, as well as any other sources of information for the child, such as social media activities and acquaintances. In this way, ChildRescue will integrate a mechanism that takes advantage of all available sources of information, thus enabling identification of activity and mobility patterns.

ChildRescue will offer an additional tool that can be used from people who decide the course of action in the investigation. That is the suggestion of possible locations the missing child may be, based on algorithms which elicit data combining multiple sources, such as: means of transportation, routes and schedules that the missing person had fairly convenient access, social media activity, pattern matching of similar past cases, places recently visited, interests, etc. For example, several algorithms and predictive analytics methods can be used, so that ChildRescue suggests a geographic region that the missing child may be or reach. This input will be taken into consideration, but no action will be made automatically. As a decision support system, ChildRescue's platform will make suggestions, but the decision maker will always be a qualified and authorised human.

Additionally, indexing functionalities will be added in the profiling process, allowing for easier and more efficient information retrieval. Automatic association between related (e.g. gone missing together) profiles and the corresponding cases' metadata could be derived during profiling stage. Any relevant correlation will be evaluated by the operator of the operation centre.

Moreover, even if ChildRescue's users get almost the same information as they do nowadays when an alert is issued, the platform will speed up the information flow, because of its immediacy. Due to the information centralisation, the case manager will be able to massively send a case record to the relevant stakeholders. The distribution of case data and of information submitted in the platform will be instant. Of course, different access levels to information will be given to users according to their role.

This way, the distribution and the collection of information will be faster. In case a citizen becomes aware of the location or any other clue about a missing child, they will be able to submit it to the

ChildRescue mobile application along with potential evidence attesting to that (e.g. photo, testimonial) and tags (e.g. missing child's condition that enhance the profiling information).

Coordination and Collaboration

As far as the coordination phase is concerned, communication and collaboration between the volunteer and rescue teams with the operations centre will be enhanced through the use of the mobile application. This application is an advanced version compared to the one available to the public, as it included extended functionality. On the other hand, citizens using the community application will have a direct channel to receive notifications and send information to the MCO relating to a case.

Furthermore, the leaders of each volunteers' team will receive instructions from their MCO with guidance relayed by the police. They will be able to instantly submit a request to the team members to take part in the investigation and be informed about their availability. Network managers and team leaders will be able to guide their members in real-time through the ChildRescue platform. As a result, volunteers' coordination will be immediate and easier. Members of the teams in the field will also have the ability to communicate with other volunteers, while moderated by their team leader and case manager, in a privacy-aware manner, in order to make necessary arrangements and exchange ideas. Tasks can also be assigned to volunteers, if required, so that specific jobs, like the flyer distribution, can be monitored and controlled.

Finally, cross-border cases will be more efficiently managed through ChildRescue, as direct sharing of the case file with another country's MCO will take place through the platform.

Action Stage

One of the key features that ChildRescue adds to the current process, concerning public dissemination of the child's disappearance, is the notifications that will be sent to smartphones of the ChildRescue mobile application users. ChildRescue aspires to turn citizens into social investigation sensors, who contribute to the identification of missing children. ChildRescue will provide geo-targeted distribution of information. The notifications will be shown to all ChildRescue users who will be near the area a child disappeared or might be after the disappearance. These targeted notifications will improve the effectiveness of the investigation compared to current practices, while at the same time reduce the total number of notifications each citizen is exposed to. As a result, protection of the privacy of the missing child will be increased. For example, a child disappears near the centre of Athens. At first, notifications will be sent to ChildRescue users in the centre of Athens. As time passes, the radius could be increased and the shape of the areas will stem from suggestions made by predictive algorithms, but ultimately will be selected by operation coordinators.

ChildRescue users will not be bombarded with alerts on cases that they have no meaningful way to assist. The immediacy and the low frequency of these alerts will increase the users' engagement. The pieces of evidence submitted by users will be validated, if considered necessary by the case manager, through the notification diffusion in a specific location.

Currently, when Publicity or Amber Alert actions are activated, people need to remember the face on a picture, perhaps for many hours before a possible sighting of the missing child occurs. The condition of the sighted child, as well as the time elapsed since briefly looking at the picture, make it virtually impossible to make a positive identification. With ChildRescue, users will be able to use their phone as direct reference to the child's picture on the spot to instantly verify the sighting. Then, if the user is

convinced that this was the missing child, he can directly provide feedback to the ChildRescue operation centre through the app and share this information. Have the citizen been uncertain of the sighting, a useful testimony could have never been given.

Archiving

ChildRescue will securely handle the closing of the cases in a privacy-respectful manner. Semantic annotation will be performed on the case's record and lessons learnt from the case will be stored so that they support the handling of similar cases in the future. Additional functionalities that enable the easier aggregation of past data and the derivation of analytics will be developed, so that the MCO users will be able to access and take advantage of past experience and knowledge. Regarding the ChildRescue mobile application, all data related to closed cases will be erased from the citizens' devices.

2.1.3.3 Derived User Requirements

The current set of derived user requirements can be found in Table 2-2. The essence of the requirements remained the same as in D1.1. A number of requirements has been added (marked as "New"), to include aspects that have not been covered in the original set or emerged as valuable assets after deliberation with pilot partners (as for example the assignment of tasks to volunteers through ChildRescue). Updates have also been made to most of the initial user requirements in order to fully adopt the developed methodology as well as the correct terminology and actor assignment (marked as "Updated"). The abbreviations of the related actors and their full description can be found in Table 4-8 of the present deliverable, but they are repeated here too for convenience.

Table 2-1 List of Actors Abbreviations

Actor	Abbreviation
Visitor (Anonymous user)	VU
Simple User (Registered user)	SU
Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Member	RT
Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Leader	TL
Hosting Facility Manager	FM
Organisation Case Manager	CM
Organisation Network Manager	NM
Organisation Coordinator Manager	OC
Organisation Owner	OO
ChildRescue Administrator	CA

Table 2-2 Updated User Requirements for Missing Child Use Case

#	Sub-Process	User Requirement Description	Related Actors	Remarks (vs D1.1)
1	Core	Registration to the ChildRescue platform.	All	
2	Core	Different access level and privileges for each user group.	All	
3	Core	Registration of advanced users to the web platform by authorised users, based on a hierarchical model.	NM, CM, OC, OO	New
4	Core	A lightweight app for Visitors and Simple users.	VU, SU	New
5	Core	An enhanced app for Volunteer/Rescue teams, requiring a special verification process.	RT, TL, NM	New
6	Preparation/Profiling	Creation and continuous update of new case profiles using extensive forms. Matching of the new profile with existing ones, in order to avoid multiple registrations.	CM, OC	New
7	Preparation/Profiling	Ability to attach document & media files coming from multiple sources (psychosocial reports, medical records etc.) to a case.	CM, OC	Updated
8	Preparation/Profiling	Easily retrieve information and patterns from past cases and profiles.	CM, OC	Updated
9	Preparation/Profiling	Receive suggestions by the system on possible Points of Interest regarding the child. The POIs could be calculated based on testimonies, historical data (if any), child's preferences stated in public in the social media and past cases analysis.	CM, OC	Updated
10	Preparation/Profiling	Fast collection of information from all users that actively participate in the investigation and can enhance the profiling process.	CM, OC	
11	Preparation/Profiling	Fast distribution of the available case data and information submitted through the mobile app to relevant authorised user groups.	RT, TL, NM, CM, OC	Updated

12	Collaboration/ Coordination	Improved communication and information exchange between the Organisation and Volunteer/Rescue teams using a real-time collaboration space.	RT, TL, NM, CM, OC	Updated
13	Collaboration/ Coordination	Notification of registered Volunteers/Rescue team members on new investigation operations and request for their participation. Affirmation of their availability.	RT, TL, NM	Updated
14	Collaboration/ Coordination	Real-time guidance from Network Managers and Team Leaders through the collaboration space.	RT, TL, NM	Updated
15	Collaboration/ Coordination	Improve cross-border and international cooperation through data sharing with other MCE members and other organisations/ NGOs that have adopted ChildRescue.	OC, OO	Updated
16	Collaboration/ Coordination	Geolocation sharing of Volunteer/Rescue team members during their active participation in an operation.	RT, TL, NM, CM, OC	Updated
17	Collaboration/ Coordination	Assignment of actions to perform by specific Volunteer/Rescue team members.	RT, TL, NM	New
18	Action Stage	Enhance the monitoring of each case's progress.	NM, CM, OC	Updated
19	Action Stage	Create suggestions about future steps (routes to follow, POIs to search)	CM, OC	Updated
20	Action Stage	Users may provide (anonymously or not) feedback (information, images, location data) regarding a missing child case	VU, SU, RT, TL	Updated
21	Action Stage	Registration of received feedback to the blockchain ledger, as an anonymised and privacy-aware log (GDPR compliant).	CM, OC, OO	New
22	Action Stage	Location-based alerts will be sent to mobile app users.	VU, SU, RT, TL, NM	Updated
23	Action Stage	Crowd validation of citizens' feedback, through diffusion of a new alert at the specific geolocation.	CM, OC	Updated

24	Archiving	After closure of a case, all sensitive/private data will be removed from mobile users' devices.	CM, OC, OO	Updated
25	Archiving	Cases and received feedback are semantically annotated for analysis purposes, and then are archived in a privacy-respectful manner.	CM, OC, OO	Updated

2.1.4 Discovery and Identification Use Case of Unaccompanied Minors

2.1.4.1 AS-IS scenario & Identified Challenges

The AS-IS scenario and the identified challenges originated through an interview with REDCROSS. The steps of the process that REDCROSS follows were identified. Since there is no standardisation of these processes, an effort was made to find what parts of it can be put down to paper as business processes. The boundary for the interview and the described processes is the actions taken by REDCROSS, since they are active ChildRescue stakeholders. All other processes are either briefly described or are presented as black boxes of external input.

REDCROSS operates three accommodation **UMC centres** and one **safe zone** program in Greece.

UMC centres provide the following services:

- Provision of food and accommodation
- Counselling and psychosocial support both in individual and group level
- Interpretation / mediation to community agencies
- Accompany to asylum services and hospitals
- Intercultural and recreational activities

The main objectives of the safe zone program are:

- Meeting the basic subsistence needs of the migrant children (safety, food, hygiene etc.),
- Facilitation of their access to health care services (vaccination, medical check-up, escort to the hospitals),

• Educational activities, creative activities, provision, legal support (in cooperation the International Organisation for Migration (IOM)), cultural mediation/interpretation, psychosocial support.

REDCROSS operates the 2105140440 Hotline. It is on from Monday to Friday from 8.00 a.m. until 20.00 pm. Specially trained employees answer the calls they receive in the following languages: Greek, English, French, Arabic, Kurdish, Farsi, Pashtu, Dari, Russian, Swahili, Kinyarwanda, Kirundi. It provides:

- Information on refugees and asylum seekers (asylum procedure, residence permit, legal issues, etc.)
- Information on agencies, services and their respective benefits
- Mediation and facilitation of agencies and services
- Interpreting by telephone
- Support and directions

The REDCROSS's **Tracing Service (TS)**, that handles the tracing cases, is not only active in unstable situations; in time of war and peace the TS traces missing persons, both in Greece and abroad, but it also facilitates communication between dispersed family members, including migrants and refugees.

Its goals are:

- Maintain family unity
- Restore family links
- Restore and maintain communication among family members
- Trace the missing persons and inform their relatives

The REDCROSS's Tracing Service has the largest tracing record in Greece and one of the largest worldwide. The "Information Bank" of the Tracing Service is constantly fed with new data and documents while, for more effective function, it collaborates closely with the International Committee of Red Cross (ICRC), the International Network of Tracing Services, State or Private Institutions, International Organisations, Mass Media and volunteers both in Greece and abroad. Its activities are:

- Collect personal data of sought persons from their immediate family members (enquirers)
- Keep record of and processing the data of the sought/missing persons and of the enquirers
- Gather and keep record of general information
- Restore and maintain communication after having traced the missing persons
- Provide Red Cross Messages (RCM)
- Contribute to the repatriation of victims of armed conflicts (under IHL provisions)
- Provide assistance to Greeks living abroad and to foreigners living in Greece to trace their relatives in cooperation with local or foreign institutions, governmental or non-governmental organisations (NGOs)
- Provide certificates to hostages, prisoners, tortured, murdered, in order to help the victims or their relatives on retirement issues or on their rehabilitation.

The activities of the REDCROSS's Tracing Service are based on the right of families to stay united and the right of the people to be informed about the fate of their beloved ones and reunite with them, expand further than just tracing people. The Mandate of the Tracing Service is "to maintain the family unity", while tracing is done always with respect to the dignity and the right to privacy.

The placement process initiates when a child comes to a REDCROSS's accommodation centre for unaccompanied minors or when a placement order is received. The tracing process starts when the REDCROSS's Tracing Department receives a request for tracing a person by an immediate relative or a legal guardian.

Regarding the first process, the starting boundary is defined by the time an unaccompanied minor is placed in a REDCROSS's accommodation centre. The process's ending boundary is when the minor is no longer under REDCROSS's care. Concerning the second process, the starting boundary is the moment there is a tracing request on the REDCROSS Tracing Service, placed by an immediate family member. The process's ending boundary is when the sought person is found; if found alive, communication between the person seeking and the person sought is restored. The Red Cross Movement fully respects individuals' right to privacy, in the regard the details of located persons might be released to enquirers only with their consent.

The extracted data from each process is the output of the two processes.

The two processes (Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors and Tracing service) can be summarised in Figure 2-3 and Figure 2-4 accordingly. The first process can be broken down to the following states:

1. A placement order is issued, and the unaccompanied minor arrives at the hosting facility (shelters, safe zone). The necessary documents (personal identification form, social history) are filled by the facility's social service.
2. Counting of the minors happens every morning and evening in the facility.
3. If someone is missing the Police, the Public Prosecutor (PP), the National Centre for Social Solidarity (EKKA) & the Ministry of Migration Policy (MoMP) are informed about the minor's voluntary departure.
4. If the minor returns to the facility within 3 days of departure, PP, EKKA, and the MoMP are informed that the minor returned. If not, PP, EKKA, and the MoMP are informed that the minor is not included in the capacity of the shelter and thus, there is a vacancy in the facility.
5. Case is closed when the minor becomes an adult and leaves the shelter, relocated or reunited with their families.

The second process can be broken down to the following states:

1. The Tracing department receives a request for tracing a person; the tracing request form is filled out.
2. If the enquirer is an unaccompanied minor or there are indications that the sought person might be dead, additional documents are filled. If there is information about a large-scale accident, e.g. shipwreck, the tracing department receives additional documents regarding the accident.
3. Communication effort is made with family members.
4. Volunteers' activation and field work can be activated after the previous step or in case there is a natural disaster and children are missing from the organisation's facility.
5. Case is administratively closed 3 years after the initial request, when all means of research have been exhausted (negative closure) or when the sought person is found (positive closure).

Figure 2-3 Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors

Figure 2-4 The Tracing Service

Preparation and Profiling

Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors

All foreign national or stateless individuals below the age of 18, who either arrive in the EU unaccompanied by a responsible adult or are left unaccompanied after their arrival, are considered unaccompanied minors.

An unaccompanied minor is located for the first time on the entry points (hot spots) to be registered by the national authorities (police), the asylum service of Ministry of Migration Policy, the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). At the same time, forensic (dental and bone) age estimation tests are conducted to detect if the minor is less than 18 years old.

After registration process, the unaccompanied minor is given priority, compared to adults, to leave the hot spot and move to the mainland. In most cases, unaccompanied minors are transported to protective custody (structures inside the police departments). Then, they are usually transported to intermediate structures called "safe zones", and after three months, to a permanent hosting facility. This happens after a placement order is issued. The placement order is issued for a safe zone program by the Ministry of Migration Policy and for a shelter by the National Centre for Social Solidarity (EKKA). EKKA is responsible for the national hosting facilities management, having the overall supervision and coordination of all hosting facilities (e.g. the number of vacancies in the hosting facilities, which unaccompanied minor is transported to a hosting facility, etc.).

When the placement order is issued, the Ministry of Migration Policy or EKKA sends an e-mail and the relevant documents to the organisation running the facility (in this case and hereafter the Hellenic Red Cross (REDCROSS)), and to this organisation's HQ (REDCROSS's Headquarters) to inform them about the unaccompanied minor placement. Sometimes, due to lack of vacancies in the permanent hosting facilities, a minor could remain more than three months in the safe zone. A public prosecutor is appointed as the legal guardian of the unaccompanied minor.

When the placement is made, the hosting facility receives additional to the placement legal documentation regarding the minor, either from the reception centre, a previous hosting facility, or from the police, where the unaccompanied minor was located beforehand. These documents are copies of the police service note (identity of the unaccompanied minor) and the asylum seeker card (if it exists) that the minor has in their possession. The police service note contains data such as: photograph, citizenship, sex, name, surname, father's name, mother's name, date of birth, passport existence or not, information about the place where the minor will be hosted.

A record of the current occupancy state is also kept by the hosting facilities. This includes the list of minors accommodated and the current vacancies, which is updated when an unaccompanied minor is transported to/from a hosting facility. The unaccompanied minor is informed by the staff about the processes that the facility follows and the risks they face. The social services of the facility fill in the social history form by interviewing the minor. The form contains profiling information that helps identifying risks to the wellbeing of the minor or his environment, or the possibility that the minor may leave the facility by his own accord (voluntary departure), usually without informing anyone. Some of the indications for high-risk cases or possibility of voluntary departure are: an age under 15 years, lack of interest in activities, difficulties adapting to the new environment, distant or aggressive behaviour, declaration that another country or city is their final destination, history or reports of receiving violence and sexual and/or psychological abuse, being marginalised in the reception classes they attend, being pushed into delinquent behaviour, etc. Early assessment of the special needs of a minor is vital to provide appropriate accommodation and support, as well as to predict possible outcomes of the person's stay at the facility. The possible negative outcomes that need to be predicted and prevented are trafficking, abuse, violence, exploitation, lack of care for health issues, either psychiatric or physical, including chronic diseases and other.

Additionally, social media accounts of the minor are requested. If they do not have one, they are suggested to create one (tracing procedure) as a mechanism for the prevention of disappearances and their protection. It has been observed that most of the communication between minors and their families takes place through social media. So, NGOs often use them to keep in touch with minors, even after they leave their care. They are more reliable means of communication than mobile phones since minors often change SIM cards after they leave one country. The social service also notes, if the unaccompanied minor has any friends from other hosting facilities, especially if the unaccompanied minor used to stay in another hosting facility in the past. There have been cases when unaccompanied minors left the hosting facility without notifying the personnel to visit friends in other hosting facilities. Five days after the unaccompanied minor's arrival to the facility, the "Best Interest Assessment (BIA)" form is filled in by the social service of the facility. BIA contains information about the unaccompanied minor, such as: current participation in education activities, additional vulnerability (unaccompanied

child, separated child, disabilities, risk of trafficking or exploitation, psychological issues, medical health issues, early marriage, mental health issues, risk of actual abuse, etc.).

These files are kept at the REDCROSS's hosting facility. Each REDCROSS's hosting facility has its own files and records on the unaccompanied minors it accommodates or accommodated in the past. There is no centralised organisation-wide, country-wide, or international database for storing these data, and every institution keeps its own records. Some of these files are in paper form, while others are in digital format.

Every morning and evening, the residents of the facility are counted. If a minor is missing, they are automatically considered as a "voluntary departure".

The Tracing Service

The main activities regarding the search for a missing or unaccounted person are performed by the tracing service or under its coordination. In general, tracing refers to activities involving the restoration of family links, where a person is looking for another person, who isn't necessarily legally missing or in danger. When communication is restored or is deemed impossible, the tracing procedure ends.

The REDCROSS's Tracing Service opens tracing cases and initiates a tracing procedure only on the ground of an individual request for finding a person placed by a relative residing in the same or another country. The person placing the Tracing Request provides information about the person, such as: if they were on a boat, a possible location, their characteristics, etc. in the framework of a standardised procedure.

Tracing requests are placed by relatives with the assistance of accredited REDCROSS members. The Tracing Request form contains data about the person to be traced, persons(s) that accompanying the sought person, intended final destination, details of enquiry: date, place, details of last news and source of information (exact circumstances that led to the loss of contact), contact details of persons able to provide information, where was the sought person last seen, and information on the enquirer.

Additionally, if a separated or unaccompanied child looks for their family, the "Registration form for separated and unaccompanied children" is filled in by the Tracing department experts. It contains information such as: the identity of the child who looks for their family, any siblings or other children accompanying the child, child's current location, the history of separation, protection concerns (girl mother, street child, etc.), the person(s)/relatives the child wishes to locate, information disclosure, etc.

In case there are indications that the sought person might be dead, an Annex is attached to the tracing request. This annex contains the physical description of the sought person. It is called Physical Description Document (PDD). The PDD contains the following data: physical description, distinguishing features, e.g. visible skin marks (scars, tattoos, birthmarks, etc.), visible medical characteristics (injuries, malformation, etc.), dental distinguishing features: (missing front teeth, gold teeth, etc.), what the sought person was wearing (jewellery, watch, etc.), identity documents (identity card, driving license, credit card) the person might have been carrying, details of type of clothes, etc.

The tracing request and the Annex are saved on a specialised software for tracing (FLAnswers¹).

Another activity of the Tracing Department is "Trace the Face", a tracing program set up by the International Family Links Network consisting by the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) and the Tracing Services of the Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (in Europe initially) to help mainly people on the move, such as refugees and migrants to find their missing family members. 23 countries in Europe participate in the specific program and currently the program is expanding outside Europe as well. On the website <http://www.tracetheface.org>, people who look for missing relatives or who lost contact with their loved ones along the migration route, are able to publish a photo of themselves. Then, this photo is placed on posters hanged on REDCROSS offices and in key places all around Europe. In this way, they increase the chance to find their family, who may look for them too. The only information published is the picture and the nature of the family link to the missing relative. All other information is kept confidential.

Coordination and Collaboration

Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors

Whenever a minor voluntarily departs from a REDCROSS's hosting facility or there is a change on the unaccompanied minor's status, e.g. the minor is transported to another hosting facility, then the facility's social service immediately informs the other accommodation centre (if the child is transported there), the police, the public prosecutor, the Ministry of Migration Policy, the EKKA, and the REDCROSS's Headquarters. Additionally, if a person is transported from a hosting facility that REDCROSS operates to another organisation's hosting facility, the social service of the REDCROSS's facility forwards the minor's file to the new facility.

If a resident of other facility visits a REDCROSS's hosting facility (to meet with friends or family), the social service of the facility informs relevant actors, to verify that the person hasn't been registered as missing.

In case an unaccompanied minor voluntarily departs from a REDCROSS's hosting facility and goes to other country's hosting facility (REDCROSS's or not) and gives the same or a different name than before, there is not any centralised method to cross-check the person's previous accommodation.

One day after the voluntary departure of a person, and if he or she is not accounted for, their place in the facility is considered vacant, so EKKA and the Ministry of Migration Policy are informed, and they are able to issue a new placement order for another unaccompanied minor. Of course, if the unaccompanied minor returns to the hosting facility or transported to another facility and requests to return where they were staying, they are able to do so, but only within the one-day time limit, otherwise the process restarts from an earlier stage.

Concerning REDCROSS's volunteers, there are three types of volunteers: nursing volunteers, volunteers of social welfare and the volunteer Samaritans corps. The REDCROSS's volunteer corps includes more than 12000 active volunteers in Greece. The Samaritans act also as a Search and Rescue Team.

¹ Familylinks Answers is a web-based application that takes advantage of latest technologies. It allows online entry and therefore timely access to the data, and it benefits from ICRC long standing experience and wide range of expertise in managing data and restoring family links.

<https://uncareer.net/vacancy/familylinks-answers-application-integration-specialist-1441>

Additionally, there is cooperation between Samaritans and SoC's volunteers, since the two volunteer networks are complementary.

Furthermore, REDCROSS also collaborates with METAdrasi, which is the first structured Network of specially trained Guardians in Greece, who act in close cooperation with the Public Prosecutors for minors and with the First Instance Public Prosecutors. It supports minors who are detained or staying in accommodation centres and provides them with care specific to their needs². REDCROSS also collaborates with the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), the local medical services in the cities that REDCROSS operates its centres and safe zones, plenty of organisations that deal with children, drug rehabilitation centres, UNHCR.

The Tracing Service

Few volunteers are directly engaged in active tracing activities when required, and they are not necessarily members of Search & Rescue teams. They are dispersed in Greece. Only nine out of the thirteen administrative regions of Greece are covered, which means that when needed, volunteers from other regions travel to perform these activities.

In case the Tracing department decides that a tracing request is a police matter, e.g. when an unaccompanied minor is sought and there are indications that the minor is in imminent danger, the enquirer is suggested to inform authorities. In such cases, humanitarian tracing can also be the case in parallel after the request of the initial enquirer.

If a person being traced might be dead, the Physical Description Document (PDD) is sent to other REDCROSS's divisions (both Greece and other countries) and the forensic team.

In case an active investigation is required, especially regarding disasters (shipwrecks, natural disasters, large scale accidents, etc.), search and rescue teams of the Samaritans might be activated, however with the green light of authorities and in cooperation with the Tracing Service.

Action Stage

Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors

The REDCROSS doesn't perform active investigations in case of an unaccompanied minor's voluntary departure from its shelters.

The Tracing Service

After filling out or receiving the tracing request and if needed coordinate with the authorities, the Tracing Service tries to communicate with the sought person's family members, relatives and acquaintances. If this effort fails and there are indications that the sought person might be in a specific area in the country, and is deemed necessary, the Samaritans corps can be notified to initiate a search and rescue operation according to a standardised operational procedure with the consent of the REDCROSS Governance.

A special case where a form of an active investigation that usually starts with a tracing request can be activated for the specific case of unaccompanied migrant minors under REDCROSS's care, is if there is a natural disaster or other catastrophic event at a location where minors are accommodated. The list of accommodated minors in a hosting facility can be used as a reference document for the Samaritans.

² <http://metadrasi.org/en/campaigns/guardianship-of-unaccompanied-minors/>

During emergencies, all REDCROSS activities are coordinated through a task force consisting of the Heads and Coordinators of the different REDCROSS Divisions and are validated by the REDCROSS Governance (centralised system).

Archiving

For the protection service, if an unaccompanied minor, who voluntarily departed from a REDCROSS's facility, is not detected within one day of their absence, the REDCROSS's social service stops documenting the case. However, the case remains open, until the minor is found. Nevertheless, an unaccompanied minor cease to be under the organisation's care if they reach adulthood while in the care of REDCROSS.

For the Tracing Department, a sought person's case is closed when they are traced, or 3 years after the initial tracing request, or when the tracing request is cancelled. Additionally, in case of an unaccompanied minor's disappearance, if the minor reaches a guardian, the case is closed successfully. Communication of the minor with the guardian is enough; then, the unaccompanied minor's file is updated, and they are no longer considered missing.

The case files for the tracing requests, as well as the files collected for the unaccompanied minors remain secured in the REDCROSS's TS Archives; information extracts and certificates from individual files might be issued after a relative request with the consent of individuals involved and only to serve a humanitarian purpose.

2.1.4.2 TO-BE Scenario

The main purpose of ChildRescue is to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of existing processes, by providing new tools that will help with the coordination and the decision making in the organisations. An important requirement is the enhancement of the coordination mechanisms within the organisation and more specifically between the services for the accommodation and protection of unaccompanied minors and tracing. This is taken into account in the following scenario, by enabling an internal mechanism for information sharing and smooth information flow.

Facility Management

Firstly, the hosting facility management will be enhanced by ChildRescue, as the details of minors who either stay in the facility or have been registered in the organisation and are not hosted by any hosting facility will be kept in digital record. Additionally, the facility manager and the organisation's manager will have an overview of the facility's capacity and the number of its vacancies.

Preparation and Profiling

Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors

A problem in the profiling process is the information discontinuation. For example, an unaccompanied minor is registered multiple times e.g. when the minor is transported from one hosting facility to another, even if managed from the same organisation. Additionally, it is common for a child to go missing and re-emerge in different locations, with the obvious risk of being re-registered. Nowadays, no crosschecking mechanism checks if an unaccompanied minor voluntarily leaves from a hosting facility and reaches another hosting facility in another country or in some cases in the same one, is the same child. EKKA keeps relevant records of the minors, but crosschecking becomes challenging if the minor gives a different name each time, or if their name is spelt differently each time.

To prevent multiple registrations and duplicates, ChildRescue will aggregate the unaccompanied minor's available information of the facilities that they stayed in the past, extending their profile with information that may help with the identification even without providing a name, so that the unaccompanied child will be more easily found and matched. This record will also include information about the locations the minor has been, the routes that she/he followed or intends to follow, etc. This information will be shared between organisations, which operate hosting facilities of unaccompanied minors and will be accessible only to users in the centre of operations of the organisations. Under certain circumstances, it will also be available to users managing the facility centres.

Consequently, paperwork will be reduced and both accommodation and protection, and tracing processes will be reinforced. When a minor is transported to another hosting facility, their record will be transferred as soon as the minor reaches the new hosting facility, instead of copying or physically moving documents. Furthermore, if a minor has voluntarily left a facility and a tracing request has been put on him, the tracing service will be able to search the records and immediately retrieve the relevant information. As a result, there will be better communication and collaboration between the two services. Most of the information collected in the various forms for tracing requests will become part of the profile in the platform.

Lastly, the platform may be used for holding the list of the currently accommodated minors, allowing the facility manager to directly review the names of the minors when counting them and be able to instantly declare that one of them is missing to the operations centre. If there are reasons to suspect that their life is in danger, an active investigation could be also launched.

The Tracing Service

When there is a request to the Tracing Service of the Red Cross, ChildRescue will support the process by allowing the case manager to search the database of currently and previously registered unaccompanied minors, using smart searching techniques. This will allow the case manager to either verify or cross-out shelters from the possible locations that the child may be found.

Coordination and Collaboration

Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors

When there is a change to the unaccompanied minor's status (return or not within 1 day of voluntary departure or minor's transport to another facility), the relevant platform actors will be informed through the platform.

The Tracing Service

Information sharing will be performed by instantly providing access to all or part of the information contained in a minor's profile to the team leaders and possibly to some members of S&R or other volunteer teams. Additionally, checking the availability of volunteer teams' members will be quicker since a request will be broadcasted to all of them at once. This will be extremely helpful on emergencies and natural disasters, where instant help is needed. If there is an active investigation, team members will be able to share multimedia files (e.g. photographs) on the fly with the entire team and team leaders will guide their team members in real-time.

For instance, if volunteers are on a Greek island's beach searching for someone who is on a shipwreck after a tracing request, and there are indications that the person may have reached the shore, and they have only been given a description of the sought person, the organisation could update the profile with

pictures or other information, and instantly make it available to all team members or teams looking for them. In this way, the information will not be scattered.

This sharing of information can become a significant tool for cross-border collaboration, in which, if access is provided between different organisations or national branches of the same organisation, identifying minors that have travelled across borders will be as easy as if they travelled between cities in one country.

Action Stage

The Tracing Service

The ChildRescue platform could assist in locating minors that have voluntarily left a hosting facility and a tracing request has been made for them or in case of natural disasters hitting hosting facilities. For example, if a hosting facility is destroyed by an earthquake, the minors evacuate the facility and the organisation needs to run a Search & Rescue operation. For this reason, the participating volunteer and rescue team members will be provided on-the-fly with the necessary information through the mobile app, about the minors who need to be found. Additionally, location-based alerts and relevant information about the incident could be sent to ChildRescue users in the nearby area.

Archiving

As noted, currently most of the documents kept in every case's record are in paper format. Consequently, the accumulated records over a prolonged period require a lot of physical storage space and searching through them is not efficient. Therefore, ChildRescue aims to reduce the paperwork and printed material by creating, metadata annotated, digital content. This will not only allow for faster search and retrieval of past cases, but also for data analysis in uniformly built historical data. A dashboard with statistics, analytics, and other important information in the passage of time based on the archived records will be a very useful reporting tool and an asset for the organisation.

Finally, when the case is resolved, the case can be closed and then archived after it has been pseudoanonymised, In case there is a "right to be forgotten" request by the data subject, all personal information will be completely anonymized and will not be retrievable anymore.

2.1.4.3 Derived User Requirements

The initial user requirements for the unaccompanied minors use case were initially derived from the AS-IS and TO-BE scenarios in [M3] and have been updated in order to reflect the current understanding of project partners regarding the functionalities that should be offered by the platform. A new sub-process, namely "Facility Management", and two related requirements emerged as a core need of pilot organisations which are responsible for hosting facilities. Except for those requirements, new ones have been added to existing sub-processes and the numbering has been modified accordingly. Minor phrasing changes have been made to the initial requirements, so as to be aligned with the decided platform functionalities and adopted terminology. The updated list of requirements is presented in Table 2-3. The abbreviations of the related actors along with their full description can be found in Table 4-8 of the present deliverable, but a short list of actors abbreviations is also provided in Table 2-1.

Table 2-3 Updated User Requirements for Unaccompanied Minor Use Case

#	Sub-Process	Updated Requirement Description	User group (related Actors)	Remarks
1	Core	Registration to the ChildRescue platform.	All	
2	Core	Different access level and privileges for each user group.	All	
3	Core	Registration of advanced users to the web platform by authorised users, based on a hierarchical model.	NM, CM, FM, OC, OO	New
4	Core	A lightweight app for Visitors and Simple Users.	VU, SU	New
5	Core	An enhanced app for Volunteer/Rescue teams, requiring a special verification process.	RT, TL, NM	New
6	Facility Management	Hosting facility monitoring using a list of hosted minors and their presence status. Facility Managers are informed of minors gone missing through the platform dashboard.	FM, OC	New
7	Facility Management	Overview of facility's capacity and any vacancies.	FM, OC	New
8	Preparation/Profiling	Creation and continuous update of new children profiles using extensive forms. Matching of the new profile with existing ones, in order to avoid multiple registrations.	FM, OC	New
9	Preparation/Profiling	All available information about the unaccompanied minor from current and past hosting facilities are part of its profile record.	CM, FM, OC	Updated
10	Preparation/Profiling	Enhance the minor's profile with multimedia content (e.g. photos) and public social media details.	CM, FM, OC	Updated
11	Preparation/Profiling	Improve the data exchange and synergies between departments of REDCROSS for a more complete profiling process.	CM, OC	Updated
12	Preparation/Profiling	Information sharing between the Organisation and hosting facilities. Easy retrieval of minor's	CM, FM, OC	Updated

		existing record in case of transfer between facilities.			
13	Preparation/ Profiling	In case of a tracing request, an advanced search functionality is provided that goes through the organisation's records seeking matching profiles.	CM, OC	FM, OC	Updated
14	Collaboration/ Coordination	Improve the communication and information exchange between the REDCROSS services, the volunteer corps, the search & rescue teams and the authorities by using a collaboration space.	RT, NM, OC	TL, CM,	Updated
15	Collaboration/ Coordination	Notification of registered Volunteers/Rescue team members on new investigation operations and request for participation. Affirmation of their availability.	RT, NM	TL,	Updated
16	Collaboration/ Coordination	Real-time guidance from Network Managers and Team Leaders through the collaboration space.	RT, NM	TL,	Updated
17	Collaboration/ Coordination	Improve cross-border and international cooperation through data sharing with other REDCROSS national societies, or with other organisations/ NGOs that have adopted ChildRescue.	OC, OO		Updated
18	Collaboration/ Coordination	Notification sent to Volunteer/Rescue team members on emergencies and natural disasters.	RT, NM, CM	TL,	Updated
19	Action Stage	Location-based alerts to citizens regarding a natural disaster or emergency and relevant information.	VU, CM	SU,	Updated
20	Action Stage	Users may provide (anonymously or not) feedback (information, images, location data) regarding minors that went missing during a natural or mass disaster.	VU, RT, TL	SU,	New
21	Action Stage	Registration of received feedback to the blockchain ledger, as an anonymised and privacy-aware log (GDPR compliant)..	CM, OO	OC,	New
22	Action Stage	Necessary information available to participating Volunteer/Rescue team members through an enhanced mobile application.	RT, NM, CM	TL,	Updated

23	Action Stage	Geolocation sharing of Volunteer/Rescue team members (e.g. Samaritans) during their active participation in an operation.	RT, TL, NM, CM	Updated
24	Archiving	After closure of a case, all sensitive/private data will be removed from mobile users' devices.	CM, OC, OO	Updated
25	Archiving	Unify information and eliminate overlaps among departments by using a common database structure. Necessary for analysing past data and finding patterns.	OC	Updated
26	Archiving	Cases and received feedback are semantically annotated for analysis purposes, and then are archived in a privacy-respectful manner.	CM, OC, OO	Updated

2.2 System Requirements

2.2.1 Changes from 1st iteration

The system requirements have been updated since the first iteration, in order to meet the needs of the final Stakeholder Requirements of Section 2.1 **Error! Reference source not found.**. The main updates include the following:

- Social media monitoring has been removed and replaced with information accommodation from social media, since, during the project, the various social media platforms have changed their policy related to data sharing and processing from third parties, due to GDPR.
- The provision of a consent form during the user registration has been clearly stated. The content of the consent form is defined in D2.4.
- The ability of the mobile user to provide information under a pseudonym has been replaced with the option to use the app anonymously (by skipping the registration process).

On what concerns the project's user stories, after the initial set up of the ChildRescue user stories backlog in D1.1, a series of discussions among partners took place, in parallel to design, implementation and pilot activities. These discussions led to adjustments, additions and updates on the list of user stories. Restrictions introduced by the GDPR articles, mainly regarding social media, have been taken into account. Apart from that, in the context of D3.1 – "ChildRescue Architecture and Platform Design", a prioritisation process both from the end-user and technical point of view produced a recommended order for the implementation of user stories. The prioritisation was based on the Lant model³, which was appropriately adapted to reflect the added value of a user story in conjunction with technical feasibility and implementation requirements. The updated user stories are presented in Table 2-8.

³ <https://michaellant.com/2010/05/21/how-to-easily-prioritize-your-agile-stories/>

2.2.2 Generalised System Requirements

In this section, an analysis of the System Requirements will be performed based on the scenarios and the derived user requirements performed in Sections 2.1.3.2, 2.1.4.2 and 2.1.3.3, 2.1.4.3 respectively. The analysis will take the form of the definition of functional and non-functional requirements which will provide input to the second iteration of *Task 3.1-Components and APIs Design and Platform Architecture*. More specifically, the requirements described in the present deliverable address the issue of *what* the system should perform; the technical requirements and the architecture which will be defined in *T3.1* will then address the issue of *how* the functionality derived from the functional and non-functional requirements will be achieved.

The specification of both the functional and non-functional requirements will follow the same approach. All requirements are given a unique identifier. Non-functional requirements will be prefixed by "NFR_" while functional requirements will be prefixed by "FR_" for requirements applicable to both scenarios, "FR_MC_" for requirements applicable to the Missing Children Emergency Use Case and "FR_UM_" for the requirements applicable to the Discovery and Identification Use Case of Unaccompanied Minors.

The phrasing for every requirement will also follow a common schema. Figure 2-5 depicts the sequence of phrases and words used to form a requirement. More specifically,

1. Optionally, define the condition under which this requirement is expected to be fulfilled at first
2. State the name of the "system". ChildRescue will be used exclusively here.
3. Denote whether this requirement is a must-have requirement by using *must*, or a nice-to-have requirement by using *should*.
4. Denote what the system is supposed to do in this requirement. This can be an active process, a process by which the system provides something to other parts of the system/user or a passive process in the sense that the system should be able to react in a specific way under the conditions described.
5. State the object to which the actions performed by the system apply to.
6. Denote any additional details about the object that may be needed.

Figure 2-5 Requirement Specification

For the purposes of the system requirement analysis when a requirement refers to a "user", this will be done in the general user of platform. In case the requirement refers specifically to an operator (a user typically belonging to the organisation staff group) this user will be denoted as "operational user". Users of the mobile application (typically belonging to the volunteers' user group, or citizens) will be

referred as “mobile users”. “Volunteer” or “citizen” will be used if a requirement relevant to a mobile user refers exclusively to a member of the respective sub-group.

The next two sections perform the above exercise for all the identified requirements.

2.2.2.1 Functional Requirements

The functional requirements address specific behaviour and functionality that the ChildRescue platform should have. As noted in Section 2.2.1, three groups of functional requirements are considered, the ones that are common on all use cases, the ones specific to the Missing Children Emergency Use Case and the ones specific to the Discovery and Identification Use Case of Unaccompanied Minors. The set of functional requirements documented in the present deliverable, is derived from the final TO-BE scenarios and reflects, broadly, the set of features that are identified from the stakeholder’s requests. Based on the Methodology of ChildRescue, every functional requirement documented here will be expanded to functional requirements derived for each use case; this process is taking place under the second iteration of *T3.1-Components and APIs Design and Platform Architecture*.

In general, ChildRescue must provide mechanisms for exchanging information between the various user roles within the same organisation and other participating organisations, as well as, between the operational users of the ChildRescue Platform and the volunteers and citizens. Anonymisation and pseudonymisation of the user profile data and the case data should be provided. Alerts should be able to be disseminated to the public, based on the location of the missing child case and the current location of the mobile users.

For the Missing Children Emergency Use Case, volunteers should be notified according to their location, so the mobile application of ChildRescue should be location-aware and provide almost real-time communication for the volunteers’ team coordination.

Table 2-4 summarises the list of general functional requirements while Table 2-5 and Table 2-6 summarise the functional requirements for the cases of Missing Children Emergency Use Case and the Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors Use Case respectively.

Table 2-4 General Functional Requirements

Requirement	Description
FR_1	ChildRescue must provide operational users the ability to dispatch information to field teams
FR_2	ChildRescue must provide operational users the ability to dispatch information to volunteer users
FR_3	ChildRescue must provide operational users the ability to dispatch information between departments
FR_4	ChildRescue must allow operational users to anonymise data
FR_5	ChildRescue must allow operational users to send push notifications to mobile users
FR_6	ChildRescue must be able to accommodate information from public social media accounts.

FR_7	ChildRescue must provide the mobile users that want to register with a consent form
FR_8	ChildRescue must provide the citizens with the ability to provide information as anonymous

Table 2-5 Functional Requirements for the Missing Children Emergency Use Case

Requirement	Description
FR_MC_1	When the functionality is enabled, ChildRescue must provide mobile users with location-based alerts
FR_MC_2	ChildRescue must be able to correlate the location of mobile users with the area of incident.
FR_MC_3	ChildRescue should be able to provide operational users suggestions for next steps regarding the investigation
FR_MC_4	ChildRescue must allow authorised operational users to update the record of any child's case
FR_MC_5	ChildRescue should provide the operational users with suggestions based on analysis of past profiles and past cases
FR_MC_6	ChildRescue should provide the operational users with suggestions based on analysis of social media aggregated data.

Table 2-6 Functional Requirements for the Discovery and Identification Use Case of Unaccompanied Minors

Requirement	Description
FR_UM_1	ChildRescue must provide the operational users the means to digitise any past archived forms
FR_UM_2	ChildRescue must provide the operational users the means to store centrally information needed by the various departments
FR_UM_3	ChildRescue must allow operational users from different teams and departments to exchange information
FR_UM_4	ChildRescue must be able to generate event reports for natural disasters
FR_UM_5	ChildRescue must be able to normalise data by merging duplicate information and categorising existing entries.
FR_UM_6	ChildRescue must be able to analyse missing children profiles
FR_UM_7	ChildRescue should be able to recommend geographical areas to send alerts based on the results of the data analysis.

2.2.2.2 Non-functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements refer to the general operation of the system rather than specific behaviour or functionality. In general, since all agencies work 24/7, the system is expected to have no downtime. Personal data must under no circumstance be exposed, while significant data need to be archived and, if needed, recovered. Generally, response times may not need to be rapid, since the critical processes for finding a child or a parent take place on the field; however, they must be acceptable by the end users (both operators and participating citizens) and should be the lowest possible.

Table 2-7 lists all the non-functional requirements expected to be fulfilled by ChildRescue.

Table 2-7 Non-functional Requirements

Requirement	Description
NFR_1	ChildRescue must have mean time between failures close to zero to address the need of no downtime of the platform
NFR_2	ChildRescue must provide a user with the ability to register with credentials
NFR_3	ChildRescue must be able to protect any personal data stored
NFR_4	ChildRescue must be able to encrypt any data transmitted
NFR_5	ChildRescue should provide the operational user with the ability to operate it in any platform
NFR_6	ChildRescue must be able to archive any significant data required by the operational user
NFR_7	In the case of physical destruction, ChildRescue must be able to recover all significant data
NFR_8	ChildRescue must have acceptable response times
NFR_9	ChildRescue should have low response times
NFR_10	ChildRescue must provide role support with different authorisation levels

2.2.3 Updated User Stories

The updated User Stories table is sorted in decreasing priority order: user stories that acquired relevantly high priority ranking lie higher on the table. User stories that achieved complete development and platform integration in Release I, are highlighted. Reasonably, the development activities for Release I were focused on user stories and functionalities with high ranking, as these combine high added value for the user while being technically feasible at this point of the project or are a prerequisite for components that will be implemented later. Stories that involve more complex functionalities, such as the analytics, will be implemented in the next platform iteration.

The updated user story backlog consists of around 140 user stories. These stories can be considered almost finalized in terms of described functionalities that shall be provided by the ChildRescue platform and mobile application. However, following an Agile approach, user stories can be added, removed or updated at any time as development proceeds and feedback is acquired from the pilot phases. The final user story backlog will be reported in the context of D3.4- "ChildRescue Platform, APIs and Mobile App, Release II" in [M27].

Table 2-8 Updated User Stories Backlog

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
VU.00.0	Download	Visitor	to download the light ChildRescue app	I can be informed, receive alerts and provide feedback.
VU.01.0	Registration	Visitor	to be able to register using minimal details	I can be part of the ChildRescue platform.
VU.01.2	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to use the app without registering	I can still receive alerts and contribute anonymously, without having a ChildRescue account.
VU.01.3	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to allow geolocation services	I can receive alerts based on my current location.
VU.02.0	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view currently active alerts near my vicinity	I can actively participate in the investigation.
VU.04.0	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to visit the page with more information on a single case, when I receive notification for this case	I can view more details concerning the case.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
VU.05.0	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view a list of the participating organisations and their contact details	I can communicate with organisations by other means, such as telephone or postal services.
VU.05.1	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to get informed on the process to become a volunteer for a specific organisation	I can offer my help in a more official and permanent way.
VU.06.0	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view information about the platform, terms of service and usage, etc.	I can be fully aware of what the platform is about and what requirements it involves.
VU.07.0	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view information about DOs and DON'Ts regarding missing children investigation.	I can assist the investigation in an appropriate for the child at risk manner, abiding by the law and respecting human rights.
VU.08.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Visitor	to send geotagged (with a location I can choose from a map or my current mobile location) and timestamped feedback in the form of text and image to the organisation concerning a missing child by filling-in an appropriate form	I can assist in the investigation mission.
VU.08.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Visitor	to be able to submit a piece of information, even for a case I am not informed about with a localised notification (e.g. if I've seen the child via TV alert or otherwise, and I want to give information about it)	I can assist also in cases that I am not actively informed about through ChildRescue.
VU.08.2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Visitor	to view a list with the emergency operating lines of each organisation, with a brief description, when I want to provide input regarding a child and I don't find a matching case in the list	I can assist also in cases that I am not actively informed about, in the most appropriate manner.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
VU.08.3	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Visitor	to view a confirmation screen after I submit feedback	I know that the process has been successful.
SU.04.0	Profile Editing	Simple User	to be able to use my "right to be forgotten" under the GDPR, and permanently remove my account from the system	I am no longer a member of the ChildRescue platform and my personal information cannot be retrieved by any means.
SU.12.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to be able to view all feedback I have submitted through the ChildRescue app	I have an overview of my actions.
SU.15.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to get notified when there is a missing child alert in my vicinity	I can act on it and help the investigation.
SU.16.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to have the option to select and "follow" specific cases	I receive notification if case is closed.
SU.17.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to get notified when a case I follow or had provided feedback for, is closed	I can stop any actions I have started.
FM.01.1	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Manager	Facility to match a new child profile with existing profiles using simple name search (surname, first name)	I can identify if a new coming minor has been registered before or was in another facility before.
FM.02.0	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Manager	Facility to be able to fill in profiling information about an unaccompanied migrant minor residing in the premises	I can keep track of the minors residing in the facility I am responsible for.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
FM.04.1	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to edit the case info and the documents in the ChildRescue platform	I can easily update the record of a minor under my responsibility.
FM.04.2	Facility Management	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to see a list of all children accommodated in a hosting facility	I can have a better overview.
CM.01.0	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to fill in the basic information about a new missing child case	I can provide basic details on that case.
CM.01.2	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to edit the case info and documents in the ChildRescue platform	I can easily find and make changes to the history of a child.
CM.01.3	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to have access to all cases of my organisation	information about the same case is not lost between different case managers and shifts.
CM.01.6	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to find a case that is documented in the system using simple name search	I can see if it is a multiple case and a relevant record already exists in the system.
CM.02.0	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to update and extend the information of a case with more details or specify crucial information (like location last seen, latest info gathered, etc.)	I can offer an updated description of a case.
CM.02.1	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to update the open case record with received feedback, after I have approved this information	all case data is stored in a well-maintained and continuous manner.
CM.02.2	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to tag received feedback as irrelevant/relevant/credible	I can easily assess feedback.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
CM.11.1	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to configure the centre, radius and duration of the alert for the crowdsourcing feedback validation process	I can focus the process.
CM.13.1	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	all notifications sent through the platform to the general public to include only information approved by the authorities	the whereabouts of the missing child cannot be inferred and malicious use of the platform is prevented.
CM.13.2	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	to configure the dissemination area and duration of the alerts that will be sent to users based on my expertise	crowdsourcing is more focused and efficient.
CM.13.3	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to change the configurations of an active alert or even deactivate it	I can have control on the alert system.
CM.13.4	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	the alert to remain on the user's mobile until it expires or is set inactive by me	the location of the alert is not easily inferred.
CM.15.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to get feedback from all available human resources regarding a missing child case (e.g. citizens, anonymous users, volunteers)	I can gather all possible information.
CM.18.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to view all information about a case, sent by all participants, in historical order	I can have a more detailed view on the progress of the investigation.
CM.23.0	Archiving	Organisation Case Manager	the personal case data of a closed case to not be retrievable any more through ChildRescue for any user, if the child has requested it	the rights of the child on its personal data, under GDPR, are respected.
OC.01.0	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Coordinator	To have access to all cases' information and be able to edit, open or close a case	I have total control of all cases.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
OC.06.1	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Coordinator	to have a basic monitoring dashboard for each case	I can understand at which state is each case and what assistance is required.
OO.01.1	Organisation Information Filling	Organisation Owner	to be able to set and edit the basic information about my organisation	I can provide an informative profile of the organisation.
CA.01.0	ChildRescue Administration	ChildRescue Administrator	to create the organisation profile and add organisation owner	the organisation can use ChildRescue.
CA.02.0	ChildRescue Administration	ChildRescue Administrator	to delete an organisation	it is no longer part of the ChildRescue platform.
SU.01.0	Registration	Simple User	to be able to specify some basic, optional personal profile information during the initial registration process	I can have a more complete and reliable personal profile which increases my integrity thus making me a trusted collaborator.
SU.02.0	Profile Editing	Simple User	to be able to edit my personal profile information	I can update my profile if any change occurs.
SU.16.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to have the option to select and "follow" specific cases	I receive notification if case is closed.
SU.17.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to get notified when a case I follow or had provided feedback for, is closed	I can stop any actions I have started.
FM.01.0	Profile Editing	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to edit my personal profile information and add more details regarding my skills, personality or general background.	I can have a more complete personal profile.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
FM.04.0	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to upload documents to the platform concerning the children of my facility	there is a repository of profile records with the corresponding digital files (e.g. id papers, forms, departure report, etc.).
FM.05.0	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to edit/replace the documents I have uploaded to the platform	there is always the updated version of all pieces of information regarding a profile record.
CM.00.0	Profile Editing	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to edit my personal profile information and add more details regarding my skills, personality or general background.	I can have a more complete personal profile.
CM.01.1	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to upload a scanned document of signed consent or other relevant files (reports, testimonies, etc.)	I can have documents related to a case gathered and easily retrievable.
CM.01.2	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to edit the case info and documents in the ChildRescue platform	I can easily find and make changes to the history of a child.
CM.01.8	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	fields of an old case for the same child to be automatically copied to a new case, and then I can check and modify them	I avoid double typing.
CM.05.0	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to add psychological reviews, witness reports, etc.	I can enhance the profiling details of the missing child.
CM.17.1	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to have a basic monitoring dashboard for each case	I can understand at which state the case is.
CM.18.1	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	cases in my dashboard to have a notification sign, if there is an unread update regarding this case	I can distinguish cases with updates which I haven't seen yet.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
CM.18.1.2	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to click on a notification and directly go to the case	I can easily browse all available info on a case and better relate the notification.
CM.18.2	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to easily link related cases or cases of siblings	I work more efficiently but at the same time cover all possible scenarios (children are together or separated).
CM.18.3	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to have a list of missing people cases which are correlated (gone missing together)	I can handle a natural disaster incident efficiently and quickly.
OC.08.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to view all current and past cases (that have not been removed after request of the child) and their full details	I have access to all available information.
OC.09.1	Investigation Management	Organisation Coordinator	to have a log of the activity history (alerts sent, messages sent etc.) of all administrative users (CM, FM, NM)	I have a clear overview of the taken actions and be able to allocate cases accordingly.
OC.10.0	Organisation Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to allow location-based alerts to inform citizens regarding a natural disaster or emergency by having a checkbox "All information included in the message is approved by the authorities" to be checked, in order for the text message to be sent to the public, through ChildRescue	I can inform citizens, always in consultation with the authorities.
OO.02.0	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to be able to view a list of members of my organisation and at what position and general location	I can have an overview of our human resources assignments.
OO.05.0	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to remove users from my organisation	I can re-organise our human resources.
VU.01.1	Registration	Visitor	to have the option to register by using social media accounts	I can be part of the ChildRescue platform.

#	Epic			
		ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
VU.02.1	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to have only one active alert per case	I have a clear overview of cases and my device is not spammed with notifications.
VU.03.0	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to sort the list of alerts on my app based on the disappearance date of the child	I can see the most recent ones.
SU.11.1	Platform Browsing	Simple User	to see statistics (e.g. cases solved per country) in front page if there are no active cases in vicinity, or as menu item if there are	I have a general picture of the work done by the organisations.
FM.05.1	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to mark the absence of a minor living in my hosting facility	I can have an easier overview of the facility and the hosted minors.
FM.05.3	Facility Management	Hosting Facility Manager	the system to be updated regarding vacancies in my hosting facility	everyone responsible is easily informed and can decide on the distribution of the applications for hosting.
FM.07.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to have all historical data of the child under the same case (e.g. previous facilities stayed at)	I can have complete and consistent information about the child, and can extract possible POIs.
FM.10.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Hosting Facility Manager	to have access to the collaboration space so that I get guidance and information about the case	I can be constantly informed about the case's status and act in a more efficient way.
CM.01.31	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to have a prioritised view of the cases based on urgency (amber alert, simple alert, feedback given)	I have a better overview of the cases and most important/urgent ones have a better ranking.
CM.01.4	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to match a new child profile with existing profiles using multiple criteria, fuzzy matching and intelligent methods	I can check if it's a multiple case or if there is an active tracing request.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
CM.01.5	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to find a case that is documented in the system using multiple profiling criteria and fuzzy matching	I can see if it is a multiple case, or there are other cases with strong resemblance.
CM.01.7	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	profiling fields that are common with other existing systems of the organisation (ex. CRM), to automatically take input from these systems through API end-points (if available)	I avoid double typing.
CM.04.0	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to add social media accounts of the child and relevant information	I can enhance the profiling process by using knowledge extraction on social profile preferences, activities, public posts, etc., in alignment with GDPR.
CM.05.1	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to perform profiling analytics	I can have insights and predictions on behavioural patterns of the case.
CM.07.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to engage in discussions with user groups (e.g. volunteers, rescue teams) regarding the same case and a specific location	I can carry forward relevant information in a secure and private virtual space and exchange real-time messages.
CM.07.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to set up a collaboration space dedicated to the missing child case and uniquely identified by the given search area (note: we may have multiple search areas for the same case)	I can invite rescue and volunteer teams close to the area, monitor and manage them.
CM.08.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to upload/download files of information in the collaboration space	I can exchange multimedia files, like photos or videos, with the case members.
CM.12.0	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to configure the settings of the feedback evaluation validation process	I can evaluate a piece of information based on criteria of my choice.

# Epic				
		ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
CM.16.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to view and explore open data	to get more and location-related information about transportation, weather etc.
CM.17.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to monitor the overall progress of the investigation	I can understand at which state it is.
CM.18.4	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to ensure that all feedback from mobile users will remain logged and unchanged	the platform operates based on integrity and trust.
CM.20.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to upload my evaluation report for the Coordinator to view	the important information propagates to the top.
CM.20.1	Archiving	Organisation Case Manager	to archive a closed case	the case is removed from the active cases list, is appropriately tagged and can be used as a new input in analytics.
CM.20.2	Archiving	Organisation Case Manager	to mark as true or false all received feedback on a finished case	I can use this information for analytics.
CM.20.3	Archiving	Organisation Case Manager	to semantically tag a closed case	it can be easier matched to similar past or future cases.
CM.22.0	Archiving	Organisation Case Manager	the case data of a closed case to be deleted from the mobile users' devices within a fixed period of time	the privacy of the child and family is protected after closure.
RT.00.0	Registration	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to be able to sign in to the enhanced app for rescue teams following a two-step verification process	I can have access to the S&R/ operational/coordination functionalities of ChildRescue in a safe manner.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
RT.01.0	Profile Editing	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to be able to edit my personal profile information and add more details regarding my skills, personality or general background.	I can have a more complete personal profile.
RT.02.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to get notified when there is a missing child case and my contribution is required	I can act on it and help the investigation in the field.
RT.02.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to be able to decline an invitation to join investigation team and continue as a simple user for this specific case if at all	if I am not able to actively participate as a team member, still be able to help and receive location-based notifications as any simple registered user.
RT.03.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to have access to a collaboration space with other team-members and case coordinators	I can communicate with my team in a secure and private virtual space.
RT.03.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to be able to turn my geolocation off temporarily, but continue receiving the messages and notifications of the discussion team	I can pause and rest from an active investigation I am taking part in, but still be updated with latest news.
RT.03.2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to be able to quit from an investigation case and the related collaboration space	I can disengage from the search operations of this case and the respective team's affairs.
RT.05.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to get guidance and announcements about the case from my superiors	I can be constantly informed about the case's status and act in a more efficient way.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
RT.05.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to have a list of actions to perform and be able to mark them when done	I have a clear overview of what I have to do.
TL.01.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Leader	to be able to watch my current location, as well as other teams/team members' locations, on an interactive map	I can have a clear overview of the team's current situation and the area each member covers.
TL.02.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Leader	to get guidance and announcements about the case from coordinators	I can be constantly informed about the case's status and act in a more efficient way.
TL.03.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Leader	to have access to a collaboration space with teams and case coordinators with the ability to upload/download files	I can offer the necessary information (e.g. a profile record) to the investigation group or my superiors.
NM.01.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	To get notified as soon as there is a new case that requires my skills	I can act rapidly to assemble the appropriate teams.
NM.02.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to invite available Volunteer/S&R members, to join the collaboration space	we can setup a collaboration space about the case and the investigation.
NM.02.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to notify with free-text message all volunteers of local S&R Teams or/and Volunteer Teams of the new case and receive their availability	I can setup teams for the investigations and give volunteers some basic contact details.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
NM.02.2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to receive a confirmation of delivery for every invitation I have sent to volunteers	I know if my notification has reached the members.
NM.02.3	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to manually assign the team leader of every volunteer/S&R team from the available members	it is easier to coordinate separate teams.
NM.02.5	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to notify new members and teams to join the collaboration space according to the investigation progress, especially if a new geographical location is suggested	adequate rescuers and volunteers are participating in each stage and place of the investigation.
NM.03.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to engage in discussions with selected team leaders and case managers	I can guide my teams in a secure and private virtual space.
NM.03.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to post announcements for all team members participating in the case to view, similar to a news feed	I can give one-way instructions to the teams, which will be easily viewable.
NM.03.2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to mark important announcements in the timeline with different colour (highlight)	the volunteers can easily see what I think is important.
NM.03.3	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	assign actions to be performed to participating team members	they can have a clear view of what they have to do.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
NM.03.4	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to create discussions with selected members from the volunteer/S&R teams for communications	I can instantly exchange information with team leaders.
NM.05.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to contact and get guidance by the Organisation Coordinator	I can be constantly informed about all cases' status and distribute human resources accordingly and more efficiently.
NM.06.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to view where all field resources (humans, vehicles, dogs) are located	I can be constantly informed about the status and whereabouts of all field resources.
NM.07.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to monitor the current progress of the investigation location-wise	I can direct teams to search in specific areas.
NM.08.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to view predictions regarding the possible POIs related to the missing child	I can direct teams to search in specific areas.
NM.09.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to send my evaluation and current status to the Coordinator	the important information propagates to the top.
OC.02.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to communicate with all Case and Network Managers through the collaboration space.	I can coordinate all available resources.
OC.02.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to access case-related files and documents	I can view more explicit case information and reporting.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
OC.02.2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to send the case files and documents to organisations in another country	I can rapidly inform and activate legitimate organisations in case of a cross-border country.
OC.03.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to exchange messages with users in the collaboration space (e.g. volunteers, rescue teams)	I can carry forward relevant information in a secure and private virtual space.
OC.05.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to contact the mobile users of the platform personally	I can send and get information directly from users.
OC.06.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Coordinator	to monitor the overall progress of all the active investigations per location	I can understand at which state is each case and what assistance is required.
OC.09.0	Investigation Management	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to assign Case and Network Managers for each case	each case is covered in the most efficient way.
OC.11.0	Archiving	Organisation Coordinator	to aggregate data from past cases	useful outcomes are provided to be exploited in the future, in a manner always respecting privacy issues.
OC.12.0	Archiving	Organisation Coordinator	statistics to be generated from every case and to be correlated	I gain insights in the performance of the organisation.
OO.01.0	Organisation Information Filling	Organisation Owner	to receive invitation to activate my organisation's profile in ChildRescue	I take control of the new profile and start managing it.
OO.03.0	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to be able to send invitation e-mails to my personnel and associated with their new accounts in the platform	they join the platform and I can gather all my human resources in this collaboration platform.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
OO.04.0	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to create profiles in the ChildRescue platform for administrative users of my organisation (OC, CM, FM, NM)	I can add admins of my organisation to the platform.
OO.04.1	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	To setup organisation facilities and assign members in each one	I can have all of my members assigned to one location (facility) for better management.
OO.07.0	Organisation Monitoring	Organisation Owner	to have an overview of all active cases and the human resources (e.g. organisation members, volunteers, etc.) assigned on each one	I can have a clear picture of the current effort and possible deficiencies.
OO.08.0	Organisation Monitoring	Organisation Owner	to have an overview of the duration of all historical cases and the human resources assigned on each one	I can have a clear picture of the past performance of my staff.
OO.10.0	Organisation Communication	Organisation Owner	to be able to communicate with other organisations using their e-mail	we can cooperate together in a mission or cause.
OO.11.0	Organisation Policy	Organisation Owner	all case data to be anonymised if there is a request related to the "right to be forgotten" according to GDPR.	the privacy of the family and the child are protected and my organisation is aligned to the GDPR requirements.
OO.12.0	Organisation Policy	Organisation Owner	all case data to be encrypted	I ensure my organisation's policies regarding personal and private data.

2.2.4 Integrated Use Case Scenarios

2.2.4.1 Use Case Scenario 1: Missing Children Emergency

This scenario involves a standard case where a child goes missing from his home, his parents report the incident, an Amber Alert is raised, the community and search parties become engaged, and the child is located and returned to his family. The procedure follows the processes as described in the Stakeholders' Requirements and the System Requirements sections, emphasising the contribution of the ChildRescue parallel processes along the way. Processes or events that are outside of the immediate interest of ChildRescue as an enhancement of already existing operations are either omitted or only briefly mentioned. Those that refer to the User Stories from this document also include their corresponding Epic's User Story code.

The actors involved in this scenario are the following:

Missing Child, Parent/Guardian/Relative of the missing child, Visitor, Simple User, Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Member, Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Leader, Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator Manager

The Scenario:

A parent contacts the Organisation Case Manager (call operator), conveying, by phone, that a missing child report has been made to the police. The Case Manager verifies this with the police. The Organisation Case Manager creates a Case file in ChildRescue (CM.01.0, CM.01.2), asks for and enters the basic information in the case. The Case Manager requests and receives from the parent and/or the police other relevant information, such as pictures, location last seen, social media accounts etc. that get entered in ChildRescue (CM.01.1, CM.02.0, CM.02.1, CM.04.0). An Amber Alert is requested to be created and is issued. The Case Manager creates a relevant alert in the ChildRescue platform by configuring the centre, radius and duration of the alert (CM.11.1) and assures that all notifications sent through the ChildRescue to the general public include only information approved by the authorities (CM.13.1). An evaluation of the profile and the case is added to the platform (CM.05.0), while performing in parallel analytics about the profile (CM.05.1). A proposal for the possible location to look at leads to the creation of localised notifications for the mobile application Visitors and Simple Users, including some extended areas along public transportation routes (CM.12.0).

A Simple User who is about ten kilometres away from the area where the child went missing has already registered with the platform via the mobile application eponymously (SU.01.0, SU.02.0). While driving his car near a forest area, he sees at the edge of the road a child that seems disoriented. After a few minutes and wondering what he should do, he opens the ChildRescue mobile application. He sees an alert of a child looking like the one he saw on the street went missing about ten kilometres away from his current position. He decides to "follow" the specific case (SU.16.1). He then receives a localised notification (SU.15.0), that the child he thought to have seen might be near him, based on the possible public transportation routes and their range. He opens the Missing Child card in the application and selects to notify the organisation looking for him, by providing feedback. He selects the exact spot on the online map where he believes he saw the child (VU.08.0, VU.08.1 (inherited by the Visitor actor), SU.12.1) and adds some description. He then receives a confirmation on his screen that the feedback he submitted has been successfully sent (VU.08.3 (inherited by the Visitor actor)).

The Case Manager that monitors the investigation has received a number of messages that end up being false alarms (CM.15.0, CM.17.0, CM.18.0, CM.18.1). The Case Manager also monitors the missing

child's social account for new public posts but nothing has been uploaded (CM.16.0). Then, she sees the message sent by the aforementioned Simple User. She examines the details provided and decides to contact the Simple User through his mobile phone number which is available since he is a registered user. The Simple User and the Case Manager discuss about the case, the latter adds the witness report to the platform, and she tags the received information as relevant (CM.02.0, CM.02.1, CM.02.2, CM.05.0, CM.05.1).

The Organisation Coordinator receives a request from the Case Manager (OC.02.0) and opens the list of active cases and the map (OC.06.0). Looking at the specific case (OC.01.0), he determines that the witness report could be valid and assigns the Network Manager to perform a Search & Rescue Operation giving him information about the case and a specific location to search (OC.01.0, OC.02.0, OC.09.0).

The Network Manager receives his assignment and the information regarding the case (NM.01.0, NM.05.0). He initiates an active Search & Rescue operation and notifies the appropriate team members (NM.02.0). While the operation is active, he monitors and coordinates the communication of the search team and exchanges crucial information in the form of messages and additional pictures of the missing child (NM.03.0, NM.03.1, NM.03.2, NM.03.4) by locating them on the map, widening and generally modifying the search area as time passes (NM.06.0, NM.07.0, NM.08.0).

A Search & Rescue Team Leader gets notified. Then, a Team Member receives a notification that his team was requested to search for the missing child in a pinpointed area on the map, together with the location where the team will gather up and additional pictures (RT.02.0, TL.03.0). He couldn't accept the invitation due to an illness and he declines to join the investigation (RT.02.1). Another Search & Rescue Team Member gets notified, who accepts the invitation (RT.02.0). He confirms his availability (RT.03.0), prepares himself and goes to that location. When reaching the location where the search is going to start, he receives updated information on the case with the new radius and locations to look at (RT.05.0). The team coordinates with the police where everyone is going to be headed and start to look for the child. A Team Member starts looking for the child and after a while he sees a child sitting exhausted under a tree. Speaking calmly to the child, he takes a geo-tagged picture of the child and sends it to the group discussion, mentioning that he found a child who seems to be the one they were looking for (RT.03.0).

The Network Manager receives the latest information and updates from the Coordinator and the Case Manager that the child may have been found, providing the picture and the location on the map (NM.03.0, NM.09.0). The Case Manager contacts the police in case the Search & Rescue Team member hasn't already informed the police regarding the location of the sighting. The police reach the point, pick up the child, and the Network Manager notifies the team that the search is over, and the child was found (NM.03.0). The team evacuates the area.

After validation by the police that the child was identified as the one missing, the Case Manager closes and archives the case (CM.20.1). The Simple User gets notified that the case he followed and provided feedback for, is now closed (SU.17.0).

2.2.4.2 Use Case Scenario 2: Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minor and natural disaster

This scenario dives deeper into the case where a child isn't missing, but has the status of an unaccompanied minor, who is in the care of the organisation in a hosting facility. In this scenario actions regarding profiling, coordination and communication mostly refer to those that are done pre-emptively

in case the minor goes missing. This is done to cover for the lack of communication with a parent or close relative that could have provided extensive profiling information if requested. The scenario involves a minor who enters a facility and then leaves for another facility along the expected trail towards his final destination in another country to find relatives. If the minor goes missing from the facility in circumstances that might warrant the issuing of an Amber Alert or another kind of active investigation, the provisions of Use Case Scenario 1 apply, with the additional conditions that the police might not be involved and that the status of the legal guardian may be given to either the Hosting Facility Manager or a prosecutor. Instead of running this part of the scenario in this case, we are considering the possibility that a natural disaster occurs near the area of the second hosting facility and the active investigation has to do with multiple minors residing there. Like the Use Case Scenario 1, the focus is on the activities ran only by the organisation, are related to the ChildRescue platform, and the corresponding Epic's User Story code is mentioned. Additionally, a number of the activities concerning the active investigation is omitted, as they are already described in the Use Case Scenario 1.

The actors involved in this scenario are the following:

(potentially) Missing Child, Hosting Facility Manager, Visitor, Simple User, Search & Rescue Team Member, Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Leader, Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator Manager

The Scenario:

An unaccompanied migrant minor who is appointed to stay at a Hosting Facility meets the Hosting Facility Manager. The Hosting Facility Manager interviews the minor and asks a series of questions while he searches in ChildRescue using that information for a match using name search (FM.01.1). He doesn't find one, so he creates a new profile and starts to fill it in with information coming from the documents given and the minor's answers (FM.02.0). He then proceeds to upload the information to the minor's profile and edit them accordingly (FM.04.0, FM.04.1, FM.05.0). One piece of information given by the minor is that his final destination is another country. A month later, while counting the minors in the morning, the Hosting Facility Manager notices that the minor left during the night (FM.04.2, FM.05.1). Asking the other residents what happened, he concludes that the minor has resumed traveling towards his destination but might visit a cousin who resides in another hosting facility. He notifies the Organisation's Case Manager about the fact and sends some additional information (FM.10.0, CM.01.1). The Case Manager requests assistance from the Organisation Coordinator and sends him the relevant profile and his assertion (CM.12.0, OC.02.0) that an active investigation isn't warranted (CM.20.0). The Coordinator concurs, closes the case (OC.01.0) and files in a brief report.

A few weeks later the minor reappears with fresh paperwork in a Hosting Facility of the same organisation but in another country along the route towards his destination. The Hosting Facility Manager interviews the minor and asks a series of questions while he searches on the ChildRescue platform using the given information and looking for a match (FM.01.1). The minor says that he travels from his home country towards a city in the current country where his family lives. When asked about residing in other Hosting Facilities in the past, he says that he doesn't remember the names of the places he has been but says that it was an island in the country he was before. The Hosting Facility Manager searches the platform using the minor's name, as well as other details that may uniquely identify the child. He finds a match and updates the profile with the new assignment to the facility and the documents provided (FM.01.1, FM.02.0, FM.04.0, FM.04.1, FM.05.0, FM.07.0). He consults the

previous Hosting Facility Manager if there were any special issues and concerns that haven't been entered in the profile about the minor (FM.10.0) and gets a negative reply.

A few weeks later a natural disaster hits the second facility. The residencies are evacuated hastily, the buildings are damaged, but the circumstances don't allow the minors and the workers of the facility to meet somewhere in an organised way. The Hosting Facility Manager finds a few minors and reports the rest of them as potentially missing to a Case Manager (FM.05.1). The Case Manager, in collaboration with the Coordinator and Network Manager organise a Search & Rescue mission and the Hosting Facility Manager stays informed through the case's collaboration space (FM.10.0). The Search & Rescue Team members are notified by the Network Manager, who assigns one as Team Leader; they meet on a specific location and start their search. Whenever a minor is found, the Hosting Facility Manager is notified (FM.10.0) and the minor is transferred to the temporary accommodation that was set up. After all minors have been accounted for, the missing children cases close and they are returned to their previous status (OC.01.0) by the Coordinator, who also files a brief report regarding the events.

3 Part B: Regulatory Framework for data protection, privacy and ethical issues

3.1 Overview of main properties of ChildRescue Platform

3.1.1 Changes from 1st iteration

Since the 1st iteration a detailed presentation of data controllers, data processors and data subjects as well as of anticipated processing activities of personal data is available in D5.3-“ChildRescue Data Management Handling Plan”, Section 2.3 *Data Security and GDPR Compliance*.

3.1.2 ChildRescue data controllers and processors, subjects of data and data to be collected, shared and processed and processing activities

In the following Tables information is summarised regarding data controllers, processors and recipients; the ten distinct groups of data subjects that are expected to be involved in ChildRescue; the specific personal identifiable information to be collected, stored and processed per data subjects’ group and the provisioned processing activities.

Table 3-1 ChildRescue Data Controllers, Data Processors and Data Recipients

Role	Entities
Data Controllers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ The Smile of the Child (SoC) ▶ Foundation for Missing and Sexually Exploited Children (Child Focus) ▶ Hellenic Red Cross (REDCROSS)
Data Processors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ SINGULARLOGIC ANONYMI ETAIREIA PLIROFORIAKON SYSTIMATON KAI EFARMOGON PLIROFORIKIS (SLG) ▶ UBITECH LIMITED (UBITECH) ▶ SUITE5 DATA INTELLIGENCE SOLUTIONS LIMITED (S5)
Data Recipients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ European Federation for Missing and Sexually Exploited Children AISBL - Missing Children Europe (MCE) ▶ Pilot partners on other organisations’ cases ▶ Citizens

Table 3-2a Personal Identifiable Information to be collected for Missing Children (DS_01, DS_02) & Stakeholders (DS_03)

Subjects of data	Children		stakeholders
	Unaccompanied migrant minors (DS_02)	Missing children (DS_01)	Parents/guardians/tracing applicants (DS_03)
<i>Type of data</i>			
<i>contact details/ mobile phone¹</i>	1	1	
<i>name</i>			
<i>surname</i>			
<i>sex</i>			
<i>father's name</i>			
<i>mother's name</i>			
<i>date of birth</i>			
<i>physical description</i>			
<i>eye colour</i>			
<i>hair colour</i>			
<i>Height</i>			
<i>Weight</i>			
<i>last clothes worn</i>			
<i>the last place child had been seen</i>			
<i>information mined from child's public social media profiles and activities for identifying activity and mobility patterns</i>			
<i>recent photograph</i>			
<i>health issues</i>			
<i>places recently visited</i>			
<i>interests</i>			
<i>biometric data</i>			
<i>include social background</i>			
<i>habits</i>			
<i>mental health</i>			
<i>citizenship</i>			
<i>passport</i>			
<i>record of hosting facilities the minor was placed under 15 years old</i>			
<i>contacts in their home country</i>			
<i>contacts in current country</i>			
<i>contacts in destination country</i>			
<i>current participation in education activities</i>			
<i>additional vulnerability flags</i>			
<i>behavioural characteristics</i>			
<i>declaration that another country or city is their final destination</i>			
<i>history or reports of receiving violence and sexual and/or psychological abuse</i>			
<i>history or reports of being marginalised in the reception classes they attend</i>			
<i>being pushed into delinquent behaviour</i>			
Tracing and Search & Rescue			
<i>identity of the person(s) who requested the tracing</i>			
<i>timeline of separation</i>			
<i>physical description</i>			
<i>distinguishing features</i>			
<i>dental distinguishing features</i>			
<i>what the sought person was wearing (jewellery, watch, etc.)</i>			
<i>the existence but not the content of identity documents (identity card, driving license, credit card)</i>			
<i>details of type of clothes</i>			
<i>relation to missing child</i>			
<i>profiling information (derived from psychological, behavioural or other evaluations by the caseworkers)</i>			

Table 3-2b Personal Identifiable Information to be collected for ChildRescue Users (DS_05, DS_06 and DS_07) & Professionals (DS_04, DS_08, DS_09 and DS_10)

	ChildRescue Users			Professionals			
Subjects of data <i>Type of data</i>	Registered identifiable (DS_05)	Registered non-identifiable (DS_06)	Anonymous users (DS_07)	IT - Platform Administrators (DS_10)	within or outside the operating organisation (not platform users) (DS_08)	operating the system (DS_04)	IT - Platform Developers/ Testers (DS_09)
<i>contact details/ (optional)</i>			1				
<i>name</i>							
<i>surname</i>							
<i>organization</i>							
<i>role in the organization</i>							
<i>qualifications</i>							
<i>eye-witness report (optional)</i>							
<i>validated identity</i>							
<i>organisational role</i>							
<i>thematic responsibilities</i>							
<i>geographic responsibilities</i>							
<i>organisational responsibilities</i>							
<i>IP address</i>							

Table 3-3 Processing activities per Personal Identifiable Information foreseen to take place in the ChildRescue platform

Processing activity	Personal Identifiable Information
Collecting and storing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal Identifiable Information for the groups: DS_01, DS_02, DS_03, DS_04, DS_05, DS_08. Policies of data privacy and security are applied.
Profiling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal Identifiable Information for each individual case (i.e. child belonging in group of DS_01 or DS_02) are semantically enriched in order to provide a multilayer profile of each person that is reported as missing, constructed by the responsible agencies (DS_03, DS_04). The combined personal profile is generated after applying Sentiment Analysis and Social Network Analysis techniques, as well as the principles of Activity Theory on the online presence and behaviour of the missing child in popular social networks.
Notifications and Alerting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real-time and feedback-based mobile alerts and updates including some of the data of DS_01, DS_02 are shared with the citizens (DS_05, DS_06, DS_07) who are located in specific geographic areas that are defined by the operating users (DS_04) in order to assist the investigation process of a specific case. The location of the citizens is also utilised by the ChildRescue platform, but mostly on the mobile app.
Predictive analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Profile and historical data as well as data being originated from social media and open repositories are gathered in order to provide suggestions and predictions about the investigation of the case (i.e. possible routes that the missing person may have taken).
Blockchain Case Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New evidence about a case (i.e. hashed information and user id) is registered in a blockchain. The blockchain is accessed only by authorised users (DS_04, DS_10, DS_09).

Archiving	► The responsible authorities (DS_04) handle the case's closure in a secure and privacy-respectful manner. Semantic annotation of the documentation and lessons learnt of the case are provided internally in order to support its retrieval in case of similar cases in the future. In the case of the mobile application towards the community, all data related to the specific case are erased from the citizens' devices (DS_05, DS_06, DS_07), leaving behind only the non-personal information, statistics and outcome of the specific case.
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3.2 Legal Framework

3.2.1 Changes from 1st iteration (SoC)

European Legislation

No changes since 1st iteration

Greek Legislation

On 20 February 2018, the then-Minister for Justice, Transparency and Human Rights announced the opening of the public consultation on the legislative initiative of the Ministry entitled "*Adoption of legislative measures for the implementation of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) and transposition to the national law of the Directive 2016/680/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offenses or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA*". In the same announcement it was noted that "*the consultation will be completed on Monday 5 March 2018*".⁴

Indeed, public online consultation was completed in March 5 2018 but since then the draft law has not been submitted to Hellenic Parliament to be ratified and, therefore, Greece has not yet issued a national law implementing the GDPR; moreover, there is no official information regarding next steps.

In July 2019 all EU Member States have already updated their national legislation for the protection of personal data according to the EU regulations with the exception of few countries, including Greece.⁵ To this end, Greece is currently subject to Law 2472/1997 (as amended by Laws 3471/2006, 3783/2009, 3947/2011, 4024/2011, 4070/2012 and 4139/2013), which implements the Data Protection Directive, until 25 May 2018.

In May 5, 2019, however, a Decision was published in Government Gazette by the Hellenic Data Protection Authority (HDPa), following the GDPR Article 35.4 (Data protection impact assessment); specifically, HDPa established and made public a list of the kind of processing operations which are subject to the requirement for a data protection impact assessment pursuant to paragraph 1 of the

⁴ Public Consultation on draft law available at: <http://www.opengov.gr/ministryofjustice/?p=9331>

⁵ As a result, the European Commission decided to refer Greece to the Court of Justice of the EU for failing to make the EU rules on personal data protection into a law (the Data Protection Law Enforcement Directive, Directive (EU) 2016/680). In April 2016, the Council and the European Parliament agreed the Directive had to be transposed into national law by 6 May 2018. Source: <https://safety4sea.com/eu-fines-greece-spain-for-not-making-gdpr-a-law/>

same article provisioning that “Where a type of processing in particular using new technologies, and taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing, is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the controller shall, prior to the processing, carry out an assessment of the impact of the envisaged processing operations on the protection of personal data. A single assessment may address a set of similar processing operations that present similar high risks” (GDPR 35.1).⁶

3.2.2 European Legislation

Missing children successful investigation and rescue involves among other things the storage and processing of the minor’s and his/her family personal data. The development of a mobile application that will engage several users, actors and authorities intends to accelerate the missing child’s recovery. In this context, law concerning data protection and personal data processing shall be taken into consideration, in order for the ChildRescue application to be fully aligned with current international, European⁷ and national legal provisions.

3.2.2.1 The right to private life and data protection

For the first time, a right to protection of an individual’s private sphere against intrusion from others, especially from the state, was established in Article 12 of the United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) of 1948 on respect for private and family life⁸. Thereafter European legal instruments have been influenced and established. The right to data protection evolved out of the right to respect for private life.

The European Convention on Human Rights

The Council of Europe, as it was formed in the aftermath of the Second World War, adopted the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (European Convention on Human Rights - ECHR)⁹ in 1950, which entered into force in 1953¹⁰. ECHR sets forth a number of fundamental rights and freedoms (right to life, prohibition of torture, prohibition of slavery and forced labour, right to liberty and security, right to a fair trial, no punishment without law, right to respect for private and family life, freedom of thought, conscience and religion, freedom of expression, freedom of assembly and association, right to marry, right to an effective remedy, prohibition of discrimination). More rights are granted by additional protocols to the Convention. Noteworthy that,

⁶ List of the kind of processing operations which are subject to the requirement for a data protection impact assessment pursuant to GDPR Article 35(4) ([Government Gazette B’ 1622/10-5-2019](#)).

⁷ For the structure of the European legal framework, the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA), Handbook on European data protection law, 2014, available at: http://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra-2014-handbook-data-protection-law-2nd-ed_en.pdf has been also considered.

⁸ United Nations (UN), Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), 10 December 1948, available at: <http://www.un.org/en/universal-declaration-human-rights/index.html>.

⁹ CoE, European Convention on Human Rights, CETS No. 005, 1950, available at: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/005>.

¹⁰ States have an international obligation to comply with the ECHR and to this end, the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR), was set up in 1959, where complaints from individuals, groups of individuals, NGOs or legal persons and States alleging violations of the Convention are received and considered to ensure the observance of the engagements undertaken by the Parties. To date, the Council of Europe comprises of 47 member states, out of which are 28 EU member states; <https://www.coe.int/en/web/about-us/who-we-are>

under the Lisbon Treaty, fundamental rights, as guaranteed by the ECHR and as they result from the constitutional traditions of the Member States, constitute the general principles of the Union's law¹¹.

Under the ECHR the right to protection of personal data is guaranteed in Article 8 as part of the right to respect for private and family life, home and correspondence and lays down the conditions under which restrictions of this right are permitted, such as when in accordance with law and in the interests of public security and public safety, for the prevention of disorder or crime, for the protection of rights and freedoms of others.

Council of Europe Convention 108

In need for the development of more detailed rules to safeguard individuals by protecting their personal data and following a series of resolutions that were adopted by the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe,¹² in 1981 the Convention for the protection of individuals with regard to the automatic processing of personal data (Convention 108)¹³ was opened for signature¹⁴. Convention 108 applies to all data processing carried out by both the private and public sector, here including the judiciary and law enforcement authorities and seeks to regulate the trans-border flow of personal data. It lays down principles for the collection and processing of personal data in order to protect the individual from abuses during these processes, namely fair and lawful collection and automatic processing of data, storage for specified legitimate purposes (legitimacy) and for the time necessary and appropriate and use compatible with the legitimate purposes. Data processed shall be adequate, relevant, proportionate to the purpose and accurate (quality of data; proportionality). At the same time, 'sensitive data', such as a person's race, politics, health, religion, sexual life or criminal record are excluded from collection and processing, unless the necessary legal requirements are met. Moreover, under the Convention the individual has the right to be aware that information is stored on him or her and, if necessary, to react (transparency and free, specific and informed consent). Restrictions on the provided rights are possible only when overriding interests, such as state security or defence, are at risk.

In 2017 the Consultative Committee of the Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to automatic processing of personal data issued the Guidelines on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data in a world of big data¹⁵. These comprise of recommendations to state parties to the Convention, controllers and processors to undertake measures related to data

¹¹ Article 1 of the Lisbon Treaty amending article 6 para 3 of the Rome Treaty.

¹² Resolution (73) 22 on the protection of the privacy of individuals *vis-à-vis* electronic data banks in the private sector, 26 September 1973; CoE, Committee of Ministers (1974), Resolution (74) 29 on the protection of the privacy of individuals *vis-à-vis* electronic data banks in the public sector, 20 September 1974).

¹³ CoE, Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, Council of Europe, CETS No. 108, 1981, available at: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/108>. In 1999, Convention 108 was amended to enable the EU to become a Party (see Art. 23 (2) of the Convention 108 in its amended form). In 2001, an Additional Protocol to Convention 108 was adopted, introducing provisions on transborder data flows to non-parties (third countries) and on the mandatory establishment of national data protection supervisory authorities; available at: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/181>. Note: Greece and Belgium have not ratified the Protocol.

¹⁴ Up to date, all 47 members of the Council of Europe have ratified the Convention and 4 non-members of the CoE. Convention 108 is the only legally binding international instrument in the data protection field.

¹⁵ Available at: <https://rm.coe.int/16806ebe7a>

protection for the prevention of potential negative impact of the use of Big Data¹⁶ on human dignity, human rights and fundamental freedoms. The purpose is to limit the risks for data subjects' rights, such as the potential bias of data analysis, the underestimation of the legal, social and ethical implications of Big Data on decision-making processes (e.g. mere de-contextualised information being the grounds of a decision), and the marginalization of an effective and informed involvement by individuals in these processes (e.g. in case of power imbalance between controller and data subject). Finally, modernization proposals for the Convention 108 have been elaborated since 2013 transmitting a draft amending protocol in 2016, but it has not been finalised yet.

European Union data protection law

EU law is composed of primary EU law, namely Treaty on European Union (TEU)¹⁷ and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU - Lisbon Treaty)¹⁸ and secondary EU law, i.e. regulations, directives and decisions of the EU.

The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union

In 2000 the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (Charter)¹⁹ was proclaimed²⁰ by the EU. Though a political document at first, the Charter became legally binding as EU primary law with the coming into force of the Lisbon Treaty in 2009²¹.

The rights enshrined in the Charter are divided into six sections: dignity, freedoms, equality, solidarity, citizens' rights and justice. The Charter guarantees the respect for private and family life²², and explicitly raises the level of data protection to that of a fundamental right in EU law by establishing the right to data protection²³. It refers to key data protection principles, such as fair processing and for specific purpose, individual's consent or based on other legal basis²⁴, and ensures that an independent authority will control the implementation of these principles²⁵.

3.2.2.2 General Data Protection Regulation

Under article 16 of the TFEU, where the right to protection of personal data is safeguarded, the competency of the European Parliament and the Council to legislate on data protection matters is foreseen²⁶. The principal EU legal instrument on data protection is the Regulation (EU) 2016/279 of the

¹⁶ Therein the term Big Data encompasses both Big Data and Big Data analytics. Big Data are identified as extremely data sets with heterogeneous characteristics that may be analysed computationally to extract inferences about data patterns, trends and correlations; Guidelines, p.2

¹⁷ Consolidated version of the TEU available at: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:12012M/TXT>

¹⁸ Consolidated version of the TFEU available at: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:12012E/TXT&from=EN>

¹⁹ EU (2012), Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, OJ 2012 C 326, available at: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:12012P/TXT&from=EN>

²⁰ Namely, at that time, it was not incorporated into the Treaty and was not legally binding.

²¹ All amendments available here: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:12007L/TXT>

²² Art. 7: "Everyone has the right to respect for his or her private and family life, home and communications."

²³ Art. 8(1): "Everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her."

²⁴ Art. 8(2): "Such data must be processed fairly for specified purposes and on the basis of the consent of the person concerned or some other legitimate basis laid down by law. Everyone has the right of access to data which has been collected concerning him or her, and the right to have it rectified."

²⁵ Article 8(3): "Compliance with these rules shall be subject to control by an independent authority."

²⁶ TFEU, Art. 16(2), available at: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:12012E/TXT&from=EN>

European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR)²⁷. By this Regulation, Directive 95/46/EC (Data Protection directive)²⁸ was repealed and GDPR comes into force on 25 May 2018. As stipulated in the recitals of the GDPR, while a high level of natural persons' protection must be ensured with regards to the personal data processing, this should be balanced against other fundamental rights in accordance with the principle of proportionality. The technological developments and the expansion of data processing and sharing made it imperative upon the Union bodies that a strong and more coherent data protection framework should be established. Thus, a homogenous application of law throughout the EU could only be established with an EU regulation²⁹.

Table 3-4 Key points

Key points³⁰
<i>Citizens' rights</i>
<p>The GDPR strengthens existing rights, provides for new rights and gives citizens more control over their personal data. These include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • easier access to their data — including providing more information on how that data is processed and ensuring that that information is available in a clear and understandable way; • right to data portability — making it easier to transmit personal data between service providers; • right to erasure ('right to be forgotten') — when an individual no longer wants their data processed and there is no legitimate reason to keep it, the data will be deleted; • right to know when their personal data has been hacked — companies and organisations will have to inform individuals promptly of serious data breaches. They will also have to notify the relevant data protection supervisory authority.
<i>Rules for businesses</i>
<p>The GDPR is designed to create business opportunities and stimulate innovation through a number of steps including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a single set of EU-wide rules; • a data protection officer, responsible for data protection, will be designated by public authorities and by businesses which process data on a large scale;

²⁷ General Data Protection Regulation, available at: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&qid=1522240823531&from=EN>

²⁸ Data Protection Directive, OJ 1995 L 281, available at: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31995L0046>.

²⁹ "Regulations are of general application, binding in their entirety and directly applicable. They must be complied with fully by those to whom they apply (private persons, Member States, Union institutions). Regulations are directly applicable in all the Member States as soon as they enter into force (on the date stipulated or, failing this, on the twentieth day following their publication in the Official Journal of the European Union) and do not need to be transposed into national law.

They are designed to ensure the uniform application of Union law in all the Member States. Regulations supersede national laws incompatible with their substantive provisions."; information retrieved from 'Sources and Scope of European Union Law', Fact sheets in the European Union - 2018, available at: http://www.europarl.europa.eu/ftu/pdf/en/FTU_1.2.1.pdf

³⁰ Retrieved from: Protection of personal data, Regulation (EU) 2016/279, Summary of legislation, available at: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/LSU/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&qid=1522240823531>

- one-stop-shop — businesses only have to deal with one single supervisory authority (in the EU country in which they are mainly based);
- EU rules for non-EU companies — companies based outside the EU must apply the same rules when offering services or goods, or monitoring behaviour of individuals within the EU;
- innovation-friendly rules — a guarantee that data protection safeguards are built into products and services from the earliest stage of development (data protection by design and by default);
- privacy-friendly techniques such as pseudonymisation (when identifying fields within a data record are replaced by one or more artificial identifiers) and encryption (when data is coded in such a way that only authorised parties can read it);
- removal of notifications — the new data protection rules will scrap most notification obligations and the costs associated with these. One of the aims of the data protection regulation is to remove obstacles to free flow of personal data within the EU. This will make it easier for businesses to expand;
- impact assessments — businesses will have to carry out impact assessments when data processing may result in a high risk for the rights and freedoms of individuals;
- record-keeping — SMEs³¹ are not required to keep records of processing activities, unless the processing is regular or likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of the person whose data is being processed.

3.2.2.2.1 *Definitions and scope*

GDPR lays down rules for the protection of natural persons³², irrespective their nationality or residence, regarding the processing of their personal data and rules relating to the free movement of personal data (Article 1). Particularly, it applies to the processing of personal data wholly or partly by automated means, as well as by other than automated means when the personal data form or are intended to form part of a filing systems (Article 2). Furthermore, with regard to the territorial scope of the GDPR³³, it applies to processing of personal data by an establishment³⁴ of a controller or a processor in the Union, whether a branch or a subsidiary with legal personality³⁵; the processing of data of data subjects who are in the Union by a controller or processor not established in the Union, where the processing activities are related to offering goods or services to such data subjects, irrespective of payment³⁶; the processing of personal data of data subjects who are in the Union by a controller or processor not

³¹ Small and medium-sized enterprises

³² And not deceased; Recital 27.

³³ Art. 3 GDPR

³⁴ According to Art. 4(16) of the GDPR, “‘main establishment’ means:

(a) as regards a controller with establishments in more than one Member State, the place of its central administration in the Union, unless the decisions on the purposes and means of the processing of personal data are taken in another establishment of the controller in the Union and the latter establishment has the power to have such decisions implemented, in which case the establishment having taken such decisions is to be considered to be the main establishment;

(b) as regards a processor with establishments in more than one Member State, the place of its central administration in the Union, or, if the processor has no central administration in the Union, the establishment of the processor in the Union where the main processing activities in the context of the activities of an establishment of the processor take place to the extent that the processor is subject to specific obligations under this Regulation;”

³⁵ Recital 22

³⁶ Recital 23

established in the Union, when it is related to the monitoring of the behaviour of such data subjects in so far this behaviour takes place within the Union³⁷.

Noteworthy that anonymous information, namely information that cannot be attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person or personal data that have become anonymous by making the data subject no longer identifiable, including for statistical or research purposes, are not regulated by the GDPR. Files or sets of files, as well as their cover pages, which are not structured according to specific criteria do not fall within the scope of the GDPR³⁸. Moreover, the processing of personal data by private individuals for merely personal or household purposes falls also out of the scope of this Regulation (household exemption)³⁹. GDPR does not apply for the processing of the personal data by the Union institutions, bodies and offices and agencies, as this falls under the scope of Regulation (EC) 45/2001. In addition, with regard to processing by the judiciary and law enforcement authorities concerning the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, including the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security, Directive (EU) 2016/680 applies.

Under article 4 of the GDPR,

'personal data' means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable person is one who can be identified directly or indirectly, particularly by reference to an identifier such as name, ID number, location data (e.g. GPS), online identifier via devices, applications, tools and protocols (e.g. cookies, IP address, radio frequency identification tag)⁴⁰ or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person (para 1); Personal data which have undergone pseudonymisation and thus could be attributed to a natural person with the use of additional information, should be regarded as information of an identifiable person⁴¹. To ascertain that, objective factors should be taken into account, such as the costs and the time required for identification, as well as the available technology at the time of processing⁴².

Through the use of modern technology traces might be left, which when combined with unique identifiers and other information received by the servers, may be used to create profiles of the natural persons and identify them⁴³.

'processing' means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction (para 2);

'profiling' means any form of automated processing of personal data consisting of the use of personal data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyse or predict

³⁷ Recital 24

³⁸ Recital 15

³⁹ Recital 18

⁴⁰ See also recital 30

⁴¹ Recital 2

⁴² Ibid.

⁴³ Recital 30

aspects concerning that natural person's performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences, interests, reliability, behaviour, location or movements (para 4);

'pseudonymisation' means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person (para 5);

'filing system' means any structured set of personal data which are accessible according to specific criteria, whether centralised, decentralised or dispersed on a functional or geographical basis (para 6);

'controller' means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or national law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or national law (para 7);

'processor' means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller (para 8);

'recipient' means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or another body, to which the personal data are disclosed, whether a third party or not. However, public authorities which may receive personal data in the framework of a particular inquiry in accordance with Union or national law shall not be regarded as recipients; the processing of those data by those public authorities shall be in compliance with the applicable data protection rules according to the purposes of the processing (para 9);

'third party' means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or body other than the data subject, controller, processor and persons who, under the direct authority of the controller or processor, are authorised to process personal data (para 10);

'consent' of the data subject means any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her (para 11);

'personal data breach' means a breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed (para 12);

'genetic data' means personal data relating to the inherited or acquired genetic characteristics of a natural person which give unique information about the physiology or the health of that natural person and which result from the analysis of a biological sample from the natural person in question (e.g. DNA or RNA analysis)⁴⁴ (para 13);

'biometric data' means personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physio- logical or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person, such as facial images or dactyloscopy data (para 14);

⁴⁴ See also recital 34 GDPR

'**data concerning health**' means personal data related to the physical or mental health of a natural person, including the provision of health care services, which reveal information about his or her health status⁴⁵ (para 15);

3.2.2.2.2 *Basic principles of processing personal data*

Table 3-5 Basic principles of personal data (PD) processing – Article 5 GDPR

Basic principles of personal data (PD) processing – Article 5 GDPR
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Lawfulness, fairness and transparency – PD processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject; ➤ Purpose limitation – PD collected for specific, concrete and legitimate purposes and any further process must be compatible with these purposes⁴⁶; ➤ Data minimisation – adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary to the purposes for which they are processed ➤ Accuracy – ensure that PD are accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; PD that are inaccurate shall be erased or rectified without delay ➤ Storage limitation – PD shall be kept in a form that permits the identification of the data subject solely for the time necessary for the purpose for which the PD are processed⁴⁷; ➤ Integrity and confidentiality – during processing security of PD, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, shall be ensured, by undertaking appropriate technical and organisational measures ➤ Accountability - The controller shall be responsible for, and be able to demonstrate compliance with the aforementioned principles

The *principle of lawfulness* requires that personal data should be processed *on the basis of the consent of the data subject concerned or some other legitimate basis*, laid down by GDPR or other EU or national law⁴⁸ (article 6).

Other legitimate basis, according to article 6 points (b) – (f), includes:

- the necessity for compliance with the legal obligation to which the controller is subject⁴⁹;

⁴⁵ E.g. according to Recital 35 GDPR, "a number, symbol or particular assigned to a natural person to uniquely identify the natural person for health purposes; information derived from the testing or examination of a body part or bodily substance, including from genetic data and biological samples; and any information on, for example, a disease, disability, disease risk, medical history, clinical treatment or the physiological or biomedical state of the data subject independent of its source, for example from a physician or other health professional, a hospital, a medical device or an in vitro diagnostic test".

⁴⁶ Further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes (art. 5(b)). See also art. 89(1) GDPR.

⁴⁷ Personal data may be stored for longer periods only if they are intended to be processed for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with article 89(1) subject to implementation of the appropriate technical and organizational measures in order to safeguard the rights of the data subject (Article 5 point (e)).

⁴⁸ Art. 6 GDPR.

⁴⁹ "This Regulation does not require a specific law for each individual processing. A law as a basis for several processing operations based on a legal obligation to which the controller is subject or where processing is necessary for the performance of a task

- the necessity for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or as step prior to entering into a contract at the request of the data subject;
- the necessity for the protection of the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person⁵⁰;
- the necessity according to the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party⁵¹, unless the interests or fundamental rights of the data subject, especially where he/she is a child, which require protection of personal data, transcend⁵².

Based on European Court of Human Rights case-law, the limiting of the fundamental right to protection of personal data must be strictly necessary⁵³. 'Necessity shall be justified on the basis of objective evidence and is the first step before assessing the proportionality of the limitation'⁵⁴. Moreover, the means of processing, the categories of data processed, and the duration of data storage shall be necessary for the purpose of the processing⁵⁵. Proportionality requires that the disadvantages for not fully exercising the right to data protection do not override the advantages due to limiting the right, namely the limitation should be justified and accompanied by safeguard measures⁵⁶. A prerequisite is that 'the measure is adequate to achieve the envisaged objective' and that only adequate and relevant personal data for the purposes of processing are collected and processed⁵⁷.

The purposes for personal data processing should be compatible with the purposes for which the personal data were initially collected, and thus common legal basis covers both cases⁵⁸. If the processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority that the controller holds, EU or national law shall determine and specify the tasks and purposes for which the further processing should be regarded as compatible and lawful. Where the data subject has given consent or the processing is based on Union or national law and constitutes a necessary and proportionate measure in a democratic society to safeguard, particularly, important objectives of general public interest, the controller should be allowed to further process the personal data irrespective of the compatibility of the purposes⁵⁹. Yet, further processing of personal data should be compatible with legal, professional or other binding obligation of secrecy⁶⁰.

Further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes should be considered to be compatible lawful processing operations. However,

carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of an official authority may be sufficient. It should also be for Union or Member State law to determine the purpose of processing." Recital 45 GDPR

⁵⁰ This should take place principally only where the processing cannot be established on another legal basis; Recital 46 GDPR.

⁵¹ "At any rate the existence of a legitimate interest would need careful assessment including whether a data subject can reasonably expect at the time and in the context of the collection of the personal data that processing for that purpose may take place"; Recital 47 GDPR. Under Recital 49 GDPR, processing of personal data, where this is strictly necessary and proportionate for the purposes of ensuring network and information security, corresponds to a legitimate interest of the data controller.

⁵² "The interests and fundamental rights of the data subject could in particular override the interest of the data controller where personal data are processed in circumstances where data subjects do not reasonably expect further processing"; Recital 47 GDPR

⁵³ European Data Protection Supervisor, Necessity & Proportionality, available at: https://edps.europa.eu/data-protection/our-work/subjects/necessity-proportionality_en

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ Ibid.

⁵⁶ Ibid.

⁵⁷ Ibid.

⁵⁸ Recital 50(1)

⁵⁹ Recital 50(2)

⁶⁰ Recital 50(2).

appropriate safeguards should be in place, for example pseudonymisation. Specific provisions are foreseen under article 89 and these are thoroughly described in recitals 156-162.

The *principle of transparency* requires that any information addressed to the public or to the data subject be concise, easily accessible and easy to understand, and that clear and plain language or even visualisation be used⁶¹, especially for information addressed to a child⁶². Information should be provided in writing or by other means, including electronic means. When information is provided orally, the identity of that data subject must be proven by other means⁶³.

Accountability corresponds to the active implementation of measures by controllers to promote and safeguard data protection in their processing operations. Controllers are responsible for the compliance of their processing activities with the GDPR and should be able at any time to demonstrate compliance to the general public and to supervisory authorities⁶⁴.

*Processing of special categories of personal data*⁶⁵

- Under Recitals 51-54 of the GDPR, it is highlighted that there are personal data which are particularly sensitive in relation to fundamental rights and freedoms and for this reason these require specific protection, as the context of their processing could create significant risks⁶⁶. These data include personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation⁶⁷. Processing of such personal data should be prohibited, unless it meets concrete conditions, such as the following^{68,69}:
 - (a) the data subject has given explicit consent to the processing of those personal data for one or more specified purposes⁷⁰;
 - (b) processing is based on obligation and specific right of the controller or of the data subject in the field of employment and social security and social protection law and is established in EU or national law or a collective agreement pursuant to national law providing for appropriate safeguards for the fundamental rights and interests of the data subject⁷¹;
 - (c) processing is necessary to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person where the data subject is physically or legally incapable of giving consent;

⁶¹ Art 13(1). Such information could be provided in writing or electronic form, for example, when addressed to the public, through a website; Recital 58.

⁶² Recital 58

⁶³ Art. 12(1)

⁶⁴ See accordingly, European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA), Handbook on European data protection law, 2014, p. 75, available at: http://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra-2014-handbook-data-protection-law-2nd-ed_en.pdf

⁶⁵ Art. 9 and Recital 51-54

⁶⁶ See particularly Recital 51

⁶⁷ Art. 9

⁶⁸ Art. 9(2)

⁶⁹ According to art. 9(4) of the GDPR, 'Member States may maintain or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health'.

⁷⁰ except where EU or national law provide that the prohibition may not be lifted by the data subject; GDPR, Article 9(2) point (a)

⁷¹ See also recital 52.

- (d) processing is carried out by a foundation, association or any other not-for-profit body with a political, philosophical, religious or trade union aim within its legitimate activities and concerns solely the members or former members of the body or persons having regular contact with it in relation to its purposes and the personal data are not disclosed outside that body without data subjects' consent;
 - (e) processing concerns personal data which are manifestly made public by the data subject;
 - (f) processing is necessary for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims or whenever courts are acting in their judicial capacity;
 - (g) processing is necessary on the basis of substantial public interest according to EU or national law, which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the right to data protection and provide for measures to safeguard the data subject's fundamental rights and interests;
 - (h) processing is necessary for health-related purposes for the benefit of natural purposes and society as a whole, such as medical diagnosis, the provision of health or social care or treatment or the management of health or social care systems and services on the basis of EU or national law or pursuant to contract with a health professional who is bounded by professional secrecy⁷²;
 - (i) processing is necessary for reasons of public interest in the area of public health on the basis of EU or national law which provides for measures to secure the rights and freedoms of the data subject, particularly professional secrecy;
 - (j) processing is necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) GDPR based on EU or national law which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the right to data protection and provide for measures to safeguard the data subject's fundamental rights and interests.
- Processing of personal data concerning criminal convictions and offences, or related security measures will only be possible when conducted under the control of a public authority or when this is based on EU or national law and appropriate safeguards are in place⁷³.

3.2.2.2.3 *Consent*

Consent, as examined above, is, in numerous cases, the legal basis for legitimate data processing. Consent must be free, informed, specific and unambiguous; it should be a clear affirmative act indicating the data subject's acceptance of the proposed processing of his/her personal data, in the form a written statement or an electronic form or an oral statement (e.g. ticking a box when visiting a website, choosing technical settings for information society services).⁷⁴ Especially where processing is based on consent, the controller shall be able to demonstrate that the data subject has consented to processing of his or her personal data⁷⁵. Therefore, a declaration of consent pre-formulated by the

⁷² See also art. 9(3) and recital 53.

⁷³ Art. 10.

⁷⁴ Recital 32.

⁷⁵ Art. 7(1); Recital 42

controller should be provided in a comprehensible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language and it should not contain unfair terms, ensuring that the data subject is aware and particularly of the extent to which consent is given⁷⁶. In addition, in the case of a written declaration including other matters as well, the request for consent shall be presented in a manner which is clearly distinguishable from the other matters⁷⁷. Any part that does comply with the GDPR rules is not binding⁷⁸.

For consent to be informed, the data subject should know at least the identity of the controller and the purposes of the processing⁷⁹. At the same time, consent should not be regarded as freely given, not unless the data subject has genuine or free choice or is able to refuse or withdraw consent without detriment⁸⁰. Data subject should be informed prior to giving his/her consent that he/she is able to withdraw at any time⁸¹; the procedure should be as easy as giving consent⁸². In addition, consent to be freely given requires that it allows separate consent to be given to different personal data processing operations⁸³. Further, in case of contract performance or service provision, these must not be conditional on the consent for processing, if this is not a prerequisite for the performance of the contract or service⁸⁴. Where there is clear imbalance between the controller and the data subject, it should be presumed that consent is not given freely and thus consent should be the legal basis for processing⁸⁵.

Under the GDPR, it is acknowledged that children should be granted specific protection with regard to their personal data, as they may be less aware of the risks, consequences and safeguards at stake, as well as their rights with regard to the processing of personal data⁸⁶. This is especially apparent as concerns the field of marketing and information society services⁸⁷. On that account, a child shall be at least 16 years old to consider the consent lawful⁸⁸. For children below the age of 16 years, consent is given or authorised by the holder of parental responsibility over the child⁸⁹ and the controller should

⁷⁶ Recital 42; see also Council Directive 93/13/EEC (1)

⁷⁷ Art. 7(2) GDPR

⁷⁸ Art. 7(2)

⁷⁹ Recital 43

⁸⁰ Recital 42

⁸¹ Art. 7(3). Note: According to art.7(3), 'the withdrawal of consent shall not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal'.

⁸² Art. 7(3)

⁸³ Recital 43

⁸⁴ Art. 7(4); Recital 43

⁸⁵ Recital 43

⁸⁶ Recital 38

⁸⁷ According to point (b) of Article 1(1) of Directive (EU) 2015/1535 of the European Parliament and of the Council, 'Information society service'⁸⁷ means any service normally provided for remuneration, at a distance, by electronic means and at the individual request of a recipient of services. For the purposes of this definition: (i) 'at a distance' means that the service is provided without the parties being simultaneously present; (ii) 'by electronic means' means that the service is sent initially and received at its destination by means of electronic equipment for the processing (including digital compression) and storage of data, and entirely transmitted, conveyed and received by wire, by radio, by optical means or by other electromagnetic means; (iii) 'at the individual request of a recipient of services' means that the service is provided through the transmission of data on individual request; Art.4(25) GDPR. Examples are: web shops and marketplaces, search engines, online advertising, video sharing sites, blogs, hosting, video-on-demand, online consultancy, online marketplaces, social networking, etc.

⁸⁸ Art. 8(1)

⁸⁹ Ibid.

make reasonable efforts to verify that⁹⁰. By contrast, in the context of preventive or counselling services offered directly to a child, the consent of the holder of parental responsibility should not be necessary⁹¹.

3.2.2.2.4 *Responsibilities of the controller, the processor & the data protection officer*

Responsibility of the controller

The controller is responsible for the implementation of appropriate technical and organisational measures to secure and be able to demonstrate that processing is performed according with the GDPR by taking into account the context and purpose of processing as well as the impact that this might have on the rights and freedoms of natural persons⁹². These measures may include data protection policies⁹³ or the application of approved codes of conduct or certification mechanisms⁹⁴. Where two or more controllers define together the purpose and means of the processing, they are joint controllers with concrete responsibilities to comply with the GDPR⁹⁵. This arrangement should be available for the data subject too⁹⁶.

Where the controller delegates a processor to perform the processing of personal data and to act on behalf of the controller, the latter must use only processors providing sufficient guarantees to implement suitable technical and organisational measures in compliance with the GDPR and with respect to the data subject's rights⁹⁷.

Each controller, or representative of a controller in the EU, with regard to enterprises or organisation employing more than 250 persons, is responsible for keeping a record of the processing operations, in writing including in electronic form⁹⁸. This record shall be available upon request of the supervisory authority⁹⁹. The obligation to keep a record applies to organisations with less than 250 employees, where processing is likely to result in a risk to the data subject's rights, the processing is not occasional, or it includes personal data revealing sensitive information about an individual or relate to criminal convictions¹⁰⁰.

The controller is anticipated to cooperate with the supervisory authority upon request¹⁰¹. Nevertheless, in case of a personal data breach, the controller has to notify the supervisory authority within 72 hours after having become aware of the breach, except for breaches that are unlikely to result in a risk to the data subject's rights¹⁰². If the notification takes place later than 72 hours, the reasons for this must be

⁹⁰ Art. 8(2)

⁹¹ Recital 38

⁹² article 24, para 1.

⁹³ Art. 24 para 2.

⁹⁴ Art. 24(3). See also articles 40 & 42 GDPR.

⁹⁵ Art. 26(1).

⁹⁶ Art. 26(2).

⁹⁷ Art. 28(1).

⁹⁸ Art. 30 paras 1,3,5.

⁹⁹ Art. 30(4).

¹⁰⁰ See articles 9(1) & 10.

¹⁰¹ Art. 31.

¹⁰² Art. 33(1).

made known¹⁰³. In the notification 'the nature of the personal data breach including where possible, the categories and approximate number of data subjects concerned and the categories and approximate number of personal data records concerned' should be described; 'the name and contact details of the data protection officer or other contact point where more information can be obtained' should be communicated; 'the likely consequences of the personal data breach' should be described; as well as 'the measures taken or proposed to be taken by the controller to address the personal data breach, including, where appropriate, measures to mitigate its possible adverse effects' should be described¹⁰⁴. The controller is responsible for documenting any personal data breaches (facts relating to the breach, effects and remedial measures taken) in order for the supervisory authority to verify compliance with GDPR provisions¹⁰⁵.

The controller is responsible for communicating a personal data breach to the data subject, using a clear and plain language, if it is likely to affect negatively the natural person's rights¹⁰⁶. If measures have been taken, such as encryption or other, that either render personal data intelligible or the risk no longer exists, the controller does not have to inform the data subject¹⁰⁷. In case, it demands disproportionate effort to reach the data subject(s) affected, then public communication or similar measure should be employed¹⁰⁸.

The controller is liable for any damage caused by a processing that violated the GDPR¹⁰⁹, unless the controller proves that it is not responsible for the cause of the damage¹¹⁰.

Responsibility of the processor

The processor must be bound by a contract or other legal act under EU or national law with regard to the controller and act in accordance as to the processing operations¹¹¹. Therein 'the subject-matter and duration of processing, the nature and purpose of processing, the type of personal data and categories of data subjects and the obligation and rights of the controller' are set out¹¹². Under article 28 para 3 of the GDPR specific clauses to be part of the contract or legal act are foreseen, such as that (a) the processing takes place only under documented instructions by the controller unless the processor is obliged to act so by EU or national law; (b) the processor ensures that authorised persons to process personal data are bound by confidentiality obligation; (c) the processor takes all necessary technical and organisation measures to secure the protection of data subject's personal data; (d) the processor cannot engage other processors unless there is a prior written authorisation of the controller¹¹³ - in case the authorisation is general, the processor has to inform the controller for any intended changes

¹⁰³ Ibid.

¹⁰⁴ Art. 33(3).

¹⁰⁵ Art. 33(5).

¹⁰⁶ Art. 34 paras 1-2.

¹⁰⁷ Art. 34(3).

¹⁰⁸ Ibid.

¹⁰⁹ Art. 82(2).

¹¹⁰ Art. 82(3).

¹¹¹ Art. 28(3).

¹¹² Ibid.

¹¹³ Art. 28(2).

regarding the engaged processors¹¹⁴; (d) the processor assist the controller to respond to requests by data subjects exercising their rights under the GDPR; (e) the processor, if requested so by the controller, shall delete or return all personal data to the controller by the end of the provision of services and delete copies unless obliged otherwise by EU or national law; (f) processor provides necessary information to the controller for the latter to establish compliance of the first with the obligation laid down in article 28 GDPR and contribute to audits and inspections conducted by the controller¹¹⁵. If, to processor's opinion, a controller's instruction infringes the GDPR, the processor must immediately inform the controller¹¹⁶. Standard contractual clauses for the aforementioned matters may be laid down by the European Commission or the supervisory authority¹¹⁷. In any event, the contract or other legal act must be in writing, including in electronic form¹¹⁸.

If the processor engages another processor to perform specific processing activities on behalf of the controller, the same data protection obligations must be stipulated in a similar contract or other legal act¹¹⁹. Where that processor does not fulfil its data protection obligations, the initial processor remains fully liable to the controller for the acts of the other processor¹²⁰. Sufficient guarantees of implementing appropriate technical and organisational measures in a manner that processing meets the requirements of the GDPR may be demonstrated by the adherence of the processor to an approved code of conduct or certification mechanism¹²¹. The processor or any person acting under the authority of the controller or the processor, shall process personal data only on the instructions of the controller or the processor, unless EU or national law defines otherwise¹²².

Each processor or the representative of a processor in the EU is responsible for keeping a record of all categories of processing operations performed on behalf of the controller, in writing including in electronic form¹²³. This record shall be available for the supervisory authority upon request. The same criteria for the obligation to keep record in relation to the size of an enterprise or organisation, as with the controller, apply¹²⁴. In any event, the processor is anticipated to cooperate with the supervisory authority, upon request¹²⁵.

The processor as soon as becomes aware of a personal data breach must notify the controller¹²⁶.

¹¹⁴ Ibid.

¹¹⁵ See also article 28(3), point (f) & article 32: "security of processing".

¹¹⁶ Art. 28(3).

¹¹⁷ Art. 28 paras 6-8.

¹¹⁸ Art. 28(9).

¹¹⁹ Art. 28(4).

¹²⁰ Ibid.

¹²¹ Art. 28(5).

¹²² Art. 29.

¹²³ Art. 30 paras 2& 4.

¹²⁴ GDPR article 30 para 5.

¹²⁵ Article 31 GDPR.

¹²⁶ GDPR Article 33 para 2.

A processor is liable for damage resulting from a processing only where he has acted contrary to or outside the obligations under the GDPR or the lawful instructions of the controller¹²⁷. The processor is exempted from liability, if it proves that it is not responsible for the cause of the damage¹²⁸.

The role of the data protection officer

A data protection officer (DPO) must be designated by the controller or the processor, if: (a) processing is carried out by public authority or body, (b) in the context of the processing, regular and systematic monitoring of data subjects on a large scale takes place, (c) large scale processing of personal data revealing sensitive information about individuals or criminal convictions takes place¹²⁹. Apart from the aforementioned cases, the controller or processor should designate a data protection officer, where required by EU or national law¹³⁰. One data protection officer may serve more controllers or processors¹³¹. He/she must have expert knowledge of data protection law and practices and the ability to carry out tasks provided under the GDPR¹³². He/she may be a staff member of the controller or processor or be engaged by a service contract¹³³. Contact details of the DPO shall be published and communicated to the supervisory authority too.¹³⁴

DPO shall be involved in all issues concerning the protection of personal data¹³⁵ and shall directly report to the highest management level of the controller or processor¹³⁶. The controller and processor support the DPO in carrying out his/her tasks under the GDPR (resources, access to personal data processing activities, continuous training)¹³⁷ and do not instruct him/her¹³⁸. However, the controller or processor shall make sure that there is no conflict of interest, if the DPO is engaged in several positions¹³⁹. In any event, DPO must be bound by secrecy or confidentiality with regard to his/her tasks¹⁴⁰. Finally, DPO should be available for data subjects to contact him/her in relation to their personal data¹⁴¹.

Under article 39 para 1 of the GDPR the DPO is assigned with specific tasks, namely (a) 'to inform and advise the controller or the processor and the employees who carry out processing of their obligations pursuant to' the GDPR and to other EU or national data protection provisions; (b) 'to monitor compliance with' the GDPR, with other EU or national 'data protection provisions and with the policies of the controller or processor in relation to the protection of personal data, including the assignment of responsibilities, awareness-raising and training of staff involved in processing operations, and the

¹²⁷ GDPR article 82 para 2.

¹²⁸ GDPR article 82 para 3.

¹²⁹ GDPR article 37 para 1.

¹³⁰ GDPR article 37 para 4.

¹³¹ GDPR article 37 paras 2-3.

¹³² GDPR article 37 para 5.

¹³³ GDPR article 37 para 6.

¹³⁴ GDPR article 37 para 7.

¹³⁵ GDPR article 38 para 1.

¹³⁶ GDPR article 38 para 3.

¹³⁷ GDPR article 38 para 2.

¹³⁸ GDPR article 38 para 3.

¹³⁹ GDPR article 38 para 6.

¹⁴⁰ GDPR article 38 para 5.

¹⁴¹ GDPR article 38 para 4.

related audits'; (c) 'to provide advice where requested as regards the data protection impact assessment and monitor its performance pursuant to Article 35' of the GDPR; (d) to cooperate with the supervisory authority; (e) to act as the contact point for the supervisory authority on issues relating to processing, including the prior consultation referred to in Article 36' of the GDPR, 'and to consult, where appropriate, with regard to any other matter'.

During the performance of his/her tasks, the DPO has to take into consideration the risks deriving from processing activities, including the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing¹⁴².

3.2.2.2.5 *Data protection safeguards*

■ *Information to be provided, where personal data have been collected from the data subject*

As soon as personal data are obtained from the data subject and insofar as the data subject is not already aware of, the controller has to provide certain pieces of information, such as (a) the identity and contact details of the controller or the controller's representative¹⁴³, (b) the contact details of the data protection officer where applicable, (c) the purpose of the personal data processing and the legal basis for it, (d) if processing is based on the legitimate interest of the controller, then these should be made known (e) the recipients of the personal data, if any (f) where applicable, the intention to transfer of data¹⁴⁴. Apart from the aforementioned, the controller shall provide further information about (a) the time period of data storage, (b) the existence of the right to request access to and rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing, as regards the data subject's personal data or to object to processing as well as the right to data portability, (c) when processing is based on the data subject's consent, the right to withdraw consent at any time, without affecting the lawfulness of processing before its withdrawal, (d) the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority, (e) whether the provision of personal data is a statutory or contractual requirement, or a requirement necessary to enter into a contract, as well as whether the data subject is obliged to provide the personal data and of the possible consequences of not providing them, (f) the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, the logic involved and the significance or potential consequences of such processing for the data subject¹⁴⁵. Lastly, if the controller intends to proceed with further processing of the data subject's personal data for a purpose different from the one for which the data were initially collected, then the data subject must receive all relevant information¹⁴⁶.

■ *Information to be provided, where personal data have not been collected from the data subject*

In case the personal data have not been obtained from the data subject and the latter is not already aware of, the controller has the same obligation to inform the data subject within a reasonable period after obtaining the personal data, but at least within a month or if applicable in the first communication with the data subject or if applicable in the first disclosure of the data to another recipient¹⁴⁷. In addition

¹⁴² GDPR article 39 para 2.

¹⁴³ 'representative' means a natural or legal person established in the Union who, designated by the controller or processor in writing pursuant to Article 27, represents the controller or processor with regard to their respective obligations under this Regulation; Article 4 (17) GDPR.

¹⁴⁴ Article 13 (1), (4) GDPR.

¹⁴⁵ Article 13(2) GDPR.

¹⁴⁶ Article 13(3) GDPR.

¹⁴⁷ Article 14 (1)-(4) GDPR.

to the previously mentioned, the controller has to further inform the data subject about the categories of personal data concerned¹⁴⁸ and the sources from which the data originate and whether these publicly accessible sources¹⁴⁹. Information should be provided free of charge¹⁵⁰. There is no obligation for the controller to inform the data subject, if this proves impossible or involves disproportionate effort or it might not serve the objectives of the processing¹⁵¹. Making information publicly available could balance both sides interests¹⁵². Moreover, where obtaining or disclosure is directly provided in EU or national law taking into account the necessary rights protection safeguards or where data must remain confidential (statutory obligation of secrecy), the controller shall not provide any information to the data subject¹⁵³.

- *Data protection by design and by default*

By design of the processing and implementation of it, the controller has to apply technical and organisational measures for safeguarding data protection principles effectively¹⁵⁴. Moreover, by default, the amount of personal data collected, the extent of their processing, the period of storage and their accessibility must be regulated in a manner that all principles are ensured¹⁵⁵.

- *Security of processing*

The controller and processor have to take all necessary technical and organisation measures to ensure data protection and prohibit personal data breaches or any other potential risks for the rights and freedoms of natural persons¹⁵⁶. Pseudonymisation and encryption are introduced as measures which could be applied to reduce these risks¹⁵⁷. In the case of pseudonymisation, it is stipulated that additional information which could render a natural person identifiable should be kept separately¹⁵⁸. Furthermore, to ensure a level of security against such risks, measures that safeguard the ongoing confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services, or that restore the availability and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident shall be implemented. Therein, the establishment of a process for regularly testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of the security measures is provided. Additional safeguards can be adherence to an approved code of conduct¹⁵⁹ or an approved certification mechanism¹⁶⁰. At any event, in assessing the security level, risks to be considered should be the ones deriving from accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to personal data transmitted, stored

¹⁴⁸ Article 14(1), point (d) GDPR.

¹⁴⁹ Article 14(2), point (f) GDPR.

¹⁵⁰ Article 12(5) GDPR.

¹⁵¹ Article 14(5), point (b) GDPR.

¹⁵² In this case the legislator suggests that appropriate measures should be taken to protect the data subject's rights and interests, including making the information publically available; Article 14(5)b GDPR.

¹⁵³ Article 14(5), points (c)-(d) GDPR.

¹⁵⁴ GDPR, article 25, para 1.

¹⁵⁵ GDPR, article 25, para 2.

¹⁵⁶ See for example recital 28 GDPR; articles 25 & 32 GDPR.

¹⁵⁷ Article 32 para 1 & recital 28 GDPR.

¹⁵⁸ Ibid.

¹⁵⁹ See article 40 GDPR.

¹⁶⁰ See article 42 GDPR.

or otherwise processed¹⁶¹. Moreover, precautions must be taken for natural persons acting under the authority of the controller or the processor who have access to personal data to process them only on instructions from the controller or according to EU or national law¹⁶².

- *Codes of conduct*

Codes of conduct are encouraged to be drafted to contribute to the proper application of the GDPR by the Member States, the supervisory authorities¹⁶³, the European Data Protection Board¹⁶⁴ and the European Commission¹⁶⁵. 'Associations and other bodies representing categories of controllers or processors may prepare codes of conduct or amend or extend such codes' to specify the application of the GDPR, with regard to the particular features of the processing operation and principles for data protection and processing (e.g. fair and transparent processing, legitimate interest of the controller, collection of personal data, pseudonymisation, information provision to data subjects)¹⁶⁶. The monitoring of compliance with a code of conduct, as foreseen in article 41 GDPR, 'may be carried out by a body which has an appropriate level of expertise in relation to the subject-matter of the code and is accredited for that purpose by the competent supervisory authority.

- *Processing which does not require identification*

In case the controller is not able to identify a data subject from the personal data processed, then the controller should not be obliged to obtain additional information in order to identify the data subject, unless this is offered by the data subject in order to help the latter exercise his/her rights. In such a case, an authentication mechanism could be applied as a digital identification of the data subject (e.g. logging in to the online service)¹⁶⁷.

- *Data protection impact assessment and prior consultation*

When there is the likelihood that a type of processing, particularly by the use of new technologies, could result in a high risk to the rights of natural persons, the controller should conduct beforehand an assessment of the impact of the intended processing operations on the protection of personal data¹⁶⁸. This would be particularly required in case of (a) systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects of natural persons, based on automated processing, including profiling, and which further becomes grounds for decisions that produce legal effects for the natural person or significantly affect him/her, (b) processing on a large scale of special categories of data revealing sensitive information about a natural person¹⁶⁹, or of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences¹⁷⁰; (c) a systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area on a large scale¹⁷¹. Similar processing operations that present the same high risk could be addressed with one single assessment¹⁷². Such processing

¹⁶¹ GDPR, article 32 para 2.

¹⁶² GDPR, article 32 para 4.

¹⁶³ See articles 51-59 GDPR.

¹⁶⁴ See articles 68-76 GDPR.

¹⁶⁵ GDPR, article 40, para 1.

¹⁶⁶ GDPR, article 40 para 2.

¹⁶⁷ Recital 57 GDPR.

¹⁶⁸ GDPR, article 35, para 1.

¹⁶⁹ See also article 9(1) GDPR.

¹⁷⁰ See also article 10 GDPR.

¹⁷¹ GDPR, article 35, para 7.

¹⁷² GDPR, article 35, para 1.

occasions should be listed by the supervisory authority, as well as those cases where no impact assessment is necessary¹⁷³. Where processing is based on EU or Member State law under specific clauses¹⁷⁴ to which the controller is subject, a data protection impact assessment has already been carried out in the context of the adoption of that legal basis¹⁷⁵.

Under article 35 para 7 of the GDPR, the minimum content of an assessment is provided. In accordance, the assessment should contain at least: (a) a systematic description of the anticipated processing operations and its purposes, including, where applicable, the legitimate interest pursued by the controller, (b) an assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing in relation to the purposes, (c) an assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects, and (d) the measures envisaged to address the risks, including safeguards, security measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data and to demonstrate compliance with the GDPR taking into account the rights and legitimate interests of data subjects and other persons concerned. Compliance with approved codes of conduct will be taken into account for the assessment¹⁷⁶.

Where a data protection impact assessment indicates that the processing would result in a high risk, if no measures are taken by the controller to mitigate the risk, the controller must consult the supervisory authority prior to processing¹⁷⁷.

3.2.2.2.6 *Data subject's rights*

GDPR provides for the rights of the data subject in relation to the processing of his/her personal data. The controller should facilitate the exercise of the data subject's rights by providing modalities, such as easily accessible and free of charge mechanisms to make the request¹⁷⁸.

Right of access by the data subject¹⁷⁹

The data subject holds the right to receive a confirmation as to whether or not his/her personal data are being processed and where that is the case to information such as the purpose of processing, the categories of personal data in question, the recipients that the data have been or will be disclosed, the existence of the right of rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing or the right to object to the processing, the right to lodge a complaint; the sources from which the controller collected the data, the existences of automated decision-making. Moreover, the controller shall provide a copy of the personal data being processed¹⁸⁰. Importantly, the controller should verify the identity of a data subject prior to giving access¹⁸¹.

Right to rectification¹⁸²

¹⁷³ GDPR, article 35, paras 4-5.

¹⁷⁴ See GDPR, article 6 para 1, point (c) or (e).

¹⁷⁵ GDPR, article 35 para 10.

¹⁷⁶ GDPR, article 35, para 8.

¹⁷⁷ See article 36 GDPR.

¹⁷⁸ See recital 59 GDPR.

¹⁷⁹ Article 15 GDPR.

¹⁸⁰ See also Recital 63 GDPR.

¹⁸¹ Recital 64 GDPR.

¹⁸² Article 16 GDPR.

The data subject has the right to demand from the controller to correct inaccurate personal data. If data are incomplete, the data subject has the right to have them completed.

Right to erasure ('right to be forgotten')¹⁸³

Under certain conditions, the data subject has the right to demand from the controller the erasure of personal data without undue delay. These conditions are limited to the following¹⁸⁴:

- (a) the necessity principle is no longer satisfied in relation to the purposes for which the personal data were initially collected or processed;
- (b) where consent was the only legal basis for personal data processing and the data subject withdraws consent;
- (c) the data subject objects to the processing in the context of controller's task performance in the public interest or on controller's legitimate interests and there are no overriding legitimate grounds for the processing, or the data subject objects to the processing for marketing purposes;
- (d) the personal data have been unlawfully processed;
- (e) the personal data have to be erased for compliance with a legal obligation in EU or national law to which the controller is subject;
- (f) the personal data have been collected from a person below 18 years of age in the context of information society services¹⁸⁵.

In case of personal data made public by the controller and the latter is obliged to erase the personal data, the controller has to take all reasonable measures to inform controllers processing these personal data too, that the data subject has requested erasure 'of any links to or copy or replication of those personal data'¹⁸⁶.

The controller shall notify all recipients of personal data in case of correction or erasure of personal data or restriction of their processing, unless this proves impossible or demands disproportionate efforts (article 19 GDPR).

However, the right to erasure is balanced with other rights, legal obligations or reasons and, to the extent that processing is necessary for respecting these, can only partly apply¹⁸⁷. Such cases are the right to freedom of expression and information, the legal obligation to comply with EU or national law or the exercise of official authority of the performance of a task in the public interest where in all previous occasions processing is required, the public interest for public-health related reasons, archiving purposes in the public interest, 'scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1)' GDPR 'in so far as reassurance of personal data is likely to render impossible

¹⁸³ Article 17 GDPR.

¹⁸⁴ GDPR, article 1, para 1.

¹⁸⁵ For example, if a person had given his/her consent as a child and was not aware of the risks deriving from the processing, and later on, as an adult, desires to remove his/her personal data especially from the internet; recital 65 GDPR.

¹⁸⁶ GDPR, article 17, para 2.

¹⁸⁷ GDPR, article 17, para 3.

or seriously impair the achievement of the objectives of that processing' and the right to exercise and defend a legal claim¹⁸⁸.

Right to restriction of processing

In terms of provisional protection, the data subject has the right to obtain from the controller restriction of processing¹⁸⁹ under specific circumstances, which are: when the accuracy of personal data is contested by the data subject (for necessary time to the controller to verify the accuracy); the processing is unlawful and the data subject's requests restriction of processing and not erasure of the personal data; the personal data are no longer necessary for the purposes of processing, but the data subject needs them to establish, exercise or defend legal claims; the data subject has objected to the legitimate interests of the controller and claims are examined¹⁹⁰. In these cases, personal data cannot be processed unless with the data subject's consent or for the purpose of establishing, exercising or defending legal claims or for protecting the rights of another natural or legal person or for reasons of important public interest of the EU or of a Member State¹⁹¹. If restriction is about to be lifted, the controller must inform the data subject beforehand¹⁹².

Right to data portability

Where processing of personal data is based on the data subject's consent and this is conducted through automated means, the data subject has the right to receive his/her personal data from the controller who was provide with the data, 'in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format' and transmit those data to another controller¹⁹³. This right does not apply 'to processing necessary for the performance of task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller¹⁹⁴ or when it significantly impacts the rights and freedoms of others¹⁹⁵.

Right to object

Under certain conditions, the data subject has the right to object at any time to the processing of his/her personal data, which was grounded on the performance of tasks in the public interest or on the legitimate interests of the controller¹⁹⁶. Unless the controller demonstrates that there are interests overriding the data subject's rights or that processing is necessary for the exercise of legal claims, the controller shall no longer process the personal data¹⁹⁷. Until the first communication with the data subject, the controller must inform the data subject about this right explicitly¹⁹⁸. Furthermore, 'where personal data are processed for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes pursuant to Article 89(1), the data subject, on grounds relating to his or her particular situation, shall have the

¹⁸⁸ Ibid.

¹⁸⁹ See also recital 67 GDPR.

¹⁹⁰ GDPR, article 18, para 1.

¹⁹¹ GDPR, article 18, para 2.

¹⁹² GDPR, article 18, para 3.

¹⁹³ GDPR, article 20, para 1. See also Recital 68 GDPR.

¹⁹⁴ GDPR, article 20, para 3.

¹⁹⁵ GDPR, article 20, para 4.

¹⁹⁶ GDPR, article 21, para 1.

¹⁹⁷ Ibid. Paras 2 & 3 concern processing for marketing purposes, which the data subject unconditionally can object to (see also recital 70 GDPR).

¹⁹⁸ GDPR, article 21, para 4.

right to object to processing of personal data concerning him or her, unless the processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out for reasons of public interest¹⁹⁹.

Right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing

The data subject has the right not to be subjected to a decision which is based on the evaluation of personal aspects that have been automatically processed, namely profiling, and which has legal effects upon him/her or significantly affects him/her²⁰⁰. The right is not applicable in case such a decision is (a) necessary for entering into, or the performance of a contract between the controller and the data subject, (b) is authorised by EU or national law and the controller adheres to it (e.g. fraud and tax-evasion monitoring) and which foresees appropriate safeguards for the data subject's rights, (c) is based on the data subject's explicit consent²⁰¹. Under (a) and (c) occasions, the controller has to provide suitable measures to ensure the data subject's rights and interest, such as 'the right to obtain human intervention on the part of the controller, to express his or her point of view and to contest the decision'²⁰². Such measure cannot involve a child data subject²⁰³.

The controller must provide information on action taken upon the request of the data subject under articles 15-22 of the GDPR without undue delay and in any event within one month from the receipt of the request²⁰⁴.

Restrictions

Restrictions to the rights of the data subject and corresponding obligations of the controller may be imposed by EU or national law, as long as these respect fundamental rights and freedoms and is a necessary and proportionate measure to safeguard: national security; defence; public security; operations related to criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties; other significant objectives of public interest of the EU or of a Member State; the protection of judicial independence and judicial proceedings; the prevention/investigation/detection/prosecution of breaches of ethics for regulated professions; monitoring, inspection or regulatory function related to the exercise of official authority; the protection of rights and freedoms of the data subject or others; the enforcement of civil law claims (GDPR, article 23, para 1). Such legislative measure shall contain minimum specific provision as stipulated under para 2 of the article 23 GDPR.

Right to remedy

Every data subject has the right to lodge a complaint before the competent supervisory authority²⁰⁵. In case the supervisory authority does not handle the complaint or does not inform the subject within three months on the progress or outcome of the complaint, the data subject has the right to an effective judicial remedy²⁰⁶. Furthermore, every natural or legal person has the right to an effective judicial

¹⁹⁹ GDPR, article 21, para 6.

²⁰⁰ GDPR, article 22, para 1.

²⁰¹ GDPR, article 22, para 2. See also recital 71 GDPR.

²⁰² GDPR, article 22, para 3.

²⁰³ Recital 71, GDPR.

²⁰⁴ The time period may be extended if necessary and the controller has to inform the data subject for any extension; GDPR, article 12 para 3.

²⁰⁵ Article 77 GDPR.

²⁰⁶ GDPR, article 78, para 2.

remedy against a legally binding decision of a supervisory authority that concerns them²⁰⁷. The data subject, who considers that his/her rights under the GDPR have been violated by the controller due to processing in non-compliance with the GDPR, has, in addition, the right to an effective judicial remedy (directly)²⁰⁸. In case controllers were two or more, the data subject may exercise his/her rights under the GDPR against each of the controllers²⁰⁹. If such an infringement of the GDPR has caused material or non-material damages to a person, then the controller or the processor have to compensate the person²¹⁰.

3.2.2.3 Other specific European data protection law

More specific provisions have been laid down with regard to the processing of personal data by police and criminal justice authorities, as well as the electronic communications.

Data protection law in the context of the police and criminal justice

In order to balance the individual's interests in data protection and society's interests in data collection for the purpose of fighting crime and ensuring national and public safety, a specific legal instrument was adopted together with the General Data Protection Regulation, namely the Directive (EU) 2016/680 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data ('Police Directive')²¹¹. This Directive has repealed the Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA, as to align with the provisions of the GDPR. Given that directives are not directly applicable, in order to come into force, they need to be transposed into national law. Therefore, national legislator must adopt a transposing act or other 'national implementing measure' to bring national law into line with the directive's objectives. EU countries have to incorporate the Police Directive into their national law by 6 May 2018.

Table 3-6 Key points

Key points ²¹²
<p>The directive requires that the data collected by law enforcement authorities are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • processed lawfully and fairly; • collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and processed only in line with these purposes; • adequate, relevant and not excessive in relation to the purpose in which they are processed; • accurate and updated where necessary; • kept in a form which allows identification of the individual for no longer than is necessary for the purpose of the processing; • appropriately secured, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing.

²⁰⁷ GDPR, article 78, para 2.

²⁰⁸ Article 79 GDPR.

²⁰⁹ GDPR, Article 26 para 3.

²¹⁰ Article 83 GDPR.

²¹¹ Available at: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016L0680&qid=1522240823531&from=EN>

²¹² Retrieved from: Protection of personal data, Directive (EU) 2016/680, Summary of legislation, available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/LSU/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2016.119.01.0089.01.ENG

Time limits

EU Member States must establish time limits for erasing the personal data or for a regular review of the need to store such data.

Individuals concerned ('data subjects')

The directive requires that the law enforcement authorities make a clear distinction between the data of different categories of persons including:

- those for whom there are serious grounds to believe they have committed or are about to commit a criminal offence;
- those who have been convicted of a criminal offence;
- victims of criminal offences or persons whom it is reasonably believed could be victims of criminal offences;
- those who are parties to a criminal offence, including potential witnesses.

Information available or provided to data subject

Individuals have the right to have certain information made available to them by the law enforcement (i.e. data protection) authorities including:

- the name and contact details of the competent authority which decides the purpose and means of the data processing;
- why their data is being processed;
- the right to launch a complaint with a supervisory authority and the contact details of the authority;
- the existence of the right to request access to and correction or deletion of their personal data as well as the right to restrict processing of their personal data.

Security

National authorities must take technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security for personal data that is appropriate to the risk. Where data processing is automated, a number of measures must be put in place, including:

- denying unauthorised persons access to equipment used for processing;
- preventing the unauthorised reading, copying, changing or removal of data media;

preventing the unauthorised input of personal data and the unauthorised viewing, changing or deleting of stored personal data.

The Police Directive aims at the enhanced protection of individuals' personal data, irrespective of their nationality or place of residence, when their data are processed by the police and criminal justice authorities and at the same time, at the improvement of cooperation in the fight against terrorism and cross-border crime within the EU by enabling police and criminal justice authorities in Member States to exchange information necessary for investigations more efficiently and effectively²¹³. In particular, as articulated in recital 11 of the Directive, it regulates 'the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties,

²¹³ See also European Commission - Directorate General for Justice and Consumers, *How will the data protection reform fight international crime?*, factsheet January 2016, available at: http://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/just/document.cfm?doc_id=41527

including the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security, respecting the specific nature of those activities'. An important aspect is that such competent authorities may be public, namely judicial authorities, the police or other law-enforcement authorities, but also private bodies or entities that have been assigned by national law to exercise public authority and public powers for the purposes of the Police Directive, i.e. the fight against crime. Therefore, 'a body or entity which processes personal data on behalf of such authorities within the scope of this Directive should be bound by a contract or other legal act and by the provisions applicable to processors pursuant to this Directive, while the application of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 remains unaffected for the processing of personal data by the processor outside the scope of this Directive'²¹⁴. Moreover, this directive lays down the rules for the transfer of personal data for purposes that fall within the scope of the directive, such as from a member state to Interpol²¹⁵.

Member states are directed, to the extent feasible, to make a clear distinction between different categories of data subjects such as: suspects; persons convicted of a criminal offence; victims and other parties, such as witnesses, informants or associates of suspects and convicted criminals²¹⁶. At the same time, this should not prevent the application of the right of presumption of innocence²¹⁷. States should also distinguish verified and accurate data from personal data based on personal assessments²¹⁸. Inaccurate data should not be made available or transmitted²¹⁹. Moreover, states are directed expressly to establish appropriate time limits for deleting personal data or for a periodic review of the need for the storage of personal data and set a procedure to monitor whether time limits are respected²²⁰.

The principles for processing personal data, the role of controller, processor and data protection officer, as well as the rights of the data subject, as articulated in the Directive, are in alignment with the provisions of the GDPR. Yet, specific rules are further established to secure potential breaches of personal data that may adversely affect the data subject's fundamental rights and freedoms and to set limitations to the data subject's rights. Controller and processor should keep a record of all processing operations²²¹. In addition, considering the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing of personal data under this Directive, and the necessity for cross-border transfer of personal data in the fight against crime, concrete safeguards and conditions are set out.

Data protection in the electronic communications sector

Given that public communication services, such as the internet, mobile and landline telephony and their accompanying networks, information is exchanged, and this may involve great interference to the individual's private life, specific rules and safeguards were necessary to ensure the users' right to privacy and confidentiality. European law in relation to data protection and electronic communications networks and services consists of the Directive 2002/58/EC on the processing of personal data and the protection

²¹⁴ Recital 11, Police Directive.

²¹⁵ Recital 25, Police Directive.

²¹⁶ Article 6 & Recital 31, Police Directive

²¹⁷ Recital 31, Police Directive.

²¹⁸ Article 7(1), Police Directive.

²¹⁹ Article 7(2), Police Directive.

²²⁰ Article 5, Police Directive.

²²¹ Articles 24 & 25, Police directive

of privacy in the electronic communications sector (*Directive on privacy and electronic communications*)²²² as amended by Directive 2009/136/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2009²²³.

The Directive concerns the use of communication services in public electronic networks (internet & mobile phone networks) and sets out rules to ensure security in the processing of personal data, the notification of personal data breaches, and confidentiality of communications. It also bans unsolicited communications where the users have not given their consent. The Directive covers the communications of both natural and legal persons.

Table 3-7 Key points

Key points ²²⁴
<p>Providers of electronic communication services must secure their services by at least:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ensuring personal data are accessed by authorised persons only; • protecting personal data from being destroyed, lost or accidentally altered and from other unlawful or unauthorised forms of processing; • ensuring the implementation of a security policy on the processing of personal data.
<p>The service provider must inform the national authority of any personal data breach within 24 hours. If the personal data or privacy of a user is likely to be harmed, they must also be informed unless specifically identified technological measures have been taken to protect the data.</p>
<p>EU countries must ensure the confidentiality of communications made over public networks, in particular they must:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prohibit the listening, tapping, storage or any type of surveillance or interception of communications and traffic data without the consent of users, except if the person is legally authorised and in compliance with specific requirements; • guarantee that the storing of information or the access to information stored on user's personal equipment is only permitted if the user has been clearly and fully informed, among other things, of the purpose and been given the right of refusal.
<p>When traffic data are no longer required for communication or billing, they must be erased or made anonymous. However, service providers may process these data for marketing</p>

²²² Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (*Directive on privacy and electronic communications*), OJ 2002 L 201. The consolidated version of the directive is available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02002L0058-20091219>. 'This directive is one of five which together form the telecoms package, a legislative framework governing the electronic communications sector. The other directives cover the general framework, access and interconnection, authorisation and licensing and universal service. The package was amended in 2009 by two directives on better law-making and citizens' rights as well as by a regulation establishing the Body of European regulators for electronic communications.' For more information, see the European Commission's [ePrivacy directive website](#).

²²³ Directive 2009/136/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2009 amending Directive 2002/22/EC on universal service and users' rights relating to electronic communications networks and services, Directive 2002/58/EC concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector and Regulation (EC) No 2006/2004 on cooperation between national authorities responsible for the enforcement of consumer protection laws. Available at: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32009L0136>

²²⁴ Retrieved from: Data protection in the electronic communications sector, Directive [2002/58/EC](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communications), available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/LSU/?uri=CELEX:02002L0058-20091219>

purposes for as long as the users concerned give their consent. This consent may be withdrawn at any time.

User consent is also required in a number of other situations, including:

- before unsolicited communications (spam) can be sent to them. This also applies to short message services (SMSs) and other electronic messaging systems;
- before information (cookies) is stored on their computers or devices or before access to that information is obtained - the user must be given clear and full information, among other things, on the purpose of the storage or access;
- before telephone numbers, e-mail addresses or postal addresses can appear in public directories.

EU countries are required to have a system of penalties including legal sanctions for infringements of the directive.

The scope of the rights and obligations can only be restricted by national legislative measures when such restrictions are necessary and proportionate to safeguard specific public interests, such as to allow criminal investigations or to safeguard national security, defence or public security.

Definitions

According to article 3 of the E-privacy Directive,

'user' means any natural person using a publicly available electronic communications service, for private or business purposes, without necessarily having subscribed to this service;

'traffic data' means any data processed for the purpose of the conveyance of a communication on an electronic communications network or for the billing thereof; traffic data may include 'data referring to the routing, duration, time or volume of a communication, to the protocol used, to the location of the terminal equipment of the sender or recipient, to the network on which the communication originates or terminates, to the beginning, end or duration of a connection. They may also consist of the format in which the communication is conveyed by the network'²²⁵.

'location data' means the data indicating the geographic position (latitude, longitude, altitude) of the terminal equipment of a user of a publicly available electronic communications service (e.g. direction to travel, identification of the network cell, in which the terminal equipment is located at a certain point in time and to the time the location information was recorded)²²⁶;

'communication' means any information exchanged or conveyed between a restricted number of parties by means of a public electronic communications service. 'This does not include any information conveyed as part of a broadcasting service to the public over an electronic communications network except to the extent that the information can be related to the identifiable subscriber or user receiving the information'²²⁷; 'a communication may include any naming, numbering or addressing information

²²⁵ Recital 15.

²²⁶ Recital 14.

²²⁷ See also recital 16.

provided by the sender of a communication or the user of a connection to carry out the communication²²⁸.

*Main provisions*²²⁹

The provider of a public electronic communications service must take appropriate technical and organisational measures to guarantee security of its services, such as restricted access - authorised persons, for legally authorized purposes, protection against personal data breaches²³⁰, implementation of security policy, if necessary together with the provider of the public communications network with respect to network security²³¹.

Three main data categories generated during communication are identified and regulated in the e-privacy directive, namely the content of a communication, the traffic data and the location data. Confidentiality of electronic communications concerns not only the content of a communication (what was said or sent) but also to traffic data, such as information about who communicated with whom, when and for how long, and location data, such as from where data were communicated²³². Traffic data have to be erased or made anonymous when they are no longer needed for the purpose of a communication transmission, unless the user has provided consent after being comprehensively informed about transmitting the data to added value service providers²³³ (e.g. what is near my location- restaurants, bus station etc. or directions²³⁴) or for the improvements to the service provision. Location data can be processed only when they are made anonymous or with the specific and informed consent of the user²³⁵. Calling line identification (caller identification) and location data may be disclosed in cases of emergency²³⁶. Surveillance or interception of communications, for example, by listening or tapping devices, is prohibited unless it is provided for by law and constitutes a necessary measure in a democratic society in the interest of: protecting state security, public safety, the monetary interests of the state or the suppression of criminal offences; or protecting the data subject or the rights and freedoms of others²³⁷.

Furthermore, processing or transmission of data solely for marketing is fairly restricted to the cases where consent is provided²³⁸, the user holds the right to be informed about the traffic data that are being kept and processed. In case a data breach occurs, as a result of unauthorised access, loss or

²²⁸ Recital 15.

²²⁹ See also European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA), Handbook on European data protection law, 2014, pp. 166-170, available at: http://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra-2014-handbook-data-protection-law-2nd-ed_en.pdf

²³⁰ Under article 2, personal data breach' means a breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed in connection with the provision of a publicly available electronic communications service in the Community

²³¹ Article 4 para 1.

²³² Article 5.

²³³ Article 6.

²³⁴ See Recital 35.

²³⁵ Article 9.

²³⁶ Articles 8 & 10(2) & Recital 36.

²³⁷ Articles 5(1) & 15(1). See also European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA), Handbook on European data protection law, 2014, p.170, available at: http://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra-2014-handbook-data-protection-law-2nd-ed_en.pdf

²³⁸ Article 5.

destruction of data, the competent supervisory authority must be notified immediately²³⁹. Users must be informed if possible, damage to them is the consequence of a data breach²⁴⁰. The establishment of judicial remedies is also foreseen²⁴¹.

3.2.3 National Legislation

3.2.3.1 Greece

3.2.3.1.1 The right to private life and the protection of personal data under the Greek Constitution

The right to private life

Under article 9(1) of the Greek Constitution, “the private and family life of an individual is inviolable”. As a significant aspect of the free development of personality, the right to private life is expressly stipulated in the 1975 Constitution, influenced by the provisions of Article 8 of the 1951 European Convention on Human Rights on the right to respect of a person’s private and family life, home and correspondence²⁴². The right to private life constitutes a right with evolving concept and scope. In order to meet current protection safeguards, in light of technological advancements in the sector of information and communication, as well as of the intrusion of the mass media and the internet into a person’s private sphere, an evolving interpretation is deemed necessary. In the context of article 9(1) of the Constitution, the individual is protected against intrusion from others, public authorities or other natural and legal persons.

The right holders are natural persons, nationals and non-nationals and under conditions persons under the 18 years of age. With regard to children (persons under the age of 18), their right to privacy is guaranteed under article 16 of the 1989 United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, which has been ratified by the law 2101/1992. This should be considered in conjunction with the Civil Code regulating legal capacity and legal custody of parents and legal guardianship.

Main infringements of the right to private life can be a) the disclosure of an individual’s personal data related to his/her private sphere without his/her consent or with no legal and justified grounds in the public interest, b) the surveillance with the use of technology and devices, which can result in the disclosure of data containing sensitive information and place a risk to the individual’s fundamental rights and freedoms, and c) transmission of information related to an individual’s private life²⁴³.

The right to private life is connected with articles 9 A of the Constitution on the right to the protection of personal data and article 19(1) on the right to communications confidentiality and thus must be examined in conjunction. All the aforementioned comprise the principal aspects of an individual’s private sphere, especially with regard to communication and exchange and transmission of information and data.

The right to the protection of personal data

²³⁹ Article 4(3).

²⁴⁰ Ibid.

²⁴¹ Article 15(2).

²⁴² See also Ακριβοπούλου Χ.Μ., Άρθρο 9, in: Σύνταγμα, Κατ’ άρθρο ερμηνεία, Φ. Σπυρόπουλος, Ξ. Κοντιάδης, Χ. Ανθόπουλος, Γ. Γεραπετρίτης (eds), Εκδόσεις Σάκκουλα, Αθήνα- Θεσσαλονίκη, 2017.

²⁴³ Δαγτόγλου Π. Δ., Συναγματικό δίκαιο, Ατομικά δικαιώματα, Εκδόσεις Σάκκουλα, Αθήνα-Θεσσαλονίκη, 2012, p. 331.

In article 9 A of the Greek Constitution it is stipulated that 'All persons have the right to be protected from the collection, processing and use, especially by electronic means, of their personal data, as specified by law. The protection of personal data is ensured by an independent authority, which is constituted and operates as specified by law'. This clause has been introduced with the 2001 revision of the Constitution in alignment with European standards. Within the scope of this provision falls every information which relates to an identified or identifiable natural person in the context of both his/her private sphere and in the public sphere^{244,245}. In addition, it includes all aspects of intervention and not solely automated processing, though the risks of technological developments are considered. Limitation to the right can be imposed only where provided by law setting requirements such as the informed consent of the data subject or the exercise of other rights (e.g. to information, to freedom of expression, to a legal claim) or a public interest (e.g. the investigation of crimes)²⁴⁶. In any event, the principle of proportionality, as stipulated in article 25 of the Constitution, must be met and the respect and protection of the value of the human being should be guaranteed^{247,248}.

The right to personal data protection concerns every natural person. Legal persons' data are not personal data. Under the constitutional provision, state authorities, bodies and agencies shall ensure the unhindered implementation of the right and for this shall take also safeguard measures²⁴⁹. Furthermore, an independent authority must be in place to ensure the implementation of the right to personal data protection.

The right to confidentiality of correspondence

According to article 19(1) of the Constitution, 'secrecy of letters and all other forms of free correspondence or communication shall be absolutely inviolable. The guaranties under which the judicial authority shall not be bound by this secrecy for reasons of national security or for the purpose of investigating especially serious crimes, shall be specified by law'. Though the article was stipulated in the 2001 Constitution's revision, within the meaning of correspondence, all current means of communication are included. This constitutional protection is provided for communications where the individual (a party) expresses a reasonable subjective expectation that the content and other elements of the communication will not be disclosed to third parties²⁵⁰. Data identified and protected in the course of communication comprise of the content of the messages transmitted, the data necessary for the establishment and maintenance of a communication (communication partners, time and duration of the communication; traffic data) and the data related to the location of the communication device employed

²⁴⁴ See Council of State, Decision 1616/2012.

²⁴⁵ Μίτλεπτον Φ., Η έννοια των προσωπικών δεδομένων, in: Προσωπικά δεδομένα, Κοτσαλής Λ. (ed.), Νομική Βιβλιοθήκη, 2016, Νομική Βιβλιοθήκη, 2016, p. 10.

²⁴⁶ Μήτρου Λ., Άρθρο 9 Α, in: Σύνταγμα, Κατ' άρθρο ερμηνεία, Φ. Σπυρόπουλος, Ξ. Κοντιάδης, Χ. Ανθόπουλος, Γ. Γεραπετρίτης (eds.), Εκδόσεις Σάκκουλα, Αθήνα- Θεσσαλονίκη, 2017, p. 225.

²⁴⁷ Article 2(1) of the Constitution.

²⁴⁸ See Council of State, Decision 3545/2002.

²⁴⁹ Μίτλεπτον Φ., Η έννοια των προσωπικών δεδομένων, in: Προσωπικά δεδομένα, Κοτσαλής Λ. (ed.), Νομική Βιβλιοθήκη, 2016, Νομική Βιβλιοθήκη, 2016.

²⁵⁰ Παπαδόπουλος Ν., Άρθρο 19, in: Σύνταγμα, Κατ' άρθρο ερμηνεία, Φ. Σπυρόπουλος, Ξ. Κοντιάδης, Χ. Ανθόπουλος, Γ. Γεραπετρίτης (eds.), Εκδόσεις Σάκκουλα, Αθήνα- Θεσσαλονίκη, 2017, p. 477 citing ECHR case law.

(location data)²⁵¹. Limitations to the right to confidentiality may be introduced in case (a) it is necessary for complying with a legal provision; (b) safeguards are in place that prohibit any infringement of the constitutional statutes; (c) there is court order to do so; (d) this serves the purposes of public security and the investigation of serious crimes²⁵².

3.2.3.1.2 *Legal framework on personal data protection and processing*

3.2.3.1.2.1 *Main provisions*

The principal legal instrument regulating the protection of personal data is up until May 2018 law 2472/1997 as amended²⁵³, which was originally adopted to transpose the 'Directive 95/46/EC on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data' into national law. However, from 25 May 2018 and on, the General Data Protection Regulation will come into force directly in all Members States. Therefore, law 2472/1997 will be repealed. For the necessary changes and adjustments in national legislation, a new legal act has been proclaimed. The developed draft bill includes regulatory measures for the correct implementation of the GDPR nationwide and the transposition of the Police Directive into national law. Therefore, the law provides in Greek and within the Greek context all principles, measures, safeguards, processes, rules, exceptions and rights which are included in the GDPR and the Police Directive. A more concrete provision on making certain personal data public where a crime is being investigated is also foreseen. In addition, the upcoming role of the independent supervisory authority is laid down. Nevertheless, the draft bill has not been adopted yet (April 2018) and for this reason it is not possible to proceed with further description. In any event, the clauses of the GDPR, as spelt out, will come into force as expected.

3.2.3.1.2.2 *The role of the Authority for the Protection of Personal Data*

The role of the national supervisory authority, "the Authority for the Protection of Personal Data"²⁵⁴, has changed by the introduction of the GDPR. To this end, no particular prior permission from the competent independent authority is necessary for the processing of personal data. To the contrary, the Regulation has established a certain procedure and safeguard measures to be applied in order for every controller and processor to know beforehand how compliance directly with the GDPR can be achieved. At the same time, the national supervisory authorities may set forth more concrete rules for processing activities that involve various categories of personal data and monitor the implementation of the GDPR in the country by providing consultation, conducting investigation, receiving complaints and issuing decisions. In the context of an investigation the member of the national authority has the right to have

²⁵¹ Παπαδόπουλος Ν., Άρθρο 19, in: Σύνταγμα, Κατ' άρθρο ερμηνεία, Φ. Σπυρόπουλος, Ξ. Κοντιάδης, Χ. Ανθόπουλος, Γ. Γεραπετρίτης (eds.), Εκδόσεις Σάκκουλα, Αθήνα- Θεσσαλονίκη, 2017.

²⁵² Δαγτόγλου Π. Δ., Σύνταγματικό δίκαιο, Ατομικά δικαιώματα, Εκδόσεις Σάκκουλα, Αθήνα-Θεσσαλονίκη, 2012, σελ. 361.

²⁵³ Consolidated version of the law, available at:

<http://www.dpa.gr/pls/portal/url/ITEM/E3BC3C1B7FC83BA6E040A8C07D24022A>

²⁵⁴ Website of the Greek Authority for the Protection of Personal Data available at:

http://www.dpa.gr/portal/page?_pageid=33,15048&_dad=portal&_schema=PORTAL

full access to the processing operations except for public security cases or for serious crime investigation²⁵⁵.

All members of the Greek Authority for the Protection of Personal Data are bound by a duty of confidentiality. In case of any personal data leak by a member of the authority, the perpetrator is charged with fine or even incarceration and violations are regarded as cause of disciplinary action too. The national independent authority, pursuant to the provisions under articles 57 & 58 of the GDPR should, inter alia, encourage the drawing up of codes of conduct²⁵⁶ and provide an opinion and approve such codes of conduct²⁵⁷; encourage the establishment of data protection certification mechanisms and of data protection seals and marks²⁵⁸ and approve the criteria of certification²⁵⁹.

3.2.3.1.2.3 Decision of the Hellenic Authority for Data Protection for Data Protection Impact Assessment-DPIA

In May 2019 Hellenic Authority for Data Protection established and made public a list of the kind of processing operations which are subject to the requirement for a data protection impact assessment according to GDPR Article 35(4).²⁶⁰

3.2.3.1.3 Legal framework on electronic communications privacy

3.2.3.1.3.1 Main provisions and the case of disclosing communication

The primary legal instrument regulating privacy issues in the electronic communications sector is the law 3471/2006 which transposed the E-privacy Directive (2002/58/EC concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector) into national law. Within the scope of the law falls any type of communication through land and mobile telephony, as well as the internet (public communications services & networks). Further on, by law 3674/2008 more safeguard measures were introduced such as obligations of the communication service providers to draft security policies, to encrypt voice messages, to record any processing activity, to inform the user and the supervisory authority where a personal data breach has occurred²⁶¹. As the 2002 e-privacy directive was significantly amended by the Directive 2009/136/EC, law 3471/2006 had to be amended accordingly. Therefore, with the law 4070/2012 under articles 168-173 modifications were introduced to law 3471/2006²⁶².

²⁵⁵ Draft available at: http://www.opengov.gr/ministryofjustice/wp-content/uploads/downloads/2018/02/sxedio_nomou_prostasia_pd.pdf

²⁵⁶ See article 40(1) GDPR.

²⁵⁷ See article 40(5) GDPR.

²⁵⁸ See article 42(1) GDPR.

²⁵⁹ See article 42(5) GDPR.

²⁶⁰ List of the kind of processing operations which are subject to the requirement for a data protection impact assessment according to GDPR Article 35(4) ([Government Gazzete B' 1622/10-5-2019](http://www.gazzette.gr/1622/10-5-2019))

²⁶¹ Available at: <http://www.adae.gr/fileadmin/docs/nomoi/N.3674.2008.pdf>

²⁶² Consolidated version of the law 3471/2006, available at: http://www.dpa.gr/pls/portal/docs/PAGE/APDPX/LAW/NOMOTHESIA%20PROSOPIKA%20DEDOMENA/FILES/N3471_06.PDF

The meaning of personal data breach has been broadened pursuant to the provisions of the amended e-privacy Directive, as new forms of breach were discovered²⁶³; 'personal data breach' means a breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed in connection with the provision of a publicly available electronic communications service. In accordance, the obligations of the service provider where a data breach has occurred were more explicitly laid down pursuant to article 4(3) of the E-privacy Directive²⁶⁴.

With regard to the security of processing and without prejudice to the principal legal instrument on data protection (be it previously the Directive 95/46/EC and now the GDPR), the service providers must ensure that personal data can be accessed only by authorised personnel; protect personal data stored or transmitted against accidental or unlawful destruction, accidental loss or alteration, and unauthorised or unlawful storage, processing, access or disclosure; and ensure the implementation of a security policy with respect to the processing of personal data²⁶⁵.

Provisions on traffic data and location data, as previously analysed, cover not only the new forms of services provided through land and mobile telephony, but also the services provided by social networking sites²⁶⁶. Processing of location data is prohibited unless the user has provided his/her consent (which can withdraw at any time) or the competent authorities for emergency situations or law-enforcement and judicial authorities, first aid services and fire-brigade request the location data to identify the call and further to manage an emergency or investigating a crime²⁶⁷.

Confidentiality of communications may be restricted only in compliance with the Constitution. Law 2225/1994 regulates the lifting of confidentiality according to the constitutional statute for the purposes of either public security or the investigation of serious crimes²⁶⁸. In the latter case, lifting of confidentiality can be ordered by the Judicial Council after a request from the Public Prosecutor or the Investigating Magistrate. Within 24 hours, the Council must issue a decision. In exceptional cases, the Public Prosecutor or the Investigating Magistrate can order the lifting of confidentiality and within 3 days, they have to introduce the request before the competent Judicial Council. Additional safeguard action has to be taken for the prevention of abusing such measures. Consequently, for each order for lifting confidentiality the Authority for Communication Security and Privacy, the competent Minister (of Justice) and to the body in charge (management committee/ council/ board) of the legal person of the communication service provider or network must be notified. Moreover, the competent judicial authority shall write a report for each order issued concerning the lifting of confidentiality; the measure has to

²⁶³ Article 2(11) Law 3471/2006.

²⁶⁴ Article 12(2) Law 3471/2006.

²⁶⁵ Article 12(3), law 3471/2006.

²⁶⁶ Μίτλεπτον Φ., Η έννοια των προσωπικών δεδομένων, in: Προσωπικά δεδομένα, Κοτσαλής Λ. (ed.), Νομική Βιβλιοθήκη, 2016, Νομική Βιβλιοθήκη, 2016.

²⁶⁷ Article 6(4) & (5) Law 3471/2006 as amended.

²⁶⁸ Lifting of Confidentiality is permissible for the investigation of felonies under:

(a) articles 134, 135(1)&(2), 135 A, 137 A, 137 B, 138, 139, 140, 143, 144, 146, 148(2), 150, 151, 157(1), 168(1), 187(1)&(2), 207, 208(1), 264 points (b)&(c), 270, 272, 275 point (b), 291(1) point (b)&(c), 229, 322, 324(2)&(3), 374, 380, 385 of the Penal Code; Article 4(1) point (a) of law 2225/1994 as amended by Law 3658/2008. Kidnapping for the purpose of ransom or kidnapping of a child under 14 years old falls under this provision.

be limited to the minimum necessary duration and the user (data subject) holds the right to be notified after the measure has been taken.

3.2.3.1.3.2 The role of the Authority for Communication Security and Privacy

The national independent authority for safeguarding the privacy of communications, the "Authority for Communication Security and Privacy"²⁶⁹, was established with Law 3115/2003 (article 1)²⁷⁰, pursuant to article 19(2) of the Greek Constitution. The authority is, inter alia, responsible for monitoring the cases where lifting of confidentiality has been employed; carries out investigations; receives complaints; keeps a record of personal data processing and provides advices on issues of privacy. According to the amended article 6(4) of Law 3471/2006, the national authority issues acts where the procedure, the means any other technical detail for disclosing location data is described.

3.2.3.2 Belgium

3.2.3.2.1 The right to private life and the protection of personal data under the Belgian Constitution *The right to private life (and family life)*

The Belgian Constitution provides the right to respect for private and family life in Article 22 and the right to freedom of expression in Articles 19 and 25. In addition, it regulates the right to respect of a person's home (Article 15) and the right to secrecy of communication (Article 29).

In addition, there are several specific laws in Belgium that include provisions protecting the right to privacy, such as:

- The Law on the protection of privacy in relation to the processing of personal data (Wet tot bescherming van de persoonlijke levenssfeer ten opzichte van de verwerking van persoonsgegevens/Loi relative à la protection de la vie privée à l'égard des traitements de données à caractère personnel) (Data Protection Law) of 8 December 1992.
- The Belgian Criminal Code provides criminal sanctions for certain infringements of private and family life, including:
 - telephone tapping (*Article 314bis*);
 - violation of domestic privacy (*Article 439*);
 - stalking and mobbing (*Article 442bis and ter*);
 - libel (*Article 443 to 447*);
 - professional secrecy (*Article 458*);
 - secrecy of correspondence (*Article 460 to 460ter*).

In addition, there are various laws and regulations containing privacy rights that relate to specific situations, including employee rights, patient rights, electronic communications, installation and use of surveillance cameras.

Belgium is also a signatory to several international conventions (including the European Convention on Human Rights) that provide protection of an individual's right to privacy and the right to freedom of expression.

²⁶⁹ Website of the Hellenic Authority for Communication Security and Privacy available at: <http://www.adae.gr> . Relevant legislation available at: <http://www.adae.gr/nomothetiko-plaisio/elliniki-nomothesia/nomoi-gia-to-aporritho-epikoionon/>

²⁷⁰ Available at: <http://www.adae.gr/fileadmin/docs/nomoi/N.3115-2003.pdf>

The right to protection of personal data

The Data Protection Directive has been implemented into Belgian law by the Law on the protection of privacy in relation to the processing of personal data (*Wet tot bescherming van de persoonlijke levenssfeer ten opzichte van de verwerking van persoonsgegevens/Loi relative à la protection de la vie privée à l'égard des traitements de données à caractère personnel*) (DPL) of 8 December 1992 (as subsequently amended), which entered into force on 1 September 2001. The DPL has been further implemented by the Royal Decree of 13 February 2001 (*Koninklijk besluit ter uitvoering van de wet van 8 december 1992 tot bescherming van de persoonlijke levenssfeer ten opzichte van de verwerking van persoonsgegevens/Arrêté royal portant exécution de la loi du 8 décembre 1992 relative à la protection de la vie privée à l'égard des traitements de données à caractère personnel*).

Sectoral laws

Belgium has not adopted a genuinely "sectoral" approach for the regulation of the protection of privacy and personal data, but has nevertheless adopted specific rules for certain cases. In addition to the DPL and the Royal Decree of 13 February 2001, a number of specific laws and rules also contain provisions on the protection of privacy and personal data, such as:

- The installation and use of surveillance cameras (except for cases subject to specific regulations) is governed by the Camera Surveillance Law of 21 March 2007 (*Wet tot regeling van de plaatsing en het gebruik van bewakingscamera's/Loi réglant l'installation et l'utilisation de caméras de surveillance*).
- The installation and use of surveillance cameras for monitoring employees is subject to Collective Bargaining Agreement No. 68 concerning the camera surveillance of employees of 16 June 1998 (*Collectieve arbeidsovereenkomst 68 betreffende de bescherming van de persoonlijke levenssfeer van de werknemers ten opzichte van de camerabewaking op de arbeidsplaats/Convention collective de travail 68 relative à la protection de la vie privée des travailleurs à l'égard de la surveillance par caméras sur le lieu de travail*).
- Monitoring of employees' online communication is regulated by Collective Bargaining Agreement No. 81 concerning the monitoring of electronic communications of employees of 26 April 2002 (*Collectieve arbeidsovereenkomst 81 tot bescherming van de persoonlijke levenssfeer van de werknemers ten opzichte van de controle op de elektronische onlinecommunicatiegegevens/Convention collective de travail 81 relative à la protection de la vie privée des travailleurs à l'égard du contrôle des données de communication électroniques en réseau*).
- The implementation of exit checks for employees with a view of preventing theft in the workplace is regulated by Collective Bargaining Agreement No. 89 concerning the prevention of theft and exit checks for employees leaving the company or the workplace of 30 January 2007 (*Collectieve arbeidsovereenkomst 89 betreffende de diefstalpreventie en de uitgangscodes van werknemers bij het verlaten van de onderneming of de werkplaats/Convention collective de travail 89 concernant la prévention des vols et les contrôles de sortie des travailleurs quittant l'entreprise ou le lieu de travail*).
- The Electronic Communications Law of 13 June 2005 (*Wet betreffende de elektronische communicatie/Loi relative aux communications électroniques*) contains provisions on the secrecy of electronic communications and the protection of privacy in relation to such communications.

- The Patient Rights Law of 22 August 2002 (*Wet betreffende de rechten van de patient/Loi relative aux droits du patient*) regulates, among other things, the use of patients' data and the information that patients need to receive in respect of this use.

3.2.3.2.2 *Legal framework on personal data protection and processing*

Main provisions

The Law of 30 July 2018 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data (hereafter Law) was published in the Belgian Gazette and immediately entered into force on 5 September 2018. It has been stated that the Law will apply to companies and organisations that process personal data in relation to the activities of an establishment which is situated on Belgian territory, irrespective of where the processing takes place; or in relation to data subjects residing on Belgian territory, even if the company is not established there, and it offers goods and services to these subjects on Belgian territory or it monitors the behavior of such data subjects, for as far as this behavior takes place on Belgian territory; or which are established in a place where Belgian law is applicable under public international law.

The GDPR prohibits the processing of special categories of personal data (i.e. racial or ethnic origin, political beliefs, religious or philosophical beliefs, etc.). However, there are several exemptions in which case the processing of these special categories of personal data is allowed. One of the exemptions allows Member States to determine when the processing of these special categories of personal data is necessary for reasons of substantial public interest. Consequently, the Law lists three situations in which processing is deemed to be of substantial public interest. In concreto, the most relevant of these three situations relates to processing by associations who have as their statutory goal the defense and improvement of human rights and fundamental freedoms. The two other situations apply to sex offenders and are irrelevant to private companies and organisations.

Genetic, biometric data or data concerning health

In relation to the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health, the Law introduces three new obligations for the data controller or processor:

1. to indicate which categories of persons have access to the data and explain their relation to the processing of the personal data;
2. to maintain a list of these categories of persons for the Belgian data protection authority;
3. to make sure that the designated persons are subject to a legal, statutory or equal contractual obligation to ensure the confidential character of the personal data.

Cease and desist procedure

The Law introduces a so-called "cease and desist" procedure. This procedure allows the data subject, whose rights have been infringed, to bring a claim of infringement of data protection obligations before the President of the competent Court of First Instance. If the Court decides that there is indeed an infringement, it can prevent, in a rapid manner, further infringement of the data subject's rights via an injunction. The Court can also impose a penalty if the infringing party does not comply with the provisions of the injunction. The Court can also order a publication of its decision/order.

The role of the Authority for the Protection of Personal Data

The General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 creates a new privacy regime immediately applicable across the EU as from 25 May 2018. Under the GDPR, national supervisory authorities will have a strengthened role and increased enforcement powers.

In order to meet GDPR requirements, the Belgian legislator has adopted a law reforming the current Belgian Privacy Commission. The law was submitted in the Chamber of Representatives on 23 August 2017 and was approved by the Parliament in plenary meeting on 16 November 2017.

The main purpose of the new law is to reform the existing Privacy Commission ("Commissie voor de Bescherming van de Persoonlijke Levenssfeer" – "Commission de la Protection de la Vie Privée") to ensure that it can fulfil its tasks in accordance with the GDPR as from 25 May 2018. Unlike the current Privacy Commission, which has limited prosecutorial and no direct sanctioning powers, the new "Data Protection Authority" is to become a real investigative and sanctioning authority.

The name of the new authority will be "Gegevensbeschermingsautoriteit" in Dutch and "Autorité pour la protection des données" in French.

The law provides for a structural change of the composition of the current Belgian Privacy Commission. The existing sector committees (responsible for controlling the lawfulness of sector-specific data processing activities) will be replaced by six new bodies:

- An **Executive Committee** ("*Directiecomité*" – "*Comité de Direction*") responsible for defining the general policy of the Authority, including the use of the annual budget;
- A **General Secretariat** ("*Algemeen Secretariaat*" – "*Secrétariat general*") taking care of the daily operations of the Authority (e.g. providing advice on Data Protection Impact Assessments, creation of an accreditation system for certification bodies, adoption of standard contractual clauses, etc.);
- A **Front-line Service** ("*Eerstelijnsdienst*" – "*Service de première ligne*"): the intermediary player between data subjects and the inspection and litigation bodies. This body receives requests and complaints, starts mediation procedures, provides information and makes efforts to raise awareness;
- A **Knowledge Center** ("*Kenniscentrum*" – "*Centre de Connaissance*") issuing advice and recommendations on GDPR compliance;
- An **Inspection Body** ("*Inspectiedienst*" – "*Service d'inspection*"): the investigating body of the Data Protection Authority having an extensive range of investigative powers; and
- A **Dispute Chamber** ("*Geschillenkamer*" – "*Chambre contentieuse*"): a legal and administrative body holding the prosecution and sanctioning powers. Appeals against the decisions of the Dispute Chamber will be dealt with by the Market Court ("*Marktenhof*" – "*Cour des Marchés*") of the Brussels Court of Appeal.

These six bodies may be assisted by **experts** in the exercise of their tasks. The experts may come from different sectors (academic, private and public sector, civil society, etc.). Their advice will not be binding. The Data Protection Authority will also regularly consult a **Reflection Council**, who reflects the society in its entirety and who will be providing non-binding advice to the Authority.

The powers of the Data Protection Authority may be summarised into four categories, in order of priority:

- **Providing information and advice** to individuals, controllers, processors and policy makers to enforce or comply with data protection legislation;

- **Assisting** controllers and processors to make maximum use of the prevention tools provided for in the GDPR, such as certification, adherence to codes of conduct, appointment of a Data Protection Officer (DPO), etc.;
- **Monitoring** of controllers and processors, and carrying out investigations, through the Inspection Body.
- **Imposing sanctions**, ranging from a simple warning to administrative fines amounting up to 20 million EUR or 4% of the total worldwide annual turnover of the infringing undertaking, whichever is higher.

3.2.3.2.3 *Legal framework on electronic communications privacy*

3.2.3.2.3.1 *Main provisions and the case of disclosing communication*

The basic law regulating telecommunications in Belgium is the federal Electronic Communications Act of 13 June 2005 (Electronic Communications Act), which replaces most but not all of the provisions of the federal law of 21 March 1991. The Electronic Communications Act covers all essential fields of electronic communications, including:

- Defining the objectives and powers of the national telecommunications regulator, the Belgian Institute for Postal Services and Telecommunications (BIPT).
- Establishing specific regulations for telecommunication operators in relation to the notification requirements for the provision of electronic communications services and networks, the use of numbers and radio frequencies, shared use of sites and infrastructure, administrative fees, terminal equipment, directories and enquiry services and cryptography.
- Protecting fair market competition (for example, market analysis and the determination of significant market power (dominance), the imposition of regulatory obligations and so on).
- Protecting public interest, society and consumers (for example, universal service obligations, services of public interest and the protection of final users (including information of end users, quality and security of services, the provision of supplementary services, secrecy of communications, and the processing of personal data)).

The Electronic Communications Act was amended in 2012, 2014 and 2017, notably to implement the amended EU regulatory framework for telecommunications. A great number of Royal Decrees implement the various aspects covered by this Act.

The two other relevant federal Acts are the:

- Act of 17 January 2003 regarding the statute of the regulator BIPT.
- Act of 17 January 2003 on the appeals and dispute settlement arising from the law of 17 January 2003 on the statute of the regulator of the Belgian postal and telecommunications sectors.

Both acts have also been amended a few times, the last one by the federal law of 16 March 2015 to further ensure the independence of the BIPT following the intervention of the European Commission.

The Law of 8 December 1992 on the protection of privacy with respect to the processing of personal data applies to the telecommunications sector. This was amended by the Law of 11 December 1998, which implemented Directive 95/46/EC on data protection (Data Protection Directive) into Belgian law. The Law of 1992 was subsequently amended by the Law of 21 February 2003.

The 1995 EU Directive has been revised through the adoption in April 2016 of Regulation (EU) 679/2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)). The EU additionally adopted Directive 2016/21148/EU concerning measures for a high common level of security of network and information systems in July 2016, regulating cybersecurity standards for essential infrastructure at EU level for the first time. Both measures will take effect in May 2018. A separate directive adopted at the same time as the GDPR governs the data protection and data breach notification of public authorities processing personal data in the context of criminal law.

The GDPR grants regulatory authorities stronger investigative and enforcement powers and the ability to impose high fines for infringements of the legal framework regarding data protection. The exiting Belgian Commission for the Protection of Privacy was not authorised to impose fines and had to refer cases to the public prosecutor's office. Under the Law of 3 December 2017, the Belgian Data Protection Authority will have increased investigative and enforcement powers, such as the power to conduct on-site reviews and to impose administrative fines. The GDPR also requires all companies that process personal data to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures, such as pseudonymisation and encryption, to ensure a level of security that is appropriate to the risk.

Before the adoption of the GDPR, the Commission for the Protection of Privacy issued in December 2016 recommendations on the right to data portability, identification of the lead authority and the requirement to appoint a data protection officer. These recommendations were updated in May 2017.

The current Belgian general data protection rules contain numerous requirements regarding the processing of personal data. The Electronic Communications Act also creates a specific regime for operators (providers of electronic communications services) (based on the e-privacy directive also under revision by the EU institutions) in relation to the:

- Processing of data.
- Secrecy of communications.
- Protection of privacy.

Firstly, under the Electronic Communications Act operators must destroy all data traffic from subscribers or final users, or make such data anonymous, as soon as the information is no longer necessary for the transmission of the communication (Article 122, section 1, Electronic Communications Act) (although this is subject to the obligation to co-operate with the judicial authorities). However, an exception to this general rule applies in relation to limited data for the purposes of billing, marketing and investigating fraud (Article 122, sections 2 to 4, Electronic Communications Act). In this context, data can only be processed by the person responsible for billing, traffic management, the processing of client inquiries, fraud detection, marketing, and (under certain conditions relating to the end-user's consent) the provision of services with traffic and location data (Article 122, section 5, Electronic Communications Act). The processing of data must also be strictly limited to what is necessary for the exercise of these activities.

Secondly, the Electronic Communications Act protects the secrecy of communications (Article 124, Electronic Communications Act). This includes clear prohibitions on intentionally doing the following:

- Gain knowledge of the existence of information transmitted through electronic communications.
- Identify persons concerned by the transmission of information and its contents.
- Gain knowledge of electronic communications data regarding another person.

- Process or use any information, identification or data obtained.

A number of very limited exceptions to the principle of secrecy of communications are provided for in Article 125. Operators must notably co-operate with judicial authorities and therefore retain traffic data and make them available to the authorities.

In January 2017, the European Commission published a draft e-Privacy Regulation that would replace the current e-Privacy Directive. The new Regulation will also apply to new players providing electronic communications services such as WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger and Skype and will ensure that these new services guarantee the same level of confidentiality as traditional telecoms operators. In September 2017, the Council of the European Union (the Council) proposed several amendments to the text.

Articles 126 and 126/1 of the Electronic Communications Act, which impose data retention obligation on operators, were modified in May 2016 following a judgment of the European Court of Justice (ECJ) of 8 April 2014.

In this judgment, the ECJ held that Directive 2006/24/EC on the retention of data generated or processed in connection with the provision of publicly available electronic communications services or of public communications networks (Data Retention Directive) was invalid.

The ECJ stated that by requiring the retention of data by providers of public electronic communications services or networks, and by allowing the competent national authorities to access those data, the Data Retention Directive constituted an interference with the fundamental rights guaranteed by Article 7 (right to privacy) and Article 8 (protection of personal data) of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. The ECJ held that the Data Retention Directive did not provide clear and precise rules circumscribing the interference with these rights to what was strictly necessary. The data retention obligation generally covered all persons, and all means of electronic communications and traffic data without any differentiation, limitation or exception. Furthermore, no objective criterion determined the limits of the access of the competent national authorities to the data and their subsequent use. Regarding the period of detention, no distinction was being made between categories of data.

On 11 June 2015, the Belgian Constitutional Court consequently annulled former Article 126 of the Electronic Communications Act containing the data retention obligation for operators, on the same grounds as those identified by the Court of Justice.

Under the newly modified Article 126 introduced by a law from May 2016, operators must retain the following categories of data:

- User and subscriber identification data (holder of the number/address).
- Connection and location data (place and duration of communication).
- Personal communication data excluding the content (origin and destination of the communication).

The competent authorities allowed to receive the data from the operators are the judicial investigative authorities, the intelligence and security services, the public prosecutor's office, the emergency services and the Ombudsman for Telecommunications. These authorities can only access specifically defined data for the purpose of executing specific tasks entrusted to them (for example, investigation of certain types of criminal offences, the search for missing persons or the localisation of persons in need of help). Regardless of the category of data, operators must, as before, retain the data during 12 months.

In December 2016, the ECJ stated in a preliminary ruling that EU member states may not impose a general and indiscriminate obligation to retain data on providers of electronic communications services.

Data retention must thus be targeted for the purpose of fighting serious crime. Additionally, the ECJ held that the national authorities' access to the retained data must be subject to conditions (including prior review by an independent authority). The ECJ held that any national legislation on the retention of data must:

- Be clear and precise.
- Provide for sufficient guarantees on the protection of data against risks of misuse, including by laying down the substantive and procedural conditions governing the access of the competent national authorities to the retained data.

In March 2017, the ECJ held in case C-536/15 opposing the Belgian company European Directory Assistance to Dutch operators Tele2, Ziggo and Vodafone-Libertal that under the Universal Service Directive the consent given by a telephone subscriber in any member states regarding the publication of its data in a public directory does not need to be renewed for the passing of the same data to an undertaking in another member states, if it is guaranteed that the data in question will not be used for purposes other than those for which the data were collected with a view to their first publication. The ECJ further held that such passing of data to another undertaking is not capable of substantively impairing the right to protection of personal data, as recognised by the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.

In an opinion published in September 2017, the Belgian Institute for Postal Services and Telecommunications (BIPT) drew the consequences of this preliminary ruling and held that phone service providers must freely provide data to publishers of public directories, irrespective of their place of establishment.

Regarding cybersecurity, in 2014 the Centre for Cybersecurity Belgium (CCB) was set up by Royal Decree. The NISD promotes active co-operation among cybersecurity agencies at EU level.

In the electronic communication sector, the BIPT (Belgian Institute for Postal Services and Telecommunications) Council adopted on 14 December 2017 a decision regarding the thresholds and terms and conditions for reporting of security incidents within the electronic communications sector. This decision replaces the BIPT Council Decision of 1 April 2014 laying down the circumstances in which the operators must notify BIPT of a security incident and the terms and conditions of this notification. This decision specifies which security incidents have to be reported as well as the practical manner in which to report them.

Under the Belgian Code on Criminal Procedure, the public prosecutor is entitled to request operators of electronic communications networks to co-operate with them in relation to:

- Providing information enabling the identification of the subscriber and the electronic service subscribed to (*Article 46bis, Code on Criminal Procedure*).
- Demanding information from an operator regarding calls to and from a certain device (but not regarding the content of the call) (*Article 88bis, Code on Criminal Procedure*).
- Tapping telephone conversations (*Article 90ter to 90 decies, Code on Criminal Procedure*).

Electronic telecommunications providers must make accessible to judicial authorities, upon their simple request and without delay, data for the instruction and investigation for judiciary, security and intelligence purposes (Article 126, section 2, Electronic Communications Act). The new Article 126 of the Electronic Communications Act adds the emergency services and Ombudsman for

Telecommunications to the list of competent authorities that are entitled to request access to newly defined categories of communications data. The data that can be requested from operators includes:

- Traffic data.
- Location data.
- End-user identification data.
- Service and terminal equipment data.

This duty of co-operation is implemented by Royal Decrees of 9 January 2003, of 12 October 2010 and of 19 September 2013.

For example, each operator must set up a "co-ordination unit" to which the competent authorities can address their requests. If the data is less than 30 days old, the data must be communicated in real time. If the data is more than 30 days old, the data must be communicated the next working day. Under new Article 126(1) of the Electronic Communications Act, not only judicial authorities but also emergency services and the Ombudsman for telecommunications are under certain conditions entitled to access communications data.

3.2.3.2.3.2 The role of the Authority for Communication Security and Privacy

There is no requirement under the DPL to notify personal data security breaches to data subjects or to the Privacy Commission.

However, Article 114/1, §2 of the Electronic Communications Law of 13 June 2005, as well as Commission Regulation No 611/2013 of 24 June 2013 on the measures applicable to the notification of personal data breaches, require companies in the telecommunication sector to immediately (within 24 hours), notify personal data breaches to the DPA, who must transmit a copy of the notification to the Belgian Institute for postal services and telecommunications, Het Belgisch Instituut voor postdiensten en telecommunicatie/Institut belge des services postaux et des telecommunications (BIPT). If there is a breach of personal data or privacy of individuals, the company must also notify the data subjects affected by the breach.

A telecommunications company is exempt from the obligation to notify personal data breaches to the data subject if:

- The company asks the DPA for permission to postpone the notification to the data subject if the notification may endanger the investigation of the breach of personal data.
- The company can show that it has applied sufficient technical protection measures to protect the personal data that was subject to a breach. Such measures shall render the data unintelligible to any person who is not authorised to access it.

In order to facilitate the notification of personal data breaches, the DPA has published an electronic notification form specifically addressed to telecommunications operators.

BIPT is a federal institution which performs several tasks. As the regulator of the electronic communications market is, inter alia, has the task of promoting completion, contributing to the development of the internal market and protecting the users' interests.

3.2.3.3 Germany

In the course of the preparation of the D2.4, the legal framework surrounding missing children in Germany has been researched, both through analysing the German Criminal Code ("StGB") as well as through an observation of court proceedings. Due to the diverse nature of missing children cases that can range from stranger abductions to parental abductions or runaway incidents, different criminal code paragraphs were considered that shall be presented in the following. In order to fully understand the

ethical challenges connected to missing children, different criminal offenses relating to the threat to the psychological and physical health of missing children should be considered.

When using the internationally accepted MCE distinction of five different categories of missing children cases - namely Runaways, stranger abductions, international parental abductions, missing unaccompanied migrant minors, and lost, injured, or otherwise missing children - it becomes apparent that the German criminal code only directly applies to two of these case types. Both Stranger abductions and international parental abductions are both addressed in §235 StGB ("Entziehung Minderjähriger"), which criminalises the withdrawal of a minor from their parent or other caretaker. Subsection one of §235 StGB sets a punishment of up to five years in prison or a fine for the act of withdrawing a minor through the use of threat, violence or deceit as well as for abducting a child (under the age of 14 years) without being a relative of said child. Since §235 StGB subsection two states that the law also applies to cases in which a child is taken from a parent, caretaker or custodian to either bring or keep the child in another country, this law also covers cases of international custody battles that involve a parental abduction. Subsection three also includes the attempt of any abduction. Furthermore, any threat to the physical or psychological development or state of the child including a danger to the life of the child as well as the withdrawal of a child for the purpose of gaining money, is punishable with a prison sentence of one to ten years, according to subsection four of §235 StGB. If the child dies due to the crime, the prison sentence cannot be less than three years (see subsection five). Additionally, less severe cases of subsections four and five are addressed in subsections six and seven and will lead to sentences between six months and five years (for less severe cases of subsection four) or one year to ten years (for subsection five) respectively.

Yet, while the remaining categories of missing children – runaways, missing unaccompanied migrant minors, and lost, injured and otherwise missing children – are not directly addressed in the German Criminal Code, the accompanying circumstances leave the missing children highly vulnerable for further victimisation, which is addressed through different paragraphs of the criminal code. For instance, §236 StGB outlaws the human trafficking of children ("Kinderhandel"), which focusses on parents or caretakers, who leave their children with other people in order to profit financially. The crime is punishable by up to five years in prison. Severe cases, in which the offender is part of a criminal organisation, or the child's psychological and physical welfare has been jeopardised, the punishment ranges from six months to ten years in prison, according to subsection four.

Other punishable offenses that can occur in cases of missing children are forced marriages, which have been penalised in 2011 under §237 StGB ("Zwangsheirat") and are punishable with a six months to five years prison sentence as well as unlawful detention, as defined in §239 StGB ("Freiheitsberaubung"), which carries a maximum prison sentence of five years or one year to ten years for severe cases, with no less than three years prison if the victim died due to the crime.

Especially in cases of stranger abductions, runaway incidents or for missing unaccompanied migrant minors, the risk of sexual abuse is severely increased, since these children lack the protection of their legal guardians and are more vulnerable to exploitation. The sexual abuse of children – which are defined as persons under the age of fourteen in the German law – is outlawed in § 176 StGB ("Sexueller Missbrauch von Kindern"), as well as §176a for cases of severe sexual abuse of children ("Schwerer sexueller Missbrauch von Kindern") and §176b relating to cases of sexual abuse of children resulting in their death ("Sexueller Missbrauch von Kindern mit Todesfolge"), which all relate to the underlying definition of sexual abuse as set in §176 StGB, but differ in the sentences they carry. The prison

sentence for offenses of §176 StGB ranges from six months to ten years. §176a carries a minimum sentence of a year in prison for cases in which the perpetrator has been sentenced for similar offenses within the last five years and a minimum sentence of two years for cases in which coitus occurred, multiple offenders participated in the crime or the child's psychological and physical development or state are endangered through the offense. Furthermore, the minimum prison sentence is increased to five years according to §176a StGB if the child is severely physically abused during the sexual abuse or included a danger to the life of the child. Cases that result in the death of the child, which are punishable under §176b StGB, carry a minimum sentence of ten years to a life sentence (which is equivalent to a minimum of 15 years in prison according to §57a StGB). In 2018, the German federal police (BKA) has recorded 13.683 cases of sexual abuse of children (aggregated data from §176, 176a, 176b, PKS 2018:17).

Furthermore, some cases of stranger abductions have included the production of child pornography, which is punishable under §184b StGB ("Verbreitung, Erwerb und Besitz kinderpornographischer Schriften") with a maximum prison sentence of five to ten years. Albeit the legal definition only includes persons up to the age of 14 as children, owning, producing, and spreading pornographic material of minors over the age is also punishable with a maximum prison sentence of three to five years under §184c ("Verbreitung, Erwerb und Besitz jugendpornographischer Schriften"). According to the federal police records, there were 7449 cases that constituted a breach of §184b (PKS 2018: 21) as well as 1604 cases of §184c (cf. *ibid.*). While there are clearly also other threats to the safety of missing children, such as physical abuse, increased risk of substance abuse and resulting addictions, human trafficking including labour exploitation or organ harvesting, the named offenses can occur in a number of different case types frequently, which prioritises the analysis of the legal framework relating to these offenses.

In addition, a court trial took place in Germany in 2018 that involved four defendants that were accused of establishing an online child pornography forum that spread material in accordance with §184b. Furthermore, one of the culprits was also accused of sexually abusing children. Due to the relevance of these crimes for missing children cases, the court proceedings which involved the defendants' accounts were observed on two days in August 2018 for eight hours each time. The defendant, who was also accused of sexually abusing children in addition to sharing child pornographic material, had a prior conviction for sexually abusing children with disabilities that were in his care as a social worker at the time of the assault. During the hearing for the abuse that he stood for trial during the observation in August 2018, it became clear that the sexual abuse of the children also involved the trafficking of the children in line with §236 StGB from their father, since he – as their caregiver – had arranged for other members of the online forum to visit him and abuse the children in his care. However, since he and his family are situated in Austria, he was on trial there. Throughout the observation, all defendants displayed neutralisation strategies to explain their delinquent behaviour in participating in a child pornography forum. These strategies varied from attempting to portray themselves as only interested in the technical component of running a forum, collecting evidence for the police to wanting to council the father who had abused his own children. While it became clear that the victims of the crimes that were on trial were most likely never reported missing, the increased risk for vulnerable children such as missing children to be sexually abused has been highlighted by the grooming processes that were visible throughout the hearing of the defendant that was also charged under §176 StGB. Therefore, the

legal framework of countries involved in missing children cases should also be analysed with regard to other, related crimes that are beyond the scope of kidnappings.

3.3 General Ethical Aspects related to regulations and technical aspects of mobile applications

3.3.1 Changes from 1st iteration

The following changes concern mainly comments and suggestions provided by the Ethics Advisory Board of the ChildRescue Project.²⁷¹

Ethics Advisory Board recommended the inclusion of the notion of “accountability” (GDPR, art. 5.2), a foundational principle of the Regulation that was not explicitly described in the D1.2 and suggested that more relevant information should be provided about issues such as the obligation of data controllers to document the consent received and data breaches.

Ethical and data protection-related provisions to be taken in the context of ChildRescue are detailed in D2.4, section 2.3.3. DGPR Compliance about legitimate interest; pseudonymization and anonymization; data breaches; data subjects’ right of access and right to be forgotten; identification of users and provision of consent by both, platform users and missing children. All the above issues are quite relevant with the *principles relating to processing of personal data* (GDPR 5(1,2) where the responsibility of data controllers to be in compliance with, paragraph 1 is demonstrated. According to the EAB, the notion of “accountability” (GDPR, art. 5.2) is absent from the document despite being a foundational principle of the Regulation. More should be said about among other: the obligation to document the consent received; to document data breaches etc; Specifically:

Legitimate Interest: Concerning GDPR compliance, data controllers and processors should follow a set of rules including *legitimate interest*, namely a valid reason to store data that contain personal information. The establishment of *legitimate interest* in the case of ChildRescue derives from the existing procedures, agreements between the organisations-controllers and the public sector which are followed “as is” and from the existing legislature. SoC, for example, has a legitimate reason to publish a child’s personal data under an Amber Alert, a procedure that is regulated by the existing legislature. National Societies of the Red Cross, as humanitarian organisations, may also process personal data when a specific humanitarian activity is listed in their mission establishing legitimate interest, provided that this interest is not overridden by the fundamental rights and freedoms of the Data Subject.

Pseudonymisation & Anonymization: ChildRescue conforms to the GDPR guidelines by performing pseudonymisation to any personal data that are allowed to be stored under the Regulatory Framework or under the data subject’s explicit consent. When data expire or consent is revoked ChildRescue will provide the functionality to either remove the pseudonymised data or anonymise them.

Data breaches: ChildRescue shall incorporate and implement all best practices regarding safe registration, authentication, authorisation and data storage. Databases will be audited and monitored so that the details of every access are logged. In the case of a data breach, mitigation measures will be carried out, depending on the extent and nature of the breach. In the case that the breach occurs

²⁷¹ It is noted at this point that a specific comment provided by Ethics Advisory Board concerned the legal rules in the different EU Member States pertaining the use of National Identification Number (GDPR Art.87 ‘Processing of the national identification number’) and it was suggested the specific issue to be taken under consideration in the current iterations of WP1 (D1.4, D1.5) and WP2 (D2.4, D2.5). National Identification Number, however, is a piece of personal information that eventually is not included among the personal identifiable information that are going to be recorded, kept and processed in the context of ChildRescue (in platform, offline files or elsewhere). Therefore, any further research in relevant EU policies is not necessary.

in anonymised and/or pseudonymised data, access to the offending addresses will be blocked, whereas in case that a data breach occurs in raw data (e.g. pseudonymised data plus the database that contain the re-identification data), databases will be quarantined, and access will be restricted only to trustworthy parties. In all cases, the supervisory authority will be notified with all the information required by the GDPR. In the case of SoC and Hellenic Red Cross, the supervisory authority is the Hellenic Data Protection Authority (DPA). In the case of Child Focus, the supervisory authority is the Commission de la protection de la vie privée.

User Identification: (missing) children: the aim of ChildRescue is to be used to broadcast information concerning ongoing cases of missing children; before disclosing any children's personal data to the public, pros and cons should be examined (by the authorities) in order to decide to the best interest of the child.²⁷² Platform Users: Relevant provisions included by design in ChildRescue is that a. it will not provide to *anonymous users* any more information than that already given to the general public and already deemed acceptable by the authorities, and b. for named operational users will required to undergo an offline procedure to prove their identity before being able to use the platform.

Consent-users: Storing and processing any kind of personal data requires the explicit consent of a data subject and, therefore, it is necessary to provide to each user a consent form written in clear language that definitely describes both the kind of personal data that are going to be collected and the purposes of data processing. In the context of ChildRescue consent covers mainly the users of the platform and app, including anonymous citizens and registered users. GDPR consent-related requirements are typical for any application that uses personal data; ChildRescue, however, is not typical in the sense that data subjects are part of an official police investigation and, therefore, it may be required by the police to contact data subjects directly, while ChildRescue users data may also constitute legal evidence and as such may not be completely removed. This exception will also be stated in the Consent form and the exact kind of data that will be exempt from their right of erasure will also be clearly stated. As it is not possible at this moment to define exactly the kind of data that the consent form will cover, an example of a consent form can be found in D2.4, Annex V: Sample Consent Form.

Consent-children: Article 6 (article 8 of GDPR) '*Conditions applicable to child's consent in relation to information society services*' of the draft law (following public consultation for transportation of GDPR into Greek law) defines that "*the processing of the personal data of a child shall be lawful where the child is at least 15 years old. Where the child is below the age of 15 years, such processing shall be lawful only if and to the extent that consent is given or authorised by the holder of parental responsibility over the child*".²⁷³

Missing children, however, including unaccompanied minors, is not feasible to be asked to give their consent for storing, or even publishing personal data and, to this end, necessary consent is given by the appropriate authorities like the Distinct Attorney or by setting a legal basis like the "protection of the vital interests of the data subject" (GDPR art, 6.1.d). The consent, however, will be given for Amber Alert rather than explicitly to ChildRescue that will only disseminate Subject's information already included in the Amber Alert, while ChildRescue will further facilitate the citizens to act as social sensors thereby improving the chances of locating the child. As long as this processing increases the chances

²⁷² It is noted that conduction of Best Interest Assessment (BIA) for cases of publicizing personal data of missing children is over and beyond the scope of ChildRescue. Such an assessment shall take place for each individual case from authorities in advance, before, for example, an Amber Alert is released.

²⁷³ Public Consultation on draft law available at: <http://www.opengov.gr/ministryofjustice/?p=9331>

of finding the child, consent may not be explicitly asked to process the subject's data (GDPR 6(1.d) and recital 46). ChildRescue will try also to publicize the minimum data (e.g. the last name of the child will be omitted as in the vast majority of the cases the child is recognised by the picture). Unaccompanied minors on the other hand need to register in shelters, where they also provide consent for the usage of their data by the corresponding Legal Entity that is responsible for their sheltering (e.g. Hellenic RED CROSS). ChildRescue needs to collect these data too, in order to be able to perform predictions regarding the possible location or route of an unaccompanied minor, in case she/he has disappeared. The data needed are exactly the same as that which the original consent form already contains. However, explicit consent must be given to ChildRescue to also use these data. Therefore, a copy of the consent form, applied to ChildRescue Platform, will also be given to the subjects.

Right to erasure or to be forgotten: As it is mentioned in the *'NOTE FOR MISSING PEOPLE: General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) "Right to erasure"-Overview of the legal position of formerly missing people who wish to have information about them removed from the internet and/or excluded from internet searches'*,²⁷⁴ Article 17 of the GDPR gives individuals (both adults and children) **the right to have their personal data erased in some circumstances**. This right is known as the 'right to erasure' (also known as 'the right to be forgotten'), and applies in circumstances where, although the original collection and processing of the data may have been compliant with the GDPR, continuing to hold or publish the personal data is not.

The circumstances allowing exercise of the right to erasure that are most likely to apply in the context are where:

- **the personal data are no longer necessary given the purpose for which they were collected or processed (Article 17(1)(a))**. This relates closely to one of the GDPR's basic principles governing all processing personal data (given in Article 5(1)(e)). Personal data should not be kept in a form which allows identification of the individual for longer than is necessary given the purposes for which the data are processed. For example, it could be argued that a missing person appeal, originally posted on the internet to help find the individual, is no longer necessary (and therefore, should be erased) once the missing person is found. In this circumstance, the organisation should not wait for a request from the individual but should cease processing the data of its own accord. The right to erasure is effectively a mechanism for reminding the organisation of its existing obligation to cease processing the data
- **the individual has exercised his or her right to object to the continued processing of his or her personal data and the organisation** (e.g. a local media website, social media platform or search engine provider) **has no "compelling legitimate grounds" for continuing the processing** (Article 17(1)(c), with the right to object arising separately, under Article 21(1)). In this circumstance, the organisation's reasons for keeping the data on the internet and the public's interest in having access to the data (if any) must be balanced against the interests, rights and freedoms of the individual. The organisation has to demonstrate compelling reasons for continuing to process (in this case, to publish) the data. If it cannot, it should delete the data.
- **the individual withdraws his or her consent for the personal data to be processed** (Article 17(1)(b)). It is unlikely that a formerly missing person will have consented to the

²⁷⁴ CLIFFORD CHANCE LLP (2018). NOTE FOR MISSING PEOPLE: General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) "Right to erasure". Missing People UK. Available at: <https://www.missingpeople.org.uk/files/Noteonrighttobeforgotten155152-4-2v2.0.pdf>.

publication of their personal data (e.g. in a form of a missing person appeal) – the organisation will be processing their personal data on a legal basis other than consent, so this circumstance is unlikely to arise.

- **the personal data have been processed in breach of the GDPR** (Article 17(1)(d)). This may apply, but the missing person will not generally know whether it is the case or not.
- **the personal data must be erased for compliance with a legal obligation** (Article 17(1)(e)). Few if any legal obligations to erase, other than those arising under the GDPR itself, are likely to be relevant in practice.
- **the personal data have been processed in the context of offering information society services (ISS) to a child** (Article 17(1)(f)). This is intended to allow under-age users of social media and similar services to require personal data that they have posted to be taken down.

On the other hand, the right to erasure **does not apply** where continued publication of the personal data is necessary for: (a) compliance with a legal obligation; (b) performance of public interest or exercise of official authority; (c) public health reasons; (d) archiving, research or statistical purposes; or (e) establishing, exercising or defending legal claims.

Right of access and right to be forgotten in ChildRescue: Data subjects in ChildRescue can be distinguished in two broad categories: stakeholders' group (children and parents) and users of the ChildRescue platform. As it is detailed in D2.4, paragraph 2.3.3.3 ChildRescue will undertake all necessary measures to protect data subjects' rights of access and of be forgotten by deleting personal data *shared publicly* and by notifying users via multiple channels to delete any data that may have in their devices (only in specific cases that contact with users is impossible the GDPR Article 19 will apply). A different policy is going to be followed for personal data stored in the organization's premises. For ongoing cases the reason for keeping data is obvious; even in close cases, however, the data may be needed again either when a similar case is opened (e.g. the same child disappears again), or if a legal authority (e.g. the Police or District Attorney) requires for data from past cases for some legal reason (e.g. to press charges on a person that is suspect of being part of an abduction network that had a part to some of the past cases). Thus, stakeholder data that are part of past and ongoing cases as well as data that were never intended to be disseminated publicly, such as of unaccompanied minors, *are never deleted* and remain solely within the data controller, i.e. SoC, Hellenic Red Cross and Child Focus, and are similarly kept for an indefinite amount of time. Regardless of the extent to which stakeholder's personal data have been disseminated to the public, ChildRescue will provide the right of access and erasure by performing anonymisation on undisclosed personal data. In case the stakeholder expresses her/his desire to revoke access and/or erase the data, the already stored pseudonymised data will be converted to anonymised data by moving the relevant entries from the pseudonymised data set to the anonymised data set.

Accountability of data controllers: As part of the accountability principle, every data controller "shall maintain a record of processing activities under its responsibility" including inter alia the purposes of processing, a description of the categories of data and recipients of the data and "where possible, a general description of the technical and organisational security measures referred to in Article 32(1)" (Article 30(1)). In the context of ChildRescue, Ethics Advisory Board suggested to consider the need to keep a register of ChildRescue processing activities; according to GDPR Art. 30 'Records of processing activities', each controller and, where applicable, the controller's representative shall maintain a record of processing activities under its responsibility. Data processors or their representatives shall also

maintain a record of all categories of processing activities carried out on behalf of a controller. The controller or the processor and, where applicable, the controller's or the processor's representative, shall make the record available to the supervisory authority on request [GDPR 30(4)]. Such records shall be in writing, including in electronic form [GDPR 30(3)] and shall contain the following information:

Table 3-8 Obligation to maintain record of processing activities [GDPR30(1,2)]²⁷⁵

Data Controller or Controller's representative	Data Processor or Processor's representative
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ the name and contact details of the controller and, where applicable, the joint controller, the controller's representative and the data protection officer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ the name and contact details of the processor or processors and of each controller on behalf of which the processor is acting, and, where applicable, of the controller's or the processor's representative, and the data protection officer;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ the purposes of the processing 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ a description of the categories of data subjects and of the categories of personal data 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ the categories of recipients to whom the personal data have been or will be disclosed including recipients in third countries or international organisations 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ the categories of processing carried out on behalf of each controller;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ where applicable, transfers of personal data to a third country or an international organisation, including the identification of that third country or international organisation and, in the case of transfers referred to in the second subparagraph of Article 49(1), the documentation of suitable safeguards; 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ where possible, the envisaged time limits for erasure of the different categories of data; 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ where possible, a general description of the technical and organisational security measures referred to in Article 32(1) 	

Ethics Advisory Board recommended that it would be advisable at this stage to already have a draft of this register even if it needs to be completed at a later stage.

3.3.2 Compliance with the current national, EU and International legislation

As it is already mentioned above (Section 3.1 European legislation), missing children investigation and rescue involves, among others, the storage and processing of personal data of the missing child and his/her family's members. In the context of ChildRescue Platform other individuals are also involved, mainly as data sources and data administrators during the investigation process, including several types of users, actors and authorities. In this context, legislation concerning data protection and personal data processing shall be taken into consideration, in order to ensure the compliance of the ChildRescue Platform with current international, European and national legal provisions.

3.3.2.1 Agreements, laws and regulations (including EU directive on data protection)

At a national level, ChildRescue should be in alignment with the national legislation concerning personal data administration, as is presented in the respective section of the Chapter 3.2. Moreover, EU and international legislation should be taken into account in order to avoid any data misuse.

²⁷⁵ GDPR 30(5): These obligations shall not apply to an enterprise or an organisation employing fewer than 250 persons unless the processing it carries out is likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects, the processing is not occasional, or the processing includes special categories of data as referred to in Article 9(1) or personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences referred to in Article 10.

3.3.2.1.1 *Pre-define the legislation to be followed in cases where more than one country are involved in a case*

A number of cases of missing children are related to international kidnappings, unaccompanied refugee and immigrant children, forced disappearances and so on. In such cases, where movement of a child in more than one country takes place, it should be pre-decided which legislation prevails concerning personal data of involved parties in the context of the ChildRescue Platform. It should be, namely, pre-decided whether the legislation of the country where the child declared as missing will apply or the legislation of the country where the child has been seen and/or found or the EU or international data protection relevant legislation.

3.3.2.1.2 *Pre-define the level of access of authorities requesting data-personal identifiers of 'community sensors'*

'Community sensors', namely sources of information who are also subjects of data can be *registered identifiable users*, *registered users without personal identifiers* and *anonymous users*. Considering the two last groups, *registered users without personal identifiers* and *anonymous users*, they hypothetically are able to provide information for a case of a missing child *anonymously*. Authorities, however, like Prosecutor or the Police, may ask the Platform operator (or the data processor) to identify such a non-validated or non-registered user. The level of access in personal data of these groups of users should be clearly pre-defined in order to avoid any type of privacy violation and at the same time the Platform to operate according to the law.

**Despite users are not registered, some basic information may collected and stored automatically in the server where ChildRescue Platform is hosted, when users are using the platform and/or the mobile application (such as the name of the internet domain if they are using a private internet access account, the Internet Protocol (IP) address, the date, time and place they used the mobile app).*

3.3.3 Acquiring National Data Protection Authorities' licenses

ChildRescue operating organisations shall submit request to the National Data Protection Authority in order to obtain license for establishment and operation of register containing sensitive personal data. In this license should be clearly and detailed defined the following: type of license; purpose of the registry maintenance; identity of data processor; type of data; sources of data; duration of license; terms and conditions for granting the license according to the currently applied legislation.

In case the operating organisations are already granted with a similar license, they should inform respectively the National Data Protection Authority for the additional usage (ChildRescue Platform and App) and to proceed with the modification, if necessary.

3.3.3.1 *Including secondary use of data*

In the detailed description of the purpose of the registry and of data processing, particular reference should be made to the secondary use of data. Such secondary use can be, for example, sensitization of the community and activation of its sources towards supporting families in crisis and in particular towards the prevention of child disappearances and the more efficient management of cases of children declared as missing.

3.3.4 Obtaining parental/guardian informed consent before using child's data

Similarly, to other systems/programs of communicating information of missing children (such as the Amber Alert) parental/legal guardian informed consent should be obtained before using child's personal

data in the context of ChildRescue Platform and application, along with the permission of the Police (or other responsible authority). A standardised informed consent form is recommended to be developed on the basis of which missing child's parent/legal guardian will allow the use (upload and dissemination) of child's personal data through ChildRescue Platform and application.

3.3.4.1 Including secondary use of data

It should be decided whether obtaining of parental/legal guardian consent for secondary use of child's personal data will be part of the consent for using child's data for the investigation process via ChildRescue platform or will be a quite different process and document.

The decision should be made after considering the strengths and limitations of obtaining one or two different parental consent for main and secondary use of personal data respectively.

Note: *"Secondary use of the data is required for the validation of the platform and methodology, the performance of statistical analysis, academic research and dissemination of the project's results. Publication of the results of these analyses will not include any personal case-specific information and will only appear in the form abstractions or aggregates".*

3.3.5 Acquiring agreements with third parties

In order to promote community participation during investigations for missing children, the ChildRescue Platform may use third-party websites (including social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram). Agreements should be acquired with third parties containing terms and conditions of cooperation (it should be clear, for example, that third party service provider's terms of service and privacy policies govern ChildRescue users activity on the third party website or whether ChildRescue Platform intends to collect and maintain personal data the users make available on third party websites).

In addition, appropriate agreements may be considered with providers of telephone services, given the nature of ChildRescue mobile application.

3.3.6 Mobile Application-related Ethical aspects

Privacy by design is a technical approach to a social problem.²⁷⁶ Concerning limits of privacy by design, Danezis *et al.* (2014)²⁷⁷ noted that there is a caveat: a significant part of the low-level privacy invasion is the direct result of the internal functioning of technical systems. Thus, while the incentives and will to invade privacy may be social problems, the actual ability to do so is a technical problem in many instances. Thus, dealing with it at the technology level is necessary. The same concerns can be considered for mobile applications too.

3.3.6.1 Applying privacy design principles-ensuring appropriate level of sensitive personal data protection

The above mentioned (in Chapter 3) Directive 2002/58/EC (*ePrivacy Directive*) can be interpreted as call for privacy by design while EU data protection law, Art. 29 Data Protection Working Party ask for and refer to privacy by design; there, practical aspects are also highlighted: "In practice, the

²⁷⁶ Gürses, J. S. (2014). Can you engineer privacy? *Communications of the ACM*, 57(8):20–23

²⁷⁷ Danezis, G., Domingo-Ferrer, J., Hansen, M., Hoepman, JH., Le Métayer, D., Tirtea, R., Schiffne, S. (2014). Privacy and Data Protection by Design—from policy to engineering. European Union Agency for Network and Information Security-ENISA Available at: https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/privacy-and-data-protection-by-design/at_download/fullReport

implementation of the privacy by design principle will require the evaluation of several, concrete aspects or objectives. In particular, when making decisions about the design of a processing system, its acquisition and the running of such a system the following general aspects / objectives should be respected: Data Minimization; Controllability; Transparency; User Friendly Systems; Data Confidentiality; Data Quality; and Use Limitation".²⁷⁸

Mobile apps often rely on user data-including contact information, location, photos, and so on-all of which can be vulnerable to data breaches. Before releasing ChildRescue application it should be ensured that security policies are set appropriately and that the right measures to protect the data that users ("community sensors") share with the app. Some indicative tips for developers towards mobile app security include, among others, review of data to collect and maintain and creation of secure users' credentials (usernames and passwords).²⁷⁹

3.3.6.2 Ensuring prevention of application misuse (by any potential stakeholder of the application)

The challenge for developers of a mobile app is anticipating misuse and designing to prevent it. Providing that ChildRescue is dealing with children's data, it should be ensured that necessary standards and regulations are applied in order to prevent any misuse of application. Ways to prevent data misuse via the platform and application should be explored (such as monitoring of data access; monitoring of various stakeholders/users actions; and ensuring that the system is well-protected, as data misuse is considered a security breach and first and foremost it is a security concern²⁸⁰).

3.3.6.3 Transparent administration of log files (content; protection; access; destruction)

The first ethical dilemma mentioned in a popular article in InfoWorld²⁸¹ is about log files, what to save and how to handle them. It is noted that developers often keep records of everything, because this is the only way to debug a system. Log files, however, can expose information that users want kept secret. The mere existence of log files begs several ethical questions. Are they adequately protected? Who has access? When we say we destroy the files, are they truly destroyed? The crucial point, valid also for the ChildRescue Platform, is to decide what information is worth keeping, given the ethical risks of doing so.

3.3.6.4 Pre-define aspects of platform maintenance

Monitoring process and methodology for ensuring the smooth operation of platform and application should be defined as well as the responsible organisation/authority to undertake the monitoring and consequently the reporting to data processor.

²⁷⁸ Ibid.

²⁷⁹ Source: <https://www.sba.gov/blogs/developing-mobile-app-follow-these-12-tips-protecting-and-securing-user-data>

²⁸⁰ Source: <https://www.ekransystem.com/en/blog/4-ways-detect-and-prevent-misuse-data>

²⁸¹ Source: <https://www.infoworld.com/article/2607452/application-development/12-ethical-dilemmas-gnawing-at-developers-today.html>

3.4 Ethical Provisions related to non-technical aspects of individual Functional Components

3.4.1 Changes from 1st iteration

Since 1st iteration, the first release of the report 'Profiling, Analytics and Privacy Methodological Foundations' has been developed, that integrates the results of ChildRescue Project WP2 tasks; the D5.3 'ChildRescue Data Management Handling Plan' has also been released, containing detailed description on data controllers and processors, data subjects, types of processing activities and types of data to be collected, analysed and stored. Taking into account the abovementioned information about anticipated data processing activities and, in particular, activities related to profiling in the context of ChildRescue as well as relevant GDPR provisions and the recent decision of the Hellenic Data Protection Authority on the kind of processing activities requiring the conduction of a Data Protection Impact Assessment, a recommendation is suggested to be considered by data controllers as part of their accountability in the context of ChildRescue.

3.4.2 Profiling in ChildRescue

In the Executive Summary of D2.4 'Profiling, Analytics and Privacy Methodological Foundations' is summarised that "*the research analysis on the activity and behaviour profiling results in the identification of five distinct profiles for missing children cases*" on the basis of a set of indicators per profile deriving from various sources. It is also mentioned that "*the proposed profiling method is to be applied to new missing children cases, but also to past cases, which are considered to be the primary source of information for ChildRescue data analytics framework*" where, for each individual case, apart from the details and the child's characteristics, other information are going to be combined into a multi-source analytical procedure. Such information may include any feedback to be received by citizens during the investigation process as well as other sources of data such as social media activities and open data. The outcome of this procedure aims to generate an even more informative and complete profile; to evaluate incoming feedback; and to predict Points of Interest or routes, which the missing child is going to visit or follow.

In the same report (p. 21) is described *how* an "*activity and behavioural profile of the missing child*" may be created in the context of ChildRescue, namely through the analysis of factors related to vulnerability (for third-person abductions) and exploitation in a high-risk environment. This can be achieved by collecting information from stakeholders (interviewing peers and family members) and by analysing the online public information on their social media profiles (to identify a potential increased interest in the child's activities by specific adults). *Social Network Analysis & Sentiment Analysis* are considered, in the context of ChildRescue, as means supporting finding new, useful information about a missing child's personal profile from the viewpoint of victimology such as child's connections, his/her social network, his/her activities, his/her hidden moods, any depressive or suicidal tendencies, influences, interests, etc. (p. 36). *Descriptive Analytics* methods and techniques can also be employed -based on analysis of existing past cases of missing or unaccompanied migrant minors- to identify behavioural patterns that may be useful mainly for reducing the required time needed in locating missing children. *Machine learning techniques*, in ChildRescue, are also expected to be utilised for enabling predictions for the missing children's potential locations, exploiting each child's case data gathered and also to enable common patterns recognition based on previous cases.

It is also noted that ChildRescue will try to create analogies with various existing approaches for predicting users' individual preferences, attributes and behaviour to improve services and products, in order to develop its methodology on the profiling part and the modelling and prediction of missing children's and/or unaccompanied minors' behaviour (p. 37). Recognising that the analysis of human behaviour and relationships, along with spatiotemporal information has a vital role in the investigation process for a missing child case, focus of ChildRescue will be directed towards the most significant advancements in human behavioural profiling based on computational learning, while a wide spectrum of algorithms for spatiotemporal data processing and the most significant methods and techniques for social media analytics are going to be explored (p.39).

Data sources encountered during our literature investigation *that could potentially be used in the ChildRescue framework* include: *mobile communications* (mobile phone calls and text messages-location points; general mobile phone usage-user trajectories); *GPS* (log files); *social networks* (user check-ins e.g. from Foursquare, Facebook; geo-tagged images and videos e.g. from Flickr, Instagram; location reference in a post or activity e.g. from Facebook, Twitter; other geo-referenced content e.g. Yelp crowd-sourced location reviews; network connections); *open data* (transportation infrastructure; list of popular POIs in a particular area, national open data; transportation time schedule; land use; road networks; weather data); *other data* (such as transportation card transactions) (p.48-49).

In the ChildRescue conceptual approach, the profile assessment deriving from multiple data sources is regarded as one of the cornerstones of the project. Therefore, main task for ChildRescue is *the modelling of missing children and unaccompanied migrant minors' behavioural patterns, taking the most out of available data sources*. Using this profiling model, estimations and predictions regarding the child's whereabouts can be made. If successful, a missing child can return home, to its parents, in a faster, safer and more reliable way (methods and algorithms to be tested towards this aim presented in detail in sections 3.3.1, 3.3.2 and 3.3.3 of the D2.4) (p. 57).

The major challenge of profiling is data privacy, and that is because the primary task of profiling is the development of models from aggregated personal data, which does raise several privacy concerns (p. 44). Moreover, during the last few years, there are raising concerns about social media public data harnessing and researchers worldwide are facing the fact of the increasing access restriction set by the companies (be it for user privacy or business protection) towards social media data (p. 56). It is, therefore, crucial to apply the most appropriate profiling methodology, depending on the data available, harnessing the power of predictive analytics and machine learning in the most efficient way.

Among the major challenges expected to emerge in respect to data collection and analysis, crucial GDPR issues are included. A set of guideline and compliance of ChildRescue to GDPR is included in pages 71-72). ChildRescue shall incorporate and implement all best practices regarding safe registration, authentication, authorisation and data storage. Databases will be audited and monitored so that the details of every access are logged. In the case of a data breach, mitigation measures will be carried out, depending on the extent and nature of the breach. In the case that the breach occurs in anonymised and/or pseudonymised data, access to the offending addresses will be blocked, whereas in case that a data breach occurs in raw data (e.g. pseudonymised data plus the database that contain the re-identification data), databases will be quarantined, and access will be restricted only to trustworthy parties. In all cases, the supervisory authority will be notified with all the information required by the GDPR.

GDPR provisions on Profiling

Article 4: Definitions

- (4) '*profiling*' means any form of automated processing of personal data consisting of the use of personal data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyse or predict aspects concerning that natural person's performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences, interests, reliability, behaviour, location or movements

Section 2: Information and access to personal data

Article 13: Information to be provided where personal data are collected from the data subject

2. [...] the controller shall, at the time when personal data are obtained, provide the data subject with the following further information necessary to ensure fair and transparent processing:

- (f) *the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, referred to in Article 22(1) and (4) and, at least in those cases, meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject.*

Article 14: Information to be provided where personal data have not been obtained from the data subject

2. [...] the controller shall provide the data subject with the following information necessary to ensure fair and transparent processing in respect of the data subject:

- (g) *the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, referred to in Article 22(1) and (4) and, at least in those cases, meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject.*

Article 15: Right of access by the data subject

1. The data subject shall have the right to obtain from the controller confirmation as to whether or not personal data concerning him or her are being processed, and, where that is the case, access to the personal data and the following information:

- (h) *the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, referred to in Article 22(1) and (4) and, at least in those cases, meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject.*

Section 4: Right to object and automated individual decision-making

Article 21: Right to object

1. The data subject shall have the right to object, on grounds relating to his or her particular situation, at any time to processing of personal data concerning him or her which is based on point (e) or (f) of Article 6(1), including profiling based on those provisions. The controller shall no longer process the personal data unless the controller demonstrates compelling legitimate grounds for the processing which override the interests, rights and freedoms of the data subject or for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims.
2. Where personal data are processed for direct marketing purposes, the data subject shall have the right to object at any time to processing of personal data concerning him or her for such marketing, which includes profiling to the extent that it is related to such direct marketing.

Article 22: Automated individual decision-making, including profiling

1. The data subject shall have the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects concerning him or her or similarly significantly affects him or her.
2. Paragraph 1 shall not apply if the decision:
- a. *is necessary for entering into, or performance of, a contract between the data subject and a data controller;*

- b. is authorised by Union or Member State law to which the controller is subject and which also lays down suitable measures to safeguard the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interests; or*
 - c. is based on the data subject's explicit consent.*
3. In the cases referred to in points (a) and (c) of paragraph 2, the data controller shall implement suitable measures to safeguard the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interests, at least the right to obtain human intervention on the part of the controller, to express his or her point of view and to contest the decision.
 4. Decisions referred to in paragraph 2 shall not be based on special categories of personal data referred to in Article 9(1), unless point (a) or (g) of Article 9(2) applies and suitable measures to safeguard the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interests are in place.

Section 3: Data protection impact assessment and prior consultation

Article 35: Data protection impact assessment

1. Where a type of processing in particular using new technologies, and taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing, is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the controller shall, prior to the processing, carry out an assessment of the impact of the envisaged processing operations on the protection of personal data. A single assessment may address a set of similar processing operations that present similar high risks.
2. The controller shall seek the advice of the data protection officer, where designated, when carrying out a data protection impact assessment.
3. A data protection impact assessment referred to in paragraph 1 shall in particular be required in the case of:
 - (a) a systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects relating to natural persons which is based on automated processing, including profiling, and on which decisions are based that produce legal effects concerning the natural person or similarly significantly affect the natural person;*

Article 47: Binding corporate rules

1. The competent supervisory authority shall approve binding corporate rules in accordance with the consistency mechanism set out in Article 63, provided that they:
 - (a) are legally binding and apply to and are enforced by every member concerned of the group of undertakings, or group of enterprises engaged in a joint economic activity, including their employees;*
 - (b) expressly confer enforceable rights on data subjects with regard to the processing of their personal data; and*
 - (c) fulfil the requirements laid down in paragraph 2.*
2. The binding corporate rules referred to in paragraph 1 shall specify at least:
 - (e) the rights of data subjects in regard to processing and the means to exercise those rights, including the right not to be subject to decisions based solely on automated processing, including profiling in accordance with Article 22, the right to lodge a complaint with the competent supervisory authority and before the competent courts of the Member States in accordance with Article 79, and to obtain redress and, where appropriate, compensation for a breach of the binding corporate rules;*

Article 70: Tasks of the Board

1. The Board shall ensure the consistent application of this Regulation. To that end, the Board shall, on its own initiative or, where relevant, at the request of the Commission, in particular:

(f) *issue guidelines, recommendations and best practices in accordance with point (e) of this paragraph for further specifying the criteria and conditions for decisions based on profiling pursuant to Article 22(2);*

GDPR Recitals giving special emphasis to children in regards to profiling

(38) Children merit specific protection with regard to their personal data, as they may be less aware of the risks, consequences and safeguards concerned and their rights in relation to the processing of personal data. **Such specific protection should, in particular, apply to the use of personal data of children for the purposes of marketing or creating personality or user profiles and the collection of personal data with regard to children when using services offered directly to a child.** The consent of the holder of parental responsibility should not be necessary in the context of preventive or counselling services offered directly to a child.

(71) The data subject should have the right not to be subject to a decision, which may include a measure, evaluating personal aspects relating to him or her which is based solely on automated processing and which produces legal effects concerning him or her or similarly significantly affects him or her, such as automatic refusal of an online credit application or e-recruiting practices without any human intervention. **Such processing includes 'profiling' that consists of any form of automated processing of personal data evaluating the personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyse or predict aspects concerning the data subject's performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences or interests, reliability or behaviour, location or movements,** where it produces legal effects concerning him or her or similarly significantly affects him or her. However, decision-making based on such processing, including profiling, should be allowed where [...]. **Such measure should not concern a child.**

(75) **The risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, of varying likelihood and severity, may result from personal data processing which could lead to physical, material or non-material damage, in particular:** where the processing may give rise to discrimination, identity theft or fraud, financial loss, damage to the reputation, loss of confidentiality of personal data protected by professional secrecy, unauthorised reversal of pseudonymisation, or any other significant economic or social disadvantage; where data subjects might be deprived of their rights and freedoms or prevented from exercising control over their personal data; where personal data are processed which reveal racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religion or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, data concerning health or data concerning sex life or criminal convictions and offences or related security measures; where personal aspects are evaluated, in particular analysing or predicting aspects concerning performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences or interests, reliability or behaviour, location or movements, in order to create or use personal profiles; **where personal data of vulnerable natural persons, in particular of children, are processed;** or where processing involves a large amount of personal data and affects a large number of data subjects.

As it is noted by CIPL²⁸² about profiling regarding children, although there are no specific references to children in GDPR Art. 22, Recital 71, however, states that *generally children should not be subject to a decision that produces a legal effect or similarly significantly affects them that is solely based on automated processing, including profiling.* It is also noted that the WP29 does not consider that the Recital 71 represents an absolute prohibition on this type of processing in relation to children. The

²⁸² Centre for Information Policy Leadership (2018). GDPR Implementation In Respect of Children's Data and Consent. Hunton and Williams LLP. Available at: https://www.informationpolicycentre.com/uploads/5/7/1/0/57104281/cipl_white_paper_-_gdpr_implementation_in_respect_of_childrens_data_and_consent.pdf

guidance continues by stating that there may be some circumstances in which it is necessary for controllers to carry out solely automated decision-making, including profiling, with legal or similarly significant effects in relation to children, for example to protect their welfare.

The ICO Consultation²⁸³ notes that if GDPR Art. 22 does apply, *the controller is not prohibited from profiling children but should pay careful attention to Recital 71 and to the WP29 guidelines which state that as a rule, controllers should not rely upon the exceptions in GDPR Art. 22(2) to justify the automated decision.* However, this is not an absolute bar and the ICO continues to state that if a controller does rely on one of the GDPR Art. 22(2) exceptions, *the controller must demonstrate there are suitable measures in place to properly protect the interests of the children whose personal data it is processing.*

In D2.4 a detailed presentation of such protective measures is available. It seems, however, that the conduction of a DPIA as an additional measure may be considered by data controllers in the context of ChildRescue, as explained below.

DPIA Framework: A Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) is required under the GDPR where a type of processing in particular using new technologies, and taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing, is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons (art. 35.1 GDPR; examples are available in article 35.3).

Article 35 of the GDPR introduces the concept of a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), as does Directive 2016/680. A DPIA is a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data⁴ by assessing them and determining the measures to address them. DPIAs are important tools for accountability, as they help controllers not only to comply with requirements of the GDPR, but also to demonstrate that appropriate measures have been taken to ensure compliance with the Regulation (see also article 24)⁵. In other words, **a DPIA is a process for building and demonstrating compliance.** Under the GDPR, non-compliance with DPIA requirements can lead to fines imposed by the competent supervisory authority.

A DPIA is not always mandatory and is only required when the processing is “likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons” (Article 35(1)).

The obligation for controllers to conduct a DPIA in certain circumstances should be understood against the background of their general obligation to appropriately manage risks presented by the processing of personal data. A “risk” is a scenario describing an event and its consequences, estimated in terms of severity and likelihood. “Risk management”, on the other hand, can be defined as the coordinated activities to direct and control an organization with regard to risk.

DPIAs are a useful way for data controllers to implement data processing systems that comply with the GDPR and can be mandatory for some types of processing operations. They are scalable and can take different forms, but the GDPR sets out the basic requirements of an effective DPIA. Data controllers should see the carrying out of a DPIA as a useful and positive activity that aids legal compliance.

Article 24(1) sets out the basic responsibility of the controller in terms of complying with the GDPR. The DPIA is a key part of complying with the Regulation where high risk data processing is planned or is taking place. This means that data controllers should use the criteria set out to determine whether or

²⁸³ The ICO is the UK's independent body set up to uphold information rights. More info available at: <https://ico.org.uk/>

not a DPIA has to be carried out. Internal data controller policy could extend this list beyond the GDPR's legal requirements. This should result in greater trust and confidence of data subjects and other data controllers.

Hellenic Data Protection Authority: List of the kind of processing operations which are subject to the requirement for a data protection impact assessment pursuant to GDPR Article 35(4) ([Government Gazette B' 1622/10-5-2019](#))

The criteria for conducting DPIA are grouped into the following three categories:

1st category: based on types and purposes of processing.

2nd category: based on the type of data and/or subject categories.

3rd category: based on the additional characteristics and/or the means used for the processing.

The implementation of a DPIA is mandatory when at least one of the criteria of the 1st or 2nd category is fulfilled. It is also mandatory when at least one criterion is met with respect to the 3rd Category and the processing relates to the types and purposes of processing of the 1st category and / or data types and / or categories of subjects of the 2nd category.

Table 3-9 1st category of criteria for conducting DPIA

1 st Category: types and purposes of processing	ChildRescue
1.1 Systematic evaluation, scoring, predicting and profiling, especially in aspects relating to the financial situation, health, personal preferences or interests, the credibility or behavior, the position or the moves or the creditworthiness of the data subjects.	Yes
1.2 Systematic data processing aimed at taking automated decisions that produce legal effects on data subjects or significantly affect data subjects in an analogous manner and may lead to exclusion or discrimination against the individual.	No
1.3 Systematic processing of data that may prevent a person from exercising his rights or from using a service or contract, particularly when taking into account data collected by third parties.	Yes
1.4 Systematic processing of data relating to profiling for the purpose of promoting products and services where the data is combined with data collected by third parties	No
1.5 Systematic and large-scale ²⁸⁴ processing for the monitoring, observation or control of individuals using data collected through video surveillance systems or via networks or by any other means in a public space, publicly accessible space or private space accessible to an unlimited number of persons. Includes tracking of movements or location/ geographical position in real time or non-time identified or identifiable individuals.	Yes
1.6 Large-scale systematic processing of personal data relating to private and public health for public interest purposes, such as the introduction and use of e-prescription systems, and the introduction and use of an electronic file or electronic health card.	No

²⁸⁴ In the decision of the Hellenic Data Protection Authority ([Government Gazette B' 1622/10-5-2019](#)) data processing on a large scale follows the guidelines of WP243 and WP248, providing that the GDPR does not define what constitutes large-scale, though recital 91 provides some guidance. The WP29 recommends that the following factors, in particular, be considered when determining whether the processing is carried out on a large scale:

- the number of data subjects concerned, either as a specific number or as a proportion of the relevant population;
- the volume of data and/or the range of different data items being processed;
- the duration, or permanence, of the data processing activity;
- the geographical extent of the processing activity.

1.7 Large-scale systematic processing of personal data for the purpose of introducing, organizing, providing and controlling the use of e-Government services as defined in Article 3 of Law 3979/2011 as in force.	No
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Table 3-10 2nd category of criteria for conducting DPIA

2nd category: data type and/or subject categories	ChildRescue
2.1 Large-scale processing of specific categories of data (including genetic and biometric identifiers) referred to in Article 9 (1) and the data referred to in Article 10 of the GDPR	Partially
2.2 Systematic and large-scale processing of data of particular importance or exceptional character such as:	
2.2.1 Social welfare data (data on poverty, unemployment, social work, etc.)	Yes
2.2.2 Electronic communications data, including content data such as e-mail, metadata and geographical position / location data, except for the recording of telephone conversations pursuant to Article 4 paragraph 3 of Law 4771/2006,	Yes
2.2.3 Data relating to a national identification number or other general purpose identifiers or to a change in the terms and conditions of processing and use thereof and personal data relating thereto,	No
2.2.4 data contained in personal documents, diaries, e-reader notes and life logging applications, which offer the possibility of keeping notes and very personal information,	Yes
2.2.5 data collected or produced by devices (such as sensors), in particular through IoT (such as smart TVs, smart home appliances, connected toys, intelligent cities, intelligent energy meters etc) and / or other means.	Yes
2.3 Systematic monitoring – where permitted – of the position / location as well as content data and metadata of employees' communications except from logs for safety reasons, provided that the processing is limited to the absolutely necessary data and is specifically documented. An example of this is the use of DLP systems. Systematic processing of biometric data of employees for the purpose of undoubted identification of the person as well as of genetic data of employees.	NA

Table 3-11 3rd category of criteria for conducting DPIA

3rd category: additional characteristics and/or processing means used	ChildRescue
3.1 Innovative use or application of new technologies or organizational solutions, which may include new forms of data collection and use, possibly posing a high risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals such as the combined use of fingerprints and facial recognition for improved physical access control, or mhealth applications or other "smart" applications that create user profiles (eg daily habits), or artificial intelligence applications or public access technologies blockchain containing personal data.	Yes
3.2 Combining and/or linking personal data from multiple sources or third parties, from two or more processing activities carried out for different purposes and/or by different controllers in a way that might exceed the reasonable expectations of the data subject.	Yes
3.3 If the processing concerns data that has not been collected by the subject and the information of the subjects under Article 14 of the GDPR proves impossible or would entail a disproportionate effort or is likely to make impossible or significantly harm the achievement of the purposes of processing.	

Based on the above it is recommended for ChildRescue to consider a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)

It is considered that the criteria for the implementation of a DPIA in the context of ChildRescue are fulfilled.

In case that data controllers decide to conduct such a DPIA, further information on methodology and tools to be used are available in the *WP29 Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)*²⁸⁵ and the *Decision of HDPa on the kind of processing operations which are subject to the requirement for a DPIA*.²⁸⁶ A general guide on how to conduct a DPIA is outlined in GDPR Art. 35 and requires DPIAs to contain the following elements:

- A systematic description of the envisaged processing operations and the purposes of the processing, including, where applicable, the legitimate interest pursued by the controller (concerning ChildRescue, such information is already available in D2.4 and 5.3)
- An assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing operations in relation to the purposes
- An assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects

Also

- The measures envisaged to address the risks, including safeguards, security measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data and to demonstrate compliance with the GDPR, taking into account the rights and legitimate interests of data subjects and other persons concerned (this information is also available in D2.4 of ChildRescue project).

DPIA should be prepared before beginning any data processing activity. Ideally, it should be conducted before and during the planning stages of the project. Data Protection Officer and any other key stakeholders involved in the project should be asked to provide consultation throughout the course of the DPIA.²⁸⁷

Even if data controllers ultimately decide not to carry out a DPIA, it is recommended to proceed with the assessment of whether a high risk is likely.

3.4.3 Collaboration space

One of the core components of the ChildRescue Platform is a *collaboration space* allowing all investigators to securely share location-based multi-media information regarding the investigation in groups, with specific access rights. Instant messaging will be granted among the voluntary organisation and rescue team members, as well as with citizens who have provided evidence for the missing person. In this space, all contributors to the investigation will be also able to provide their perspective about the missing person through a collective tagging dashboard.

²⁸⁵ WP29 (2017). Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is "likely to result in a high risk" for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/item-detail.cfm?item_id=611236

²⁸⁶ Hellenic Data Protection Authority (2019). List of the kind of processing operations which are subject to the requirement for a data protection impact assessment pursuant to GDPR Article 35(4) (*Government Gazette B' 1622/10-5-2019*)

²⁸⁷ Source: <https://gdpr.eu/data-protection-impact-assessment-template/+&cd=1&hl=el&ct=clnk&gl=gr>

Given the importance of *collaboration space* component it is important to take into account ethics related to non-technical aspects during the development of the platform such as the following.

3.4.3.1 *Ensuring user friendly interface*

Real time messaging, collaborative tagging and data sharing are all actions that various users will be called to undertake –often in restricted time- when they will use the ChildRescue Platform and app. In order to facilitate the right usage of the app by the users or, otherwise, to minimise the risk of misuse by mistake, a user-friendly interface should be ensured. There are numerous studies and examples on how to design a “perfect mobile app user interface” including suggestions about colours, fonts, icons (App Icons – for representing an app; Clarifying Icons – explain certain tasks; Interactive Icons – used mainly for navigation; Decorative Icons – created for a more attractive look;) and navigation tools; moreover, guidelines are available for developers (related, for example, to consistency and simplicity of the interface -not to create the sensation that customers need instruction manual for using the app; to use only needed and essential information without overloading the app; to avoid ambiguity-everything should be as clear as possible, without the possibility of misinterpretations; and so on).²⁸⁸

Additionally, through an easy-to-use interface, app users provided with the ability to set their privacy settings, namely they have direct control over their own personal data. As for the user-friendly systems it is noted that “*privacy related functions and facilities should be user friendly, i.e. they should provide sufficient help and simple interfaces to be used also by less experienced users*”.²⁸⁹

3.4.3.2 *Terms of Use for main investigators (national authorities, volunteer organisations and rescue teams)*

In order to ensure appropriate use of the ChildRescue platform and app during cases’ investigation process and at the same time to prevent misuse of the system or breach of confidentiality and data privacy, detailed “Terms of Use” is recommended to be drafted –although it is not mandatory by law-concerning all groups of main investigators (national authorities, volunteer organisations and rescue teams) and taking into account their specific roles and level of access in the platform. Various templates are available online that may be used as a basis for preparing such a document for the needs of the specific platform and app²⁹⁰.

3.4.3.3 *Code of Ethics of professionals provide and administrate information*

Main professional specialties to be involved in the ChildRescue Platform either as sources of data or as data administrators are already subjected in (national and international) professional codes of ethics [Psychologists²⁹¹; Social Workers²⁹²; Sociologists²⁹³]; to this end, they shall considered as *eligible* in terms of ethics for the ChildRescue.

²⁸⁸ Source: <https://appsamurai.com/6-necessary-elements-for-designing-a-perfect-mobile-app-user-interface/>

²⁸⁹ Source: https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/privacy-and-data-protection-by-design/at_download/fullReport

²⁹⁰ <https://media.termsfeed.com/docx/terms-of-use-template.docx>

²⁹¹ <http://www.apa.org/ethics/code/>

²⁹² <https://www.socialworkers.org/About/Ethics/Code-of-Ethics>

²⁹³ <https://www.isa-sociology.org/en/about-isa/code-of-ethics/>

3.4.3.4 *Detailing step-by-step instructions for data sharing, real-time messaging and collaborative tagging*

Detailing step-by-step instructions for data sharing, real-time messaging and collaborative tagging should be included in both, Terms of Use for main investigators (national authorities, volunteer organisations and rescue teams) and Terms of Use for users-*community sensors*, as all of them are expected to be involved in these activities in platform's collaborative space.

3.4.3.5 *Privacy Policy*

The EU legal framework²⁹⁴ applies in any case where the use of apps on **smart devices involves processing personal data of individuals**. The ePrivacy directive (2002/58/EC, as revised by 2009/136/EC) sets a specific standard for all parties worldwide that wish to store or access information stored in the devices of users in the European Economic Area.

ChildRescue is expected to collect, store, and share personal data (e.g. names, email addresses, IP addresses, location data etc.) of missing children as well as of other groups of users and, therefore, a privacy policy is mandatory, as both the above directives are imperative laws in that the individual's rights are non-transferable and not subject to contractual waiver.

Therefore, an easily accessible privacy policy shall be drafted to inform users at least about

- what is ChildRescue (identity and contact details)
- what personal data the app collect and process and why this is necessary (purpose)
- whether personal data will be disclosed to third parties (if yes, specifically to whom)
- what are their (users') rights, in terms of withdrawal of consent and deletion of data

Content of the privacy policy could be structured as follows:

- Information Collected by the app
- Information Shared with Third Parties
- Cookies
- Security
- Information from Children Under the Age of 13
- Questions

Note: Concerning Privacy Policy changes in project's GA is mentioned that *although most changes are likely to be minor, ChildRescue may change its Privacy Policy from time to time, and in ChildRescue's sole discretion, after acceptance by the consortium, the EAB and the responsible national agencies. ChildRescue will inform users for any such change, asking for their acceptance, in order to continue using of the platform. User's that have not accepted the revised policies will be put into a "frozen" state, meaning that their data will not be shared anymore until they decide to accept or reject the new policies. Rejecting them, would mean that user's data will be treated using the previous policy, while users will also be able to choose to delete their account and remove their data from the platform.*

²⁹⁴ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:31995L0046:en:HTML>

3.4.3.6 *Terms of Use of mobile app for community users-sources of information /'community sensors'*

Similarly, as for the groups of main investigators (national authorities, volunteer organisations and rescue teams), a detailed "Terms of Use" is recommended to be drafted –although it is not mandatory by law- concerning all groups of community users (registered identifiable users; registered users without personal identifiers; and anonymous users).

3.4.3.7 *Safeguarding users' privacy and confidentiality of personal data*

ChildRescue should follow necessary procedures to ensure that all staff and others who have access to any personal information held by the Platform and App, are fully aware of and abide by their duties and responsibilities under the main EU legal framework.²⁹⁵ Duties and responsibilities could be described either as part of the Terms of Use of main investigators' groups or in a separate "Data Protection and Confidentiality Policy" document which will be developed.

3.4.3.7.1 *Inform users about what personal information the app may access, collect and use, how and why the information will be used and how they can control this use*

This information should be clearly provided to users in the context of Privacy Policy; in addition, they should be informed on whether and how they can control the use of their personal data, providing them with appropriate tools (see above "Ensuring user friendly interface" where it was mentioned that "...through an easy-to-use interface, app users provided with the ability to set their privacy settings, namely they have direct control over their own personal data").

3.5 Ethical issues related to unaccompanied minors

3.5.1 Changes from 1st iteration

The main change in regard to Unaccompanied Migrant Children legal framework in Greece involves the adoption of the **Law 4554/2018**.

On governmental level, the Ministry of Migration and Asylum Services have been integrated into the Ministry of Civil Protection, as of July 2019, in the framework of the re-organization of the public sector following the national elections and the establishment of a new governmental scheme under the New Democracy party.

Law 4554/2018, published in State Gazette no.130, is set to strengthen children protection systems and mechanisms in the country. The innovating part of the new law is the:

- ✓ introduction of a regulatory framework for the guardianship of unaccompanied and separated children, as by EU and national law, a guardian should be appointed for all unaccompanied and separated children.

In compliance to directives 2013/32/EC and 2013/33/EC, by Article 2 in law 4540/2018 and Article 34 in law 4375/2016 as "unaccompanied children" are determined all alien or stateless persons under the age of 18 who arrive in Greece without being accompanied by an adult exercising parental guardianship or custody or who get separated from their legal guardian while in Greece. That includes children

²⁹⁵ namely Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC; The ePrivacy directive 2002/58/EC as revised by 2009/136/EC

separated by their legal guardian, although they might be still accompanied by family members or other adults.

Any authority detecting the entry of an unaccompanied or separated child into the Greek territory shall take the appropriate measures to inform the closest Public Prosecutor office and the competent authority for the protection of unaccompanied and/or separated children, which is the **General Directorate of Social Solidarity** of the Ministry of Labor, Social Security and Social Solidarity.

- ✓ The *General Directorate of Social Solidarity* is responsible for further initiating and monitoring the procedure of appointing a guardian to a child and ensuring an unaccompanied child's best interests are met at all times
- ✓ The Public Prosecutor for Minors or the local competent Public Prosecutor, if no Public Prosecutor for minors exists, is considered as the **temporary guardian** of the unaccompanied child and holds - among others - the **responsibility to appoint a permanent guardian of the child**

According to the new system, guardianship is passing over to public sector with the aim the number of guardians to be increased. The guardian of the unaccompanied minor is selected from:

- ✓ a **Registry of Guardians** created under the National Centre for Social Solidarity (*Εθνικό Κέντρο Κοινωνικής Αλληλεγγύης* - EKKA) and its
- ✓ newly established **Directorate for the Protection of Unaccompanied Minors**.

Article 18 sets out the terms for the appointment and replacement of a Guardianship Commissioner for Unaccompanied Children.

The guardians provide individualized support to the unaccompanied children ensuring the assessment and determination of unaccompanied children's best interest.

- ✓ The law foresees a best interest of the child determination procedure to be developed with relevant secondary law

Moreover, the guardian holds responsibilities relevant to the integration of unaccompanied children, facilitating thus their access to legal protection and basic social services, as follows:

- Ensuring decent accommodation in special reception structures for unaccompanied children
- Representing and assisting the child in all judicial and administrative procedures
- Accompanying the child to clinics or hospitals
- Guaranteeing that the child is safe during their stay in the country
- Ensuring that legal assistance and interpretation services are provided to the child
- Providing access to psychological support and health care when needed
- Taking care of enrolling the child in formal or non-formal education
- Taking necessary steps to assign custody of the child to an appropriate family (foster family), in accordance with the applicable legal provisions;

- Ensuring that the child's political, philosophical and religious beliefs are respected and freely expressed and developed
- Behaving with sympathy and respect to the unaccompanied child

Furthermore, the law:

- ✓ Establishes the ***Department for the Protection of Unaccompanied Minors*** at the National Center for Social Solidarity, which will have the responsibility of guaranteeing safe accommodation for unaccompanied children and evaluating the quality of services provided in such accommodation
- ✓ Creates the ***Supervisory Guardianship Board***, which will be responsible for ensuring legal protection for unaccompanied children with respect to disabilities, religious beliefs and custody issues

Secondary legislation, such as Ministerial Decisions and standard operating procedures, are required by law in order to further regulate the functioning of the Registry of Guardians and the best interests of the child determination procedure.

By provision of the new law and according to secondary legislation 26943/1073/2019 EKKA is responsible to keep a ***National Registry of Unaccompanied Children*** as part of the *National Registry for Child Protection* (established by law 3962/2011 - Article 8). EKKA is responsible to register the personal details and data of all the unaccompanied minors that come to its attention from any authority or third party and in full compliance to GDPR provisions.

The personal details of the registered unaccompanied children include:

1. Full name
2. Sex
3. Date and place of birth
4. Nationality and nationality by birth
5. Linguistic ability
6. Parents or parental-guardian's personal details

Overall evaluation

The new law:

- Aims to strengthen the national protection system for unaccompanied children
- Establishes for the first time a framework for the guardianship of unaccompanied and separated children in Greece
- Sets the basis to increase the number of professional legal guardians and
- In the new law there are no specific timeframe or deadline provisions in regards to the proposed procedures
- In the framework of the new law however, there is little provision for homeless or not into the system children
- The actual number of accommodation services remains low to meet relative needs

- Advanced powers on Public Prosecutor's level raise concerns in regards to adequate human resources available

Notice: In practice, as of July 2019, the system of guardianship is still not operating.

Under the existing regime, the Public Prosecutor has the duty to appoint a representative of the unaccompanied children coming to his/her attention that will be responsible for the respective child and defend his/her interests.

For unaccompanied children under 15 years of age their appointed representative is responsible for the submission of the child's application for international protection. Children of 15 years age may submit their protection application themselves.

Resources:

- *National Gazette 130*
- *European Website on integration*
- *Ministry of Citizen Protection – Asylum Service*
- *Greek Council for Refugees*

3.6 Summary of Recommendations

Given that the *ChildRescue platform* follows a tiered approach and it consists from multiple layers where personal data are collected, analysed or reported, data protection should be ensured at all levels before the platform become fully operative and for the piloting phase in at least Greece and Belgium.

To this end, the following actions are recommended to ensure in advance that ChildRescue R&D activities -including methods, tools, technologies and processes- comply with existing legal framework, ethical and privacy principles concerning access to personal information and data protection.

The following recommendations categorized under the four fundamental ethical principles are suggested to be taken into account:

1. ***The Principle of Beneficence.*** ChildRescue should aim to bring about good in all its actions; in this case special attention should be given in order to avoid direct conflict with respecting the autonomy of other involved parties.
 - a. Acquiring National Data Protection Authorities' license for establishment and operation of register containing sensitive personal data. In this license should be clearly and detailed defined the purpose of the ChildRescue Platform and App concerning both, the primary and secondary uses of data to be collected and processed; the benefit of primary use of data is the investigation for finding a missing and/or unaccompanied child while the benefit of secondary use of data is about the sensitization of the community and activation of its sources towards supporting families in crisis and in particular towards the prevention of child disappearances and the more efficient management of cases of children declared as missing.
 - b. All ChildRescue functions (including profiling methods, semantic extraction of tags, sentiment analysis, social network analysis, applying activity theory principles and predictive analytic methods) should target to identify the missing child; treatment of

personal data of third parties (such as anonymous app users) should be appropriate for avoiding any violation in the agreed terms of use of the app.

2. **"First, do no harm"-The Principle of nonmaleficence. ChildRescue should undertake the obligation not to harm any of the involved parties** including **children** (missing and/or unaccompanied refugee and migrant children or to be traced); **guardians** (including parents/other legal guardians/tracing applicants); **professionals** (either who work with the cases such as psychologists, social workers, the police and public prosecutors or have administrative, operational or IT roles); and **platform users** (namely "community sensors", at various levels including registered identifiable users; register users and anonymous users).
 - a. ChildRescue should respect the first principle concerning both, children who are the main platform's beneficiaries but indirect users and all relevant stakeholders who are platform's direct users and have the role of data sources and data administrators. To achieve these various techniques to ensure data privacy could be applied such as data anonymization; blockchains; pseudonymization; physical or digital restriction of access; and controlled (graded) access to data.
 - b. Protection of privacy and personal data is a human right and any inappropriate use of these data can harm the subject of data; the ability, however, to protect privacy and personal data in the context of a platform or mobile application is a technical matter. Therefore, in order to ensure appropriate level of sensitive personal data protection and avoid harm application of *privacy design principles* (including data minimization; controllability; transparency; user-friendly systems; data confidentiality; data quality; and use limitation) is recommended.
 - c. Providing that ChildRescue is dealing with children's data, it should be ensured that necessary standards and regulations are applied in order to prevent any misuse of application (as, for example, monitoring of data access; monitoring of various stakeholders/users actions; and ensuring that the system is well-protected).
 - d. Detailing step-by-step instructions for data sharing, real-time messaging and collaborative tagging is recommended to be included in Terms of Use for main investigators (national authorities, volunteer organisations and rescue teams) and Terms of Use for app Users.
 - e. Transparent administration of log files should be adopted regarding their content, protection, access and destruction; in other words it should be decided in advance what information is worth keeping in the context of ChildRescue, given the ethical risks of doing so.
3. **The Principle of Respect for autonomy. ChildRescue should respect the autonomy of involved parties**, namely, to respect their decisions concerning the collection and use of their personal data according to what it was agreed per case.
 - a. Subjects' of data (and missing children's legal guardians) should be adequately aware in advance for primary (*investigation for missing children*) and secondary (*profiling; identifying patterns; extraction of lessons learned; retrieval of similar cases*) use of their data, before they provide their consent for data collection and use. Informed consent forms as well as Terms of Privacy should include explicit information on this issue.

- b. Clearly described *Terms of Use* is recommended to be drafted (although it is not mandatory) concerning all groups of community users (registered identifiable users; registered users without personal identifiers; and anonymous users) and main investigators of the ChildRescue (national authorities, volunteer organisations and rescue teams) in order to ensure appropriate use of the platform and app during cases' investigation and to prevent misuse of the system or breach of confidentiality and data privacy.
 - c. Personal data should be processed on the basis of the consent of the data subject concerned; in the investigation cycle for a missing or unaccompanied child, however, the main subject of data collection and processing (the child) is practically not feasible to provide his/her assent and therefore informed consent can be challenge and should rely to legal guardian of the child. Similarly to other systems/programs of communicating information of missing children (such as the Amber Alert) parental/legal guardian informed consent should be obtained before using child's personal data in the context of ChildRescue Platform and application, along with the permission of the Police (or other responsible authority). A standardized informed consent form is recommended to be developed on the basis of which missing child's parent/legal guardian will allow the use (upload and dissemination) of child's personal data through ChildRescue Platform and application.
 - d. Acquisition of agreements with third parties (such as social media platforms) containing terms of cooperation is recommended; in the context of such agreements it should be clearly stated, for example, whether the third party service provider's terms of service and privacy policies govern ChildRescue users activity on the third party website or whether ChildRescue Platform intends to collect and maintain personal data the users make available on third party websites.
4. ***The Principle of justice. ChildRescue should have an obligation to treat all people equally, fairly, and impartially.***
- a. Clear definition of roles, rights and accountabilities of the users working in operating organisations should be the first step toward appropriate treatment of platform relevant stakeholders' personal data. Operating organisations should guarantee that ChildRescue platform and application comply with existing national and European data protection laws and regulations and that users' rights according to GDPR (such as easier access to their data; right to data portability; right to erasure or '*right to be forgotten*'; right to know when their personal data has been hacked) are respected.
 - b. Apart from the phase of the platform design and build, it should be ensured that during the pilot and, afterwards, the full operation phase ChildRescue will operate according to what provisioned by the law, ensuring in this way equal, fair and impartial treatment of all involved stakeholders.
 - c. Processing of personal data should also follow basic principles as they are referred in Art. 5 of GDPR including awfulness, fairness and transparency; purpose limitation; data minimization; personal data accuracy; storage limitation; integrity and confidentiality and accountability.

- d. In cases that more than one countries are involved in an investigation (as, for example, in cases of international kidnappings or unaccompanied refugee and immigrant children) the legislation to be followed should be pre-decided.
 - e. The level of access of authorities requesting data (such as the IP address, the date, time and place they used the mobile app) of non-identifiable 'community sensors' (namely registered users without personal identifiers and anonymous users) should be clearly pre-defined in order to avoid any type of privacy violation and at the same time the Platform to operate according to the law.
 - f. **Privacy Policy:** ChildRescue is expected to collect, store, and share personal data (e.g. names, email addresses, IP addresses, location data etc.) of missing or unaccompanied children as well as of other groups of users. Therefore, an easily accessible privacy policy shall be drafted to inform users at least about what is ChildRescue; what personal data the app collect and process and why this is necessary; whether personal data will be disclosed to third parties and if yes, specifically to whom; and what are their (users') rights, in terms of withdrawal of consent and deletion of data. Drafting of a privacy policy is mandatory, as both the relevant directives are imperative laws.
5. ***The Principle of Accountability. Data controllers shall be responsible for, and be able to demonstrate compliance of ChildRescue with GDPR concerning processing of personal data***
- a. As part of the accountability principle (GDPR Art. 5(b) and 30), each controller and, where applicable, the controller's representative shall maintain a record of processing activities under their responsibility. Data processors or their representatives shall also maintain a record of all categories of processing activities carried out on behalf of a controller. These records shall include –among other information- the purposes of processing, a description of the categories of data and recipients of the data and “where possible, a general description of the technical and organisational security measures referred to in Article 32(1)” (Article 30(1)). The controller or the processor and, where applicable, the controller's or the processor's representative, shall make the record available to the supervisory authority on request [GDPR 30(4)].
 - b. Taking into account GDPR provisions on personal data processing including profiling, the *Decision of HDPa on the kind of processing operations which are subject to the requirement for a DPIA, the WP29 Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and the anticipated processing activities in the context of ChildRescue (as they detailed in D2.4)*, it is considered that the criteria for the implementation of a DPIA are fulfilled. Therefore, it is recommended to ChildRescue to consider the necessity of a DPIA. Even if the ultimate decision is not to carry out a DPIA, it is recommended to proceed with the assessment of whether a high risk is likely, even if they ultimately decide not to carry out a DPIA.

4 Part C: ChildRescue Integrated Methodology Release II

4.1 ChildRescue Landscape Analysis

4.1.1 Changes from 1st iteration

During the first iteration of WP1, a landscape analysis took place in order to thoroughly study the state-of-play on the domains that would be of direct interest to ChildRescue, to form thereafter the ChildRescue methodology and ChildRescue developments capitalising on the insights drawn from the literature review. In that view, an identification and categorisation of these domains to be analysed bibliographically preceded, based on the scientific areas that are associated with ChildRescue and from which ChildRescue can profit with ideas, methodologies and opinions.

The categorisation of these domains, presented in the context of D1.3 "ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release I", was split into three research areas, starting from the more high-level but core area of "Business Process Re-engineering" and continuing to more specific and complementary areas for the ChildRescue interests, that of "Crowdsourcing, Social Innovation and Collective Awareness" and "Behavioural and Activity Profiling".

During this second iteration of WP1, the aforementioned research areas are revisited and complemented by a fourth, broad research area, that of "Human Mobility Patterns", analysed from two different perspectives, that of the ChildRescue social sensors, namely the citizens that are registered, informed ChildRescue users, and that of the missing child, to support the prediction of the child's most probable location. Therefore, an integrated literature review, in the context of WP1 actions and needs, is provided, concluding the landscape analysis cycle for WP1. An analysis of the domains of interest selection and their interlinking can be found in the next section 4.1.2, while in section 4.1.3 the key take-aways from each of the three research areas, analysed in the first iteration, are presented, before proceeding with the landscape analysis on the "Human Mobility Patterns" research area in section 4.1.4. Then, the relevant technologies and systems that have been developed so far all over the world for designing and managing missing persons cases and that were presented in the previous deliverable D1.3 "ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release I" are concentrated again in section 4.1.5 in a more concise and comparative way, contrasting them with respect to the existence or absence of different features.

4.1.2 ChildRescue Domains of Interest

As mentioned above, the categorisation of the ChildRescue domains of interest is, now, split into four research areas, starting from the more high-level but core area of "Business Process Re-engineering" and continuing to more specific and complementary areas for the ChildRescue interests, that of "Crowdsourcing, Social Innovation and Collective Awareness", "Behavioural and Activity Profiling" and "Human Mobility Patterns".

While these four areas might seem independent and detached at a first glance, they "bind" together harmoniously under the ChildRescue concept. In particular, "Business Process Re-engineering – Change Management" serves as a cornerstone area as it encapsulates ChildRescue's vision, i.e. to define new processes, methods, techniques and means for the investigation of missing children that will complement the current systems and processes of the engaged organisations and gradually – and certainly not intrusively – substitute and relieve their present predicaments. ChildRescue perceives that its assets to achieve the desirable re-engineering step upon crowdsourcing and collective intelligence

on the one hand and innovative profiling on the other hand, using data sources not considered before, such as social media data or past cases insights, to deduce an informed, combined profile for the missing child. In order, however, to be able to profit from both previous research areas, human mobility needs to be analysed and patterns to be extracted on what concerns both the citizens, contributing with their action on the collective intelligence aspect, as well as the missing children, following the deduction of his/her combined profile.

Therefore, "Crowdsourcing, Social Innovation and Collective Intelligence" area, presented in brief in section 4.1.3.2, will serve as a source of new or not yet sufficiently exploited input in the investigation process of missing children, being in other words an "enabler" in the ChildRescue value proposition. Citizens are engaged as social sensors in the investigation of missing children, offering their collective insights and intelligence into the investigation process. "Behavioural and Activity Profiling" is explored as an area that will provide added value to ChildRescue, concentrating all existing information, as well as new sources of information, regarding a missing child's case, to build a combined, personal profile for the child, able to reveal potentially hidden moods, influences, acquaintances and activities. The insights that will arise from this profiling along with information regarding the location of a missing child provided through crowdsourcing means, will support prediction with a better accuracy of all child's possible locations. Towards this goal, analysis of the mobility behaviour and patterns of past cases of missing children in different situations based on the type of disappearance is expected to unfold new opportunities in the prediction of the expected mobility behaviour of a missing child and contribute significantly in the as accurate as possible proposition of probable locations of the child, serving as directions that the investigations should follow. On the other side, analysis of citizens' mobility patterns may give an insight on the coverage of the area, where the child went missing or other areas of interest for the child's case, by "social sensors", that know about the case and might actively contribute with evidence. This information for the coverage of the area and the probable distribution of social sensors, based on the insights extracted from the analysis, may give an indication on the probability of the child's early identification, as well as the need to further intensify the call for help towards the community. In that sense, the area of "Human Mobility Patterns" analysis is considered a driver, stepping upon the collective intelligence deriving from the citizens and the profiling insights deduced for the missing child, towards the most important piece of information, the current, most probable location of the child. The above presented structure and categorisation of the ChildRescue scientific areas that are considered as domains of interest, and will be analysed bibliographically along the following lines, is also illustrated in Figure 4-1, below.

Figure 4-1 Structure and Categorisation of ChildRescue Domains of Interest

4.1.3 Key Take-aways from 1st iteration

4.1.3.1 Business Process Re-engineering

4.1.3.1.1 Change management

Organisational change is a field of management theory examining the stages that organisations go through as they progress [1] and it is a tool widely used to define the most appropriate strategy depending on the stage of the change organisations are currently at. Change management is a subdiscipline of organisational change and according to the Innovation and Organizational Change management Institute (IOCFI)²⁹⁶ it is the people side of change. The people or human side of change management can be described as the alignment of the organisation's culture, values, people and behaviour [2]. According to [3], change management can also be defined as "the process of continually renewing an organisation's direction, structure, and capabilities to serve the ever-changing needs of external and internal customers.

The attention in academia has been shifted towards organisational management especially after the 80s that labour mobility, market transparency, global capital flows and international communication has changed the scenery for the companies [2]. According to [4], companies only needed to utilise their resources in a way that was profitable when operating in a relative stable environment, but change management emerged in the moment companies started to face competitive environments that changed profoundly and in a high pace.

²⁹⁶ <https://www.iocmi.org>

The constant changes and the adaptation of companies and organisations to those changes have boosted the development of change management theories, frameworks and models that can be of aid when employing change management. As in [5] review, change management can be analysed from different perspectives. They reviewed the existing literature from four different aspects, namely: the internal and external environment perspective (contextual issues), the substance of contemporary organisational changes point of view (content issues), the actions taken while the organisation undergoes the change angle (process issues), and the outcomes of the change aspect (criterion issues). Regarding the external or internal factors, they found out that change may be mainly imposed by two factors. The first factor is regulatory changes and the second one may emerge by the technological advancements that the competitors adopt and implement. The models that focus on content factors, such as organisation structure and strategic orientation, define the mission and direction of the organisation and are the basis of a long-term success. They are suitable for the conduct of organisational diagnosis, and for planning the potential impact of the change. Depending on the behavioural aspects of the participants the content factors can be combined in different ways in order to achieve the desirable result. Concerning the process issues related studies, that analyse the ongoing actions while the organisation undergoes the change, it was found out that the change occurs in multiple steps, that require time to develop and any attempt to reduce the time of these efforts seldom yields a satisfactory result. What is more, any mistakes may hinder or even stop the process. Finally, as far as the criterion issues are concerned, the reactions to organisational changes can be assessed by a variety of methods, including computer-based analysis or observation. What also can be taken into consideration in the assessment of the reaction to the change is, apart from the traditional criteria that measure effectiveness (e.g. job satisfaction), the evaluation of less used criteria (e.g. depression). Also, the frequent communication of results or milestones can assist the members to cope with the change.

Challenges and risks when implementing change management should not of course be overseen. From a business perspective, booz&co. in the relevant report that they issued in 2004²⁹⁷ conclude that there are some issues that need to be closely monitored when implementing change management. Initially the "human side" of the organisation needs to be addressed systematically, meaning that when change management is employed the as-is situation is altered and that can lead to confusion and resistance. A way to deal with that phenomenon is to address each of the cases that may emerge separately and proactively. Another issue to be kept in mind is that the change must start at the top and involve every layer, with constant communication and with the channels of communication being open. What is more, an assessment of the cultural landscape and its potential reaction to change should be assessed before employing change management.

From an academia point of view, [6] after reviewing the existing literature came up with some steps that need to be followed if change management is to be successful. They assess that as a first step the idea or the innovation that calls for the change of the as-is situation and its context need to be clearly defined, closely followed by a clear definition of the roles and the processes that need to be changed. What is more, the climate of change needs to be assessed, meaning that there needs to be a deep understanding of how the organisation operates in the current environment. A clear plan also needs to be crafted, including specific goals and clearly defined responsibilities. The leadership needs to be a

²⁹⁷ <https://www.devex.com/organizations/booz-co-49791>

pioneer when it comes to embracing the change plan. The importance of constant communication among all the layers in the organisation is explicitly mentioned by the researchers. Finally, attention is also given to incorporating any lessons learnt that may emerge while change management is employed. It can be observed that from both a business perspective and an academia perspective, the issues that need to be given attention while implementing change management remain similar. Extra attention is given to the assessment of the current culture of the organisation, the involvement of all the people that work in it, the constant communication between the leadership and the rest of the employees, while taking into consideration the lessons learnt while the process is ongoing.

Within the concept of ChildRescue, attention needs to be given to change management. As it is mentioned and explained throughout this and previous deliverables, ChildRescue aims at being a non-intrusive driver of change. That means that the processes currently followed by the missing children response organisations will slightly alter, if these organisations decide to incorporate the platform and app in the search of missing children. Even though the change is not going to be intrusive, some readjustment is going to take place. Therefore, all the aforementioned challenges and risks need to be taken into consideration, while specific attention needs to be given in the communication among all the members of the organisations and the engagement to the change from the top to the bottom.

4.1.3.1.2 *Business Process Management and Re-engineering*

Today's highly competitive environment has made it impossible for organisations to stay static²⁹⁸. A lot of attention has been given from both the academia and the business world on techniques, theories or models that could facilitate the constant changes. Two concepts that are widely but differently used in terms of their application are Business Process Management and Business Process Re-engineering. Along the following lines, an overview of the two concepts from mainly an academic point of view is going to be presented and the relevant literature, the architectures, key success factors are going to be analysed, along with the ways both concepts, but mainly Business Process Management, applies to ChildRescue.

Process in the management science related literature mainly refers to the approach that converts inputs into outputs [7]. According to [7] a process is: "the manner in which the resources of an organisation are used in a reliable, repeatable and consistent way", in order for the organisation to achieve its goals. [8] defines business process as: "a complete, dynamically coordinated set of activities or logically related tasks that must be performed to deliver value to customers or to fulfil other strategic goals". [9] defines process as: "a collection of inter-related events, activities and decision points that involve a number of actors and objects, and that collectively lead to an outcome that is of value to at least one customer". Essentially, according to Bulletpoint (1996) there are four key features to any process, namely these are: predictable and definable inputs, a linear, logical sequence or flow, a set of clearly definable tasks or activities, and a predictable and desired outcome or result.

In the existing literature about Business Process Management, a lot of attention has been given to processes [10]. One of the issues that academia has tried to define is what constitutes a "better process". Mainly a better process includes the processes that contribute in an optimal way to meet the strategic objectives of an organisation [10]. BPM is employed when the level of contribution is not met

²⁹⁸ <https://www.devex.com/organizations/booz-co-49791>

or when the set Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are also not met. BPM is mainly utilised so that the performance of the organisation can be enhanced. BPM can be associated with the KPIs and can be a means to meet them by terms of employing the appropriate and necessary tools that can be of assistance in the analysis of what hinders and stalls meeting the KPIs. According to [10], one way to mine data in order to analyse them and extract information is the employment of statistical tools that can measure the variability of the processes. Another way can be the employment of operations research, in order to find an optimal solution for complex issues with a lot of constraints and options. [11] mention that Information Technology (IT) can also be employed to manage business processes, as more and more processes that were previously hand-filled in paper form are replaced by their electronic counterparts, giving rise to BPM.

Business Process Management

As [7] states the existing literature on modern management techniques such as business process re-engineering, benchmarking or business process management is plentiful. The concept of BPM has been defined in various ways some of them are described below. [7] states that: "BPM is a structured approach to analyse and continually improve fundamental activities such as manufacturing, marketing, communications and other major elements of a company's operation". [9] claims that: "BPM is the art and science of overseeing how work is performed in an organisation to ensure consistent outcomes and to take advantage of improvement opportunities". They also claim that BPM does not have to do with micromanagement, as in overseeing that every single task in an organisation is performed efficiently, but rather has to do with ensuring that the overall processes that add value to the organisation and its customers are performed efficiently. What is more, they mention that: "BPM has a body of methods, techniques and tools to discover, analyse, redesign, execute and monitor business processes." The above definition is what links BPM to business processes.

In the Figure 4-2 below, the BPM lifecycle is graphically explained. Mainly BPM is seen as a continuous cycle that includes: (a) the process of identification, where the problem is posed, (b) the process discovery, where the relevant processes are documented, (c) the process analysis, where the as-is situation is identified, (d) the process re-design, where the existing processes are improved, (e) the process implementation, where the improvements are implemented, and (f) the process monitoring and controlling, where the new processes are evaluated and feedback is provided.

Figure 4-2 BPM lifecycle, retrieved from [9]

Strategic Alignment	Governance	Methods	Information Technology	People	Culture	Factors
Process Improvement Planning	Process Management Decision Making	Process Design & Modelling	Process Design & Modelling	Process Skills & Expertise	Responsiveness of Process Change	Capability Areas
Strategy & Process Capability Linkage	Process Roles & Responsibilities	Process Implementation & Execution	Process Implementation & Execution	Process Management Knowledge	Process Values & Beliefs	
Enterprise Process Architecture	Process Metrics & Performance Linkage	Process Monitoring & Control	Process Monitoring & Control	Process Education	Process Attitudes and Behaviours	
Process Measures	Process Related Standards	Process Improvement & Innovation	Process Improvement & Innovation	Process Collaboration	Leadership Attention to Process	
Process Customers & Stakeholders	Process management Compliance	Process Program & Project Management	Process Program & Project Management	Process Management Leaders	Process Management Social Networks	

Figure 4-3 BPM core elements, success factors and challenges, retrieved from [12]

J. vom Brocke and M. Rosemann [12], after an exhaustive review of the relevant literature, concluded that the success factors that need to be kept in mind when employing BPM, can fall under six categories as depicted in the table above. Particularly, BPM needs to be aligned with the overall strategy of the organisation and the strategic alignment factor refers to linking the priorities of the organisation with the followed processes. The governance factor refers to establishing different roles and responsibilities in all the levels of BPM. Methods with regards to BPM are the tools and techniques employed along any BPM activities. Information technology is of extreme importance when it comes to BPM, especially with reference to process analysis, modelling and support. Special attention has been given to software with an understanding of the processes that need to be followed when BPM is to be employed. People are the ones that apply the processes or get affected by them. This factor is the reflection of BPM to the human capital. Culture stands for the collective values that govern an organisation and BPM studies indicate that culture is a very important factor when it comes to the people accepting the new processes imposed by BPM. The above six factors came up after a compilation of a variety of studies that looked at BPM through different aspects, some of them were more technical in nature, some more business oriented, and others more conceptual or behavioural.

One of the key components of BPM is that it is not intrusive as it does not radically change processes but only improves the existing ones, thus it is the one that will be followed in ChildRescue. Even though

BPM is non-intrusive, there are still challenges that need to be addressed when employing it. Mainly that the above six factors of success also hinder risks if not given proper attention. If BPM is not aligned with the strategy of the organisation, the new processes will not only not help but may even hinder the whole course of action and mission. As for the governance, the roles need to be separate and clear, or else the efficiency will be hindered. Regarding the methods and information technology, the appropriate processes and the right tools need to be employed. In this case, the appropriate needs and tools to be assessed refers to how suitable these needs and tools are. The people are of extreme importance when BPM is employed, as the human capital needs to be informed at every step of the way about the new processes thus making communication in all the levels of hierarchy of extreme importance. The culture is also an important factor as it needs to be responsive to change and processes need to be an integral part of the change. The leadership needs to be engaged when BPM is employed and needs to be in constant communication with the rest of the members of the organisation.

Business Process Reengineering

BPR originated after the 1980s, when organisations were in need of fundamental changes in order to create and maintain a sustainable competitive advantage, by radically improving the existing processes [13]. [13], who reviewed the up to that point literature presented an overview of BPR and some definitions were also given.

According to [14] BPR is: "the analysis and design of work flows and processes within and between organisations". [15] claim BPR is: "the fundamental rethinking and radical redesign of business processes to achieve dramatic improvements in critical, contemporary measures of performance, such as cost, quality, service, and speed.". [16] with a focus on rethinking defines BPR as: "the rethinking, restructuring and streamlining of the business structure, processes, methods of working, management systems and external relationships through which value is created and delivered". [17] state that BPR: "involves the concurrent redesign of processes, organisations, and their supporting information systems to achieve radical improvement in time, cost, quality, and customers' regard for the company's products and services". [18] describes BPR as: "the fundamental rethinking and redesign of operating processes and organisational structure, the focus is on the organisation's core competencies, to achieve dramatic improvements in organisational performance, as BPR's essential components".

Contribution to ChildRescue

BPR is used when the as-is processes are going to be radically and fundamentally changed, by changing the whole strategy, mission and vision of an organisation. ChildRescue, however, aims at being of assistance to the processes as they currently take place. That is why even though BPR is mentioned and up to a point analysed for the sake of completeness of the analysis, there will be no further mention of it. BPM and change management on the other hand, are the techniques that are closely connected to ChildRescue.

As mentioned in the sections above, BPM is occurring when the existing processes are slightly altered in order to achieve the same results in an optimised manner, while change management is how the human capital reacts and adapts to those changes. ChildRescue aims at being a driver of change, however this change is to happen in a non-intrusive manner. The proposed platform that is one of the main outcomes of the project will be a facilitator for SoC, REDCROSS and Child Focus, available to assist the already involved parties in the process of searching for a missing child or an unaccompanied migrant minor.

4.1.3.2 Crowdsourcing, Social Innovation and Collective Awareness

The meaning of the terms Crowdsourcing, Social Innovation and Collective Awareness do share common characteristics, specifically when seen under the scope of ChildRescue. In this section, the aforementioned concepts with respect to ChildRescue are presented, along with a description of how these concepts will be utilised in order to add value to the current missing children investigation processes and to the identification of unaccompanied minors.

4.1.3.2.1 Crowdsourcing

The term crowdsourcing was invented by Jeff Howe and Mark Robinson in the June 2006 issue of Wired magazine²⁹⁹. They claimed that crowdsourcing is “a new web-based business model that harnesses the creative solutions of a distributed network of individuals through what amounts to an open call for proposals” [19]. Etymologically, it is formulated by the words: crowd, referring to the people participating in an initiative, and sourcing, referring to all practices aimed at finding, evaluating and engaging suppliers of goods and services [20].

It is a concept that may be utilised in various occasions and can be given a plethora of definitions. For example, Wikipedia is considered to be a typical example of crowdsourcing according to [21], whereas [22] clearly claims the opposite. Definitions of crowdsourcing as they are most commonly encountered in the literature are presented in the table below.

Table 4-1 Different Definitions for Crowdsourcing

Definitions	Sources
“the act of taking a job traditionally performed by a designated agent (usually an employee) and outsourcing it to an undefined, generally large group of people in the form of an open call.”	[23]
“a strategic model to attract an interested, motivated crowd of individuals capable of providing solutions superior in quality and quantity to those that even traditional forms of business can.”	[19]
“new online distributed problem-solving and production model in which networked people collaborate to complete a task.”	[24]
“the opening of the innovation process of a firm to integrate numerous and disseminated outside competencies through web facilities”. These competencies can be those of individuals (for example creative people, scientists, engineers) or existing organised communities (for example open source software communities).	[25]

According to [26], crowdsourcing is differentiated from other, similar forms of participatory user-generated content activities as it entails a mix of top-down and bottom-up management processes that involve a community. Sometimes, little work being done by a lot of people - instead of much work being done by a few people - is more valuable and successful; and crowdsourcing is based on that fact. It is

²⁹⁹ <https://www.wired.com/2006/06/crowds/>

a distributed problem-solving model [27], in which work is divided between participants to achieve a cumulative result.

Below some crowdsourcing representative examples with social impact are given:

- In the Boston Marathon bombings, on April 2013, in addition to the usual call for any information leading to possible suspects, the FBI requested citizens to submit any audio-visual material such as videos and photos from the scene of the finish line, where the bombs went off. FBI collected a lot of data from the users, that along with the security video footage taken from nearby buildings led to the tracking and later to the arrest of the two primary suspects [26].
- Tomnod is a project that uses crowdsourcing to identify important missing objects or people and to mention interesting places in satellite images. Users have access to satellite images and are given the option to tag anything they perceive as peculiar or to add in an image. That is helpful specifically in the case that there is an on-going effort of locating missing people or objects. It can be utilised for instance in the search of a missing or injured climber on a mountain, in the search of locating refugee camps in Somalia, or in the search of Malaysia Airlines Flight 370 debris, etc. [28].

Obviously, as a mode of sourcing, but not with this specific term itself, crowdsourcing existed prior to the digital age. Regarding the present deliverable and the missing children's cases, missing children's response organisations are aware of the advantages of crowdsourcing. While the crowdsourcing term hadn't been coined in 1996, when Amber Alert was first launched, Amber Alert is in a sense a crowdsourcing process, since it is based on the provision of quick, accurate and detailed information to citizens on a missing child case, a few minutes after the reporting of the case to the police or the missing children organisation³⁰⁰.

In the past years, the growth of smartphones has given the opportunity for many new concepts to emerge [29]. One of them is **mobile crowdsourcing**, referring to crowdsourcing activities taking place via smartphones or other mobile devices. This phenomenon has been enabled due to the improvement of smartphone's technological features, including a reliable GPS, internet connectivity, high definition cameras, and the continuous launch of new apps³⁰¹.

The aforementioned improved technological features have provided mobile crowdsourcing apps with real-time data and live information³⁰¹. The increasingly high adoption rates of smartphones by citizens showcases the high volume of data that can be gathered and the great potential for mobile crowdsourcing initiatives. It is indicative that, while on 2014, the percentage of smartphone users in the population was 39.1% in Central & Eastern Europe and 57.4% in Western Europe³⁰², on 2018, the this percentage was 65.3% in Central & Eastern Europe and 78.6% in Western Europe. On 2019, the number of smartphone users is expected to rise to 68.4% and 80.5% in the respective regions³⁰². The user engagement on smartphones tends to grow, thus making mobile crowdsourcing a potentially invaluable tool in the search of missing children or unaccompanied migrant minors.

³⁰⁰ <https://www.hamogelo.gr/gr/en/eksafanismena-paidia:ambert-alert-hellas/>

³⁰¹ <https://www.clickworker.com/crowdsourcing-glossary/mobile-crowdsourcing/>

³⁰² https://insights.ap.org/uploads/images/eMarketer_Estimates_2015.pdf

What is more, smartphone users, as known, tend to carry their phones with them all day long [30]. The instant and continuous access of users to their smartphones adds into the fact that it can be a valuable tool in the process of gathering real-time data. In ChildRescue's case, this is an important advantage since users will be able to constantly stay informed and actively contribute, through their smartphone, to the missing child investigation at any time. Of course, it needs to be stressed that in order to be able to get this kind of information from users, it is necessary to get their consent before downloading or using the mobile app.

Active or passive - or else participatory or opportunistic respectively [31] - collection of data are the two main categories that the data gathered from a mobile crowdsourcing app can fall under. Passive mobile crowdsourcing is when the user gives permission to an app to collect data from their mobile device without requiring any further action from the user. Active collection of data in mobile crowdsourcing requires the active involvement of individuals. In the ChildRescue case, the users will be required to actively share data, in the form of pieces of evidence.

Contribution to ChildRescue

In missing children cases, time is the worst enemy as the first hours are the most decisive in locating the missing child. One of the most effective actions, that the missing children's response organisations can perform, is to immediately alert the crowd that a child has gone missing; let alone to send specific alerts to users who are close to where the child was last seen or close to the points of interest where the missing child is more likely to be found.

ChildRescue intention is to go one step further compared to the way investigations for a missing child are currently held, by seizing the opportunity smartphones' features provide. Prior to the development of smartphones' industry, the only way for a missing children's response organization to instantly and personally alert its users about a case was by sending an SMS to their phones. SMS's technology includes only text, though, and links that can be clicked and redirect users to a website where they could see more information about a missing child's case cannot be included to the text message. Images or any other multimedia information that might be helpful cannot be included. However, Amber Alerts or "Publicity" actions are more effective if they are accompanied by more information about a missing child. The ambition of ChildRescue project is the creation of an innovative solution that enables evidence-based alerting, publishing information such as pictures of the child, and collaborative action during the search of missing children, empowering citizens to provide information for the successful identification of the location of a missing child. Reporting live information and being able to use this information immediately fits well with the instantaneity that smartphones provide. Instant mobile alerts as well as updates, containing all necessary real-time information about the missing child's, are spread to all citizens who are in proximate areas where the missing child was last seen or in areas based on the possible routes the missing child could have taken. Then, users are able to contribute information of crucial importance that could potentially lead to the missing child's location quickly. Thus, ChildRescue takes advantage of mobile crowdsourcing for real-time and location-sensitive tasks.

A research was conducted by [32] about the attention customers pay to posters of missing children at the exits of supermarkets, and the results strengthen ChildRescue proposed approach. They indicate that despite the fact that public considers missing children an important social issue, they tend either to ignore or only briefly look at the posters, failing to memorise the children's pictures. Thus, if they happen to randomly see the missing child on the street, the most likely scenario is that they will pass by without noticing them. ChildRescue aims to eliminate this problem. Mobile app users are able to

revisit missing children's pictures any time they want, if the alert is still active in their area. That way, if they don't remember the child's characteristics, users can easily refer to the app and simultaneously compare and contrast the picture of the missing child with a child that they might see on the street resembling to the missing child.

4.1.3.2.2 *Social Innovation*

The accurate definition of social innovation varies according to the definitions attributed to both concepts "social" and "innovation" [33].

It is traced back to the beginning of 19th century, where Godin, explained that the term emerged after the French revolution and, it had both a positive (linked to social reforms) and a negative (synonymous with radical socialism) meaning. Slowly, the social innovation concept was less frequently used, and the term "innovation" was more commonly connected to technology. It re-emerged in theoretical writings in the 1960–1970s, and in the last 10 years, many scholars and ultimately the EU, are interested in it [33]. It had re-emerged as a term that contrasted social innovation with technological innovation and in this respect, it calls for action, to pay more attention to the social aspects of innovation. It is different than business innovation which is generally generated by profit maximisation [34]; social innovation initiates by the need to benefit society by solving societal problems and engaging citizens in participating in such actions. Social innovation does not contradict technological innovation but, on the contrary, technology is considered as a tool for supporting social innovation [33]. Furthermore, EU's intent is to nurture social innovation by finding new ways to meet social needs that are not adequately met by the market or the public sector³⁰³.

There is a plethora of social innovation definitions in the literature, some of them are presented in the table below.

Table 4-2 Social innovation literature definitions

Definitions	Sources
"new products, services or methods that tackle pressing and emerging social issues and, at the same time, transform social interactions promoting new collaboration and relationships"	[33]
"innovative activities and services that are motivated by the goal of meeting a social need and that are predominantly developed and diffused through organisations whose primary purposes are social."	[34]
"Social innovation is an important new field which should be nurtured. It is about tapping into the ingenuity of charities, associations, and social entrepreneurs to find new ways of meeting social needs which are not adequately met by the market or the public sector. It can also be about tapping into this same ingenuity to bring about the behavioural changes which are needed to tackle the major societal challenges, such as climate change. As well as meeting social needs and tackling societal challenges, social innovations empower people and create new social relationships and models of	European Commission ³⁰³

³⁰³ https://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union/pdf/innovation-union-communication_en.pdf

Definitions	Sources
collaboration. They are thus innovative in themselves and good for society's capacity to innovate."	
"Social innovations are changes in the cultural, normative or regulative structures [or classes] of the society which enhance its collective power resources and improve its economic and social performance."	[35]
"Unlike the terms social entrepreneurship and social enterprise, social innovation transcends sectors, levels of analysis, and methods to discover the processes—the strategies, tactics, and theories of change—that produce lasting impact."	[36]

Digital Social Innovation (DSI), in particular, brings together two prominent trends: new digital technologies and innovation aiming at creating a social impact. It leverages ICT for addressing societal and environmental challenges by pursuing synergies between both the public and the private sectors, as well as by involving citizens as co-creators of solutions [37].

People are considered as carriers of knowledge, which can be further exploited through ICT. Online collaboration platforms play a crucial role in unlocking this implicit knowledge, by allowing citizens to contribute to societal challenges [37]. DSI aims to³⁰⁴:

- Improve lives and reorient technology towards more social ends through harnessing ICT,
- empower citizens to use their collective knowledge in order to create a positive impact.

Nowadays, there are some organisations that promote social innovation; Nesta is one of them. It is a UK's innovation foundation which aims to support innovation for the public good [38], and is jointly with the EU developing "Digital Social Innovation for Europe - DSI4EU" which is a research project aiming at fostering efforts of stakeholders interested in this approach [37].

DSI stands at the intersection of three terms: digital, social and innovation. The social dimension includes the notion that technology is a means to addressing social challenges [37]. Some definitions of DSI are presented in the table below.

Table 4-3 Digital social innovation literature definitions

Definitions	Sources
"Just as digital platforms are changing how we work, shop and have fun, there's a new opportunity for communities to become a part of decision-making processes and tackle social challenges. Technology is being used to mobilise the crowd, pool resources and engage the creativity of the general public. We call this phenomenon DSI"	Peter Baeck, NESTA's head of collaborative economy research ³⁰⁵ .

³⁰⁴ <https://digitalsocial.eu/about-the-project>

³⁰⁵ <https://www.pioneerspost.com/news-views/20170721/how-digital-social-innovation-re-engaging-people-politics>

Definitions	Sources
DSI is "a type of social and collaborative innovation in which innovators, users and communities collaborate using digital technologies to co-create knowledge and solutions for a wide range of social needs and at a scale and speed that was unimaginable before the rise of the Internet".	[38]

Additionally, [39] identified six primary domains of digital social innovation: 1. The Collaborative Economy, 2. New ways of sensing, 3. Open democracy, 4. Awareness networks, 5. Open Access, 6. Funding and Incubation. Awareness networks are also a set target of ChildRescue. Dissemination is strengthened in order to make the ChildRescue initiative known to the public. Several promotion campaigns have already been implemented (refer to WP5 deliverables) to raise awareness.

Moreover, as far as the EU is concerned, DSI4EU which is supported by the European Union and funded under the Horizon 2020 Programme, is part of the CAPS (which is analysed below) community. Its main aim is to support and grow the current DSI network of projects and organisations³⁰⁶. More than 1047 projects and 1957 organisations have been engaged with DSI³⁰⁷. Of course, ChildRescue is one of them.

Below lie some examples of social innovation:

- The Internet to this day is one of the biggest social innovations. Everyone is able to participate in what it offers (e.g. information, social media, communication, and games)³⁰⁸.
- Ushahidi platform's mission is twofold: help marginalised people raise their voice and make the community listen to them and respond better³⁰⁹. It is often used for crisis response, citizen reporting/government accountability, and human rights reporting³¹⁰. It was employed in response to the Haiti Earthquake in 2010, (Ushahidi–Haiti Project) [40], and was also used to monitor violence in the Syrian civil war (Syria Tracker Crisis Map)³¹¹.
- ForestWatchers project tries to address the problem of fires and illegal logging. Individuals (locals, volunteers, NGOs, etc.) from all around the world, monitor selected patches of forest across the globe, almost in real-time. They do not need to have scientific training but they just perform or manage research-related tasks such as observation, measurement, or computation³¹².

³⁰⁶ <https://capssi.eu/caps-projects/dsi4eu/>

³⁰⁷ <https://digitalsocial.eu/projects>

³⁰⁸ <https://www.nesta.org.uk/news/everyday-social-innovations/world-wide-web>

³⁰⁹ <https://www.ushahidi.com/about>

³¹⁰ <https://techrasam.org/2017/07/06/ushahidi-a-data-collection-monitoring-and-visualization-software-for-the-humanitarian-and-development-industry/>

³¹¹ <https://www.ushahidi.com/case-studies/syria-tracker>

³¹² <http://forestwatchers.net/mission.html>

Of course, there is always the possibility of DSI initiatives to fail. Few out of the hundreds of DSI initiatives across Europe have grown to deliver positive social impact on a scale - and none has approached the comparable growth of commercial digital platforms³¹³.

Some indicative reasons digital social innovations fail are³¹⁴:

- projects and organisations involved in DSI are relatively poorly connected to each other,
- lack of funding and digital skills' shortage,
- adoption of established civil society organisations is too slow,
- conflict and lack of commitment between the partners.

Thus, there is much work to be done. There are several challenges to be tackled, such as³¹⁵:

- stakeholder engagement; ChildRescue success is directly dependent on the number of users that will be engaged – that is why the dissemination and communication efforts have already started from an early stage in the project,
- not enough understanding of growth routes and business models; ChildRescue organised a workshop in the 1st Plenary meeting on the ChildRescue business model to explore the existing possibilities and a business model canvas was also developed, though from the outset the project is not profit oriented,
- cooperation between partners; ChildRescue partners cooperate harmoniously so far, although there are different points of views, as is normal with so many different countries and scientific backgrounds. The convergence of different processes is also hindered by different organisations' operations, different practices and principles they follow, and their vision. Those differences are solved by discussion at the frequent teleconferences and Plenary meetings.

Contribution to ChildRescue

ChildRescue is consistent with the [33] definition, as it offers both a product (platform) and a service (methodology). According to the DSI description above, ChildRescue lies in the intersection of digital technology (platform), innovation process (platform and methodology), and society (challenge of finding missing children). Moreover, ChildRescue aims to engage more organisations (across Europe) in its platform that provide services similar to the services that REDCROSS, SoC or Child Focus provide to immigrants-minors or to the investigations of missing children. In this way, ChildRescue creates a communication channel between organisations that have similar objectives, or those whose objectives could be combined, achieving more effective collaboration among them. Thus, better cooperation and understanding of the organisations' procedures will be achieved.

4.1.3.2.3 *Collective Awareness*

According to [38], collective awareness platforms (collective intelligence) and crowdsourcing are in the scope of DSI. These platforms take advantage of a bottom-up approach, where knowledge is harnessed from the participating community.

³¹³ <https://www.nesta.org.uk/blog/taking-digital-social-innovation-to-the-next-level/>

³¹⁴ <https://www.nesta.org.uk/report/what-next-for-digital-social-innovation-realising-the-potential-of-people-and-technology-to-tackle-social-challenges/>

³¹⁵ <https://www.nesta.org.uk/blog/thousands-of-people-are-using-technology-to-tackle-social-challenges-but-whats-holding-digital-social-innovation-back/>

The term was introduced by the French sociologist Émile Durkheim in his *Division of Labour in Society* in 1893, in which he defines collective consciousness, or else collective awareness (French: conscience collective) as “the body of beliefs and sentiments common to the average of members of a society” [41].

With the ICT development, the term “collective awareness” has been revised and rephrased under several perspectives (e.g. human-computer interaction, computer-supported collaborative work, etc.) [42] and several definitions have been proposed, depending on the adopted perspective. Some proposed collective awareness definitions which reflect its evolution, along with alternative terms describing neighbouring concepts with that of collective awareness - which is mainly adopted by the European Commission -, such as collective intelligence, wisdom of the crowd, lie on the table below.

Table 4-4 Definitions relevant with the term Collective Awareness

	Definition	Source
Collective Awareness	“Collective awareness refers to a common and shared vision of the whole team’s context which allows members to coordinate implicitly their activities and behaviours through communication”.	[43]
	“The Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation (CAPS) are ICT systems leveraging the emerging ‘network effect’ by combining open online social media, distributed knowledge creation and data from real environments (‘Internet of Things’) in order to create awareness of problems and possible solutions requesting collective efforts, enabling new forms of social innovation.”	European Commission ³¹⁶ [33]
Collective Intelligence	“Collective Intelligence is built on the concept that when large groups of individuals cooperate higher-order intelligence, solutions and innovation can be produced while coming to function as a new individual entity, appearing to have a mind of its own.”	[44]
Wisdom of the Crowd	Wisdom of crowds is based on the idea that “a group will not always give you the right answer but that on average it will consistently come up with a better answer than any individual could provide”	[45]

In the context of the present deliverable, the approach of the EC is adopted, where collective awareness is achieved through ICT systems leveraging the network effect. ChildRescue ambition is based on the same background; creating an ICT platform that harnesses the network effect; the more users use it, the more effective it is.

³¹⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/eip/ageing/events/collective-awareness-platforms-sustainability-and-social-innovation-information-day_en

CAPS

CAPS (Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation) is a Horizon 2020 programme funded by the EC and launched in 2013, which has the aim of helping grassroots initiatives that contribute to societal change by harnessing the existing but also the emerging network technologies, by mainly using a bottom-up strategy [38].

CAPS initiative is pioneering new models to raise awareness of emerging challenges and of the role that people can play to ease them through collective action. It aims at developing online platforms to raise awareness on sustainability problems and implementing collective solutions. Its objective is to harness the collaborative power of ICT networks to create collective awareness alongside with enabling collective solutions. CAPS approach is based upon: 1) Taking advantage of the ICT network effects, e.g. using crowdsourcing, thus achieving collective intelligence, integrating human networks; 2) Setting sustainability as a goal, targeting beyond profit, tackling social challenges³¹⁷.

CAPS intend to enable citizens to³¹⁸:

- share their knowledge,
- make better informed decisions,
- create more participatory processes.

Some CAPS projects relevant to ChildRescue are³¹⁹:

- MAZI: a DIY networking toolkit for location-based collective awareness,
- CAP4Access: methods and tools for collectively gathering and sharing spatial information for improving accessibility,
- Families_Share: a social networking and awareness-raising platform dedicated to encouraging childcare and work/life balance.

Regarding motivation for a user to use CAPS, the results from [46] showed that social identity (18%), social comparison (18%), and altruism (17%) are the main motives, while monetary incentives (14%) and social approval (11%) follow. Desirability bias (9%), gamification (7%) and reputation (5%) give less incentive to users to use CAPS.

Contribution to ChildRescue

Compassion and urge to be of assistance when there is a need are elements of human nature. Improvement of society can be achieved through collective efforts of individuals [47]. ChildRescue is based on that concept, taking advantage of this natural trend, giving users the opportunity to altruistically act for the common good (i.e. find a missing child), which is inherently a collaborative task [48].

Some of the motivations for a user to use CAPS have been presented above. People sometimes want to selflessly contribute to societal problems without necessarily seeking financial profit, but they lack the knowhow or the means to do so. This is also the case for the missing children problem. Today, people contribute to missing children cases by informing the competent authorities, if they happen to

³¹⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/collective-awareness-platforms-sustainability-and-social-innovation-caps>

³¹⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/collective-awareness>

³¹⁹ <https://capssi.eu/caps-projects/>

be informed about them. ChildRescue adds value to the current processes by making it possible for the users - combining the collective awareness/intelligence concept with geo-fencing techniques to engage users according to their location - to instantly and at any time have all the necessary information about a case, so that if there is an opportunity, they can be of assistance to such cases. Thus, users' collective intelligence is exploited in the best possible way for the resolution of a missing child's case.

Finally, ChildRescue is a CAPS project³²⁰, based on the bottom-up strategy, which aims at effectively and timely raising collective awareness during the investigation of missing children, as well as supporting the identification of missing unaccompanied refugee minors. It also:

- gives individuals the opportunity to contribute in the missing children investigation process, encouraging them to share the crucial knowledge they might have,
- harnesses information from the crowd, which otherwise might be omitted, so that the location of a missing child is found more quickly,
- allows to make better decisions considering the people's testimonies.

4.1.3.3 Behavioural and Activity Profiling Theories and Research Review

While cases of missing persons, especially missing children, receive a high amount of media attention, research on the topic of finding missing persons is scarce, especially in the European context. While there have been studies on the impact of the amber alert in the US, there is a lack of research for Europe, with the exception of Shalev Greene/Hedges study on the usefulness of child alert systems in the Netherlands, UK, Czech Republic and Poland [49], which found that experts in the field agreed that the Internet and Social Media were rather effective in both raising awareness about as well as recovering a missing child [49].

Additionally, 16-24 year olds reported in 2016 to spend on average 29 hrs/week on the internet and 99 per cent reported using social media at least once a week, with social media accounting for 27 per cent of their total communication time [50]. Comparing data over time shows a trend for an increase of the social media use of adolescents, rendering a social media analysis increasingly useful in understanding and predicting behavioural patterns of children and adolescents, which has been utilised by market research to predict spending patterns or health studies to gain insights into risk behaviour [51]. With children and adolescents spending more and more time on the internet and specifically on social media applications, the analysis of social media data should be utilised in the search for missing children to predict potential points of interest. However, while the sheer mass of data generated constantly, offers a unique opportunity to understand individual choices as well as social group dynamics that can assist in identifying the location of missing persons, data mining is needed in order to make sense of the data pool. Thus, "Data mining research has successfully produced numerous methods, tools, and algorithms for handling large amounts of data to solve real-world problems. Therefore, data mining has become an integral part of many application domains including bioinformatics, data warehousing, business intelligence, predictive analytics, and decision support systems. The primary objectives of the data mining process are to effectively handle large-scale data, extract actionable patterns, and gain insightful knowledge. Nowadays, social media is widely used for various purposes. Vast amounts of user-generated data exist, and it can be made available for various kinds of analysis. There is no doubt that to utilize such data in social media is the key to improve various business processes" [52]. Data mining

³²⁰ <https://capssi.eu/caps-projects/childrescue/>

processes utilise the so-called 'big data', which are "proliferating and complex data sets that can be open or shared online" [53]. Through the increased use of smart phones and social media more specifically, and the vast amount of data willingly shared by individuals with the public, the analysis of big data becomes increasingly relevant [51] and can be adopted to help find missing persons. However, as there is still a severe lack of research on the use of social media analysis through a computer based big data analysis or sentiment analysis, this report will refer to connected fields of interest and findings from those areas as well as studies on child alert systems more generally. Additionally, due to the 2016 change in EU data protection law, namely regulation 2016/679 called the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the analysis of available data has been restricted since most platforms have minimised the amount of publicly available data to analyse. Albeit sentiment analysis or a general big data analysis can be crucial for the recovery of missing children, the underlying theory needed for the correct prediction of behaviour based on online interactions is the network theory, specifically the activity theory as well as the subcultural theory. Both the activity theory as well as the subcultural theory focus on the importance of social interaction for individual decision-making processes. However, the subcultural theory, which follows the school of thought of Cohen (1955), who observed that youth in gang structures obeyed to different norms and valued certain behaviours with respect that were looked down upon in mainstream society, thus forming a separate subculture with alternative norms and values [54]. This can offer a valuable insight into the behaviour of runaway youths as well as refugee minors, who have been reported missing, as they often find themselves in unofficial networks with deviant behavioural rules. As children and adolescents are heavily influenced by the norms of their groups of friends, or social networks [55], the analysis of those networks and their respective norms and rules is essential for a successful prediction of behaviour. In contrast, the activity theory focusses more on the interaction of humans and the way those shape individual behaviour. "Activity theory centres on mediation and the concept that the way humans undertake an activity is influenced by the environment around them and their ability to develop an understanding based upon previous experiences in order to make logical actions. This mediation is man-made in that the tools which influence a subject have been developed by the subject or other people who have previously worked in the same context"[56]. Thus, the empirical approach to identifying potential points of interest for the children is intrinsically linked to a theoretical base that centres on the relationship between the individual actor and their (social) environment.

While most cases of children who were reported missing have either run away or been abducted by a non-custodial parent [57], all cases are time-sensitive as the risk of victimisation of the child increases over time. In cases of child abductions that result in murder, almost half of the victims are killed within the first hour of the abduction and close to 80 per cent are murdered within three hours of being taken, making a quick recovery a matter of life and death [58]. In these time sensitive scenarios, the question of the most effective approach to analysing the data and spreading the information to the most crucial people arises. As "[h]umans have a limited amount of time per day to dedicate to social interaction, which poses a limit on the effort one can invest in persuading an acquaintance to act. Further, time pressure can affect the way in which people process environmental information. Consequently, people may be expected to resort to so-called blind search, focusing simply on the recruitment of as many acquaintances as possible via broadcast messaging. However, while this strategy may be effective at delivering the message to a broad audience, it results in lower effort in finding and mobilizing those recruits that have high affinity with the task (due to their location or other characteristics), and are therefore more likely to propagate the message or participate in the required action" [59]. In the study

by Rutherford et al., which used the social media app Twitter, the team was able to find three of the five actors who posed as 'thieves' all over Europe and the US within 12 hours and only a staged mugshot to distribute by utilising social media and a "recursive incentive mechanism that encourages recruitment" [59]. Consequently, ChildRescue aims at targeting points of interests and the people located there as they can be considered to have the described high affinity with the task and to combine predictive methods of analysing the data of the social media accounts with the effort of targeted recruitment. There are a variety of algorithms available to analyse mass data, such as social media data, which is currently mostly used for market analysis purposes but could be projected onto other topics. The following graphic shows different categories of analysis and the corresponding variety of algorithms to choose from depending on the method that is most appropriate for the research, giving an insight into the variety of possibilities:

Table 4-5 Different Categories of analysis and corresponding algorithms [60]

Categories of analysis and selection of algorithms	
<i>categories of analysis</i>	<i>algorithms (examples)</i>
classification	Decision Trees, Neural Networks, Bayesian Models, Induction Rules, K-Nearest Neighbours
Regression	Linear Regression, Non-Linear Regression, Logistic Regression
Anomaly Detection	Distance based, Density based, Local outlier Factor (LOF)
Time Series	Exponential Smoothing, Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) Regression
Clustering	K-Means, Density based Clustering
Association Analysis	Frequent Pattern Growth (FP-Growth) Algorithm, Apriori Algorithm

For the purpose of the ChildRescue project, the differentiation between cases of missing children, as suggested by Missing Children Europe (MCE) in Runaways, abductions by third persons, (international) parental abductions and missing unaccompanied minors [61], shall be used. The phenomenon of missing children is thus one of a vast variety that calls for nuanced approaches and cannot be explained with a 'one-fits-all' solution. Hence, the ChildRescue project will advance the theoretical understanding and the timely solution of missing children cases by utilising various theoretical approaches to enlighten the situation of the different case types as explained in D2.1. ChildRescue has therefore analysed the state-of-the-art knowledge through literature reviews to collect best practice examples, which have been refined with different theoretical approaches to the topic in order to provide the appropriate academic foundation. Albeit summarised under the same umbrella term of missing children, abductions and runaways need different theoretical approaches to account for differing levels of agency and threat. Although some theories, such as the social network theory, might be applied to various case types, different aspects of the theory will be in focus. For example, in the case of runaways, the social network theory could be utilised to find out more about the key people in the adolescents life in order to establish points of interest or potential contact sources, while the social network theory can also be applied to

cases of third-person abduction to gain a better understanding of grooming processes online. Additionally, the theories can be linked to computational strategies, such as sentiment analysis or graph theories to be utilised in a practical application as envisioned by the ChildRescue project. The following table will illustrate theories that might be useful in the explanation of these phenomena and could be applied in the course of the ChildRescue project:

Table 4-6 Different types of missing children cases and appropriate theories

Categories of missing children cases and theories	
Missing Children Case Type	Theories (examples)
Runaways	Subcultural Theory, Activity Theory, Social Network Theory
Third-person abductions	Social Network Theory, Victimology
Parental Abductions	Activity Theory, Social Network Theory
Missing unaccompanied minors	Subcultural Theory, Activity Theory, Collective Behaviour Theory

These theories have been successfully applied to the information that was gathered in expert interviews in D2.1, thereby validating the selection of underlying theories as well as the need to differentiate between case types. In order to determine the case type, the knowledge of the experts handling the case is needed, since the categorisation depends on expertise and a deeper understanding of behavioural patterns. Through the data entry into the platform, the staff members of the NGOs will have a possibility to assess these pieces of information in a more structured fashion and thus have an improved overview in the decision-making process. While the selected theories will not be applied to each individual case during the time-sensitive response to a missing child, they are vastly useful as an underlying base to establish a scientifically sound approach of the ChildRescue project.

4.1.4 Human Mobility Patterns

Human mobility refers to the movement of human beings, either individuals or in groups, in space and time. Human mobility patterns reflect many aspects of life and while earlier movement patterns were primarily driven by factors such as the climate change, inhospitable landscapes and food scarcity, in modern times, socio-economic factors, such as the living conditions and globalisation, play an increasingly crucial role in the analysis and understanding of collective mobility and mobility patterns. In a microscale, though, humans are moving daily in order to earn their living and carry out their social and leisure activities, with the former displaying a highly periodic behaviour and the latter introducing a random aspect in individuals' daily trips. The patterns extracted from this daily behaviour are outlining the regularities and recurrence that characterise human lives. Therefore, depending on the context and purpose of the analysis, the temporal and spatial scales of the human trips under examination may vary significantly.

Analysing, understanding and predicting the displacements of individuals in space and time is not new in research. Quantitative and theoretical geography has been occupied with this question from 1950's

[62], with the first efforts in capturing human displacements focusing on aggregated levels of movements between spatial units, while later studies introduced gradually analysis of individual trajectories. With the advent of technology though and the widespread adoption of mobile phones, as well as the pervasive usage of GPS technology, in the beginning of the 21st century, there was also an explosion of extensive geolocated datasets related to human movement, resulting in the subsequent rejuvenation of the scientific interest in human mobility. Scientists are now able to quantitatively study individual and collective mobility patterns, and to generate models that can capture and reproduce the spatiotemporal structures and regularities in human trajectories.

Nowadays, the study of human mobility is a highly and inherently interdisciplinary effort, occupying the interest of different academic communities, from physicians, psychologists, data analysts, health research analysts, and so on. In that view, it is evident that bridging these works is essential for advancing both the theoretical and practical aspects of such an analysis [63].

The interest in this research area is also reflected in the academic literature and the growing quantity of research papers published in this subject throughout the years. To illustrate this, Figure 4-4 showcases the number of papers in Google Scholar mentioning the keywords "human mobility", "mobility pattern(s)" and "human mobility" along with "simulation", for the years 2003-2018. It can be observed that there is a steady upward trend in the amount of publications mentioning these terms, highlighting that human mobility analysis is a very active research field, that by no means has it reached its scientific limits.

This review focuses on these later years and developments in order to draw insights on the state of the art of human mobility analysis and the current research questions that this analysis is facing.

Figure 4-4 Number of mentions of specific keywords in "Human Mobility" area for the years 2003-2018

In the following sections, the research area of human mobility patterns is analysed in two levels:

- First, typical human mobility, either of individuals or in groups, in a city-level, is examined, to draw conclusions on the factors that influence human mobility as well as the approaches that

describe human movements and flows in different scales. Analysing daily human movements, their periodicities and the laws that govern them which may translate into direction, distance, and dispersion of travel may be of great value in the development and final mission of ChildRescue, the determination of the location of a missing child. In particular, it can be crucial in identifying, based on the citizens that have downloaded and are using the app, the coverage of a geographic area by "social sensors" and their probable next movements, not in an individual level, but instead the locations and dynamics of future human movement in an aggregate level. This insight can then be used to understand the possibilities of on time locating a missing child or to early identify the need to intensify the calls for help or activate a broader community of volunteers in the investigation.

- At a second level, the landscape analysis in this field will focus on human mobility patterns of missing persons and specifically missing children, in order to examine how literature has approached this sensitive and with large degrees of freedom problem, that as expected is highly governed by the psychological status, the physical state and the sociological profile of the person lost. Insights from such an analysis can be directly exploited in the adaptation of the ChildRescue methodology and specifically the "Preparation & Profiling" phase.

4.1.4.1 Human Mobility Patterns in a city-level

4.1.4.1.1 Data sources

A number of different types of empirical data have been used in the study of human mobility. Empirical are considered the data and the respective information that has been acquired by observation or experimentation. These data are used to analyse both individual and aggregate mobility in order to adjust and validate models and their parameters. In this section, the main data sources that have been used throughout the years in mobility research, and the information extracted from them, are outlined. The data sources are presented in approximate chronological order relative to their historical availability and consequent use in research.

Census data are one of the first types of data that have been analysed to understand mobility flows, referring to data collected in periodical national surveys in which householders are asked questions about the sociodemographic and economic status of the household members [64], [65]. However, the opportunities for exploitation of census data were not common and were not applied at the same time across countries, since national censuses were introduced at different times in the various countries, and the information collected varied too in the beginning. Nowadays, census data in most cases include information on the location of the workplace, the place of current and previous residence and statistical data on the hours usually worked by employed persons. These data can then be used to estimate commuting and internal migration flows within a country and in most cases, they are combined and associated with other types of data, such as mobile phone data, as presented below, to increase the accuracy of the resulting models.

Following, chronologically, census data, currency circulation data have also been examined in the academic literature as a potential source of mobility data for inferring human mobility, as was the case of Brockmann et al. study [66] where they obtained 464,670 dollar bills from a specific website containing entries of timestamped reports of the geographic location of individual bills. A disadvantage, though, of this source, is that, although a large-scale source of mobility data, it proved to be problematic

in identifying mobility in an individual's level as the trajectories of bank notes are likely a convolution of the mobility of several individuals [67].

Mobile phones came afterwards introducing a whole new era in human mobility research. Mobile phone adoption and usage enjoyed an unprecedented success concerning the great majority of the earth's population [68]. Thus, information extracted from their usage was able to reproduce in a great extent both individual and aggregate human mobility. As an example, Bagrow et al. [69] used mobile phone billing data to track people's communication in 8 emergency events and 8 non-emergency events and identify behavioral changes in human activity and mobility under extreme conditions, for this information to be potentially applied for emergency detection and response. Call Detail Records (CDRs) are the most widely used mobile phone data in human mobility study, referring to detailed records of customer information related to their calls and text messages. CDRs include the time of the call or message as well as the telecommunication company's cell tower with which the phone was connected to route the communication. Given the fact that mobile phones are typically personal devices, CDRs allow for the extraction of individual mobility patterns, unlike census and currency tracking data. CDR data always include time stamp, caller ID, recipient ID, call duration and antenna (cellular tower) code. One of the first studies exploiting CDRs for Cellular Tower Data Analysis was in 2008 by Gonzalez et al. [70] where two anonymized dataset provided by a big mobile operator in Europe were analysed and useful information on individuals' mobility patterns were deduced, such as the distribution of displacements between the locations of consecutive calls. Most of the existing studies are based on mobile phone data to track human mobility [71]–[75]. Despite the great potential that CDR data provide in the study of individual mobility, there are also certain challenges that analysts must face. Firstly, mobility information extracted from CDRs may be limited, due to data sparsity, influencing the potentials of some approaches. Users location information is only available when they are initiating or receive some phone activity. Large CDRs datasets obtained may need to be restricted in a subset of them referring to users with very frequent phone activity, adding also a bias in the analysis. Despite data sparsity issues, data precision is also an issue in this case since it is the position of the cell tower routing the call that is recorded and not the exact location of the mobile phone user. Thus, location information in CDRs is limited to the coverage area of each mobile phone tower, typically around 1-3 km². CDRs may give a good understanding of the general patterns of human mobility over larger scales but may not be able to capture mobility changes in smaller scales (e.g. a neighbourhood)[76]. Therefore, in cases where location precision is needed, CDRs are not appropriate. It needs to be mentioned, also, that nowadays, privacy concerns and the new GDPR regulations have complicated even more the collection and analysis of mobile data even for research purposes.

Figure 4-5 Decomposition of the mobility profile over 10 days into daily mobility patterns for two anonymous mobile phone users. The home location of each user is highlighted and connected over the entire observation period with a grey line. While the entire mobility profiles (black circles and grey lines in the xy -plane) are rather diverse, the individual daily profiles (brown to red from bottom to top for different days) share common features.[72]

Global Positioning System (GPS) data are a data source that can surpass the problem of data precision, that mobile phone data are facing, and provide precise information on almost any location (covered by at least four GPS Satellites). GPS technology allows researchers to trace the movement of individuals at regular intervals with a very good accuracy. Therefore, there is no wonder for their extensive use to extract human mobility patterns. Microsoft has facilitated their use by making publicly available a GPS trajectory dataset collected in (Microsoft Research Asia) GeoLife project by 182 users in a period of over two years (from April 2007 to August 2012)³²¹. This dataset, since its release, has been used extensively in studies of human mobility [77], [78], providing also a subset of this dataset making distinction among the various transportation modes (i.e. driving, taking a bus, riding a bike and walking)³²², thus enabling support of transportation mode learning. In earlier research studies, GPS transmitters were attached to vehicles [79], [80]. In the study of [81], GPS data of 50 taxicabs' positions obtained automatically by GPS receivers were used, along with anonymized customer data as to when customers are picked up and dropped off, and the underlying street network, for a period of six months (October 2007, January – May 2008). Both the GPS data and the customer data were used to extract trails, namely the GPS trajectory, representing a movement from where one is picked up to where one is dropped off. GPS position traces are, as one might expect, heavily governed by the physical embedding of the road networks [82], and therefore are useful in the study of urban traffic and prediction and prevention of congestion [80]. Apart from the greater degree of accuracy over CDRs, GPS traces are recorded at a constant frequency, and they are thus able to reproduce individuals'

³²¹ <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/download/details.aspx?id=52367>

³²² <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/publication/gps-trajectories-with-transportation-mode-labels/>

trajectories. On the drawbacks of GPS data, there is the fact that GPS transmitters do not work indoors and periods with no signal received can be contained in the traces.

The incorporation of GPS and Wi-Fi chips in smartphones has introduced a whole, new, valuable source of location information; online social networking services. They are usually referred to as Online Social Network (OSN), or Location-Based Social Network (LBSN) services, where users share their current location by checking-in on websites such as Foursquare [83], [84], Facebook, Twitter [76], Gowalla [82], etc. Such social network providers collect, then, geotagged data every time a user enables localization of the content posted (e.g. a check-in at a bar with friends), along with the social connections of the user. The list of locations that a user has visited, other than his home, over the period of the study, can be collected to build a mobility profile for the user. These profiles can be used to examine and analyse small-scale, intra-urban mobility and routines as well as global mobility/travel patterns [85], but also to analyse social network connections and assess social interactions among users [86]. In contrast to mobile phone data, location-based social networks go beyond simple location accuracy offering content-specific location data, by providing additional information like the physical context of the location, e.g. distinguishing between a check-in in the gym in the first floor of a building from a coffee shop in the ground level of the same building. Thus, they can be used to study mobility in a broader context, as is the case of Twitter data that have been used in applications, such as crisis management [87], [88], [89]. In order to keep and exploit this contextual information, the app-collected data needs to be combined with an appropriate spatial division of the city that reserves the physical context of locations. Even though online social networking data contain valuable pieces of information in the study of human mobility, as being actively triggered by the user, are usually more scattered than GPS data, which are passively and regularly collected and therefore may retain the whole user's path. Furthermore, these data usually require extensive cleaning before their processing, while special attention needs to be paid in the avoidance of biases in the selection of the dataset and the validation of the obtained results, since the users under study and their actions may not be representative of the general population, as some studies indicate [90]. Additionally, due to uneven use of the application by users, app-collected data are heterogeneous both in spatial and temporal domain [91] and therefore require proper handling.

Nowadays, that GPS receivers are embedded in almost all smartphones and all smartphone operating systems offer free mapping and navigation service that require data connection (e.g. Google Maps Navigation, Apple Maps), the use of mobile phones as navigational services has overtaken the use of standalone GPS devices³²³. This fact enables the emergence of a novel source of data containing social and demographic information, capturing locations of travel with high spatial precision and covering long time periods. This is the case of Google Location History data, that has only lately been used in human mobility research [92]. Google Location History data consist of geographic coordinates regularly recorded by Android mobile phones that are also associated with a specific user account, containing demographic, personal information about the user. In order to obtain such data, users have to download their associated data and provide them to the researchers along with an informed consent process, a fact that renders their collection for a large number of users challenging. Location in this data source is identified using a combination of phone's internal GPS and connected Wi-Fi devices and cell towers, and therefore contain a spatial and temporal resolution, not previously available, as

³²³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/GPS_navigation_device

depicted in Figure 4-6. Furthermore, the fact that Google Location History data are passively collected avoids bias that other, previously seen, data sources are facing. Their use in human mobility is, however, still quite limited and there are still open research questions to be addressed.

Figure 4-6 Retrieved from [92], showcasing the information niche that Google Location History occupies. On the left side, traditional mobility data are displayed, while on the right mobility data available with more recent technologies are depicted. Google Location History cover a broadness of time spans and spatial scales not previously available by only one data source.

4.1.4.1.2 Applications

The generation of realistic spatio-temporal trajectories of human mobility is of fundamental importance in a wide range of applications. A large amount of research has been devoted to understanding the empirical patterns governing pedestrian movement, especially in cases where large concentrations of people occur, such as during festivals, sports events or religious ceremonies, to be able to ensure prompt evacuation in cases of emergency when considering the configuration of new buildings, public spaces and transport systems. Therefore, applications in that respect, may benefit a wide range of disciplines, including architecture, urban planning, traffic forecasting, and public service stakeholders [93], [94], [95]. On the other side of pedestrian movement, long-range transportation over thousands of kilometers, mainly represented by air and sea transportation is also studied a lot in order to better understand global connectivity, migration patterns and even the propagation and global spread of infectious diseases [96]–[99].

One of the more important and much studied applications of mobility is the intra-urban mobility, which is also the focus of interest for ChildRescue, since the great majority of missing children cases are of a city-level concern. Furthermore, the main reason for studying the human mobility research area in the context of ChildRescue has to do with the better understanding of the movements, within a city and on a daily basis, of citizens, that will have downloaded the ChildRescue mobile app and are considered as “social sensors”. Intra-urban mobility has gained much research attention firstly due to the fact that an increasing part of the global population is living in urban areas, as well as due to the availability of data

stemming from this fact (e.g. more mobile phone users, high densities of phone antennas). Other studies have also focused on the influence the area of residence has on intra-urban mobility [84], [100], highlighting the influence of a number of parameters, such as built environmental factors, the effect of population size or the morphology [101] on the travel distances and mobility patterns. The output of such research studies may afterwards be used on city planning [102], traffic forecasting [103] and location-based recommendations [104]. Other studies have also explored human mobility in disasters and emergencies [76]. Indeed, human mobility patterns reflect many aspects of life and have been exploited in many different applications, focusing on human mobility from different viewpoints.

4.1.4.1.3 *Metrics for pattern identification*

The term "human mobility patterns", and the "patterns" especially, is a quite generic term aiming to describe any trends that the data reveals, correlations among variables, groups that may show a certain behaviour, etc. In general, graphic displays are useful for seeing patterns in data, in a first level, but pattern identification can go much further than that. In this section, the most prominent metrics that are being used and measured to interpret human mobility and identify patterns are presented. Firstly, one of the key factors in modelling human mobility is the distance travelled by an individual. Different measures of distance are met in the literature, with terms such as flight length, jump length, displacement, and trip, where their definition may vary depending on the case and the source of data being used. One can, for example, may define the displacement of individuals between two locations, where the locations reflect places where they stop and spend a minimum amount of time [79]. The term stop, however, needs attention since it needs to be verified that a "stop" reflects a specific behaviour and does not come as a result of miscollection of data (i.e. oversampling or undersampling). Another measure that is frequently found in the academic literature is the "radius of gyration", rg , defined as the root mean square distance of a set of points from a given axis [70]. The radius of gyration is a measure to characterize the typical distance travelled by an individual and it depends both on the mutual distance of the locations visited and, on the time, spent (or the total number of visits) in each location. However, the radius of gyration does not allow a better understanding of the locations frequently visited by an individual. For example, if an individual's most visited locations, e.g. his home and his work, happen to be far from each other, then the individual will display a high rg , which will be also the case if the individual's most visited locations are close to each other, but he/she tends to visit a lot of other, distant places within a day.

Thus, it is evident that it is also important to be able to distinguish between locations based upon their importance when considering mobility patterns for a specific individual. As already mentioned, people tend to return home daily and thus most daily and weekly trajectories will start and finish at the same location. Evaluation of the importance of a location could be done with the use of ranks; 1 for the most visited location (e.g. home or work), 2-3 for e.g. a school, etc. [70]. The use of a network to design an individual's mobility pattern is also a method of distinguishing between locations [72].

When it comes for aggregated mobility and models of aggregate flow, the Origin–Destination (OD) matrix T is the frequently used, providing an estimate of the number of individuals traveling between locations in a given area, over a given period of time. More precisely, an OD matrix is a $n \times m$ matrix where n is the number of different "Origin" zones, m is the number of "Destination" zones, and T_{ij} is the number of people traveling from zone i to zone j . Traditionally, zones are administrative units, whose size may vary from census and electoral units to entire municipalities, departments or states,

depending on the study and question raised. OD matrices are important when developing models of human mobility at the population level, rather than individual level. [105]

As for now, the metrics that have been discussed reflect mainly the concepts of distance travelled and time elapsed within trips/stops. Another feature is that of speed. Although at first glance the time spent on a given trip might be considered proportional to the distance travelled, the transportation mode has to be also taken into account, which is, though, also dependent on the distance. For a small distance travel, slow transportation modes with many stops, such as walking or public transportation might be utilised, while for longer distances the stops are more rare and other modes of transportation, such as trains and planes, are usually chosen [106], [107]. It needs to be noted, though that mobility, as already mentioned, is multimodal, meaning that it occurs over multiple spatio-temporal scales. Therefore, studies need to also account for the effect of multimodality, especially when it comes for large cities with multi-modal transportation system. Indeed, the transition between different modes of transport necessarily implies a temporal cost that increases in proportion to the complexity of a trip (e.g. number of modes) [108].

4.1.4.2 Human Mobility in missing children

The area of human mobility when it comes for missing children and their mobility patterns, although questioned a lot from the governmental and non-governmental organisations that are occupied with cases of missing children, is not well-represented in the academic literature, while it is mostly analysed from the perspective of victimology and criminology [109] or child forensic psychology [110].

There are, however, recent studies, that has been occupied with the question of the movement and mobility patterns of a missing person. In Wilderness Search and Rescue, which is often found in the literature with the abbreviation WiSAR, a probability distribution map of the likely location of a missing person is used, guiding the coordination decisions of the search and rescue phase. In [111], a Bayesian model is proposed that uses publicly available terrain features data to model lost person behaviours. Models, as such, however, although they model a number of environmental effects, does not incorporate state-dependent effects, such as the perception of the missing person, his/her fatigue, or behavioural effects. In [112], the authors progressed from that by developing an agent-based model of missing person behaviour, incorporating the effects of the environment, as well as the goals and perception of the missing person on his/her movement. The developed model was then validated, by comparing the simulated trajectories with actual trajectories of participants in an unfamiliar wilderness environment. Other studies have come up with other interesting inferences related to the mobility patterns of missing persons, stemming from their research and experimentation, such as the fact that a missing person tend to walk in a straight line [113], or that a lost person will walk up to a high place, to have a better view of the surroundings [114].

The aforementioned studies, however, apply in cases of missing people, in general, that are lost and try to find their way back. They do not take into account the special characteristics of missing children cases. The case of a missing child's mobility and the potential locations where the child might be is a complex issue, raising a number of research challenges. A child may disappear for a variety of reasons, analysed in five categories according to the MCE distinction that ChildRescue adopts; runaways, stranger abductions, international parental abductions, missing unaccompanied migrant minors, and lost, injured, or otherwise missing children. Therefore, each case, depending on its categorisation and the special characteristics that the case pertains to, may require different means to be resolved. Analysis and statistics from past cases of missing children in Europe and globally may shed light to patterns

related to specific missing children cases, the profile and the options/potential decisions of the child and the profile and the potential decisions of the abductor, if relative. The decision on the categorisation of the case, however, can also be challenged, since it relies mainly on the child's parent's or legal guardian's subjective judgement, knowledge of the situation and his/her mental state, rather than, in a definite manner, the actual situation the child is facing [115].

4.1.5 ChildRescue-relevant Technologies and Systems

4.1.5.1 Technologies and Systems for Missing People Identification

Private and public organisations all over the world have developed or adapted systems for designing and managing missing persons cases. Several examples of systems are included below.

In this version, the features of the identified technologies were updated, and further/new technologies were added.

Πίνακας 4-1 ChildRescue-relevant technologies and systems

S/N	Title	Operator / Developer	Description	Availability and Cost	Downloads /Links	Functionalities
1	National Missing and Unidentified Persons System (NamUs)	National Forensic Science Technology Centre	NamUs is an online, national centralised repository and resource centre for missing persons and unidentified decedent records. NamUs can be searched by medical examiners, coroners, law enforcement officials and the general public from all over the country in hopes of resolving these cases.	Free, but some sections are available only to public safety personnel	Access databases (requires registration): https://www.namus.gov/Dashboard#	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - national clearinghouse of information related to missing, unidentified, and unclaimed person cases - Case management, advanced searching, and automatic matching tools - scanning, classifying, uploading, analyzing, and comparing fingerprint information submitted to NamUs - DNA analysis <p>Other, functions such as (a) the ability to print missing persons' posters, (b) to receive free biometric collection and testing assistance and (c) links to medical examiner and law enforcement agencies</p>
2	National Emergency Child Locator Center (NECLC)	National Centre for Missing & Exploited Children (NCMEC)	NCMEC activates the NECLC to manage calls and a database relating to missing children for the event. Individuals reporting or searching for a child missing as a result of a disaster can call the NECLC at 1-866-908-9570 or 1-877-908-9570. NECLC is only activated at the request of a State to support Presidentially-declared disasters.	Free, available to public.	The NECLC can be accessed at https://www.missingkids.org/disasterresponse .	Call centre
3	American Red Cross Safe and Well website	American Red Cross	A free communication tool where survivors can register and post messages to indicate that they are safe, and where their family, friends, and colleagues can conduct a search to view those posted	Free, available to public.	Safe and Well can be accessed at https://safeandwell.c	That system includes the functions of (a) Register (those affected by disaster self-register on the site) and (b) Search friends and family (search

			<p>messages. During large-scale disasters, the site is heavily promoted in the media and at local call centres. Safe and Well will also be set as the home page on computers at Red Cross congregate centres and shelters in host and evacuation areas. The website is available in English and Spanish and has also been configured for smart phones, including Blackberry, Apple, and Android devices. Safe and Well users can update statuses on Facebook and via Twitter. The site is always available and can be used by the public. Safe and Well can be accessed at http://www.redcross.org/safeandwell</p>		<p>community.org/cms/index.php</p>	<p>the list and view the registrants' posted messages).</p>
4	Restoring Family Links	International Committee of the Red Cross	<p>Every year, thousands of family members are separated by conflicts, disasters or migration. People suffer terribly when they lose contact with their loved ones and don't know where they are or whether they are safe.</p> <p>The ICRC and National Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies work together around the world to locate people and put them back into contact with their relatives. This work includes looking for family members, restoring contact, reuniting families, and seeking to clarify the fate of those who remain missing.</p>	<p>Free, available to public.</p>	<p>Emergency Welfare Inquiries can be accessed at https://familylinks.icrc.org/en/pages/home.aspx</p>	<p>on-line tracing</p>

5	National Emergency Family Registry and Locator System (NEFRLS)	Disaster Assistance Improvement Program's (DAIP)	Established in the aftermath of Hurricanes Katrina and Rita, NEFRLS is a nationally-accessible, web-based system that facilitates the reunification of families separated or displaced by a disaster. It allows adults who have been displaced from their homes or pre-incident locations to voluntarily register and share specific information on their post-disaster well-being or location with designated family members. Family members and friends may search the database for a record created by a displaced individual. NEFRLS is activated when requested by a State following a Presidentially-declared disaster or mass evacuation event and operates on a 24/7 basis. It is accessible via 1-800-588-9822.	Free, available to public.	www.disasterassistance.gov	<p>Functions: (a) web - based system where people can voluntarily register and share specific information on their post-disaster well-being or location with specified family members and (b) the SMS service that notifies the individual when an official missing person report has been submitted, could be useful.</p> <p>However the system is not currently operating.</p>
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6	Lost Person Finder (LPF)	The National Library of Medicine (NLM)	<p>The LPF Project focuses on tools and technologies to enable family, friends, and neighbours to locate missing people during a disaster event. NLM initially created this web-based people finder software for finding people who were in hospitals after a disaster. After the Haiti earthquake, it was modified to allow public access for community-wide disasters.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PEOPLE LOCATOR® and ReUnite®—ReUnite is a free iOS/Android app that assists users reunifying families after disasters and can be used by the public to search and report missing or found persons including a field for their health status. Information gathered through this app is uploaded to the PEOPLE LOCATOR website https://pl.nlm.nih.gov, which features search and report as well, including an option for interactive notification information scrolling. • TriageTrak and TriagePic®—Healthcare services providers can use this website (TriageTrak) running on their own infrastructure and free reporting tool (TriagePic) to better respond to inquiries for missing persons after large scale casualty events. Report and search is flexible via Android and iOS apps and, in the enterprise, via a Windows 7 application. Service providers and their 	Free, available to public.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ReUnite can be downloaded at https://lpf.nlm.nih.gov/PeopleLocator-ReUnite. • TriageTrak and TriagePic can be downloaded at https://lpf.nlm.nih.gov/TriageTrak-TriagePic 	<p>That system provides functions to seekers to search the database and retrieve the information on their devices. In addition, the system will display pictures and other information on missing persons as well as health care services.</p> <p>ReUnite app is multiuser where parents and citizens can upload pictures of children, and provide detailed description like name, birth mark, address, report to the police station, search and identify missing kids. The photographs will not be saved in the mobile phone's physical memory. Amazon Rekognition, web facial recognition service, is being used to identify missing kids.</p> <p>TriagePic helps quickly gather photos and minimal information about disaster victims arriving at a perimeter triage station, particularly to assist with family reunification.</p> <p>Features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reports specify the disaster event, date and time, and (optionally) who is manning the triage station. ○ Photos are captured by the device camera(s), or from Pictures folder. ○ Mass-casualty IDs can be constrained to a desired format. ○ IDs can auto-increment, or be manually adjusted; alignable with pre-printed triage forms.
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			<p>partners can help provide faster and more accurate reassurance, and thus facilitate family reunification and enhance coordination with other disaster-responding non-governmental organisations and alleviate some of the workload on public health personnel and other responders who interact with the public.</p>			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Browse, sort, or filter reports sent from this device (in Outbox) ○ Likewise with reports sent from other devices (in All Stations). ○ Search by patient name or mass-casualty ID, or use more advanced filtering. ○ For a report of interest, view it in detail, edit, or delete. ○ Review statistics of sent reports as itemized charts. <p>Code for TriagePic for Windows Store (only) is available under an open-source license.</p>
7	Google Crisis Response	Google	<p>Person Finder and Crisis Map are Google's primary tools that support reunification. Google Person Finder allows individuals to post and search for the status of relatives or friends affected by a disaster. The program also lets press agencies, NGOs, and others contribute to the Post- Disaster Missing Persons Process database and receive updates by using the Person Finder application programming interface</p>	Free, available to public.	https://www.google.org/crisisresponse/resources.html .	Interoperability methodology among multiple applications (Google Earth, Google Fusion Tables, Google Person Finder, etc.)

			(API) based on the Person Finder Interchange Format (PFIF) open standard. Google Crisis Map provides a map for a specific incident that can show its location and capacity at shelters open for a disaster. Both products can be embedded in websites, and information can be downloaded and shared.			
8	Facebook Safety Check / Facebook Crisis Response	Facebook	<p>Facebook launched its Safety Check feature in 2014 that helps users inform friends and family that ask if they are safe. Users can click the “I’m Safe” button to notify family and friends of their status. The tool does not provide information to anyone other than users’ own networks of family and friends.</p> <p>Safety Check can be activated automatically by an influx of user posts and a confirmation from a third-party news or government source.</p>	Free, available to public.	https://www.facebook.com/about/safetycheck/	<p>Function and methodology of utilising social networks.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Safety Check is a feature that lets Facebook users tell friends and family members they’re safe during natural disasters, terrorist attacks, and other life-threatening incidents. - a mix of public Facebook posts, news articles, photos, and videos to keep people informed and up to date on a given crisis - the Community Help tool, is designed for coordinating help during a disaster - it also contain an all-new fundraising feature for supporting affected individuals and groups, as well as non-profits involved with relief efforts.
9	FBI National Crime Information Center (NCIC)	FBI	The NCIC system is an electronic clearinghouse of crime data that can be tapped from virtually every criminal justice agency nationwide. In operation since 1967, NCIC helps criminal justice professionals apprehend fugitives, locate missing persons, recover stolen property, and identify terrorists. This system is divided into 21 files, including a file for	Free, available only to law enforcement	http://www.fbi.gov/about-us/cjis/ncic	Function, fields and the methodology of keeping the “Missing Persons File”

			missing persons, a national sex offender registry, and an unidentified person's file.			
10	Unidentified Victim Identification System (UVIS)	New York City	New York City's UVIS is a comprehensive disaster management system that manages and coordinates all of the activities related to missing persons reporting and victim identification. In concert with New York City's 3-1-1 Call Center, the City of New York Office of Chief Medical Examiner, the New York Police Department, and other agencies throughout the city, UVIS enables a centralised communications and data collection system to support these processes. This coordinated system is essential to developing an accurate manifest of potential victims following a disaster—a critical first step in victim identification.	Developed with public funds, UVIS is available to municipalities, counties, states, and other governmental agencies without charge, under license from New York City.	www.nyc.gov/html/ocme/downloads/pdf/Special%20Operations/UVIS%20Information%20Guide_20090917.pdf	Functions: (a) Missing Persons module (detailed data filing), (b) Records module (handles requests for records from family members, lawyers, and public administrators) and (c) Field Operation module (helps users manage incidents, field investigation, and the collection of remains and evidence, as well as maintaining records and documentation about remains and evidence)
11	2-1-1 VIRGINIA Patient Locator System	211	In 2010, 2-1-1 VIRGINIA became the call center for the Virginia Hospital and Healthcare Association's Patient Locator and Family Reunification Centers. In a mass casualty event, 2-1-1 VIRGINIA can provide real-time information on the hospital location of victims to family and friends via a system that connects 2-1-1 with Virginia EMS and hospitals.	Free, not available to public.	http://www.211.org	Features: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ User access is assigned by organization contact(s) ○ Permissions to limit user access to Input or View only ○ Ability for organization's to send HL7 patient records via secure VPN connection ○ Ability to receive patient data from mobile triage hand-held devices ○ Ability to transfer patients to other facilities

						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Ability for the Regional Triage Officer to input and view patient data for any organization in their region ○ Patient data may be updated by users with Input permission or via HL7 data feed. All patient updates are stored as transactions and may be viewed from the patient detail page. ○ Patient data is available for Family Assistance Center (FAC) ○ Application tracks all user searches and page views ○ HIPPA compliant, strict permissions for Protected Health Information (PHI) and De-Identified Data (DID) - Database encryption of all PHI data
12	Radiant RFID	Texas Department of Public Safety	The Texas Department of Public Safety has an agreement with Radiant RFID (also known as Evacuation Tracking Network [ETN]) to use their system to track evacuees during a disaster. Evacuees meet at locations known as embarkation centres. Upon arrival, each adult and child is issued a wristband, and pets have tags attached to their collars. Both the pet and child bands are linked to their legal guardians in the database. Buses are equipped with global positioning system (GPS) locators to track the whereabouts of the vehicles and the individuals inside them. As the evacuees disembark the buses, their needs are assessed and a final location destination is determined. Each individual's information is retrieved using	Free, available to public.	http://www.rfidjournal.com/article/view/4443/2 .	Function of tracking and retrieval of information in the field

			a handheld scanner used to scan their wristbands.				
13	Lost Person Locator	DHS Science and Technology Directorate	The Department of Homeland Security Science and Technology Directorate (S&T), along with dbS Productions--known as the leading source of search and rescue research, publications, and training--has initiated a program to develop guidance, protocols and strategies responders can employ while searching for lost individuals. Called the Lost Person Locator, these guidelines and data sets will be readily available in an easy-to-follow format. First responders in the field will be able to use the Lost Person Locator software to quickly and safely locate missing people.	Free, available to public.	https://www.dhs.gov/sites/default/files/publications/R-Tech_Lost-Person-Locator-FactSheet_180103-508.pdf	<p>It is now available for download on Apple iTunes, Google Play and Amazon.com.</p>	<p>Features</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ an Initial Response Search Wheel [is a waterproof plastic guide for initial response and contains the seven most common subject categories (hiker, children, dementia, hunter, climber and mountain biker)] ○ Lost Person Behaviour App (provides step-by-step search guidance, investigative questions and statistics and behavioural profiles for more than 41 subject types—including lost hikers, children and dementia patients. It also identifies high probability areas where an individual may be found and has filters for ecoregion and terrain. For responders with limited SAR experience, the app offers knowledge gained from similar searches) ○ FIND software (integrates mapping, GIS, search theory and incident management. It predicts the likely locations of the subject, suggests the best deployment of teams, tracks teams and personnel and manages clues. Once a team debriefs, FIND updates all relevant information using GPS tracks and search theory, which can be fed into SARCAT) ○ Search and Rescue Collection Analysis Tool (it is a web-hosted application that simplifies the collection and analysis of search and

						rescue data. SARCAT integrates FIND data at the end of a search; all of the search data is automatically collected from FIND and placed into the SARCAT format to allow the search manager or incident commander to print out a detailed incident report).
14	Photo Missing Children (PhotoMC)	Microsoft	The Photo Missing Children, or PhotoMC, is an application designed to help find missing children through Microsoft's face recognition application program interface (API). The Microsoft Face API is a cloud-based service that uses advanced algorithms to scan images of faces for identifying features and determines the likelihood that two faces belong to the same person. It can scan a database of thousands of faces and return a list of possible matches within seconds. The API analyzes 27 different facial characteristics and can identify a person across multiple photos, even at different angles and with varying facial expressions.	Free, available to public.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://news.microsoft.com/features/lost-boy-fathers-search-microsoft-technology-helped-solve-four-year-mystery/ • https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/services/cognitive-services/face/ 	The face recognition system does not fall in the scope of ChildRescue.

15	The CHARLEY PROJECT	The Charley Project	The Charley Project profiles approximately 10,000 “cold case” missing people mainly from the United States. It does not actively investigate cases; it is merely a publicity vehicle for missing people who are often neglected by the press and forgotten all too soon. A person must have been missing for at least one year to be listed.	Free, available to public.	http://charleyproject.org .	That system does not fall in the scope of ChildRescue.
16	Fast and Efficient International Disaster Victim Identification (FASTID)	InterPol	<p>A project is under way to create the first ever police database to identify and link missing persons and unidentified bodies on an international level. The Fast and Efficient International Disaster Victim Identification (FASTID) Project was launched in 2010 with an overall budget of almost EUR 3 million.</p> <p>Led by INTERPOL and partly funded by the European Commission, the project will establish an international system to manage enquiries concerning missing persons and unidentified bodies in the event of disasters as well as day-to-day policing and will result in the creation of a global Missing Persons and Unidentified Bodies (MPUB) database.</p>	Free, available to police only.	https://www.iosb.fraunhofer.de/servlet/is/19908/	<p>Features: image based disaster victim identification module which supports the identification of persons based on images of body modifications (e.g. tattoos, scars, etc). Previous procedures are based upon a manual classification into a fixed set of categories which is often subjective, time-consuming and sometimes error-prone.</p> <p>By using state-of-the-art computer-based image retrieval techniques, this search can be carried out faster, more accurate and more detailed as images are no longer regarded as match if they are assigned to the same category (e.g. “dragon”) but only if they show the same dragon tattoo.</p> <p>That system does not fall in the scope of ChildRescue.</p>
17	Find People & Things	Instituto Superior para as Tecnologias de	This project aims to build an online platform to facilitate the process of finding missing people and objects. For this it is intended to use facial recognition techniques and information search on the	Free, available to public.	https://www.isutic.gov.ao	The face recognition system does not fall in the scope of ChildRescue.

		Informação e Comunicação - Luanda, Angola	platform. Once a person, documents or anything else is missing, the person concerned should go to the platform, submit a picture of the missing person or object accompanied by some information such as the place where the person disappeared. Also, if someone else finds a missing person or object, makes a submission with an image, the data of the person or object and the place where he/she/it was found. After that, it is the platform's responsibility to crosscheck the submission's validity and find all relevant information. If there is no crossover, the platform stores the inserted data, and in case another user finds a person or objects already registered as missing, the system informs the user.			
18	Face First	Face First	FaceFirst provides the best-in-class facial recognition software. With the FaceFirst face recognition platform, retailers, stadiums, transportation centres, law enforcement agencies and other organisations can detect and deter threats in real time, while also leveraging biometric data to personalise service and verify personal identity. Using artificial intelligence and machine learning, FaceFirst is highly accurate and scalable, offering a full range of surveillance, mobile access control and desktop forensic face detection capabilities. FaceFirst offers a	For Non Profit Organisations the licence is free.	https://www.facefirst.com	The face recognition system does not fall in the scope of ChildRescue.

			robust SDK/API for integration into a variety of systems and platforms.			
19	DEVPOST	DEVPOST	<p>DEVPOST is a web-based app that allows users to match their cloud photo repositories with a missing person database. Upon confident matches, the app will prompt identifications to the user for further investigation. In detail, the app can:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Get photo access authorisation from repositories (Google photos for the submission) - Identify distinct faces in each photo - Match each face with identities in the databases - Return photo pairs of 2 similar faces (and mark them) - Render paired results on the website and allow users to decide if we have a match 	Free, available to public.	https://devpost.com/software/finding-missing-people	The face recognition system does not fall in the scope of ChildRescue.
20	Find My Way Home Project	CUE Center for Missing Persons	This page is for persons who either know they were abducted or believe they were abducted, as small children, and raised by their abductors. It is very difficult for these people to come forward publicly for fear of retaliation from their abductor. Sometimes they don't know where to start – they can't remember their real name, where they were born, or anything	Free, available to public.	http://www.ncmissinpersons.org/resources-links/find-my-way-home-project/	That system does not fall in the scope of Child Rescue.

			that would help them find their family. Find My Way Home project is to provide support, raise awareness, and provide resources to help reunite long-term abductees with their birth families. The project is inspired by someone who was abducted as a child and is still searching for her birth family.			
21	ICMP Online Inquiry Center	ICMP - International Commission on Missing Persons	<p>ICMP's Online Inquiry Center (OIC) is a tool to provide information or obtain information about a missing person. It is an online resource that can be accessed by families of the missing and others.</p> <p>Developed on the basis of ICMP's long-standing record of helping governments, families of the missing and others, the OIC is a place where concrete and usable information is collected and stored so that it can be utilised when it is needed in the search for missing persons.</p>	Free, available to public except for the Postmortem Sample Inquiry that is available only to government authorities and forensic experts that participate in ICMP's DNA identification program.	https://oic.icmp.int/index.php?w=intro	<p>Functions: The Identification Data Management System (iDMS) is a specialised software solution for managing large scale missing persons programs. The iDMS has a set of powerful integrated applications that support the process of storing, viewing and analysing very large amounts of data on missing persons, investigations, and identifications.</p> <p>Three different search engines, including the "Missing Persons Inquiry," the "Postmortem Sample Inquiry," and the "Excavation Site Inquiry."</p>

22	LOST - Missing people in Europe	The program is implemented by 8 partners from Italy, Greece, Portugal, Spain, Belgium & Denmark.	LOST is a 2-year European innovative program dealing with the area of action of the response on disappearances, where different kind of professionals working on cases of missing children and adults would benefit from receiving specific training and support by technical operators & VET trainers. These kinds of professionals could be members of law enforcement agencies, the police force, secret services & civil protection, representatives of voluntary associations or NGO, personnel of Public local such as social assistants, psychologists who provide support to families, health professionals & legal doctors.	Free, available to public	http://lost.team#!/project	Currently that software is under development and it is not feasible to obtain more data.
23	National DNA Index System	FBI	FBI operates a database that stores DNA records, including missing adults' records and unidentified remains. NDIS contains approximately 15 million profiles in the five databases: offenders and arrestees database, forensic evidence database, missing unidentified human remains database, missing person database, and biological relatives of missing persons database. The biological relatives of missing persons database contains DNA profiles that are voluntarily submitted by the relatives of known missing individuals. Finally, the missing person database contains DNA records of missing persons	It is free but not accessible from the public. It has been foreseen a SOP for the public.	https://www.fbi.gov/services/laboratory/biometric-analysis/codis	That system does not fall in the scope of ChildRescue.

			obtained from their belongings or derived from the profiles of their relatives.			
24	Alert Systems (AMBER & SILVER)		Amber Alert systems are voluntary partnerships among law enforcement agencies, broadcasters, and transportation agencies to activate messages in a targeted area when a child is abducted and believed to be in grave danger or a senior is at risk. Silver alert systems were created out of concern for the safety of seniors and other at-risk adult populations who are prone to wandering due to a physical or cognitive disability or medical condition such as Alzheimer's or other forms of dementia.	Free, available to public.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.amberalert.gov/about.htm • https://www.amberalert.eu • https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Silver_Alert 	Function: "Wireless Emergency Alert program" of distributing information in multiple means of communication (mobiles, tv, internet, etc.)
25	Missing Children Database	Canadian Centre for Child Protection	This database contains a listing of nationally-registered missing children in Canada. A case remains open until the child is located.	Free, available to public.	https://missingkids.ca/app/en/missing_children_database	Function: "Missing-Person Record" in terms of methodology, fields and offline and online methods of research
26	The Australian Police Child ID App	The National Missing Persons Coordination	The National Missing Persons Coordination Centre (NMPCC) is a non-operational arm of the Australian Federal Police (AFP). The NMPCC was established in 2006 to drive national coordination in response to missing persons in Australia,	Free, available to public.	https://missingperson.gov.au	The App was designed and built by AFP based on software provided under licence by the FBI to help parents and guardians more easily collect and send important information about their child/children in the event of a disappearance or abduction.

		n Centre (NMPCC)	<p>and to complement the investigative role of State and Territory police. Among other services (support services, search agencies, helping with the search, etc.), they provide a range of prevention tools. An example of that is the Australian Police Child ID App, which is a free smartphone application. It is designed to help parents quickly provide personal identification information to police in the event that any of their children go missing.</p> <p>A smartphone application has been developed to help Australian parents provide information to police in an attempt to locate their children if they go missing.</p>			<p>The application allows families to store photographs and vital information about their children on their mobile phone. In the devastating event that a child goes missing, this information can be immediately provided to authorities.</p> <p>The application also includes safety advice and checklists for parents on keeping children safe, and information about what to do in the hours immediately after a child goes missing, and provides quick and efficient access to emergency contact phone numbers.</p>
27	ECAAS (European Child Alert Automated System)	The Smile of the Child	<p>The activation of AMBER/CHILD ALERT in Greece is implemented through ECAAS (European Child Alert Automated System). The picture of the missing child together with personal information (age, name, physical description etc.) are uploaded and the system develops all necessary dissemination material needed (video spot, radio spot, posters etc.). These are sent by email to partners responsible for disseminating the alert and informing the public about the disappearance of the child, including tv and radio stations, newspapers and specific web portals and social media channels.</p>	For internal use - activation of AMBER ALERT.	https://www.hamogelo.gr/gr/el/collaboration/european-child-alert-automated-system-ecaas/	<p>The ECAAS system standardises and distributes information in multiple means of communication (mobiles, tv, internet, etc.) very quickly.</p>

28	UK Child Rescue Alert system	Missing People, in partnership with CEOP, a command of the National Crime Agency and the technology provider, Groupcall.	The app is not active	Free, available to public.	https://apps.apple.com/gb/app/child-rescue-alert-uk/id878113168	-
29	SIGN4L	Missing Children's Network	<p>SIGN4L allows parents to have a complete database of information on their child, should they ever go missing. The parent photographs his/her child, fill his physical attributes, weight, height, colour of eyes, colour of hair, any particular characteristics — scars, allergies — and saves it electronically on his/her phone.</p> <p>Parents that find themselves in an emergency situation can send it to the authorities. You don't have to go home to find an up-to-date photo of your child or, in a state of panic, try to describe your child etc. The aim is to save time.</p> <p>The app does not ask for any personal information, such as where they go to school, so if the phone is lost or stolen, the child will not be put at risk.</p>	Free, available to public.	https://www.missingchildrensnetwork.ngo/	

			The bilingual SIGN4L (pronounced “signal”) application also provides tips on what to do and prompts parents to keep their kids’ files up to date.			
30	FIA Missing Child Alert	Federation for Internet Alerts (FIA)	The Federation for Internet Alerts (FIA) and its Partners and Supporting Authorities relay alerts for serious events such as child abductions or the imminent threat of a tornado, tsunami, or other hazard. Alerts are displayed immediately using the latest information from official authorities. FIA’s emergency alerts override or overlay other online messages to the public to display this urgent information to the areas directly impacted. The mission is to be a non-profit facilitator for internet technology and services collaboration among companies, non-governmental organisations, and alerting authorities to promote standards-based, all-hazards, all-media, authoritative alerting to individuals in societies worldwide.	Free	http://blog.internetalerts.org/	Features: geo-targeted notifications & cookie blocking emergency alerts
31	GMCNgin e	The International Centre for Missing and Exploited Children (ICMEC)	A global platform to help find missing and abducted children. The GMCNgin e combines artificial intelligence and digital advertising technology to help locate missing children vulnerable to exploitation, sexual abuse, and trafficking.	Free for organisations	http://www.icmec.org	The platform uses geo-targeting and dynamic ad insertion to get missing children alerts in front of the right communities at critical times. Meanwhile, machine learning and artificial intelligence models work around the clock to scour millions of images on the dark and clear web for matches or photos resembling the images of missing children, making it easier for law enforcement and non-government

						organisations to form new case leads and ultimately bring missing children home. GMCNgin uses Amazon Rekognition, an image and video analysis tool, to detect, analyze, and compare faces in imagery associated with open cases about missing children. In addition, technology partners like FIA, Web-IQ, First Factory, and Biometrica are providing critical services and round out the core team.
32	Safety Central – NCMEC	National Center for Missing & Exploited Children	Safety Central is designed to make sure that parents have the tools they need to help them protect their families and act quickly should their children go missing. At the core of Safety Central is a digital Child ID Kit. One of the most important tools for law enforcement when searching for a missing child is an up-to-date, good quality photo along with descriptive information. A Child ID kit is a simple yet effective way to keep those tools right at your fingertips. The app, which does not share any of your personal information, reminds you when it's time to update your photos and allows you to store potentially life-saving information about your children in an easily accessible location. Safety Central does much more than keep track of personal child ID kit. The citizen can download educational tips and resources from NCMEC's award-winning educational team, stay up to date on	Safety Central is a free download thanks to a generous gift from NCMEC's partner, EMCOR.	https://apps.apple.com/us/app/safety-central-ncmec/id1153098638	The Child ID kit

			<p>news and events and help law enforcement find missing kids.</p> <p>When more families and law enforcement have access to the resources like those found in Safety Central, families can be better educated about the risks their children face, law enforcement will have more tools at their disposal, more missing children will come home safely and more children will have the childhoods they deserve, free from victimization.</p>			
33	Lost Person Behavior	dbS Productions	<p>The Lost Person Behavior App is based upon the Search and Rescue (SAR) international gold standard reference tool on where to look for lost and missing persons. Every Public Safety Official needs to know where the missing person might be, what to ask, where to look, and what to do when minutes matter. The app was built around the field needs of Public Safety Officials. No matter how remote the location, the app continues to function since no network connection is required, once installed.</p> <p>This life-saving information is customized for 41 different subject categories. The categories are organized into a hierarchy of groups including external factors (abductions, aircraft), water incidents (boats and persons in the water), wheeled incidents (ATV, mountain bikes,</p>			<p>The app guides the user in selecting the correct subject category by several means. The subject category wizard allows the user to select potential scenarios and then will suggest the best match for the subject category. For example, if a child was riding his bicycle and was then known to be abducted, the user could select Child, Wheel/Motorized, and Abduction; the wizard would suggest using the abduction category. Alternately, the user can go straight to a subject category by using favorites, an alphabetical list, or the hierarchy list. Once the subject category is selected, the Lost Person Behavior App provides the user with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • behavioral profiles • tactical briefings • specific investigative questions • spatial and survival statistics • suggestions for initial tasks (reflex tasking).

		<p>vehicles, etc.), mental states (autism, dementia, despondent, intellectual disability, mental illness, substance intoxication), children (in five different age groups), eighteen outdoor activities (hiker, hunter, climber, gatherer, skier, etc.).</p> <p>Determining where to look is one of the major functions of the search statistics, which are now provided in a graphical and tabular format. The statistics from thousands of SAR missions allow the search planner to see where similar previous search subjects were found. The SAR statistics include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distance from the Initial Planning Point • Elevation model (likelihood of going up, down, or staying at the same elevation) • Mobility model (how long will the subject keep moving) • Dispersion angle (given a direction of travel, how well does that predict subject's location) • Track Offset model (how far away from a feature such as a road or trail is subject found) • Find location (at what type of geographic feature was the subject found) • Scenario (what caused the subject to become missing) 		<p>The all-new tactical briefings distill the statistics and profiles to the key points that every field searcher must know. The more extensive profile, full statistics, and suggested initial tasks assist even the seasoned search planner. The highly detailed questions for the investigation resulted from decades of SAR experience and thousands of missions.</p> <p>The app even allows you to email a checklist of these critical tasks and interview questions so that you may print them out. The email could also be used for providing remote support or documenting tasks that have been completed.</p> <p>The Lost Person Behavior App can be easily customized to only show the statistical information you actually need. The user can customize for ecoregion, terrain, and urban incidents. The user can view the data in both metric and English units. Several additional helpful tools are built into the app. Contextual help is provided on every page with additional information boxes, which explain every element of the app on the page you need. The information page provides information about the bike wheel model used to describe initial tactical deployment (reflex tasking), a glossary, help, and contact information.</p>
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survivability overall (what is the overall chance of finding the subject alive or injured) • Survivability rate (how does survivability rate change in 24-hour increments). 			
34	Toutiao & Tuanyuan	TechNode, Bytedance, Alibaba Group	<p>Toutiao sends push notifications to users of its apps within 10 klm of where a missing person was last seen. Tuanyuan system is similar to the AMBER system (America’s Missing: Broadcast Emergency Response) in the US, but with alerts pushed to smartphones near the last known or suspected location of the missing person, rather than local broadcasts.</p> <p>When it was first launched, once a child was reported missing to the police, Tuanyuan initially let the police push notifications with photos and descriptions to all nearby users of just a few apps: Gaode Maps (AutoNavi Maps, another division of Alibaba Group) or people with Sina Weibo accounts. Within the first hour, the notification is pushed to users within one kilometer, two the next hour then three kilometers the next. An update in November 2016 linked the system to many other apps such as QQ, Taobao, Alipay, Baidu Maps, Jinri Toutiao</p>	Free	https://technode.com/2017/12/26/chinas-popular-apps-also-help-find-missing-people/	

			and Didi, pushing alerts to ever more users.			
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All the aforementioned systems/software/technologies are tailor made to address specific needs. Due to that fact, and provided that there is no meta-analysis available, one cannot objectively draw conclusion on the strengths and weaknesses of the systems since most of them are incomparable among each other.

4.1.5.2 Technologies and Systems for Refugee Management

Regarding technologies and Systems for Refugee Management there are no changes compared to the 1st iteration. The available technologies and systems, presented in D1.3, are reproduced here for reasons of coherence and completeness.

Millions of people are being forced from their homes, risking everything to escape conflict, disaster, poverty or hunger. From those fleeing the war in Syria or climate change-induced droughts, to those stranded in inadequate conditions in Europe, more than 65 million people around the world are now officially displaced from their homes by conflict, violence and persecution – the highest figure recorded by the United Nations since the Second World War.

Given the sheer number of refugees, various systems of data collection and technical capacity constraints, information management on asylum seekers, immigrants and refugees remains one of the biggest challenges.

Technology plays a critical role in the refugee and migrant crisis, through the innovation and provision of tools and solutions to governments, humanitarian organisations and relevant actors in the field, that maintain databases of incoming asylum seekers and migrants.

Moreover, in the current refugee and migrant crisis, the definitions and responsibilities outlined in the UN's 1951 Refugee Convention and subsequent 1967 Protocol are critical principles in guaranteeing to safeguard humanitarian assistance to those most in need. Beyond these agreements, international solidarity and burden-sharing together with collaboration, communication and information dissemination are absolutely necessary for increasing coordination and clarity around the growing migratory issues the world is facing.

Information on asylum seekers often is inadequate to piece together a cohesive picture at the time of decision making. Furthermore, technical standards and platforms are not always consistent across organisations, within and across countries and most databases cannot easily communicate with other databases in different countries.

Addressing challenges in information collection, management and sharing requires collaboration as well as immense technological capacity that can process and match information across billions of queries in a timely, secure and efficient manner. Mobile phone apps can also be used to provide solutions to issues faced by refugees, such as information sharing, housing, safety, aid and fund raising, healthcare, integration and jobs matching.

The three main IT systems in EUROPE regarding data collection, storage and management on immigrants, refugees, asylum seekers and unaccompanied minors are the following:

1. **Eurodac:** centralised EU database that collects and processes the digitalised fingerprints of asylum seekers
2. **Schengen Information System (SIS II):** the largest information system for public security and law enforcement cooperation in Europe
3. **Visa Information System (VIS):** a system that allows Schengen states to share visa data for those who visit or move throughout the Schengen area.

Red Cross/Red Crescent information tools available regarding data collection, storage and management on immigrants, refugees, asylum seekers and unaccompanied minors are the following:

a) Open Data Kit

Open Data Kit (ODK) is a free mobile data collection tool, designed by the University of Washington in 2009, which helps humanitarian organisations, amongst others, to collect, manage and store different kinds of data in Android devices and replace paper-based forms. The huge challenges encountered in the last decades were a critical point which forced the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies to find alternative and innovative systems to approach humanitarian action.

The Monitoring Information System 2.0 was designed by the Spanish Red Cross and implemented during the Greece Population Movement Intervention, in collaboration with the Hellenic Red Cross and other Movement Partners. The system allows the online collection of the data generated as a result of the Red Cross activities. The data are collected through an Android open source application called Open Data Kit (ODK), storing and managing the mentioned data in a server and sharing the managed results through visual online user-friendly interfaces hosted in the same server.

The data collection is designed to register on real time not only the visits/consultations (and its characteristics) performed in each Red Cross clinic by all the staff in every specialty, but also to count and identify patients. This system allows the medical staff to closely follow up on each patient treated by the Red Cross Health Services (and check the previous tests, prescriptions, symptoms, etc. –i.e. the whole medical file). The hardware used for this aim are tablets specifically configured for the occasion.

All data collected is stored and checked to resolve any possible human mistakes made during the collection process. All found mistakes are shared with the staff in the field to be properly corrected. A strong data protection and security system is in place.

In order to report and share the information collected, the Health Information System 2.0 uses two different online Dashboards particularly designed with Pentaho Business Analytics software for the specific way data is collected. The Health Report Dashboard shows statistical information about the general situation in sites for a specific period; both date and site can be used as filters to access to the desired information for reporting, monitoring or evaluation purposes. The second dashboard, Patients Follow Up, is designed only for the professional use of the medical staff to access to the specific information of the medical record of each patient.

Strengths

- Quick collection of data
- User friendly
- Quick access to statistical analysis

Challenges-Weaknesses

- Necessary to obtain appropriate IT equipment
- Dedicated staff to support its operation

b) Accompanied referrals project (ACCREF)

During the intervention in the Population Movement Crisis in Greece, the Spanish Red Cross has designed several tools in order to build a complete system focused on the collection, storing,

management and reporting of the data resulting from the implementation of the activities initially projected.

Red Cross through ACCREF project, offers a team of skilled Interpreters and Cultural mediators (available languages: Arabic, Farsi, Kurmanji, Turkish (Turkey), Urdu, English and Pashtu) accompanying beneficiaries to have access in public services in the urban area of Athens and in Thessaloniki.

Each accompaniment is requested through an urban blog managed by SpRC and the HRC and registered in a digital template during the activity; data collected includes the sector related to requested service (Health emergency, Health Services, AMKA requisition, PSS, social welfare services, advocacy and protection). The registration is done by the cultural mediator/interpreter in charge of the accompaniment using the ODK data collection application.

Strengths

- Easy to use
- Overview of the requested and provided services

c) Virtual Volunteer (Virtualvolunteer.org)

Virtual Volunteer is an easy-to-use Red Cross and Red Crescent web application that provides migrants with the information they need to know, locating services to support them where needed, and connecting them with advice and news that can help them stay safe and healthy.

The application is available from any connected device. **Virtual Volunteer** digitally complements the services offered by the Hellenic Red Cross (HRC) Hotline. The platform provides information and a space to submit questions on topics not addressed in the FAQs. Information can be updated in real-time and reflect changes in trends. The platform can also support hotline operators with an integrated database function for services and more. Given the widespread use of smartphones by migrants in Greece, Virtual Volunteer represents an opportunity to equip large numbers of people with information in an efficient and cost-effective way.

Virtual Volunteer is also a tool for staff and volunteers working on the ground. It offers a space to find updated information, facilitating face-to-face interaction and engagement with migrants.

Though fewer in number, there are still many people on the move in Greece, arriving by sea or land, and Virtual Volunteer is for them a tool to quickly access vital, sometimes life-saving information.

Challenges

The need for human resources to support the update of the information provided.

d) Feedback Database

The Feedback Database was designed in order to track effectively the feedback received from the migrant population in the camps where Red Cross operated (Skaramangas, Ritsona).

The FD was designed in excel form and included useful information regarding: The site, the date, the name of the person who received the feedback, the gender, the language, the type, the channel of the feedback reception, the sector of intervention the feedback was referring, scope and details of the feedback, grade of priority/sensitivity, organization/person to whom the feedback was reported, the date, the channel and details of the action taken regarding the feedback, date of completion and feedback management status.

More particularly, the FD was addressed to the field officers who were communicating and engaging with the migrant community daily, through face-to-face interaction, suggestion boxes, focus group discussions and community meetings.

Strengths

The tool was prepared together with the field officer and was targeting in capturing every potential feedback that needed urgent reply. Also, the staff had the opportunity to follow in detail, the whole procedure of the feedback, before the feedback loop was finally closed. In addition to the above, it was easy to “read” the information regarding the feedback (e.g. type of feedback for the period March to April 2016), due to the automatic statistical representations (very useful also, for the donor’s reporting).

Challenges

The fill up of the FD was proven to be very time-consuming, and since the field officers didn’t have the time to deal with it, it was slowly abandoned.

4.1.6 Conclusions & Key take-aways from 2nd iteration

In this chapter, a landscape analysis of the main identified domains of interest and relevant technologies has been performed. The landscape analysis has identified that there is significant maturity in the fields of business process reengineering and change management, crowdsourcing, social innovation and collective awareness, but there is limited research on behavioural and activity profiling methodologies that have been modelled to a degree that would allow them to be directly implemented on software platforms. Missing children mobility patterns are also understudied, from a research and academic viewpoint.

Regarding Business Process Reengineering and Change Management, the investigation proved that it is feasible to define and introduce the ChildRescue methodology to the NGOs where it will be applied without significantly disturbing their current method of operation, using non-intrusive techniques found in the field of Change Management. The aim will be to introduce some parallel processes to the existing ones that in time will prove to be more effective and efficient and thus drive inter-organisational change without any intrusive involvement of ChildRescue in the process. For this to work, the new processes have to be carefully designed to minimise the effort required to apply them, and to not conflict with neither the stakeholders and their processes nor legislation.

Furthermore, the extensive research on crowdsourcing, social innovation and collective awareness methodologies and platforms proves that careful design of the platform, the application and the engagement mechanisms for the public at large are crucial for ensuring the success of the project.

Regarding behavioural and activity profiling theories and research, a classification of the most relevant algorithm and theory to use depending on the category that each case belongs to, can help to both prioritise the several pieces of collected data, as well as to provide a mechanism to quantify the relevant ones for feeding the predictive algorithms.

Furthermore, in the context of the second iteration of work for WP1, the research area of human mobility has been studied, from two different viewpoints: a) the perspective of the citizens and their mobility in a city-level, since that may affect the time needed for the resolution of a missing child’s case where citizens are employed as social sensors, in both the current approach of Amber Alert and in the context of ChildRescue concept, b) the perspective of the missing child, his/her movements and the

potential locations the child might be. It is concluded, that although the area of human mobility analysis is a vivid, active research field, from the study of which many useful conclusions can be drawn on the mobility patterns of citizens, approaching a lot a realistic representation of the general dynamics of these movements, on what concerns missing children's mobility patterns, there are still open research challenges and room for further exploration of this application field.

Finally, the review of the state-of-the-art of existing and already applied information systems on missing children investigation and rescue showed that during the design of the ChildRescue platform, several avenues regarding well-documented good practices and design decisions can be explored, to facilitate the design, the development and the uptake of the platform by the pilot partners.

4.2 Stakeholders – Platform Actors Mapping

4.2.1 Changes from 1st iteration

In D1.1-“User Requirements”, user requirements and stories were related to specific ChildRescue solution Actors. In the meantime, two new Actors have emerged, the “Team Leader”, as the connecting link among Team Members and the Network Manager, and the “ChildRescue Administrator”, who has an administrative role regarding ChildRescue and has no interference with the investigations. It should be noted that a special category of entities is also included, which although considered as actors, are not direct users of the system. These are the “Special Actors”.

4.2.2 ChildRescue Stakeholders and Platform Actors

The purpose of this section is to go one step further from the Stakeholder Identification reported in the context of D1.1-“User Requirements” in Section 2.1 and visualise relationships among the different stakeholders and also their mapping to platform's actor roles.

For the sake of completeness of the content, the list of ChildRescue stakeholders, as identified and presented in D1.1, and the list of ChildRescue solution actors as reported in D3.1-“ChildRescue Architecture and Platform Design”, are cited here in Table 4-7 and Table 4-8 respectively.

Table 4-7 ChildRescue Stakeholders

Stakeholder group	Description	Relevant Actors
A. Missing children	Missing children are the target of the investigation mission, although not directly engaged in the ChildRescue solution.	Not an Actor. Considered as a special Actor; missing child.
B. Unaccompanied Migrant Minors	This group refers to all migrant children under the age of eighteen "who have been separated from both parents and other relatives and are not being cared for by an adult who, by law or custom, is responsible for doing so." ³²⁴	Not an Actor. Considered as a special Actor; missing child.

³²⁴ <http://www.unhcr.org/40f646444.pdf>

C. Legal Guardians and caretakers (Parents, Facility Managers etc.)	In this category, all people who have the legal authority (and the corresponding duty) to care for the personal and property interests of a minor (missing child or unaccompanied minor in the ChildRescue case) are considered. The members of this group are the ones responsible for the initiation of an investigation process, informing the authorities about their missing child.	Not a direct Actor. Considered as a special Actor; Parent/Guardian/Relative of the missing child
D. Missing Children Response Organisations	In this group, all organisations that are occupied with the support of the investigation process of a missing child are considered. In Europe, this accounts for all members of the MCE Network, among which, SoC and Child Focus.	Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Member/ Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator Manager, Hosting Facility Manager, Organisation Owner. Also "Organisation" as a special actor.
E. Unaccompanied Migrant Minors Care Organisations	All organisations that are dealing with the unaccompanied migrant children and their registration and care are part of this stakeholder group. REDCROSS represents this group in ChildRescue.	Hosting Facility Manager, Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Member / Leader, Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator Manager, Organisation Owner. Also "Organisation" as a special actor.
F. Other NGOs and Voluntary Organisations	Any other NGOs and Voluntary Organisations that do not fall into D and E categories, but they are offering, along with other actions and initiatives, their services in the investigation and identification of missing children are concentrated in this group. Any Search and Rescue Teams that do not belong in the Missing	Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Member / Leader, Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator Manager, Organisation Owner.

		Children Investigation Organisations themselves (or E. category) are part of this group too.	
G.	Governmental Organisations	Apart from the aforementioned organisations, there are also specific governmental agencies/organisations, such as specific ministries, that are responsible for handling such missing children cases. All such governmental agencies fall in this stakeholder category.	Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator Manager, Organisation Owner.
H.	Public prosecutors	The prosecutor is the chief legal representative of the prosecution in countries with either the common law adversarial system, or the civil law inquisitorial system ³²⁵ . Public prosecutors are discriminated from "G" stakeholder group since they play an essential role in missing children cases and especially the decision to issue an Amber Alert. Therefore, they are considered a separate stakeholder group that in many cases represents the government.	None or Simple User (indirect stakeholder)
I.	Other governmental or private collaborators	Any governmental, public or private organisations or individuals that could be of any help in the investigation of a missing child or an unaccompanied migrant minor (e.g. the fire department, security agencies, bus drivers, etc.) will be contacted and engaged in the investigation process.	Simple User, Volunteer Team Member
J.	Police/ Coast Guard	The police (or the Coast Guard in the case of a missing child near the sea) is the one responsible for searching for a missing child. ChildRescue-enabled insights are aspired to be used directly by the police to guide their investigation towards new, knowledge-based directions.	None or Simple User (indirect stakeholder)
K.	Citizens – Open, General public	The General Public is a core stakeholder for ChildRescue since ChildRescue aims to engage an as wide as possible audience to participate actively in the discovery of a missing child through the valuable information that citizens close to the place a child was lost may offer.	Visitor, Simple User.

³²⁵ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Prosecutor>

Table 4-8 ChildRescue Actors

Actor	Description	Abbreviation
Visitor (Anonymous user)	A user that lands on the ChildRescue platform page or downloads the mobile app without logging in. This user is allowed to have a limited interaction with the platform.	VU
Simple User (Registered user)	A registered user that has access to platform features of action phase of the investigation. Naturally, this user <i>inherits all privileges (user stories as well) of the "Visitor" user.</i>	SU
Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Member	A registered and authenticated user that has access to features of the coordination and action phases of the investigation. Although for ChildRescue they act as one unified role, outside the platform there is a distinction among S&R members and volunteers. Volunteers do not usually carry some special skill and follow a shorter and more generic educational training. In contrast to that, members of a Search & Rescue Team have years of expert training and have special skills and equipment that offer to the investigation cause. Both are approved off-line by the Organisation, however. <i>Inherits all privileges of the "Simple User".</i>	RT
Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Leader	A registered and authenticated user, that has the overview of a specific operating team and is the connecting link among the Network Manager and the team members. <i>Inherits all privileges of the "Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Member".</i>	TL
Hosting Facility Manager	A registered and authenticated user, usually a social worker, that is in charge of an accommodation centre of the Organisation. <i>Inherits all privileges of the "Simple User".</i>	FM
Organisation Case Manager	A registered and authenticated user, usually a social worker, that can feed the system with profiling data and information during the whole process of investigation for a specific case. <i>Inherits all privileges of the "Simple User".</i>	CM
Organisation Network Manager	A registered and authenticated user that is responsible for the network management, i.e. The human resources outside the Organisation, for a specific case. <i>Inherits all privileges of the "Simple User".</i>	NM

Organisation Coordinator Manager	A registered and authenticated user that can initiate and coordinate the whole process of investigation and archive a case when it is closed. <i>Inherits all privileges of the "Organisation Case Manager" and the "Organisation Network Manager."</i>	OC
Organisation Owner	A registered and authenticated user that can setup an Organisation and manage its users and roles. Has an overview of all phases for all cases, past and present. <i>Inherits all privileges of the "Organisation Coordinator Manager."</i>	OO
ChildRescue Administrator	A registered and authenticated user that can register the Organisation in the platform. He represents the ChildRescue side and doesn't interfere with the cases.	CA
Special Actors		
Organisation	Organisation is an Actor but not a user per se. It is the only "user" the simple users can see and contact. It can be considered an Alias for the Organisation Owner.	
Missing child	This is a special case of an actor since this person is the target of the investigation mission. He or she may contact the platform to ask for help.	
Parent/Guardian/Relative of the missing child	The actual cause of the initiation of the investigation mission. They may be granted special access by an Organisation in order to passively follow the progress - only- of their case (view news & announcements).	

Mapping stakeholders is a visual exercise and analysis task that supports a better understanding of the often-complex interactions among stakeholders³²⁶. In the context of ChildRescue, the objective of this mapping is to render the connections and categorisation of stakeholders into groups more intuitive with the help of a clear diagram and also to map stakeholders with ChildRescue solution actors in a way that all different ChildRescue stakeholders will be linked to specific platform's actors and their connections will stand out.

To achieve this objective, the KUMU tool that is a powerful visualisation platform that enables the user to organise complex information into interactive relationship maps was employed. Therefore, stakeholder mapping was implemented using that tool for the interests of ChildRescue, and it can be found in the following link: <https://kumu.io/epuntua/childrescue#map-qPUyTWPF>

³²⁶ https://www.bsr.org/reports/BSR_Stakeholder_Engagement_Stakeholder_Mapping.final.pdf

Figure 4-7 Updated ChildRescue Stakeholders and Actors in the Kumu tool

Figure 4-8 Screenshot of the ChildRescue Stakeholders/Actor Map zooming in a specific stakeholder "Missing Children Response Organisations"

Figure 4-7 demonstrates an informative screenshot of the mapping realised, while Figure 4-8 focuses on a specific stakeholder, “Missing Children Response Organisations”, to showcase the detailed information and connections that are included in the map. However, for further exploration of the ChildRescue stakeholder relationships and their mapping to ChildRescue solution actors it is advisable to visit the provided link.

4.3 ChildRescue Integrated Methodology for the Missing Children Investigation Cycle

4.3.1 Changes from 1st iteration

The four initial workflows and the corresponding dataflow diagrams that emerged from the analysis of the use cases and the TO-BE scenarios in distinctive steps, were presented in D1.3 - “ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release I”, which was released on [M6]. In the meantime, the needs of the pilot organisations and the area for ChildRescue to intervene in existing processes has been further clarified. The initial flows have been redesigned to correspond to the actual flows of functionalities and data, as developed up to this point and planned for the next months. Nevertheless, the modular philosophy of the initial methodology has been preserved. This modularity prescribes that the four stages are relatively independent and can run in parallel, although they can affect one another.

Regarding the workflows, changes have been made in the phrasing of already defined steps, to amend logical errors, ambiguities and inconsistencies in the wording and point of view. Some processes have been broken in sub-steps and these new steps have been added in the workflows (for example the feedback evaluation process in the Action stage has been broken down in three steps), while redundant steps have been omitted. The sequence of individual steps inside the workflows has been altered, although the stages preserved their essence and core functionalities. Branches and steps that made an unnecessary distinction among the two use cases have been redefined, in order to achieve an integrated experience for the platform users.

The updated dataflows reflect data exchanges that happen among ChildRescue components and involved actors. The updates concern the definition of steps and data types in more detail, the exclusion of actors that do not interact directly with the platform (e.g. police and authorities) and the redefinition of links between components.

The workflows and dataflows for each stage are briefly described and depicted with logic diagrams. Each workflow diagram is accompanied by a table illustrating the individual steps in detail. The stakeholder group abbreviations that appear in the following diagrams can be found in Table 4-7.

4.3.2 Preparation & Profiling

4.3.2.1 Scope

The main purpose of this phase is the construction of a multilayer profile of the missing child or the unaccompanied minor. It includes the personal profile (dictated by the testimonials of the family and friends, the close environment of the child), the psychological profile (representing the professional assessment of the social workers and psychologists), and the social profile (analysing the child’s

presence, activity and traces in social networks). Moreover, further assessment on the personality, as well as, the possible POIs of the child are defined using data analytics techniques.

The main data that are collected, processed and shared during this phase are personal data of the person, data concerning his/her psychological and social behaviour, data from public information provided in social networks, as well as open data (e.g. geographical and transportation).

4.3.2.2 Workflow

The workflow that is followed during the Preparation and Profiling phase includes the main steps that are followed by the ChildRescue methodology and cover both use cases of the missing child and the unaccompanied minor. The workflow is presented in Figure 4-9.

The workflow starts with a distinction between the missing child case and the unaccompanied minor case. In the first case, the case responsible acquires information about the missing person as soon as a consent form is signed by the interviewee or a court order has been issued. In the second case the case responsible acquires information as soon as a placement order or tracing request has received. The case responsible checks if the profile already exists. If not, a new empty case is created. If yes, a new case is created with predefined profile data, based on the existing profile. Moreover, in case there's a tracing request for this specific profile, the request is considered closed, since the unaccompanied minor is found. As soon as the case is stored into the ChildRescue platform, a number of procedures are taking place to update the profile: collecting more information from the responsible authorities and the family, from public information from social media, etc. Finally, the profile is further enriched with predictive analytics for possible points of interest and further profile assessment.

Table 4-9 Preparation and Profiling Workflow Steps

Activity ID	Activity	Stakeholder group (Activity -relevant Actors)
01	Request a signed consent form: Group D requests from group C to sign a consent form in order to receive the permission to collect and process personal data of the missing child and of group C. The family/guardian signs a consent form to declare that he/she is aware and that personal data will be collected and provide permission for their process	D, C
02	Wait for placement order/tracing request/court order: Group E waits for a placement order to be issued from group G or a tracing request to be made from group C. Group D waits for a court order to be issued from group H.	D, E, C, G, H
03	Acquire personal information about the missing child or the UM: The responsible person from groups D, E collects information about the missing child/ Unaccompanied Minor	D, E, B
04	Search for a relevant profile in the ChildRescue Platform: The responsible person from groups D, E	D, E

	searches if there is already an existing profile of the missing child or the unaccompanied minor.	
05	Tracing request is complete: In case there is a tracing request and the profile of the unaccompanied minor is found in the platform the request is considered as complete.	E, B
06	A new empty case file is opened: If there is no previous record a new empty case is created by the responsible personnel of groups D, E	D, E
07	A new case file is opened with predefined fields: If the profile exists, a new case is created with predefined profile data, based on the existing profile.	D, E
08	The case file stored into the ChildRescue platform: A new case file with the profiling information is created.	D, E
09	Update Profile: The responsible personnel collects additional information for the missing child/ unaccompanied minor from the police (group J) or previous hosting facilities (group E), from family (group C), and social media and updates the profile of the missing child/ unaccompanied minor.	C, D, E, J
10	Enrich Profile: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform in order to enrich the profile. This includes predictive analytics for possible points of interest and further profile assessment.	ChildRescue platform

Figure 4-9 Preparation and Profiling Workflow

4.3.2.3 *Dataflow*

The relevant data flow diagram of the aforementioned workflow is provided below. The main data set that is exchanged between the case responsible and the ChildRescue platform is the case data. As soon as the case data are stored into the platform a set of datastores are created and updated including the multilayer profile of the missing person/unaccompanied minor, data related to information deriving from the social media, predictive analytics for the possible POIs and profile assessment.

Figure 4-10 Preparation and Profiling Dataflow

4.3.3 Coordination & Collaboration

4.3.3.1 *Scope*

In order to aid the Coordination and Collaboration Stage and enable efficient cooperation among parts of the same organisation with different jurisdiction and procedures, ChildRescue provides the Collaboration Spaces. A Collaboration Space, spatially defined around an investigation area, can be created for a case or for multiple related cases. It enables real-time sharing of information and communication among S&R/volunteer teams who operate in the same field, through the discussion channel. At the same time, operational users who may not be in the field but play a managerial role, can use the announcement board for task assignments to S&R/volunteer team members and general announcements. The Collaboration Space also features a real-time interactive map showing the location of teams in the field, allowing for better operation monitoring and guidance.

The Collaboration Spaces help teams speed up their procedures (such as building up a team quickly), enhance intercommunication and enable Network Managers to provide guidance and support, while the Case and the other involved Managers have a complete picture of the investigation progress and updates. They also serve as communication and collaboration points among different organisations when the case extends beyond one organisation or even beyond borders. This can be extremely useful in cases of unaccompanied minors who have crossed a country's borders in order to reach their target destination country, where their relatives may be.

The information exchanged inside the Collaboration Spaces, in combination with feedback acquired from the public in the Action phase and the results of the data analytics, can direct the investigation to new locations and areas.

Hosting facilities could also benefit from this component, using it as a means of cooperation and profile sharing, in order to enable easier and fastest recognition of relocated unaccompanied minors.

4.3.3.2 *Workflow*

The Coordination and Collaboration workflow (Figure 4-11) is designed according to the use cases and the requirements derived thereof, as presented in this deliverable. Following an agile approach, the initial requirements included in D1.1 – "User Requirements", have been updated and the workflow has been appropriately adapted. It is a unified flow, suitable both for the unaccompanied minor and the missing child scenario. The core of this phase is the provision of a communication tool that will enhance teams during a search mission.

The workflow illustrates the following procedure: The Coordination and Collaboration phase is initiated when the formation and coordination of S&R/volunteer teams is required in an active investigation. A new collaboration space is created. As teams operate in a defined area, the collaboration spaces are spatially bound. Afterwards, the case under investigation is attached to the collaboration space. It may occur that a team searches for multiple persons, as for example in the case of a disaster or the disappearance of brothers/sisters. Therefore, multiple cases should be attached to one collaboration space. If more than one organisation/department needs to be involved in the investigation, a collaboration mechanism should be activated, enabling cross-organisation collaboration based on appropriate access policies. Record data should be shared without infringing the initial ownership rights. After the initial configuration of the collaboration space, registered S&R/volunteer team members of the organisation are notified about the case and asked for their participation. Whoever confirms availability, joins the collaboration space, otherwise continues as simple user for this case(s). The

collaboration space offers a number of functionalities: a communication channel for direct exchange of information with operational users (Network Manager, Case Manager), an interactive map with the real-time location of participating teams (accessible only from operational users) and an announcement board where the operational users can post information about the case, guidelines and assign tasks. Through the collaboration space, users with managerial role will be able to monitor progress in the search field. Combining this information with received feedback, predictions from the profiling and action stages, they can proceed with management of the search mission and guide the operating teams, in alignment with directions from the authorities. If needed, they can update the existing collaboration space or even create a new one for a new area.

Table 4-10 Coordination and Collaboration Stage Workflow Steps

Activity ID	Activity	Stakeholder group (Activity - relevant Actors)
01	Set up new collaboration space for a specific area: The operational users of the involved organisations will create a collaboration space which will be spatially defined. The collaboration space will serve as a communication point for those participating in the active investigation in the surrounding area	D, E
02	Attach related case(s) to collaboration space: One or more cases, depending on their relevancy (e.g. multiple children missing after a disaster) can be attached to the collaboration space	
03	Enable cross-organisation collaboration: If it is a cross-border case(s), or cooperation among different organisations/departments is required, read-only access to information relevant to the case(s) should be granted. This will be ensured with application of suitable access policies	D, E
04	Share case files among organisations/departments through ChildRescue: After enabling cross-organisational collaboration, the case(s) files are shared among relevant organisations	D, E
05	Invite volunteer/S&R team members to join collaboration space: The organisation's S&R/volunteer team members are informed on the case(s) and asked of their availability through the platform	D, E, F
06	Continue as simple user: If a S&R/volunteer team member cannot participate in the search mission, she/he will continue as a simple user for this case	K

07	Join collaboration space: All S&R/volunteer team members that confirmed availability can enter the collaboration space	D, E, F
08	Send/receive information directly to/from operational users: The operational users of the organisation can directly send information to other operational users and individual S&R/volunteer team members for better coordination. These users can respond to these messages through the discussion channel	D, E, F
09	Share team's real-time location on interactive map: An interactive map will contain the locations of S&R/volunteer teams participating in the investigation, in real-time	D, E, F
10	Communicate assignments, announcements and guidelines: A one-way announcement board will be available to the operational users to guide and inform users through the collaboration space	D, E, F
11	Examine information available through the collaboration space: Through the collaboration space, the operational users have an oversight of the teams operating in the field and information they have collected	D, E
12	Monitor investigation progress and decide/act accordingly: The operational users have an overview of all available information (information from the operating lines, feedback from mobile users, information in the collaboration space(s)), and in alignment with guidelines from the authorities, they will decide regarding new possible POIs and the next steps. If needed, they will create a new collaboration space for a new investigation area or update the existing	D, E

Figure 4-11 Coordination and Collaboration Stage Workflow

4.3.3.3 Dataflow

The flow of data of the Coordination and Cooperation stage is depicted in Figure 4-12. Focusing on the main functionality of this phase, namely team collaboration, login and user access processes are not included in the diagram, as trivial processes.

All data flows are streamed through a central Collaboration Space component. The stakeholders involved in this stage are the operational users and S&R/Volunteer team members. For the purposes of collaboration and communication, various data types must be exchanged among components: current case data are retrieved from the child's record to be displayed through the collaboration space, while the record can be updated with data from there. Feedback submitted from S&R/volunteer team members and operational users is another input for the collaboration space. The collaboration space is also informed with the latest results from the data analysis of the profiling and the action stage. The interactive map is populated with the locations of the participating S&R/volunteer teams. Texts are used in the bilateral communications through the discussion channel and one-way announcements. Uploading and downloading photos and other files in the space is also supported. When cross-organisation collaboration is necessary, case data from the collaboration space is transferred to the invited organisation.

Figure 4-12 Coordination and Collaboration Stage Dataflow

4.3.4 Action

4.3.4.1 Scope

ChildRescue contributes to the Action Stage by providing a social awareness tool that enables the active involvement of citizens and volunteers in the missing children investigations. However, it can be extremely time-consuming for operational users to single helpful information out of a large volume of incoming feedback. With the application of data analytics, ChildRescue assists operational users in this

task. The Action stage workflow may run in parallel to the Coordination/Collaboration workflow and the two stages may share activities, exchange data and affect one another.

The mobile application is the main conductor that links citizens with the responsible organisation. When the decision is made for public dissemination of the case, location-based alerts are diffused to mobile users of ChildRescue, containing only information approved by the authorities. The users will not only become aware of the case, but are also encouraged to actively contribute by sharing possible evidence and information through the application. As the investigation progresses, the alert notifications will be further diffused to new areas of interest.

Feedback uploaded from users will be automatically evaluated with the use of data analytics, in terms of content quality and plausibility. This assessment is based on the user's role, profile and historical contributions, but also on the actual feedback and its location. Manual validation of information is also available to operational users, as their professional experience is irreplaceable and they should always have the last word. In cases where a new location is suggested by received feedback, indirect crowd validation can take place, by diffusing alerts in the indicated area and activating local people.

Lastly, predictive analytics will calculate possible routes and points of interest throughout the whole investigation process, based on new evidence and incoming feedback. These suggestions will provide a lead for the spatial orientation of the operations and help raise awareness in key locations.

4.3.4.2 Workflow

For both use cases, the Action stage is activated when investigation for a child is needed, be it a voluntary departure from a hosting facility, a report of a missing child or a disaster affecting unaccompanied minors. The ChildRescue platform will operate in parallel to the actual investigation, adding value to the mission by estimating possible POIs and providing a means of information dissemination and collection. These functionalities constitute the Action workflow presented below in Figure 4-13.

The Action workflow is followed every time an active investigation is required. Mobile users in the vicinity of a point of interest, are informed on the case with location-based alerts. If they notice anything that could be related to the missing child, they can submit feedback through the ChildRescue app. Then, the submitted feedback is stored in the platform, in a format appropriate to be fed in the automatic evaluation engine. After the pre-evaluation is completed, the operational user can view the feedback along with the results of the analytics and manually mark it as credible, relevant or irrelevant. The updated feedback is registered in the blockchain, in the form of hashed data, along with the id of the submitter. The reason for not storing feedback "as-is", lies in the incompatibility of the blockchain's immutability with the GDPR's "right to be forgotten". If the operational user decides that collective intelligence should be employed for the accurate assessment of a new location, she/he configures new location-based alerts and initiates a new circle of Action stage activities. Otherwise, the assessed feedback is forwarded to the predictive analytics engine, for dynamic estimation of possible routes and POIs of the child. The analytics results are used as a basis for the planning of the next operation steps and together with submitted feedback, they are communicated to the collaboration spaces.

Table 4-11 Action Stage Workflow Steps

Activity ID	Activity	Stakeholder group (Activity - relevant Actors)
01	Send location-based alerts with information to ChildRescue users: When the decision is made to start an active investigation and engage the public, location-based notifications will be sent to the mobile users. These notifications will contain the same details as those employed in missing children public Alerts in the traditional media.	K
02	Keep investigating in known areas: If there is no new information indicating a new possible area for investigation, operations continue in the known locations	D, E, F
03	Inform collaboration space: The operational users will provide directives to S&R/ volunteer teams and may invite more participants based on new findings on the action field	D, E
04	Store data: Received feedback (either through ChildRescue or through the operational lines) will be stored in the platform in the appropriate form	ChildRescue platform
05	Pre-evaluation of feedback with data analytics: Credibility of all information and uploaded evidence will be evaluated depending both on the user (e.g. role, contribution history) and the information itself (e.g. proximity to known POIs etc.)	ChildRescue platform
06	Manually validate feedback: The operational user can mark manually the feedback as credible, relevant or irrelevant, based on the source (ex. The police are considered a credible source) or their own assessment	D, E
07	Update feedback status: The feedback is updated according to the evaluation results	ChildRescue platform
08	Commit to blockchain: Received feedback will be submitted to the blockchain for added trust and to ensure that it will not be tampered with. Due to GDPR and the "right to be forgotten", which can create conflicts with the blockchain, a hash code and the id of the submitter will be stored	ChildRescue platform

<p>09</p>	<p>Configure appropriate location-based notifications for indirect crowd validation: When deemed necessary, feedback will be indirectly validated by diffusing notifications in the area indicated by the feedback. Receiving more feedback from other users in the location is an indirect validation</p>	<p>D, E</p>
<p>10</p>	<p>Possible POIs and route estimation: Possible routes and POIs will be generated from the prediction engine, based on the child’s electronic record and on new evidence</p>	<p>ChildRescue platform</p>

Figure 4-13 Action Stage Workflow

4.3.4.3 Dataflow

Data exchanges that happen throughout the Action stage, are presented in the following Figure 4-14. In this stage, the involved stakeholders are the mobile users, who receive alerts and submit feedback, and the operational users, who create alerts, submit feedback they received through means outside ChildRescue, view and validate feedback from other users. As regards the data, the following types and exchanges take place: Notification configuration data are provided by the operational users - the centre and radius of the diffusion area, the duration and the content of the alert. Mobile user data required for the diffusion are retrieved from the ChildRescue storage. As mentioned previously, mobile and operational users can provide feedback, which can come in the form of text, image or video. This feedback is afterwards routed for the pre-evaluation, where it is combined with user data. The evaluated feedback is made available to operational users, who complete the assessment and the evaluated data is stored in the relevant storage. These data are the input to the procedure for the

creation of the blocks that are registered to the blockchain. Lastly, the results of the data analytics process, which are the possible POIs and routes, are used for the feedback evaluation and are communicated to the operational users.

Figure 4-14 Action Stage Dataflow

4.3.5 Archiving

4.3.5.1 Scope

The scope of the Archiving phase is to support the responsible authorities to handle the case's closure in a secure and a privacy-respectful manner. Semantic annotation of the documentation and lessons learnt of the case is provided internally in order to support its retrieval in case of similar cases in the future. In the case of the mobile application, all data related to the specific case are erased from the citizens' devices, leaving behind only the non-personal information, statistics and outcome of the specific case. The main data that are processed during this phase are the case data including the profiling of the missing child or the unaccompanied minor and the data deriving from the coordination and action phase as they are described in the previous sections.

4.3.5.2 Workflow

The workflow that is followed during the Archiving phase includes the main steps that are followed by the ChildRescue methodology. The workflow is presented in Figure 4-15.

The workflow begins as soon as the case is considered resolved. In the case of the missing child, a case is resolved when the child has been found. In the case of the unaccompanied minor a case is resolved if one the following is taking place: a) the minor has returned to the hosting facility, b) the minor has reached his/her final destination or/and c) the minor reaches a guardian d) the minor reached adulthood while in the care of the relevant organization. For the Tracing Department, a sought person's case is resolved when a) they are traced, or b) 3 years have been reached after the initial tracing request, or c) when the tracing request is cancelled.

As soon as a case is considered resolved the responsible personnel updates the case with the latest information and closes the case. As soon as a case is closed a number of actions are taking place in parallel: a) the semantic annotation of the case with keywords, metadata and other criteria in order to facilitate the retrieval of the case if required in the future, b) the extraction of analytics and statistics based on other similar cases, c) anonymization of the case data in order to remove any personal information and d) encryption of the case data to ensure data security, protection and controlled access. In case the case has already been shared with the citizens to the ChildRescue application during the action phase, the personal data are removed from the case while providing only statistical information related to the case.

Table 4-12 Archiving workflow steps

Activity ID	Activity	Stakeholder group (Activity-relevant Actors)
01	Keep the case open: The responsible personnel of groups D, E keeps the case open until the missing child is found or the Unaccompanied Minor has returned to the facility	D, E
02	The case is updated: The responsible personnel of groups D, E updates the case that the missing child is found or the Unaccompanied Minor has returned to the facility	D, E
03	The case is closed: The responsible personnel of groups D, E closes the case since the missing child is found or the Unaccompanied Minor has returned to the facility	D, E
04	Remove case info from mobile app: All data related to the specific case are erased from the citizens' devices, leaving behind only the non-personal information, statistics and outcome of the specific case	ChildRescue platform
05	Notify mobile users who follow the case: Send notification that the case has been resolved	ChildRescue platform
06	Deactivate running alerts: Deactivate running alerts of the case that is closed	ChildRescue platform
07	Semantic annotation: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform in order to enrich the case with related information (keywords, categories etc.) in order to facilitate its retrieval in case of similar cases in the future	ChildRescue platform
08	Validate received feedback: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform to provide a tool for lessons learnt and enhance past knowledge	ChildRescue platform

09	Analytics and statistics generation: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform in order to provide a tool for lessons learnt to the end users	ChildRescue platform
10	Anonymization: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform for data protection and security	ChildRescue platform
11	Encryption: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform for data protection and security	ChildRescue platform
12	Add case to archived cases: Process implemented by the ChildRescue platform. The case is added into the archived cases	ChildRescue platform

Figure 4-15 Archiving workflow

4.3.5.3 Dataflow

The relevant data flow diagram of the aforementioned workflow is provided below. The main data that are exchanged are case data and related data generated from a number of archiving procedures. These data include semantic annotations, analytics and statistics, anonymized and encrypted case data. The main data stores that are used during this dataflow are the case data records, the past cases records and the mobile data records.

Figure 4-16 Archiving dataflow

5 Conclusions & Next Steps

The scope of the deliverable at hand was threefold: a) to revisit the collected, and reported in D1.1, user requirements and identify the updates needed regarding the ChildRescue user needs, and the collected and analysed user requirements, b) to provide a concise description of the European legislation as well as of different national legal frameworks for data protection and privacy, along with an analysis of any ethical issues and provisions related both to technical and non-technical aspects of the ChildRescue development, and c) to consistently and analytically describe the methodology by which ChildRescue will be applied and implemented as a software platform, while remarking the changes that had to be made in relation to the 1st iteration.

As in any project that aims to combine the expertise of heterogenous parties, ChildRescue needs to create a mutual understanding of the particularities of what and who is involved when designing, implementing, and running new processes and new software systems. In this case, bringing together the technical partners of the project with the NGOs and sociologists, and engaging in long, structured, and meaningful conversations through the interview process and the questionnaires was enlightening. In that respect, by M21 and the ending of WP1 work package, most aspects of the initial proposal for the project have matured significantly as a result. The Smile of the Child, the Hellenic Red Cross and Child Focus have provided extensive information about the processes that they run for many years now, which in turn has allowed the identification and the extraction of all those relevant to ChildRescue. At the same time, when there was no clear answer as to how the two different pilot cases could be merged under the same methodology and platform before, now this merging appears to be obvious and intuitive. The systematic identification of these processes and the input from the NGO partners has led to the creation of an extensive set of user requirements, the generalised system requirements, the user stories, and the use case scenarios in this document and prepared the ground for the definition and afterwards the update of the project's methodology that ensues. Overall, the work done, and the results of this task have managed to set a clear shared course for the methodology and the platform, towards creating and providing tools that will be primarily useful to the pilot partners and consequently to any other similar organisations that will join ChildRescue in the future.

Given that the ChildRescue solution consists of multiple layers where personal data are collected, analysed or reported, data protection should be ensured at all levels before its release. To this end, part B (section 3) of the present deliverable is occupied with this issue to ensure in advance that ChildRescue R&D activities -including methods, tools, technologies and processes- comply with the existing national and European legal framework, as well as ethical and privacy principles concerning access to personal information and data protection.

Finally, part C of the present deliverable (section 4) have identified the main domains of research interest for the project at large, as well as the current technologies used in the fields of the investigation of missing children and the management of refugee flows and individuals. Furthermore, the identified workflows from the TO-BE scenarios have been translated to combine both pilot cases and have been marked into the four-step process of the investigation cycle. On those workflows, the relevant data flows have been also identified and mapped. Having moved forward with the tasks of "WP2 - Grassroot Collective Intelligence in the Missing Children Investigation" and "WP3- ChildRescue Platform Architecture Definition and Implementation", as well as the first cycle of the pilot operation, a few changes to the methodology were needed, as expected, and they were documented in section 4.3.1.

The results from this deliverable will be used as input for various forthcoming tasks throughout the project implementation. Especially, tasks of “WP2 - Grassroot Collective Intelligence in the Missing Children Investigation” and “WP3- ChildRescue Platform Architecture Definition and Implementation”, will adopt their development activities, workflows and decisions to the changes of the methodology, while integrating key findings of WP1 activities to their processes, if advantageous and applicable.

6 Annex I: References

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